

Hidden REF 2024

submissions

More information at

<https://hidden-ref.org/hidden-ref-competition/>

Hidden Role panel

Entry: 357

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Business development manager

Name: Green, Charlotte

Organisation/University: n/a

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Responsible for identifying commercial opportunities within DDU portfolios. Setting business strategy. Building relationships with pharma and biotech companies and working with the universities Work closely with my colleagues at Research and Innovation services (TTO) to commercialise opportunities. Importantly my role means researchers can effectively translate their research to real life benefit via translation without they themselves taking time out of research. For our unit this is essential to allow our drug discovery projects to move forward into clinical development. I have been responsible for negotiating and agreeing 2 research collaborations with big pharma this year which allows the research funding to go further and more likely to succeed in translation, additionally it brings in kind contribution during and after the grant funding end. I have negotiate the repositioning of a research project from human health to animal health as it could not be continued in human health. This will allow the project to move forward in translation rather than being put on a shelf. I also have negotiated last year collaborations with investors which could result in 2 new companies being formed with 2 research projects. Importantly my role sets strategy for the research in terms of where we can find funding , what areas we should be working in and where the potential for translation which means the route to translation and impact of research is considered from the start not after the event.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

My role involves cost criteria, we are dependent on grant funding and my role lets us have a strategic view of where we should research to make the most of the funds and translate them to further funding (grant and commercial) or economically supporting the local or UK ecosystem. Importantly my role gives us a good chance to translate grant funding to [patient benefit and impact of the funding in the real world. I rely on the research excellence of our academics and this reputation is key to my role as I promote this excellence in many national and international circles and use this to leverage funding. Generation and communication is key, part of my role involves marketing our research and communicating what we do at partnering and other events including scientific conferences and events. Leadership is key here I lead strategy in business for over >100 members of staff and this is key to our success in translation and impact. Temporality is key it takes years sometimes to foster relationships with pharma or other partners and see this fruitful my role allows a dedication to establishing and maintaining these relationships across various projects which frees time for researchers to do research. Originality and creativity I pitch and make marketing information often and lead branding of the unit this is important for reputation and translation of research

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

My role is often hidden as it makes no claims to the research findings or research excellence or appropriateness themselves. Generation and communication is often traditional thought about only from an academic PI position or research staff and is overlooked in this role. Leadership value on is the research impactful or translational from the start would often be overlooked as the research interests of the academic are usually forefront. This role takes no claim in the research but is critical to the translation of that research and the impact it has.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 373

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bowie, Simon

Organisation/University: Centre for Postdigital Cultures, Coventry University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Simon maintains servers and infrastructure for the Centre for Postdigital Cultures (CPC) and for the Arcadia and Research England funded projects, Copim and Open Book Futures. CPC and the Copim projects all work towards enabling open access publishing in one form or another and are motivated by the ethical principle of No Open Access Without Open Infrastructure.

In his role as a software developer and server administrator, Simon maintains research-enabling infrastructures using exclusively open source software while sharing these infrastructure models with the wider research and open source software communities via GitHub and Gitea. This infrastructure includes software to facilitate project management (Nextcloud, ONLYOFFICE, GoAccess, Gitea, WorkAdventure), software for publishing research outputs (WordPress, Hugo, BookStack), and his own custom software designed specifically as part of a collective research output (ScholarLed's experimental catalogue, Copim's Experimental Publishing Compendium, a guide and reference to experimental publishing which was nominated for the Best DH Tool at the Digital Humanities Awards 2023).

These bespoke infrastructures not only enable the experimental research that the CPC and Copim pursue but do so while divesting from the proprietary and corporate software systems that dominate research in the UK. Simon's infrastructures return control over systems to the researchers at the CPC and in Copim and enables them to customise their workflows in a way not possible with proprietary software. We can't pursue experimental research without experimenting with how we do that research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Appropriateness

Open source research infrastructures are rare in UK Higher Education but should be an ethical imperative on the same grounds as publishing open access. Our publics and our communities should be able to benefit from our work without the barriers imposed by commercial publishers or commercial software and infrastructure providers. On the principle of No Open Access Without Open Infrastructures, this is even more significant as best practice when working on research projects to enable open access.

Temporality

Maintaining server and software infrastructure is an ongoing process which is hidden by design. Installing updates, deploying new software, designing Docker configurations for new software, managing security, renewing SSL certificates: all of these tasks are continual, ongoing tasks but should be hidden from researchers at the front-end to ensure a smooth and seamless experience of using the software on the server.

Local importance

One-size-fits-all corporate research infrastructures fail to account for the uniqueness of each research

centre or each research endeavour. An open research infrastructure offers far more scope for customisation allowing for a localised and embedded sense of place in the infrastructure. Both CPC and Copim's infrastructures are customised to their unique and specific needs and allow the unique experimental research of their diverse researchers.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

As discussed above, maintaining research infrastructures is hidden by design from the end-user: a well-maintained server infrastructure should be invisible to the researcher using it to facilitate their research. A significant proportion of Simon's labour (and that of technicians in similar roles) is hidden in that it doesn't result in traditional published research outputs or in exciting ideas for conference presentations. It is the ongoing labour of software updates and server maintenance, much of which these days is outsourced at cost to unreliable third-party corporate providers.

Research infrastructure is often outsourced either to corporate providers or to internal IT departments and Simon's position as a technician embedded within a research centre and dedicated to maintaining infrastructure solely for that centre is a rarity in UK HEIs. It allows for more responsiveness for his centre's researchers even while it hides his work from the wider university.

The REF fails to recognise not only the infrastructures that Simon designs but the software that Simon develops for his projects. REF struggles with collaboratively-produced software outputs that don't fit inside their narrow categorisations of outputs and these are the kind of web applications or experimental publishing workflows that Simon's work is focused on.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-2437-589X

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: Open Book Futures is funded by the Research England Development (RED) Fund and Arcadia.

Entry: 398

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hayton, Jessica

Organisation/University: IOE, UCL's Faculty of Education and Society

Nominating other (name): Sideropoulos, Vassilis

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Vassilis plays a pivotal yet often unseen role in advancing research within the Mental Health and Education Sciences fields. All that follows is under his job title as Senior Technician, which veils his distinct contributions to the field, staff development, and departmental outputs.

Vassilis' expertise in statistical modelling and longitudinal designs, combined with a deep understanding (and training) of research methodologies, underpins his contributions. Vassilis secured over →£200K in research funding from prestigious bodies like the ESRC and MRC. He was instrumental in obtaining over →£300K for research equipment through UKRI's Research Capital Investment Fund, supporting departmental staff in achieving their research objectives and outputs.

Vassilis has a strong publication record in top-tier journals, including Nature's Scientific Reports and the Journal of Global Health, that highlight his academic influence, but again often overlooked in his role as a technician, despite these publications contributing to REF cycles.

Vassilis is dedicated to Science Communication and Public Engagement and was awarded the Founder's Award from QMU and the Public Engagement Award from the British Psychology Society. That said, he has not yet been truly recognised nor appreciated in how his hidden role supports the functioning and outputs of the department.

Vassilis's hidden role is crucial to the successes of our department; he ensures the seamless operation and funding of research initiatives, fostering an environment where studies of all types can thrive. His behind-the-scenes efforts, mentoring others, and strategic vision significantly contribute to the success and impact of research in his field and that of the wider department.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Vassilis' hidden role is crucial to the success of research in the Mental Health and Education Sciences fields, and our wider department. His expertise, leadership, and sustained contributions ensure the continuous operation and funding of research initiatives, fostering an environment where all research can thrive. I have mapped his contributions against 5 of the criteria below:

1. Appropriateness: Vassilis' work in statistical modelling and longitudinal designs is grounded in robust methodologies, ensuring the integrity and reliability of research outcomes. His efforts in securing significant funding from reputable bodies like the ESRC and MRC demonstrate a commitment to ethical research and open science practices.

2. Excellence: Vassilis' ability to secure over →£200K in research funding and an additional →£300K for research equipment underscores his exceptional skills and dedication in supporting the research lifecycle. His strong publication record in top-tier journals such as Nature's Scientific Reports and the Journal of Global Health further highlights his contribution to the field.

3. Leadership: Vassilis goes above and beyond his role as a Senior Technician. His hidden contributions to staff development and departmental outputs are invaluable. By mentoring others and fostering an environment conducive to research, he demonstrates outstanding leadership.

4. Temporality: Vassilis's contributions are not transient; they are the result of ongoing relationships and sustained efforts. Since 2019, he has been instrumental in obtaining funding and supporting research initiatives, ensuring continuity and long-term impact. His role in the IOE UKRI Research Capital Investment Group and as Head of Psychological Research Resources, Assessments, and Laboratories

highlights his enduring commitment to the department's success.

5. Responsibility: Vassilis' dedication to ethical research practices, securing funding, and supporting departmental staff underscores his commitment to responsible research. His recognition through awards for public engagement further highlights his dedication to making research accessible and impactful.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The role of the technician is often overlooked due to the discreet nature of their work. Despite significant contributions, such as securing funding, supporting research initiatives, and mentoring staff, technicians like Vassilis are not always visible or recognised as a foundation of academic achievement. Their essential tasks, which ensure the lifecycle of research projects, are frequently undervalued compared to more senior roles, and their distinct contributions can often be overshadowed by the achievements of others. The truth is that academic effectiveness hinges on support from our technicians, and without them the quality of outputs may be compromised. Vassilis deserves this recognition, as do so many others across all institutions, but I nominated him to show how much he is valued, respected, and needed within our department and the broader university context.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 399

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Barham, Larry

Organisation/University: University of Liverpool

Nominating other (name): Bayliss, Michael

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I nominate Mr Mike Bayliss, Senior IT and AV Technician at the University of Liverpool for his hidden roles (category 1) in producing and managing the public dissemination (category Q) of a substantial research output ('Evidence for the earliest structural use of wood at least 476,000 years ago') destined for REF 2029 (Barham et al. 2023 Nature 622, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06557-9>). The video he produced has had more than 3 million views across different YouTube channels (link via University of Liverpool:

<https://news.liverpool.ac.uk/2023/09/20/archaeologists-discover-worlds-oldest-wooden-structure/>), and 275,000 views on TikTok.

Mike managed the 23+ media interviews hosted in University's media suite to ensure the highest sound and visual quality for national and international media. His skills and selfless giving of his time contributed to the unexpected global public interest in the project which has been covered by 1200 media outlets. Altmetrics for the Nature paper recorded 178,000 downloads (06/09/2024) and have placed it in the top 5% of all publications. Mike's hidden contribution to raising the public and academic profile of the research deserves formal recognition.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The discovery of the ancient wood structure was analysed in-depth in the Nature article including in its 90 pages of supplementary information. Thirteen academic researchers were involved in the research and recognised as co-authors. (The project was funded by the Arts and Humanities Research Council.)

This submission recognises the importance of Mike's contribution against the criteria of 1) originality/creativity; 2) responsibility to research; 3) local importance; and in its 4) temporality.

In terms of originality and creativity, Mike integrated a variety of data sources from the diverse range of published supplementary research to present a narrative of scientific research that humanised the process as the work of a team of individuals. Particularly novel was the inclusion of a phase of underwater photography taken to build a 3D model of the wood without exposing the waterlogged wood to air. Each step of the process was linked to individuals, building a picture of a truly collaborative effort which is the reality of trans-disciplinary research. In doing so, he attended to delivering on the project's inherent responsibility to research. A key feature of the video was its accurate portrayal of the central role played by technical support staff, who are not eligible for the REF, in generating essential data. This behind the scenes view of the research process gave the public insight into the process of academic research.

His work is of local importance through its storyline of a team journey rooted in its place of discovery and supported by Zambian colleagues and institutions. Media in Zambia picked up on the video, and the wood has become a source of national pride (according to Zambia's National Museums Board, Ministry of Tourism).

The video has longevity as its claim to temporality as it continues to be viewed and discussed almost a year since its release. As a work of audiovisual dissemination, it plays a valuable role in contributing to the public understanding of science.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This submission could be framed as contributing to the research environment of the institution, but would require formal documentation of how the video, and media interviews, made a societal impact, such as changing public understanding of science. This kind of REF impact was not the intention of the Mike's work. His aim was to reach a broad audience to inform and entertain in a creative way. Most academics lack these audiovisual skills or treat them as of secondary importance, 'À a distraction - to the research process. As such, this contribution remains hidden within the current research culture.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 411

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Professional Services Personnel

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Doran, Heather

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): Davis, Marj

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Interdisciplinary and diverse research teams are crucial for innovative and impactful scientific research but building and maintaining these teams can present significant challenges and requires a lot of hidden effort. This submission recognises the efforts of the Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science (LRCFS) at the University of Dundee in establishing best practices that foster a positive and collaborative work environment. This work is essential for enabling researchers and support staff to work together effectively and generate excellent research.

The LRCFS has implemented several key initiatives. These include establishing a comprehensive code of conduct, the LRCFS Charter, that promotes respectful and inclusive behaviour within the research group. Additionally, the Centre has developed an independent onboarding and induction protocol to ensure that every student and staff member starts on the right foot, feeling welcomed and equipped to contribute to the team. Recognising the importance of relationship-building, LRCFS also facilitates both formal and informal meetings, as well as networking opportunities, to strengthen connections across the team.

This work is carried out through a collaborative effort between research support staff and researchers. However, the lion's share of this work is managed by the research support staff, who are responsible for implementing these processes and continuously refining them to reflect best practices and evolving workplace needs. Their contributions are vital to creating a productive and supportive environment that enables the Centre's researchers to thrive and advance forensic science.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Productive staff and students need a positive and healthy working environment. This submission highlights the crucial, yet often overlooked, work required to create and sustain a positive research culture within interdisciplinary and diverse teams. The Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science (LRCFS) at the University of Dundee has demonstrated excellence in this area by implementing strategies that ensure researchers of different disciplines and support staff can work together effectively. This work is particularly relevant in today's research environment, where the complexity of scientific challenges often necessitates interdisciplinary collaboration and diverse perspectives.

The LRCFS team is composed of 43 students, research staff from different disciplines and, professional services staff. The team come from 17 different countries and speak over 20 languages. Staff and students are both laboratory and office based and some work remotely from the University. The research culture created by the team binds the team together in a supportive, kind and respectful environment where differences, when they arise, are aired and resolved respectfully. By fostering this positive research culture and environment, LRCFS not only enhances the productivity and well-being of its own team but also contributes to the broader research community. The success of these initiatives within LRCFS serves as a model that can be replicated in other research institutions, particularly those grappling with the challenges of interdisciplinary collaboration. The Centre's work in this area underscores the importance of creating healthy research environments that enable groundbreaking

scientific discoveries.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

A significant portion of the work to build and maintain a positive research culture at LRCFS is carried out by research support staff. These individuals play a crucial role in implementing the Centre's code of conduct, onboarding processes, and team-building activities. However, their contributions are not recognised in traditional research evaluations, which typically prioritise the work of academic researchers.

The impact of initiatives aimed at fostering a positive research culture is difficult to quantify using traditional metrics. The benefits of such work are often reflected in the long-term well-being, productivity, and collaboration among team members, rather than in immediate research outputs. This makes it challenging to capture the full significance of these efforts in standard research evaluations.

Traditional research evaluation frameworks often focus on disciplinary-specific achievements, making it difficult to fully appreciate the complexity and significance of work that spans multiple fields. The Centre's efforts to bring together researchers from diverse backgrounds and disciplines, and to create a culture where they can work effectively together, is a critical aspect of its success. However, this work does not always receive the recognition it deserves within conventional evaluation systems.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Professor Niamh Nic Daeid, Director
Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science at the University of Dundee

Funding acknowledgements: The Leverhulme Trust

Entry: 412

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Public Engagement Team

Name: Doran, Heather

Organisation/University: Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science at the University of Dundee has pioneered a sector-leading approach to public engagement with research in forensic science, putting the public at the heart of what we do. From the establishment of research to the final communication, we engage audiences with purpose, working with them to decide on our research focus and/or to support the creation and analysis of data. Our ethos influences our research outcomes, ensuring that we focus on what matters the most and will make the biggest difference to society in delivering safe and fair justice.

Each engagement project and initiative is targeted to a particular audience and this approach enables the research centre to reach and engage with a diverse audience. The approach to this engagement comes from in-house support for engagement projects through a Public Engagement Manager and Public Engagement Officer, targeted training for researchers and staff and an inclusive approach that enables all members of the research centre including students and members of administrative staff to be well supported in their engagement.

Since 2020, through the activities of our Public Engagement team all of the LRCFS staff and students work together in delivering over 5,400 different engagements. This includes working with over 1300 school pupils that have participated in forensic science activities purposively designed for them and articulating the value of science in the Justice process. In addition, the LRCFS developed a podcast (Inside Forensic Science) which discusses the reality of forensic science based on historical cases in discussion with forensic science, law enforcement and legal practitioners and has over 90K listens around the world since 2021.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Centre has explored new ways of engagement working with external partners such as artists to create virtual collaborative video games (created to be flexible for schools), crime writers and film makers to advise on novels and forensic science TV programs to ensure the accurate representation of science and contributed to both print and broadcast media reaching millions of people around the globe. In addition, our engagement contributes to our research aims and encourages participation in research projects which otherwise would sit in isolation from society.

There is much focus on widening access to undergraduate studies but our approach focuses on that engagement with the research role of a university institution too. Our goals aren't to simply educate and transfer information but to encourage involvement in research and raise questions and debate about forensic science in our society. This is extremely difficult to quantify.

The results of this engagement are shown in our data collection for citizen science research projects (over 450 tape-lifts collected and analysed by school pupils to detect an abundance of fibres since January 2023) and the feedback we receive from attendees at activities. Our initiatives are not designed simply for audiences but are all designed with our audiences and, we work with teachers, pupils and members of the public throughout the design process. All projects are designed to be accessible practical

and useful.

Our researchers and staff develop their communication and engagement skills and confidence from participation in such activities.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

It is not standard practice for forensic science to undertake such extensive engagement related to research and our models have been noted by forensic science leaders around the world who have asked us to discuss and share our approach in this area, including the Center for Statistics and Applications in Forensic Evidence in the USA and Science Foundation Ireland. This sharing of expertise from LRCFS with other research bodies isn't recognised through any research reporting.

Although our approach to public engagement which fosters a community where staff and researchers are supported to initiate and participate in public engagement has been recognised by a gold award from the National Coordinating Centre for Public Engagement, there are limited other ways in which the processes in place for this work can be rewarded.

This engaged approach influences our research, generating more useful outcomes and supports forensic science to be more connected with the needs of society.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Clara Morriss, Public Engagement Officer, Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Funding acknowledgements: The Leverhulme Trust

Entry: 416

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Research Software Engineers

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ternes Dallagnollo, Patricia

Organisation/University: University of Leeds

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

As the Research Computing Team Leader in Research IT at the University of Leeds, I have led significant changes that have enhanced the delivery of Research Software Engineering (RSE) services and IT infrastructure support. My leadership has expanded the team and improved our consultation service model, with a strong focus on financial sustainability. One major achievement was implementing a new system for charging projects, which secured 20 months of funding in just 6 months in the role. I also advocated for a RSE time allocation in grant applications to ensure our services are integrated into the early stages of research planning, increasing awareness and recognition of our team's essential role.

A key milestone during my leadership has been the acquisition of a new High-Performance Computing (HPC) system, providing ten times more computing power than our previous infrastructure. I played a critical role in securing this system, always advocating for the needs of researchers. I am now leading the migration from the old system to the new one, which involves creating new training programs, user documentation, workflows, and tailored support to meet the diverse requirements of different research areas.

In addition to infrastructure improvements, I have restructured our training curriculum to better align with researchers' needs. I introduced new courses, including Data Visualisation and Software Development Best Practices, specifically designed for the demands of research. I also led efforts to engage more deeply with the research and RSE communities, mentoring PhD students, providing consultancy services, and strengthening our presence in strategic university meetings. My goal is to establish our team as the central RSE authority on campus. By increasing our consultancy capacity, improving financial workflows, and fostering stronger community engagement, I am building a sustainable and impactful team that plays a crucial role in shaping the future of research at the University of Leeds.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The leadership I provide within Research Computing at the University of Leeds is significant due to the transformative changes I've implemented in both the infrastructure and support systems that facilitate cutting-edge research. One of the most important achievements is the acquisition of a new High-Performance Computing (HPC) system. This new system delivers ten times the computing power of its predecessor, greatly enhancing the computational capacity available to researchers. It enables them to work with larger datasets, conduct more complex simulations, and accelerate the pace of their discoveries. I played an active role in advocating for this system, ensuring that it meets the diverse and evolving needs of the research community.

Another key initiative I am leading is the migration from the old HPC system to the new one. This involves a complete overhaul of how computational resources are accessed and used, and my team and I are creating new training materials, documentation, and workflows to enable researchers from various disciplines to make the best use of the new system. We are also providing tailored support to meet the unique computational requirements of different research areas.

In addition to technical improvements, my focus on service development and financial sustainability ensures that our team is well-positioned to support research in the long term. Our efforts have established our team as a key enabler of research excellence, providing researchers not only with access to cutting-edge tools but also with the guidance and training they need to maximise their impact. This drives forward the university's research capabilities in a profound and sustainable way.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite my significant contributions, much of the work I have done remains hidden within the current research culture. Traditional research evaluation methods primarily recognise high-profile outputs such as publications, grants, and breakthroughs led by principal investigators, while essential contributions from RSE teams often go unnoticed. My role involves creating the backbone for research projects by providing technical expertise, advice, and training, but this critical support rarely gets formal recognition in the research process. The changes I promoted, such as creating financial sustainability, embedding RSE services in grant applications, and leading training initiatives, have had a wide-reaching impact, but they are behind-the-scenes efforts. Researchers are the visible face of their projects, and the recognition usually centres on them, while the technical, infrastructural, and operational support provided by my team remains in the background. This lack of visibility makes it difficult to appreciate the full extent of the transformative work I have undertaken to enhance the research environment. Additionally, RSE roles are often undervalued in the wider research culture because they do not directly result in traditional academic outputs. While our work is essential for enabling cutting-edge research, it is not reflected in the metrics typically used to evaluate success. This systemic under-recognition means that the leadership, strategic changes, and improvements I have spearheaded are largely invisible in formal evaluations of research achievements. Career progression challenges within the RSE field further compound this invisibility. I took on the role of team leader to address these very challenges, not only within my own team but across the broader RSE community. However, the contributions of RSE professionals remain underappreciated, even though we are critical enablers of the university's research success. This submission seeks to highlight these hidden contributions and the transformative role I have played in reshaping the research infrastructure.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-3116-3692

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 420

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Community Manager

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ennis, Emily

Organisation/University: University of Leeds

Nominating other (name): Pontin, Fran

Nominating other (organisation): Consumer Data Research Centre, University of Leeds

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Fran Pontin, at the Consumer Data Research Centre Leeds (CDRC-L), uses her data science expertise to provide invisible but invaluable contributions to the research of others, as well as to produce her own nation-leading research. As Senior Research Data Scientist she works directly with external partners to facilitate research relationships, including the preparation of data sharing agreements and advanced data governance, and she has become a key contact in our collaboration with Asda (<https://www.leeds.ac.uk/news-working-business/news/article/5123/university-and-asda-announce-data-partnership>). She is also responsible for the cleaning and preparation of externally-sourced data, working collaboratively with data teams outside academia. She also prepares public-facing data for the CDRC data store (<https://data.cdrc.ac.uk/>), which makes datasets available to researchers worldwide. Pontin has also supervised research projects as part of the Data Scientist Development Programme (DSDP) run by Leeds Institute for Data Analytics (<https://lida.leeds.ac.uk/data-scientist-development-programme/>), working with external partners such as Good Food Oxfordshire, Office for Health Improvement and Disparities, consumer champions Which?, and supermarket retailers.

Alongside the contributions she makes to the research of others, Pontin leads on the creation of impactful data products that are frequently overlooked as research outputs. Pontin led on the creation of CDRC's Priority Places for Food Index (<https://priorityplaces.cdrc.ac.uk/>), launched in 2022, bringing together multiple open datasets to identify areas in the UK at risk of food insecurity. To create and update (2024) the tool, Pontin collaborated with consumer champions Which?, as well as other key stakeholders, to ensure the tool is sufficiently rigorous and accessible to influence policymakers. Pontin has been the technical lead for this project but has also been active in public engagement, speaking directly with 60+ key stakeholders, including charities, policymakers, and businesses. In 2023, Pontin used this work to provide written and verbal evidence to the Fairness in the food supply chain consultation run by the EFRA Committee (<https://committees.parliament.uk/work/7682/fairness-in-the-food-supply-chain/>).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

By working as part of a larger, interdisciplinary group of cross-sector researchers both within academia and outside it, it can be difficult to identify the best audience to celebrate Pontin's excellence, even where she produces impactful research. This is particularly difficult when work is protected by non-disclosure or data sharing agreements. Likewise, open and collaborative data products, which Pontin leads on producing, do not always have visibility among academic communities. These points demonstrate the appropriateness and excellence of Pontin's work for this award. She also meets the criteria in the following ways:

Cost: As an early career researcher, Pontin's time supporting research comes at considerable cost to establishing her own research independence. Recognition through the Hidden REF award would highlight the essential technical contributions she makes to the research of others.

Generation & Communication: Pontin works across the research lifecycle, including: from research

question creation to data analysis to dissemination of findings. Her collaborations with external partners also enable her to work reflexively and in a positional way to ensure her research is appropriate to the sectors where it can most effect change.

Leadership: Pontin has rapidly established herself as a leader in data science. She has been jointly responsible for grant income of over –£2million and has provided de facto research leadership during prolonger absences of project PIs. The work she has initiated and conducted under data sharing and non-disclosure agreements have also set sector-leading examples of good data governance.

Originality/creativity & Rigour: Pontin's creation and ongoing development of data tools demonstrates her commitment to innovative and accessible research. In the 2024 update of Priority Places, Pontin was able to analyse industry recommendations (e.g. from the Food Foundation) regarding the eligibility and provision of free school meals in order to create proxy values for food insecurity (i.e. following recommendations made by organisations such as the Food Foundation, Pontin recalibrated the Index's calculation of food insecurity to include households on Universal Credit, despite this not being a criterion for the eligibility of free school meals). This demonstrates innovative and rigorous thinking in her desire to effect real-world change.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Pontin has been recognised internally by her peers and through University award schemes for the work she has delivered on the research projects led by others. But the culture of the UK research environment more broadly has made it difficult for her contributions to be recognised in a more public way. As an example, in the last 8 years Pontin has made considerable contribution to a large multi-retailer project exploring healthy and sustainable diets. Her involvement has included seeking and developing retailer partnerships, data procurement and governance, data analysis and evaluation (including writing openly-available codes and algorithms), data visualisation and dissemination, public engagement, and impact evaluation. This project was recently nominated for a UKRI award and while team submissions to the awards were possible, the promotion materials and award ceremony itself prioritised focusing on the PI only. This meant that Pontin was not recognised. Likewise, as someone with a variety of digital outputs, who works within an interdisciplinary research centre, she also does not neatly fit into Units of Assessment or REF process within the University, even where her research, such as Priority Places, has demonstrable impact.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 421

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role
Hidden role: Professional Services Personnel
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Newport, Roger
Organisation/University: n/a
Nominating other (name): Auty, Kelly
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission singles out one individual but also celebrates all such non-academic individuals in similar positions across all HEIs. The nominee is an intangible genius who lives in the liminal space, between institutional strategy, impact, research communication, governance, strategic planning, compliance, ethics & integrity and policy. This unrecognised 'magician' contributes to research by providing that spark of insight that comes from having a discipline-agnostic view of research and a deep understanding of the power and benefit of communicating the obscure to a range of different audiences. That spark - whether it be from being able to join dots, see connections, filter through the jargon to what is meaningful, think across-disciplines, understand the needs of stakeholders, 'get' evaluation, or appreciate the joy and potential of non-standard outputs, has transformed research and outputs for their institution, leading to 4* case studies, successful grant applications, publications, and transformative exhibits. Across two institutions, this individual has rolled impact case studies in glitter adding (in the DVC's words) half a star across the board, articulated the real-world significance of the impenetrable, provided UKRI reviewer-recognised input to successful grants, trained academics and practitioners at all levels to understand the purpose of their work, and genuinely altered the direction of travel for researchers and their research. They are a true leader, an inspirational communicator, focussed on unearthing the relevance of research by applying originality and creativity tinged with genius, while maintaining the utmost rigour in advising on all aspects of knowledge exchange throughout the lifecycle of projects, from helping to shape the germ of an idea, through stakeholder mapping, ethical awareness, theories of change, responsible and proportionate evaluation, and engaging with relevant publics, and all done with the openness, honesty, sense of shared excitement and fun that fosters great working relationships.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The importance of this submission lies in the crucial importance of the understanding of, and application of, true knowledge exchange. Knowledge exchange underpins absolutely (pretty much) everything in good research. Without good knowledge exchange: 1) there is no two-way Communication between researchers and the publics or organisations that need and can co-create high quality research; 2) the Generation of research ideas is stunted and academia-centric; 3) opportunities for genuine and informed Leadership in research is restricted for academics, practitioners, professional services and the publics we work with; 4) the Local importance of the research is lost, not realised, or perhaps never even discovered, stifling opportunities to reveal pride in place. Good knowledge exchange also requires Rigour, and Reflexivity, through honest and open reflection from all parties. It is the cornerstone of Responsible research, and it takes real insight to be able to appreciate how it should be applied throughout, and beyond, the lifetime of the project (Temporality). Understanding and applying knowledge exchange well requires huge Expertise, as well as Creativity and Originality. To possess the ability to support and train others in all of these elements is a rare thing indeed.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The main characters in the Star Wars franchise (both good and evil characters) are all amazing; they are the heroes (or villains) that get the fame and glory (except when it ends in spectacular failure). Despite their amazingness, the galaxy (far far away) they inhabit could not function, and the Rebel Alliance would not be successful in their endeavours, without the support of droids. Droids are beings endowed with intelligence, specialist knowledge and expertise that do all the necessary jobs the heroes of the story don't want to do, or can't do. Many droids have self-awareness, emotions and, apparently, never sleep, and some can even be almost human in appearance. What droids never seem able to achieve, however, is parity with their more illustrious organic colleagues. Droids don't get medals - the formal, permanent recognition of doing amazing things - and they can't get promoted to being a better droid for just doing their job well. Even the most valued droids - like R2-D2, who saves the day in just about every episode, and who helps shape the narrative and makes dynamic and purposeful interventions - get little more than a pat on the head and a bit of a polish (probably carried out by another droid). In HEIs, those main characters (the heroes) are academics, and the droids are professional services staff. The traditional view is that that the academics have all the ideas and expertise while professional services do 'stuff' in the background that helps (or hinders, depending on whether you are operating within the rules or not). Academics then get named on grants and are listed on Impact Case Studies. What gets missed in this scenario, much like the contribution of R2-D2, is that professional services staff also have amazing ideas and expertise that change the plot or the course of the narrative, saving the day and leading to successful missions. Professional services staff can bring ideas and expertise that fundamentally change or shape the direction, outcomes or dissemination of the research. For academics, such input would lead to co-authorship or other acknowledgment (not to mention promotion), yet for the (real) unsung heroes, this input is not formally recognised - they never appear on published case study templates, institutional narratives, research outputs or successful exhibits. It is about time that changed, and we moved towards more transparent and inclusive co-authorship.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 424

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Librarians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Chisholm, Robert

Organisation/University: University of Sheffield

Nominating other (name): Adams, Jenni

Nominating other (organisation): University of Sheffield

Description of submission

Summary

Jenni, as the Open Research Manager at the University of Sheffield Library, has played a pivotal role in advancing the university's research success through her leadership in promoting open research practices. One of her most significant contributions is the establishment and management of OpenFest, an annual conference that celebrates and explores open research, attracting collaboration with Sheffield Hallam University and engaging the broader academic community. This event has gained substantial attention, fostering a culture of transparency and inclusivity in research.

Jenni also launched Open Research Conversations, a series of free online monthly meetings where researchers discuss various aspects of open research, which now sometimes attract international attention. These sessions have become a well-attended and highly valued resource, further extending the university of Sheffield's reach and impact within the global research community. Additionally, her coordination of Unleash Your Data, a program designed to enhance the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles of research data and software, has provided crucial funding and support for research projects, ensuring these outputs are handled more effectively and openly.

Her leadership in the Open Research Prize has helped showcase successful open research projects, serving as case studies to guide and inspire others. By co-leading the Open Scholarship Community Sheffield and being actively involved in various working groups, she has strengthened the university's commitment to open research initiatives.

Furthermore, Jenni's efforts in co-authoring the The University of Sheffield's Open Research Digital Handbook and leading events like Changing Research Culture demonstrate her dedication to improving the research environment. Her involvement in initiatives like ORCID advocacy and Open Access Monograph Case Studies shows her continuous work towards making research more accessible, ensuring that Sheffield's research output is both impactful and widely disseminated.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Jenni's role as the Open Research Manager at the University of Sheffield is fundamental to the university's research success and its broader impact on the academic community. By championing open research practices, she plays a crucial role in fostering a culture of transparency, collaboration, and innovation, all of which are essential for modern research excellence.

Her leadership in establishing initiatives like OpenFest, Open Research Conversations, and Unleash Your Data directly impacts how research is conducted and shared. These programs promote the principles of open access, data sharing, and FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable) practices, which are now becoming critical standards in global research. OpenFest, for example, has grown over 3 years into a key event that not only highlights best practices but also brings researchers together across institutions, increasing Sheffield's visibility as a leader in open research. This kind of knowledge-sharing and collaboration is vital for accelerating discoveries and ensuring research outputs have a wider societal impact.

Jenni's ability to build communities and foster long-term cultural change has been essential in embedding open research principles within the university of Sheffield and beyond. Her efforts to lead initiatives like the Open Research Prizes and Open Scholarship Community Sheffield encourage researchers to embrace open practices, making their work more accessible and reusable by others. This ensures that Sheffield's research has a broader reach and higher potential for real-world impact.

Her actions have not only elevated the quality and visibility of Sheffield's research outputs but have also created pathways for future innovation by starting early career researchers out on a path adopting more transparent and ethical practices.

In sum, Jenni's role is pivotal to both the strategic success and global impact of Sheffield's research, ensuring that the university remains at the forefront of the open research movement.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite Jenni's pivotal contributions as the Open Research Manager at the University of Sheffield, her work often remains overlooked by current research evaluation frameworks, which tend to prioritize traditional metrics over the hard to measure impact of open research initiatives. This oversight stems from several structural issues within the academic assessment landscape, which still heavily relies on narrow measures such as journal impact factors, citation counts, and individual publication metrics. These narrow measures overlook, work like Jenni's which catalyse research culture rather than working directly on research projects.

One of the key reasons Jenni's work is underappreciated is the misalignment between traditional evaluation systems and the principles of open research. Open research, by design, encourages broader accessibility, data sharing, and transparency. These practices often do not fit neatly into traditional evaluation systems, which focus on specific outputs like high-impact publications. Initiatives like OpenFest, Open Research Conversations, and Unleash Your Data foster collaboration and inclusivity but may not generate immediate, quantifiable outcomes that align with conventional metrics. The contributions Jenni makes, such as building communities, enhancing the FAIRness of data, and leading knowledge-sharing events, play a crucial role in improving research culture and quality, but these outcomes are not easily captured by standard evaluative tools.

Another overlooked aspect of Jenni's work is the qualitative, rather than quantitative, nature of her contributions. Many of her initiatives, such as the Open Research Prizes or Open Scholarship Community Sheffield, aim to change mindsets and practices across the academic community. These changes are critical for fostering a more ethical, transparent, and collaborative research environment but are difficult to quantify. Traditional metrics do not account for the way Jenni's initiatives foster inclusivity, facilitate international collaboration, or empower early-career researchers to engage with open practices.

Finally, collaborative and community-focused contributions like Jenni's are often undervalued compared to individual achievements. Open research is inherently collective, yet evaluation frameworks tend to prioritize individual outputs, further marginalizing her broad contributions that rely on community-building, institutional change, and global outreach.

In sum, Jenni's significant role in promoting open research practices remains overlooked because current evaluation frameworks are ill-equipped to recognize the long-term, collaborative, and qualitative impact of her work.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0003-3379-9042

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Neil Shephard, University of Sheffield, 0000-0001-8301-6857, Research Software Engineer

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 431

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Chalcraft, Rebecca

Organisation/University: Oxford University, Paediatrics department

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

My role is to carry out the in vivo procedures for a variety of researchers within my group. I describe my role as Technical Research Technician.

I will help advise and organise all in vivo experiments to the researchers needs, this includes advice on colony management (as well as running 4 of my own active colonies) and breeding strategies to obtain the needed number of animals. This involved detailed research into a vast number of different strains including breeding quality and numbers. This also includes reviewing the best method of induction for treatment/compounds depending on the base formulation of the compound and the desired target areas. For example compounds with cholesterol based formulas can be very toxic so if non specific targeting is required it is best to inject via subcutaneous or interperitoneally as higher doses can be used without harm/less risk to the animal model.

I act as a middle step between the researchers and the animal care technicians, making sure researchers get the data they need as well as maintaining respect for the care technicians. Making sure the work is carried out as quick as possible but following the law and the buildings regulations aimed at protecting and improving animal welfare.

I carry out the technical in vivo procedures on mice, under a PIL license. Procedures include but are not limited too; intravenous, intramuscular, intraperitoneal, subcutaneous injections as well as intrathecal cannulation surgeries.

I will also carry out lab work analysing tissue samples which I collect at the end of in vivo experiments through schedule 1 culling and harvesting of the animal models. Including but not limited too RNA extraction, cDNA synthesis and qPCR processing.

For some researchers I have done data analysis too a lesser extent.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

In vivo experiments in animals are vital; not only are they required by law for new pharmacological products but they provide invaluable data for research such as our which focuses on genetic neurological disorders (such as Duchenne Muscular Dystrophy).

For the group (of around 20 researchers with many research assistants and students) having one person who can perform a variety of in vivo procedures means that they as individuals do not need to take both the time and money to train and learn a procedure that realistically they will use very rarely.

I not only help the group save money by reducing the need for individual licenses for many researchers I also save all researchers time and help improve the speed of in vivo experiments being completed. For example it can take an individual multiple training sessions to learn and be signed off for a intravenous injection into the tail vein of mice, this can take weeks due to trainer availability. this means a delayed

start for the in vivo experiment and less time for the researcher to continue with experiment planning or writing up publications. It also can mean more animals used for the study as animals have to be culled via the training they cannot stay alive after training is conducted (even when using non-active compound or water).

I also feel that another great benefit to the research my role brings is standardisation to in vivo experiments. All procedures I do are done in a controlled and methodical way meaning all intravenous injections are done the same way. All prep work and steps are the same so the only variation would be the compound. This helps create more reliable data in the long term experiment as well helping cross and compared experiment data.

on another point the standardisation helps maintain and improve animal welfare which again helps the reliability of data provided by ensuring a better animal model that is as free from pain and distress as much as possible depending on the procedure being carried out.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

I feel animal procedure work is very hidden as it is an ethical concern obviously and no organisation really like to highlight and showcase animal models being used for research.

However it is a vital and needed work, legally required and as of now we have no non-animal models which can be used for gene therapy production that provide better whole body and target disease reliable model.

As I don't often help with publication (such as writing or contributing much data analysis) I am never included on the authorship of papers produced even with helping in the in vivo experiments. In research I found unless you are a co author of a paper you can get very overlooked.

Currently, for my department (and as far as I know organisation) I am the only one in my role or a role similar to mine where technical skills are solely focused on in vivo procedures and experiments. My official job title is research assistant but I feel my personal role is not encapsulated in this job title role. I provide professional, technical and often rare skills (one of 3 people in oxford university who is signed off for intrathecal cannulation) to both assist and carry out research; which I feel is often over looked or swept up in the research assistant title.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 434

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Holmes, Kate

Organisation/University: University of Bristol

Nominating other (name): Research Support, Open Access Team

Nominating other (organisation): University of Bristol

Description of submission

Summary

The University of Bristol Open Access Team contributes to the success of research by putting Open Access (OA) at the heart of what we do. We have built an organisational culture where our user-centred processes lead researchers to embrace OA publishing as the default, increasing the visibility and reach of their research.

Our team places our researchers at the centre of processes that we are committed to continuously improving. We educate them on administrative requirements and support them throughout their publication journey, by offering a combination of online training and information alongside individualised support and advice. This involves rigorous hidden work that assures they meet their contractual, funding and policy obligations without inserting barriers into their communication goals. We strongly advocate for our authors to retain their rights. Publishing through our Scholarly Works Policy protects their intellectual property even if they choose to publish via the traditional, subscription route.

Building culture is no simple task. It requires selfless commitment, professional humility and the ability to support researchers. The only way to do this is by mastering a broad and constantly changing body of knowledge, ranging from individual copyright agreements to institutional policies. This creates a palpable sense of trust that is deeply felt but rarely publicly credited. One recent emailer articulated it evocatively as, 'I like this level of care.'

The impact of our work is research that has global reach that extends beyond traditional metrics, to provide global equity of access to information. It enables us to fulfil our civic duty by meeting the ethical imperative to extend access to marginalised groups, those who live in academic deserts, or those who lack the financial means to penetrate paywalls. It also increases engagement, collaboration via visibility and diversity of thought in the advancement of research fields.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

OA is a vital means of communicating research that contributes to Open Research Culture, acting as the visible, accessible, front door to Open Research practices. Making research freely available online is an ethical imperative also driven by compliance with fast-moving funder and REF OA policies. Our team helps researchers achieve their communication goals and obligations through rigorous administrative processes and 'knowledgeable' customer services (recent survey feedback). Our work improving record metadata increases research visibility through searchability.

OA improves research culture by ensuring non-academic and low-income communities can read research about themselves, either through publisher charges, or - at no cost to the author or reader - on our institutional repository. We mobilise up-to-date sector knowledge to shift our academics behaviours through our practices, training and communications. Our Scholarly Works Policy prioritises making research free for readers, at no cost to the researcher, while enabling researchers to retain their copyright by applying Creative Commons licenses. This doesn't place additional demands on academics, which has meant more research is freely and immediately available via our repository. We support

researchers by increasing the visibility of non-traditional outputs by making them OA, encouraging researchers to attach any file format to institutional repository research records.

Our support enables researchers to make equitable OA choices. For instance, advising Zenodo as a means of enabling one researchers' work to be given the same significance as other special issue contributors based in lower income countries, when our researcher's work could have been given more visibility via an institutional OA deal.

We work with educators to promote our students-as-researchers by using our institutional repository as a publishing platform, improving the long-term stability and visibility of student research eg Bristol Institute for Learning and Teaching Student Research Journal.

Our interest in access led us to lobby our repository supplier to include the 'Request an Accessible Copy' option on every record. Other initiatives include developing Author Accepted Manuscript templates to encourage screen reader friendly manuscripts as standard.

Our team supports researchers from grant writing to how to publish OA when leaving our University. For those new to publishing we provide a source of advice and help researchers find ways OA can support their methodology eg recommending Diamond (community-funded) publishers for an output developed through participatory workshops. We invest in Diamond initiatives and infrastructure that make OA available to those without institutional funds/support. We are committed to making initiatives more visible through face-to-face training and the inclusion of Diamond OA journals in our journal search tool - an unforeseen benefit being more non-English language publications are visible to our researchers.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Researchers often see publication as the end of their research journey rather than as an integral 'how' of communication. Our OA team quietly promotes the San Francisco Declaration on Research Assessment's ethos by proactively inviting researchers to think about life beyond traditional output types and publishing routes, rather than 'impact factors'. We encourage academics to embrace Diamond or Green OA, with the latter's flexible media formats and in line with our Scholarly Works Policy. By eschewing traditional metrics and formats, we look to the long-term benefit of encouraging as many readers as possible towards their work, which will educate, inform and inspire future research; ultimately leading to greater impact in their fields. Our OA Team's work acts as an iceberg with vast amounts of work taking place below the surface-view of academics. From policy development and guidance to supporting individuals through the process, our work is critical to the long-term impact of our academics' outputs, but we are rarely acknowledged as a contributing factor to the success of their research.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 436

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Senior Web Developer

Name: Seth, Anil

Organisation/University: University of Sussex

Nominating other (name): Alvarez, James

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Dr. James Alvarez, from the University of Sussex, is a Senior Web Developer who has been integral to an ambitious citizen science project, The Perception Census. Dr. Alvarez has worked tirelessly since 2021 on many essential aspects of this unique online experiment. It simply would not have been possible without his contributions.

The Perception Census (<https://perceptioncensus.dreamachine.world/>) is one of the largest ever scientific studies on perception. The academic leads are Professor Anil Seth (neuroscientist, University of Sussex) and Professor Fiona Macpherson (philosopher, University of Glasgow). It was commissioned and produced by Collective Act as part of the Dreamachine Programme, a unique collaboration blending leading academic researchers with world-class artists (<https://dreamachine.world/>).

The Perception Census is a suite of over 60 online questionnaires, interactive tasks and illusions, and educational resources developed to examine individual differences in perception. Running from June 2022 to November 2023, 33,780 people took part, completing nearly 800,000 tasks. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 80s and hailed from 133 countries. Data analysis is ongoing.

The scale and aim of The Perception Census posed distinctive challenges in design, implementation, and rollout which required deep integration of science, design, and critically, innovative web development and data services. Dr Alvarez's skills and proactive attitude were invaluable in this regard. He worked extensively on many aspects: implementing experimental tasks, creating and managing data services, ensuring data privacy, anonymity, and integrity, verifying data quality, summarising findings, and more. His combination of technical prowess with deep familiarity and fluency with academic research is, we think, highly underappreciated.

As the academic leads, we (Seth and Macpherson) have long recognised that bringing Dr. Alvarez into the collaboration was the moment we knew that the Census could be a success. His combination of abilities is very rare, and we hope that his work will get the wide recognition it deserves.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The significance of this submission turns on Dr. Alvarez's central role in bringing The Perception Census into existence, and in ensuring its successful roll-out and enduring scientific value.

When it comes to online scientific studies of perception involving the general public, the Perception Census (PC) is an unprecedentedly ambitious attempt to map out this inner diversity. Previous studies have looked at one or a few aspects of perception, but PC is the first to examine many different forms of perception together, painting a detailed and multi-dimensional picture of how we each encounter the world in a unique way.

This scale and ambition posed unique challenges. Creating the PC involved developing dozens of experimental tasks examining different aspects of perception, making them accessible and easy for

users to complete by themselves on their own computers, and ensuring that the users had (as much as possible) a fun and engaging experience. It also involved creating a data back-end that could safely and robustly manage a wide range of experimental personal data.

Much has been achieved, but these challenges are ongoing as we move to the analysis stage. The data has to be handled carefully in order to render it useful for testing hypothesis, while respecting data privacy and constraints arising from pre-registration. The entire database will be made openly available to the scientific community to spark further discovery and new hypotheses.

Dr. Alvarez's contributions have been absolutely central to meeting these challenges. He programmed and/or integrated the 54 (widely varying) experimental tasks, and created the front-end for users accessing the site. He created and managed the back-end database. He ensured data privacy and integrity, verified data quality, organised and automated data extraction and transformation for tasks, and circulated the data to the individual research collaborators. He also summarised findings for the research team, set up pages for open sourcing the data and experiments, and -not least - made sure that The Census was robust under high data load, and that it scaled infrastructure to save budget after the main period of activity.

Experiments like The Perception Census involve collecting potentially sensitive personal data, in this case, at scale. Here, Dr. Alvarez was again invaluable in working with the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) to deliver the Census. He ensured that the PC ran smoothly from remote servers, in ways that furnished clean and interpretable data, and that participant pseudo-anonymity was rigorously maintained according to stringent ethical application and approval. We believe the PC represents a new standard in how to combine citizen science with data privacy.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Throughout all the above, James has been a joy to work with. He anticipates problems ahead of time, always comes up with creative solutions, exemplifies rigour and reliability, and gave the rest of the team the confidence that we could do what hasn't been done before. And, with his help, we did. We are delighted that the PC as a whole (but not James specifically!) was awarded an honorable mention for the EU Prize in Citizen Science (2024).

Altogether, the findings of the PC have the potential to rewrite our understanding of how we perceive the world, forming a unique body of scientific and philosophical research that will be valuable for years to come.

The Perception Census is an unusual citizen science project involving many different elements, from design and focus grouping, to robust implementation suitable for large-scale deployment. Making it a success required the combination of strong web development skills and in-depth familiarity with the needs of academic research, a combination which Dr. Alvarez exemplifies. Web development in general is often undervalued in academia despite it being crucial to innovations reaching the public and having impact. Overall, contributions like those made by Dr. Alvarez are typically not recognised within current research and evaluation culture, which tends to prioritise externally visible scientific aspects, such as publications, and public impact.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-1421-6051

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Professor Fiona Macpherson (other lead academic), University of Glasgow

Funding acknowledgements: UK Government via Unboxed 2022; Canadian Institute for Advanced Research

Entry: 437

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Measham, Fiona

Organisation/University: University of Liverpool

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I set up a charity in 2012 which combined cutting edge technology with a harm reduction ethos, as a university action research project and pioneering health service. The Loop introduced the UK's first onsite drug testing for harm reduction purposes, 'back of house' testing, at nightclubs in 2013 and at festivals in 2014. It was at this point that I applied the use of a specific type of analytical process, Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy, to achieve a reduction in harm from taking illegal drugs of unknown content or strength. This came about because I sat on a government scientific committee and listened to chemists presenting their work testing for police intelligence purposes. I shadowed the Home Office and TICTAC chemists who were using that technology onsite at UK festivals. FTIR is a rapid and reliable analytical laboratory method which makes it ideal for mobile labs in such settings.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As founder and director of The Loop, I then spoke with national and international stakeholders, I spent time doing media and social media, alongside writing some of the first peer reviewed academic papers on harm reduction. I publicised the value of FTIR for drug checking and drug testing purposes. FTIR was then adopted by a New Zealand drug checking charity called Know Your Stuff in 2015 (one of the earliest adopters), then in Australia from 2018, and in other European and North American drug checking organisations. FTIR is now the number 1 core government-approved technology of New Zealand drug checking services, embedded within its legislative framework after the passing of the Drug Checking Act in 2021. FTIR is now the primary technology used by drug checking services across the world to reduce drug-related harm. It would be impossible to quantify how many overdoses, hospital admissions and potentially even drug-related deaths have been averted around the world due to the use of FTIR in drug checking services. However, to give just one measure from my own work, 2/3 of people throw away their drugs and don't take them if they are tested and found to be other than what they thought they had bought, thereby reducing the risk of poisoning from adulterated or contaminated drugs (Measham and Simmons, 2022). This issue is ever more important with the growing adulteration of the illicit drug market with synthetic substances causing a declared public health crisis.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Although the technology is very widely used around the world for harm reduction purposes now, the origins of its application for harm reduction purposes are hidden for several reasons. Firstly, I am a criminologist and the development was in the field of applying chemistry to health services, there wouldn't be any reason for a chemistry academic to know the story behind the new application of the technology, due to the boundaries between academic disciplines and also between academia and service delivery. (I was jumping lanes in terms of both!) Secondly, the nature of drug testing for harm reduction is that it is at the cutting edge with legal and political sensitivities, so planning and negotiations happen behind closed doors and out of the public domain. Thirdly, as with the widespread and rapid uptake of any new technology, as time passes, it becomes increasingly difficult to identify the initial instigator/ inventor/ advocate for this new way of working. It has expanded so fast and so far, that it would

be increasingly difficult to track it back to one person. As it is only just over 10 years ago, it is still possible to track the introduction of FTIR for harm reduction purposes back to me but that won't be the case for much longer. A number of people can verify the accuracy of this claim, including Trevor Shine, CEO of TICTAC, and senior staff in the New Zealand Government. This account is also on the website of my charity at www.wearetheloop.org.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Loop Drug Checking Service (charity number 1200533) receives funding from The Tudor Trust.

Entry: 441

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hibbett, Mark

Organisation/University: University Of The Arts London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Simon Hettrick's note: Mark sent me a copy of the comic to share with the Hidden REF panelists.

My submission is a comic strip called "The Adventures Of Administrator-who-is-also-a-Researcher" which has been emailed to info@hidden-ref.org as MH_HiddenRef_AwiaaR.jpg. It tells the everyday story of an administrator who also conducts their own research on their own time. As the strip explains, this helps not only helps them to understand the needs of academic researchers but also to explain these needs to administrative colleagues.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Administrators-who-are-also-Researchers are legion across academia, often continuing research work begun in post-graduate studies alongside their day jobs. We publish papers, attend and organise conferences, and submit our own funding bids, and then we use the skills we gain from this to help academics do the same.

For example, my own ongoing research experience in Comics Studies has been vital to my role as UAL's Head of Research Information Systems as it has allowed me to plan processes from the researcher's point of view and explain the reasons for these processes to other professional services staff. Also, having a list of research outputs longer than some academics is a great way of getting them to actually listen to me!

The fact that academia follows what The Times Literary Supplement calls a "dualistic approach", whereby staff must be categorised as either academic or professional services, means that we cannot be officially recognised for this work. Thus we receive no financial support or allocated time, and so our research must be conducted out of our own pockets and in our own time, despite the contribution it makes to the overall research culture.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

There are three ways that this activity is hidden within the current culture.

Firstly, although the new REF guidelines claim to cover the research culture as a whole, it only includes those who have "significant responsibility for research" in their contract. This means that those who are research active but work on non-academic contracts are personally excluded, even though their research outputs may be included.

Secondly, on a practical level, there are usually no funds for administrators to pursue research, so that - for example - they are forced to take annual leave to attend conferences. Here they may present papers in the name of their institutions, but all fees, travels expenses and accommodation costs must be met from their own pocket. This restricts their ability to attend, and hides them from the culture.

Finally, there is not even a proper description for this activity. Staff must be either "academic" or "professional services" and so those of us who straddle both fields can only be officially recognised for the one stated in our contract.

This submission is therefore not really about my own position, but about all those of us who work in this

way, in the hope that it will encourage recognition and, if at all possible, a better name than "administrator who is also a researcher".

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2170-5689>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 447

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Irving, Samantha

Organisation/University: Royal Brompton and Harefield NHS Foundation Trust

Nominating other (name): Henderson, Laura

Nominating other (organisation): Royal Brompton Hospital

Description of submission

Summary

Laura is a Research Development Manager at the Royal Brompton Hospital, part of Guys and St Thomas' Foundation Trust. She supports our community of clinicians and researchers to make timely and appropriate submissions to many different funding calls. She and her team have been pivotal in preparing 80 applications to research bodies so far in 2024 alone.

Laura has developed special expertise in assisting nurses, AHPs and other non-medical professions allied to healthcare with their applications for personal fellowships.

Non-medical researchers are underrepresented in the research context, despite campaigns from major funders such as the NIHR to improve representation. Key barriers include lack of awareness about funding schemes, lack of understanding of what constitutes a good application, and difficulties in completing sections covering organisational liability such as signatories and finance.

Laura has recognised this gap and been proactive with the support of her department. Her knowledge of the research field and her skills in communication are evident in the very comprehensive package of assistance she provides for this workforce. Laura's style is reassuring so that research novices are confident that no question is too basic and nothing that's too much trouble. She shows as much curiosity and enthusiasm for a first research internship application as for a postdoctoral fellowship, and she assists people at every stage.

Candidates report they are confident and optimistic when they know their application has been supported by Laura but her support is for the most part hidden. Our Trust has generic awards for administrative staff but nothing that recognises an individual who is so key to the research process.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Appropriateness

In some institutions tailored support is only available once a researcher has achieved success in the field. Laura's knowledge of the research context and clinical application of research ensures that inexperienced clinical staff seeking her advice will be guided to design ethically framed projects that reflect best research practice.

Cost

Many of individuals seeking Laura's advice are busy NHS clinicians who must find brief periods of time within a busy clinic schedule or spend their own time researching topics and research designs. Laura's expertise ensures that time is not wasted on poor background literature searches, badly framed research questions or inappropriate study designs. She is therefore contributing to cost efficient working for NHS staff interested in improving the evidence base for their work.

Excellence

The package of assistance Laura provides to researchers is extensive and could be used as a model for other NHS organisations looking to support non-medical led research. Laura circulates funding calls as they are made. Having a thorough understanding of the focus and eligibility criteria for the very wide range of opportunities, Laura uses example of previous submissions (with permission) when providing support. She often summarises Programme Chairs' reports and shares up to date information from previous rounds. Laura helps candidates to navigate guidance notes and application forms. She coordinates other departments like Finance and HR and she advises applicants on appropriate

signatories. She plays a vital role in assisting department leads and manager, who may not be researchers, to understand what is expected of them. When candidates are shortlisted, Laura supports them by organising mock interviews and detailed feedback. After a successful application Laura liaises with contracting colleagues and helps the individual to notify the relevant people.

When candidates are unsuccessful, Laura reads the reviews thoroughly and provides detailed and constructive feedback and additional notes to help them produce an improved application, thus encouraging inexperienced non-medical professionals, who may feel discouraged at an early stage.

Relevance

The majority of funded research opportunities are not tailored to research topics and study designs suitable for research delivered by non-medical healthcare staff. Laura's knowledge of schemes and her track record with professions allied to medicine ensure that her guidance is relevant to the individuals career structure and clinical context.

Temporality

Laura's has formed long term working relationships with clinical and research staff over several years. She remembers their interests and backgrounds, and shares opportunities or news that she knows will be a good fit. She's also supported many researchers through challenges or maternity career breaks, to enable them to restart their research afterwards.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite the very high value of Laura's work to clinical and research colleagues and thereby to patients and families, funders and employers have not previously formally recognised excellence in research support. Laura's work is not included in any metrics or reported to funders. Laura is referred to as 'Research Support Participant', on applications and not therefore personally acknowledged for her essential role. Recognition from the Hidden REF project would demonstrate how much she is valued to our NHS Trust and university partners the importance of her work, and maybe even allow other centres to adopt this model of working.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 448

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Librarians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priston, Sarah

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): Drake, Claire

Nominating other (organisation): Bath Spa University

Description of submission

Summary

I am writing to nominate the Research Support Librarians at Bath Spa University for their hidden work supporting the submission of non-text-based outputs to the REF. Specifically, their work in relation to improving the process for creating and submitting creative practice research portfolios to the REF and promoting this type of research more widely. Their work builds on the work of the wider Library and Research Support Office team that led to the preparation of over 100 portfolios for REF2021, which formed around 25% of Bath Spa's submission to REF2021 and which were made Open Access at the time of submission to the REF.

Post REF2021, the Research Support Librarians embarked on a project to assess the REF2021 submissions both from Bath Spa University and other institutions and to improve the process at Bath Spa University for REF 2029. The team consulted with the AHRC-funded PR Voices and Sparkle teams, other HEIs, and suppliers of repositories, specifically HAPLO/CAYUSE and Figshare over the effectiveness of repositories for storing and showcasing practice research. School research leads at Bath Spa University were also consulted for their views on the outputs, then meetings were held with 20 HEIs who submitted creative practice research to REF2021.

The project led to the realisation that practice researchers without a PhD or prior REF experience needed additional assistance or training to write the necessary 300-word supporting statement, etc., for their REF submission. We also found that practice researchers felt 'left out' because they felt that 'everything' was aimed at STEM researchers, particularly the language that is used, e.g. data. The fact that in many repositories, arts research had to be classified as 'other' was also found to be a problem. The Research Support Librarians made a series of actions to endeavour to resolve these issues.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The first outcome of the project was to move from submitting portfolio content entirely via our Figshare repository, BathSPAdata, to a PDF-based submission. The PDFs will contain links to audio-visual content in BathSPAdata. This change has been favourably received by researchers at BSU, who feel that having a permanent, downloadable record of the entire research process puts their practice research on a par with research published in journal articles. They also welcomed the idea of creating a resource that can be shared with research contacts and added to student module reading lists. This has led to increased enthusiasm to spend the additional time necessary to collate a REF portfolio.

The linear format of the PDF will make it easier for REF assessors to read and assess the portfolios. The Research Support Librarians are working towards making practice research Open Access via BSU's repositories as soon as possible after the completion of each project, leading to improved citations and visibility for practice research at BSU.

To resolve some of the issues for practice researchers at Bath Spa University, the Research Support Librarians devised a new form which can be used by researchers to prepare a draft of the necessary textual content for a REF submission (300-word statement, research questions, research timeline). The

form contains guidance and headings to assist researchers with putting together their content. Each draft form is shared with the Research Support Librarians, Research Support Office, school research and UoA leads so that staff can obtain support with the process of recording their research.

The Research Support Librarians now lead university, school, research centre, and individual meetings with researchers advising how to put together a REF portfolio. Liaising with the Research Support Office, a new Researcher Development Programme session on writing the necessary textual content for a REF portfolio submission has also been established and has been running since 2023-24. External consultants have been invited into the University by the Research Support Office to give additional advice to researchers.

This project directly led to the establishment by the Research Support Librarians of a jiscmail list to for Library and Research Support staff in the UK to share best practice, arts-practice-led-research@jiscmail.ac.uk, and also to the establishment of an annual conference to raise the profile of practice research and to share best practice, Capturing Creativity. This took place as a one-day conference in September 2023 and was expanded, by popular demand, to a week of events in September 2024. Bath Spa recruited the assistance of Dr. Gareth Cole and the research support team at Loughborough University to help organise and manage these events.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Note from Simon Hettrick: Sarah got in touch to say that this should be a joint application from Claire Drake and Becky Atkins. We will need to understand whether to do this as two separate-but-equal applications to the Hidden Role.

Practice Research should form a proportion of REF outputs submitted by institutions who have Arts departments and could be submitted by researchers in other UoAs. However, in REF 2021 only 46 out of 157 HEI submissions submitted greater than 5% of non-text-based outputs.

The work of Librarians in supporting researchers to add their research to institutional repositories is also not recognised by the REF, and yet their work is essential in ensuring that research is not only added to repositories but made Open Access. Whether in terms of helping to compile and then copyright-check practice research portfolios so that they can be made Open Access; coordinating the payment of individual APCs and publisher Read & Publish deals to make text-based research Open Access; their wider work with promoting Green Open Access and Rights Retention strategies in order to comply with Funder and REF requirements; or metadata and compliance-checking repository records of research outputs prior to REF submission, the work that Librarians do in the area of Research Support is essential to any HEI REF submission.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 449

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Viggiani, Giulia

Organisation/University: University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): Desnerck, Pieter

Nominating other (organisation): Department of Engineering University of Cambridge

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Pieter Desnerck, Senior Technical Manager of the UKCRIC National Research Facility for Infrastructure Sensing (NRFIS) at the University of Cambridge, plays a pivotal role in advancing research through his extensive expertise in experimental design, data acquisition and advanced test methodologies. With a PhD from Ghent University and extensive international research experience, including positions at the University of Sherbrooke, Missouri University of Science and Technology, and Brunel University, Dr Desnerck has made significant contributions across academia and industry. Since rejoining Cambridge in 2018 to establish NRFIS, Dr Desnerck has been instrumental in fostering collaborations between academic and industrial partners, enhancing the scope and impact of NRFIS projects such as the large-scale tests for HS2, Heathrow Airport and Network Rail. His guidance in using sophisticated equipment and his deep knowledge of testing frameworks have directly supported key research projects in infrastructure sensing, helping researchers achieve reliable, high-quality results. One notable research output is the paper, "Carbon Reduction and Strength Enhancement in Functionally Graded Reinforced Concrete Beams," published in *Engineering Structures*, Vol. 277 (DOI: 10.1016/j.engstruct.2022.115358). These contributions are vital for both fundamental research and applied industry solutions, particularly in fields like civil engineering and infrastructure monitoring. Although Dr Desnerck's academic-related role does not directly contribute to REF recognition, his influence is undeniable. His ability to bridge the gap between cutting-edge research and practical implementation has strengthened NRFIS's research output, exemplified by the paper "Experimental Investigation and Modelling of Carbonation of Functionally Graded Layered Concrete for Cement Content Reduction," published in *Cement and Concrete Research* (DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4525280). His contributions not only ensure the facility's smooth operation but also enable researchers to push boundaries and achieve meaningful, high-impact results.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As NRFIS Senior Technical Manager, Dr Desnerck plays a vital role in advancing research in infrastructure sensing. His leadership in developing and managing this world-class facility has been instrumental in driving significant academic and industrial advancements.

Dr Desnerck's oversight of the ~£5 million laboratory fit-out exemplifies his management and technical expertise. By working closely with academics, suppliers and finance teams, he facilitated the development of cutting-edge test setups. A notable achievement is his securing of funding for a unique high capacity hydraulic universal testing machine, which enables full-scale testing of components for major infrastructure projects like Hinkley Point C and HS2. This innovation is critical for advancing civil engineering research and addressing real-world challenges in infrastructure resilience and safety. His efforts have extended NRFIS's capabilities across engineering disciplines, expanding its research potential. His expertise in experimental design has supported many research programmes, benefitting both undergraduate and graduate students. A notable publication resulting from this work is "Experimental Investigation of the Rotational Behaviour of Apex Connections in Cold-Formed Steel Portal Frames" (DOI: 10.17863/CAM.106446). Dr Desnerck's leadership in equipment maintenance, procurement, and health and safety practices has become a model for other departments, elevating the university's standards.

He also developed a bespoke health and safety system, aligned with HSE legislation, ensuring NRFIS operates with the highest level of safety. This system now serves as a benchmark across the university. Additionally, Dr Desnerck established NRFIS as a Small Research Facility (SRF), ensuring financial sustainability and proper equipment maintenance.

Beyond his technical contributions, he has fostered a culture of knowledge sharing by training staff and students in data acquisition and measurement techniques, nurturing the next generation of researchers. His involvement in the Centre for Postdoctoral Development in Infrastructure, Cities and Energy further demonstrates his commitment to developing world-class talent in the infrastructure sectors.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite Dr Desnerck's pivotal role in advancing research, his contributions are often overlooked in a system that prioritises traditional academic outputs such as publications and citations. As a Senior Technical Manager, his work is essential to the success of many research projects, yet it remains unrecognised by formal evaluation metrics like the REF. This oversight stems from the academic-related nature of his role, which differs from conventional academic posts. His critical efforts, 'overseeing large-scale laboratory fit-outs, securing advanced equipment, and implementing health and safety systems,' play a fundamental role in research outcomes but are not reflected in the standard criteria for research assessment.

Dr Desnerck's contributions to health and safety, such as developing a comprehensive database platform aligned with HSE legislation (including PUWER and LOLER) to track equipment purchases, compliance, maintenance schedules and training records, are crucial for the smooth and safe operation of the research facility. These efforts nevertheless are often considered 'behind the scenes' and are not rewarded by traditional academic metrics. His leadership in establishing access procedures for cross-departmental use of the facilities has opened new avenues for interdisciplinary and industry collaborations, yet these contributions, which foster innovation remain under-recognised.

Moreover, his role in providing technical expertise and training for students and staff is essential for the effective use of NRFIS's state-of-the-art equipment, yet such contributions are rarely acknowledged in research evaluations. By guiding experimental test programmes and offering hands-on training, Dr Desnerck plays a crucial role in shaping research outputs,. For example, the large number of test reports produced by NRFIS (more than 50 reports over four years) often help inform research outputs, but these reports are not eligible for REF.

Recognising technical expertise, health and safety innovation, and interdisciplinary collaboration is vital for redefining research success, making submissions like this essential for broadening research recognition.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-0993-0322

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 450

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: RMAs (Research Managers and Administrators)

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Viggiani, Giulia

Organisation/University: University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): Desnerck, Pieter

Nominating other (organisation): Department of Engineering University of Cambridge

Description of submission

Summary

Dr Pieter Desnerck, Senior Technical Manager of the UKCRIC National Research Facility for Infrastructure Sensing (NRFIS) at the University of Cambridge, plays a pivotal role in advancing research through his extensive expertise in experimental design, data acquisition and advanced test methodologies. With a PhD from Ghent University and extensive international research experience, including positions at the University of Sherbrooke, Missouri University of Science and Technology, and Brunel University, Dr Desnerck has made significant contributions across academia and industry. Since rejoining Cambridge in 2018 to establish NRFIS, Dr Desnerck has been instrumental in fostering collaborations between academic and industrial partners, enhancing the scope and impact of NRFIS projects such as the large-scale tests for HS2, Heathrow Airport and Network Rail. His guidance in using sophisticated equipment and his deep knowledge of testing frameworks have directly supported key research projects in infrastructure sensing, helping researchers achieve reliable, high-quality results. One notable research output is the paper, "Carbon Reduction and Strength Enhancement in Functionally Graded Reinforced Concrete Beams," published in *Engineering Structures*, Vol. 277 (DOI: 10.1016/j.engstruct.2022.115358). These contributions are vital for both fundamental research and applied industry solutions, particularly in fields like civil engineering and infrastructure monitoring. Although Dr Desnerck's academic-related role does not directly contribute to REF recognition, his influence is undeniable. His ability to bridge the gap between cutting-edge research and practical implementation has strengthened NRFIS's research output, exemplified by the paper "Experimental Investigation and Modelling of Carbonation of Functionally Graded Layered Concrete for Cement Content Reduction," published in *Cement and Concrete Research* (DOI: 10.2139/ssrn.4525280). His contributions not only ensure the facility's smooth operation but also enable researchers to push boundaries and achieve meaningful, high-impact results.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As NRFIS Senior Technical Manager, Dr Desnerck plays a vital role in advancing research in infrastructure sensing. His leadership in developing and managing this world-class facility has been instrumental in driving significant academic and industrial advancements.

Dr Desnerck's oversight of the ~£5 million laboratory fit-out exemplifies his management and technical expertise. By working closely with academics, suppliers and finance teams, he facilitated the development of cutting-edge test setups. A notable achievement is his securing of funding for a unique high capacity hydraulic universal testing machine, which enables full-scale testing of components for major infrastructure projects like Hinkley Point C and HS2. This innovation is critical for advancing civil engineering research and addressing real-world challenges in infrastructure resilience and safety. His efforts have extended NRFIS's capabilities across engineering disciplines, expanding its research potential. His expertise in experimental design has supported many research programmes, benefitting both undergraduate and graduate students. A notable publication resulting from this work is "Experimental Investigation of the Rotational Behaviour of Apex Connections in Cold-Formed Steel Portal Frames" (DOI: 10.17863/CAM.106446). Dr Desnerck's leadership in equipment maintenance, procurement, and health and safety practices has become a model for other departments, elevating the university's standards.

He also developed a bespoke health and safety system, aligned with HSE legislation, ensuring NRFIS operates with the highest level of safety. This system now serves as a benchmark across the university. Additionally, Dr Desnerck established NRFIS as a Small Research Facility (SRF), ensuring financial sustainability and proper equipment maintenance.

Beyond his technical contributions, he has fostered a culture of knowledge sharing by training staff and students in data acquisition and measurement techniques, nurturing the next generation of researchers. His involvement in the Centre for Postdoctoral Development in Infrastructure, Cities and Energy further demonstrates his commitment to developing world-class talent in the infrastructure sectors.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite Dr Desnerck's pivotal role in advancing research, his contributions are often overlooked in a system that prioritises traditional academic outputs such as publications and citations. As a Senior Technical Manager, his work is essential to the success of many research projects, yet it remains unrecognised by formal evaluation metrics like the REF. This oversight stems from the academic-related nature of his role, which differs from conventional academic posts. His critical efforts, 'overseeing large-scale laboratory fit-outs, securing advanced equipment, and implementing health and safety systems,' play a fundamental role in research outcomes but are not reflected in the standard criteria for research assessment.

Dr Desnerck's contributions to health and safety, such as developing a comprehensive database platform aligned with HSE legislation (including PUWER and LOLER) to track equipment purchases, compliance, maintenance schedules and training records, are crucial for the smooth and safe operation of the research facility. These efforts nevertheless are often considered 'behind the scenes' and are not rewarded by traditional academic metrics. His leadership in establishing access procedures for cross-departmental use of the facilities has opened new avenues for interdisciplinary and industry collaborations, yet these contributions, which foster innovation remain under-recognised.

Moreover, his role in providing technical expertise and training for students and staff is essential for the effective use of NRFIS's state-of-the-art equipment, yet such contributions are rarely acknowledged in research evaluations. By guiding experimental test programmes and offering hands-on training, Dr Desnerck plays a crucial role in shaping research outputs,. For example, the large number of test reports produced by NRFIS (more than 50 reports over four years) often help inform research outputs, but these reports are not eligible for REF.

Recognising technical expertise, health and safety innovation, and interdisciplinary collaboration is vital for redefining research success, making submissions like this essential for broadening research recognition.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-0993-0322

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 466

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Design Manager

Name: Holliday, Nikki

Organisation/University: Coventry University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to put forward a submission for my work as a Design Manager within a Research Centre. The role supports research developed collaboratively with input from the public, patients, clinicians, and other stakeholders. This approach ensures that research is more relevant and thus impactful by embedding diverse perspective. The Design Manager role supports and enhances engagement and impact in research not only by tailoring outputs to make complex findings explorable and accessible during the data collection phase, and by fully involving patients, the public and a wide variety of stakeholders in the design and execution of research. This ensures that research is inclusive but also aligns with real-world needs, which supports impact and societal and academic value. Design professionals, and in particular those with co-creation skills in research are thus important, as they advocate and support a more inclusive system that acknowledges the vital role of co-creation in achieving research success.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The role of a Design Manager with co-creation skills is essential in meeting several key criteria of the Hidden REF. A Design Manager ensures that research methods and outputs are tailored to the target audience by applying design methodologies to meet the specific needs and contexts of relevant stakeholders. This includes selecting and adapting arts and design-based research tools that resonate with diverse groups, making the research more inclusive, accessible, and impactful.

Including a Design Manager in a research department can also lead to cost savings. By integrating co-creation early in the research process and involving patients and the public more deeply, research outputs are aligned with user needs from the start. This approach helps avoid costly revisions, misaligned outcomes, or the development of knowledge that doesn't translate into real-world applications, ultimately resulting in more cost-effective research.

Additionally, Design Managers facilitate interdisciplinary collaboration by acting as a bridge between researchers and stakeholders, such as patients, clinicians, engineers, and third-sector workers. They guide the co-creation process, ensuring that all voices are heard, fostering an inclusive environment where diverse perspectives are integrated. Their ability to facilitate dialogue ensures that the research is not only robust but also inclusive of a broad range of disciplinary viewpoints.

Furthermore, Design Managers use their skills to translate complex research findings into visual and interactive formats that are easily understood by non-experts. This not only enhances stakeholder engagement but also broadens the impact and dissemination of the research.

Lastly, the co-creation skills of a Design Manager promote reflective practice, enabling researchers to continually evaluate their positionality and the impact of their work on different stakeholders. This ongoing reflexivity ensures that research remains ethically grounded and socially responsible.

Co-creation methods can also be adapted to equalize power dynamics among stakeholders who may have varying levels of influence or assumed authority in society.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

My work as a Design Manager at Coventry University highlights a critical issue in research culture: the undervaluation of contributions from a design thinking perspective. My work focuses on involving the

public, patients, and key healthcare practitioners and clinicians in healthcare intervention research. Despite my more traditional research outputs such as publications, much of the work, particularly that form the Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) aspect remains overlooked with regards the research impact. This underappreciation reflects a broader systemic issue, where non-academic roles in design, project management, and public engagement are often seen as peripheral to research success. My contributions can be largely 'behind-the-scenes' in terms of the REF assessment, such as supporting the co-creation of research grants and feasible project plans with patients and the public, and the design and development of the actual health and care interventions which are the product of research. However, because co-creation and PPIE outputs do not align with traditional academic measures, the excellence and rigour, as well as their impact on the success of the funding grants and the eventual conducted research, means that these contributions remain unmeasured. The oversight of these types of contributions underscores a need for change in research culture, where the focus shifts from narrow, publication-driven metrics to a more holistic evaluation system that values diverse contributions, including design thinking, co-creation and stakeholder engagement to support originality, rigour and impact in our work. Addressing this gap is essential for fostering a more equitable and innovative research environment.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 477

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: mclaughlin, scott

Organisation/University: University of Leeds

Nominating other (name): Bradburne, Colin

Nominating other (organisation): University of Leeds

Description of submission

Summary

My research involves experimental approaches to musical instruments for composition and performance, usually by altering ('preparing') them: this is a tradition that is best known in the work of John Cage in the 1950s, but existed in less public ways before this. In order to carry out my research I have to make these preparations, and while my prototypes are often enough to work as a proof of concept, the rigour in my research is facilitated by our school technician Colin Bradburne who contributes to the research by perfecting the design and construction of the instrument preparations. It's important to note here that Colin doesn't simply implement my designs, he provides invaluable insight to materials and construction by iterating through versions until we get to what works best. Colin is very much an active researcher as we co-think the best ways to achieve the research goal. I can safely say that without Colin's enthusiasm, expertise, and active involvement, the research would be poorer and in some cases not happened at all since as well as solving my problems Colin also suggested entirely novel devices that have since become central to the work

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Significance:

As stated above, since John Cage's work in the 1950s on the 'prepared piano' there has been continued use of these preparations by composers and performers, but very little work has been done on (a) applying these ideas to other instruments for compositional purposes*, and (b) advancing the research from simply creating new 'static' timbres to embracing the dynamic possibilities of preparations that can transform the resonant characteristics of an instrument and open up quasi-chaotic timbral structures that can be explored in composition and performance. My work extends both of these fields by developing novel preparations but also developing novel performance techniques, and the compositional techniques to explore them, and notational strategies to disseminate these to the communities.

Colin's contribution has ranged from implementing my ideas as 3D printed objects, and developing and implementing novel solutions to problems that I cannot solve, but also he has extended my work with completely novel approaches to questions I had not yet asked. For example:

- Colin implemented my 3d print design of grooved ring-like preparations to fit a range of violin/cello/bass strings; with varying thickness and materials to alter how they affect the string timbre. These couple together two adjacent strings so that vibrations pass between them and they modulate each other, leading to highly novel inharmonic timbres.
- Colin then designed and built a new preparation that could work on electric guitars using an EBow resonator in place of the bow used by violins etc. To make this work required a preparation that could skip over one string, which Colin achieved using a curved design. I had not even considered this possibility so this contribution is entirely Colin's.
- Colin also designed a casing and power-unit to allow an EBow, which is designed for use on a guitar, to work on piano strings: solving various issues of different string spacings, and greater string thickness/mass which required more power. Colin subsequently iterated this over several minor design

improvements

- Colin is currently developing a casing for small loudspeakers that can be attached to pianist's fingers to explore performative feedback generation. Colin suggested varying enclosure port size to vary feedback frequency and response.

While the initial project impulse and direction came from me, Colin's contribution has taken it much farther than I could have alone.

* some improvisors also use preparations on other instruments but these techniques are always specific to one player's practice, and lack any documentation or dissemination. Also, the practice is different to that of composers, who are the primary audience for my research.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Colin's contribution is overlooked because, while I will mention his contribution as technician, the current repository and output structures/formats don't allow for explicit identification of collaborators, or for their contribution to be properly documented.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-5869-1869

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 491

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Hamilton, jeremy

Organisation/University: ulster university

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Hidden ref submission: JWW.Hamilton

Jeremy has provided critical support to student support, academic research, tech transfer, prototyping and commercialisation activities whilst working at ulster university.

These activities include in extensive youth outreach, playing a critical role in engineering futures events and the Belfast science festival to promote science and engineering. Whilst also engaging in Nuffield foundation to enable access to research placements for predominantly female students considering a career in STEM.

Regarding technology development and transfer Jeremy was part of a team that brought prestige to UK universities by beating other global universities to the final of an X-Prize tricorder competition. Wherein we designed built and tested software and hardware diagnostics to empower ordinary people to diagnose over 20 medical potential medical conditions by themselves see;

<https://www.siliconrepublic.com/machines/ulster-university-tricorder-prize>

<http://www.usatoday.com/story/news/nation/2014/08/27/qualcomm-tricorder-xprize/14586959/>

More recently Jeremy worked as part of a team to develop and deploy technology for drinking water purification and remote water quality assessment in LMICs. Through working with local NGOs in Mexico, Colombia, Brazil, India and Africa they were able to employ technology to improve the health outcomes of those from lower socio-economic communities in See

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=fHFh4mAeJhs>

<https://www.safewater-research.com/safewater-technologies/translate>

<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=BMEaXDE2NOW>

Through performing extensive laboratory characterisation Jeremy has co-authored over 50 peer review publications generating close to 8 thousand of citations see

<https://scholar.google.com.sg/citations?user=3QQaTYAAAAAJ&hl=en>

Which if included in the google scholar ranking for ulster university would put him in the top 20 staff for research output, for comparative citation outputs by institution see

https://scholar.google.com/citations?view_op=view_org&hl=en&org=14457494617935235883&before;_author=VzfQ_0QSAAAJ&astart;=20

However due to the REF independence criteria, Jeremy has never been included in a ref submission

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This submission highlights the people at the bottom of the university hierarchy are often the creators and facilitators of the research outcomes from which universities generate publicity and prestige.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This submission is overlooked due to the REF criteria requiring submitted persons to have independence, ie a research income in their own name. As such contributors such as myself other technicians and post doctoral researchers are excluded from REF despite being creators of many of the outputs attributed to grant holders.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4500-4625>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 492

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Fox, James

Organisation/University: University of York

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The phlebotomy team at the University of York are volunteers who take blood from healthy volunteers for research. They are rigorously trained in venepuncture and consent taking and undertake blood draws when researchers request blood. The phlebotomy team provide access to a vital research 'reagent' that cannot be bought, is essential for multiple research projects and is fundamental to facilitating scientific understanding. The blood provided by the phlebotomy team has been used in studies to provide data for grant applications and publications, for PhD theses, posters, scientific talks and of course to further scientific understanding. The phlebotomy team are never named in grant applications as being an integral part of the team that would undertake the funded grant research and never in person on research outputs. If at all, "The Phlebotomists" may be the way in which the team is acknowledged but the actual people behind the 'phlebotomy team' are never known. To ensure donor anonymity to the researcher and for health and safety reasons, the phlebotomist cannot be the researcher or a member of their direct research team. This means that the phlebotomist gives up their time to undertake a technically difficult procedure but receives no direct benefit from taking the blood. The team consists of four technicians and they are: Jenny Baker, Susanna Rose, Karen Hogg and James Fox, in addition to one more recent addition to the team, an academic and group leader - Katrien Van Bocxlaer. This application is to recognise the vital hidden role of these dedicated and talented individuals.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Scientific research can be undertaken on cell lines but working with human blood is often required, for example to fully understand responses of cells to a variety of stimuli. In the field of blood cancers/immunology (amongst others) attempting to publish fundamental research without using human blood can be difficult and there is an 'expectation' that for higher impact journals work with human blood, rather than cell lines, would either minimally be the focus of the work or that any cell line work is validated in human blood cells. As such, access to fresh human blood unaffected by storage or transport is critical to high impact research. Blood can be purchased, at cost, from some commercial suppliers or the national blood service (research) but these sources often involve significant cost, storage or time in transport after blood draw, which might affect experiments. Access to fresh human blood is really advantageous and scientifically important. The phlebotomy team have provided blood for multiple researchers within multiple research groups at the University of York, the blood has been used in experiments that have provided data for grant applications - which has secured financial support to the grant applicants and the university and may have provided jobs for research staff. The experiments with the blood have provided data for several PhD theses, supporting the next generation of scientists (who in turn may go on to secure grant income). Experiments with the blood have been used in research outputs - presentations, posters, publications etc. supporting the careers of the researchers, supporting understanding, research culture, conferences, editors/journals, outreach, public understanding of science etc.

Ethically, the blood donor should be anonymous to the researcher. This is in case any incidental findings as part of the research, which in the case of research at York is not clinically diagnostic, is suggestive of any potentially medically relevant condition of the donor. For health and safety purposes, working with your own blood or working in the lab where your blood might be present presents a hazard. As such, the

researcher should not take or provide the blood. This means that the phlebotomist should not be the researcher or part of the direct research team. Therefore, there is no real benefit for the phlebotomist in terms of experimental data/outputs. The university does not recognise the phlebotomists with any additional reward, they are all volunteers.

The phlebotomists provide the starting "reagent" for all of the above and for the reasons stated but their role is hidden.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Phlebotomy team are never mentioned in grant applications; without a phlebotomy team delivering blood research would be much more difficult. The individuals within the phlebotomy team are not acknowledged by name and it's possible that researchers may not even know who they are when they receive blood from them! The team consists of 4x technicians and 1x academic. Technicians at our university are not allowed access to "PURE", the university's Current Research and Information System. PURE captures a wide range of research-related outcomes and activities and promotes the University's research excellence to the wider community via the York Research Database (YRD). Despite being a founding signatory of the Technician Commitment and having 'provide access to PURE for technicians' within our actions plans there is resistance from the university so our contributions to research are overlooked. There is no outward facing link to the "phlebotomy service" on the university's webpage and internally no mention of the individuals within the team.

Culturally, when research papers are accepted or grants are awarded the authors celebrate and often invite other academics/researchers but are unaware of phlebotomists being invited to such celebrations. High impact papers are celebrated in internal emails/bulletins or in media releases but only the authors of such research papers are mentioned.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-2473-7029

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 493

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Deputy Director

Name: Long, Susan

Organisation/University: Alleviate Pain Data Hub, University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): Milligan, Gordon

Nominating other (organisation): Alleviate Pain Data Hub, HIC, University of Dundee

Description of submission

Summary

I am honoured to nominate Gordon Milligan for the 'Hidden Role' category in his role as Deputy Director of the Alleviate Data Hub. In addition to his Deputy Director role, Gordon also fulfils the Project Manager role within the project. This dual role spans multiple areas of responsibilities including, but not limited to, managing a large team consisting of data engineers, administrative staff and patient partners, primary responsibility of onboarding data partners, overseeing data transformation and day to day activities within the project which also involves a PPIE workstream.

I believe that Gordon deserves recognition of his exceptional commitment to the project and his unwavering dedication to bridging the gap between scientific research and public engagement, ensuring that the voices of those affected by pain are heard, valued, and integrated into research processes. He continues to prioritise public involvement within the pain research community which is reflected in his enthusiasm for creating campaigns for public engagement and presenting Alleviate's work at various conferences and events nationally and internationally.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Gordon has championed and fostered collaborative partnerships between researchers, patients, healthcare professionals, and the wider community. By facilitating dialogue and mutual learning, he has led a culture of inclusivity and transparency, where research priorities are shaped not just by scientists but also by those who are directly impacted by chronic pain conditions.

Gordon embeds patient representative throughout the Alleviate programme where patient representative is actively involved in co-designing research, setting priorities, and contributing to decision-making processes within the project governance structure.

Gordon has been a vocal advocate for the ethical inclusion of public and patient voices in research, ensuring that their contributions are recognised and respected in all stages of research development.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This is a unique position that Gordon not only fulfils but excels in. It demands skilful and various leadership styles to manage the many different workstreams of this project. He seamlessly transitions from his technical area of expertise and analytical skills: creating a national pain data research hub as part of the wider APDP (Advanced Pain Discovery Platform) initiative by collaborating with partners including other institutions, clinicians, researchers and existing pain data hubs to employing more soft leadership styles when focusing on PPIE (patient and public involvement and engagement), with 7 public members fully embedded into the project team and a further group of over 300 members of a reference community that receive monthly updates on the work Alleviate is doing in pain research. The continued meaningful input from our public members ensures that PPIE is at the heart of Alleviate, rather than just ticking a box.

Gordon is a successful leader which is evidenced by Alleviate's achievements throughout the project.

Alleviate Pain Data Hub's 'Embedding Patient and Public Involvement in the Alleviate Pain Data Hub' won best poster at the Advanced Pain Data Hub (APDP) 1st Annual Conference in June 2023. Alleviate was also awarded in the inaugural Dundee Difference Awards, taking home an award for Positive Impact in January 2024. Alleviate was further recognised by a panel of Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement (PPIE) professionals and Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) public contributors for their work in the chronic pain community. The panel commended the team on their unique inclusion of two community members with lived experience as co-leads and Alleviate's research was applauded for being proactive and exemplary.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0005-6779-7696>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: MRC

Entry: 500

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Open Source Infrastructure Maintainers

Name: Lee Steele, Anne

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission is to collectively nominate the co-leads of the Infrastructure Working Group, consisting of Sarah Gibson, Danny Garside, Brigitta Sipöcz, and Jim Madge, for their crucial contributions as volunteer open-source maintainers to The Turing Way project. They have played a fundamental role in supporting and maintaining The Turing Way, an open-source project that promotes best practices in reproducible, ethical, and inclusive data science.

The Turing Way is a large open science and community-led project at The Alan Turing Institute, widely known and renowned for its high-quality data science handbook. Co-created by a global community, the handbook includes over 350 chapters across five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration, and Ethical Research. With over 500 contributors from various backgrounds, identities and lived experiences, the project has expanded greatly in its past five years of growth. Web analytics show monthly engagement with 7,000 users, 17,000 page views, 35,000 resource downloads (from Zenodo), and 100+ citations to date. Readers and users span multiple countries, including Australia, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, India, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Turkey, the UK, the USA, Venezuela, and beyond. In many ways, The Turing Way itself has become research infrastructure for teams and research labs across the world.

Maintaining and developing this resource has required developing the infrastructure, both human and technical, to support it. The Infrastructure Working Group's expertise has been instrumental in scaling The Turing Way to meet the needs of its growing community while maintaining the project's usability and functionality.

Composed of experienced and long-term contributors to the project, the team stewarded our move from a single Github repository to a broader organisation, liaising across sub-communities and teams within the project to ease this transition. They also work to maintain the project's website, collaborating with other working groups to support their work, automating workflows, and ensuring

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Infrastructure Working Group of The Turing Way, composed of Sarah Gibson, Danny Garside, Brigitta Sipöcz, and Jim Madge, demonstrates significant impact on the global research community by maintaining and developing the infrastructure of one of the most widely-used open-source projects in data science.

Composed of experienced and long-term contributors to the project, the team stewarded our move from a single Github repository to a broader organisation, liaising across sub-communities and teams within the project to ease this transition. They also work to maintain the project's website, collaborating with other working groups to support their work, automating workflows, and ensuring that contributions from our diverse global community are smoothly integrated. Their support ensures that all contributors, from early-career researchers to senior academics, can meaningfully engage with the project, enabling it to remain a vital component of the global research landscape.

By maintaining the backbone of the project, the Infrastructure Working Group has contributed to the advancement of research worldwide, ensuring that best practices in data science continue to be widely shared and implemented through The Turing Way project. Their voluntary, often unrecognised contributions have been critical to the success and sustainability of this impactful research infrastructure, used by many other researchers.

Leadership:

The group has gone beyond what is typically expected of their roles. They have taken on the challenge of managing a complex, evolving infrastructure in a voluntary capacity, contributing significantly to the development of new features and improving user experience. Their leadership in creating robust, scalable infrastructure has set a standard for other open-source projects and has empowered contributors to actively participate in the project.

Furthermore, the team has contributed significantly to the wider notion of maintenance as a core value of The Turing Way community, leading . Shared by working group leads at the FOSS Backstage and FOSDEM conferences in Berlin and Brussels, the Infrastructure Working Group team has.

Responsibility:

The Infrastructure Working Group embodies a deep sense of responsibility to the global research community. Their work ensures that The Turing Way infrastructure remains accessible, functional, and responsive to the needs of users from diverse backgrounds. They are committed to maintaining the project's core principles of openness, collaboration, and inclusivity, which are crucial to its role as a global resource.

Responsibility:

The Infrastructure Working Group embodies a deep sense of responsibility to the global research community. Their work ensures that The Turing Way infrastructure remains accessible, functional, and responsive to the needs of users from diverse backgrounds. They are committed to maintaining the project's core principles of openness, collaboration, and inclusivity, which are crucial to its role as a global resource.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The contributions of the Infrastructure Working Group in The Turing Way are often overlooked in current research culture because research infrastructure, much like other forms of infrastructure, is only noticed when it fails or breaks. The contributions of Sarah Gibson, Danny Garside, Brigitta Sipocz, and Jim Madge embody this hidden role. Their maintenance of the project's infrastructure ,Ä ensuring smooth collaboration across our global network of contributors, automating workflows, as well as managing technical complexities has been crucial to the success of the project, yet is seldom acknowledged as a critical research activity. Their role is akin to Nadia Eghbal's concept of open source maintainers as "digital public infrastructure builders," whose contributions are essential but often go unnoticed in traditional evaluation systems that focus on visible outputs like publications or datasets.

Current research evaluation approaches typically prioritise visible academic outputs such as peer-reviewed papers, over the essential, yet invisible work that supports them. The Infrastructure Working Group's contributions are fundamental to The Turing Way's continued impact, yet this critical technical work is not traditionally rewarded or even visible within academic metrics.

By maintaining an open-source infrastructure that facilitates global collaboration and knowledge-sharing, this team has provided the essential foundation for The Turing Way's success. However, the invisibility of this work within traditional research evaluation frameworks means that their role remains hidden, despite its profound impact on the project and the wider research community.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-9262-8641

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Way is funded by the Alan Turing Institute, but has volunteer contributors and collaborators from across different institutions.

Entry: 504

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: I'm not on the list, so I'll describe the role below

Role submitted: Computational Biology and Data Science Trainer

Name: George, Charlotte

Organisation/University: University of Oxford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Over the last 6 years I have devised and delivered advanced data science and bioinformatic training to over 150 post-graduate students, post-doctoral researchers, clinicians, fellows and principal investigators at the University of Oxford in courses lasting 1 week to 3 months. The training grounds those with a biological or biomedical training in the data science and statistical skills and best practises required to analyse biomedical genomic data in a robust and most importantly reproducible manner. As well as the technical skills the training builds in best practises in computational analysis so these skills become second nature to those performing thier research. Rather than just providing a list of steps to follow we train researchers in a manner that builds there confidence and independence in carrying out thier own analysis, meaning they are equiped to embrace new computational challenges they face outside of the teaching environment. Many of the researchers who I have taught have gone through the course have not only been sucessful at analysing thier own complex data steps, but they have gone on to take on senior interdisciplinary and computational roles, training others and becoming computational biology leaders both within academia and in industry.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This role is highly important as without dedicated data science and computational biology trainers, many biologists and clinicians would have struggled to adopt the advanced data science and analytical skills that are required to analyse the relms of data modern biomedical research produces. Many of the course participants have very little computational and mathmatical knowledge before starting the course. Researchers are supported over multiple weeks to advance thier skill and confidence levels that simply is not possible through self learning on even the most comprehensive online courses and MOOCs. Trainers require a high level of domain knowledge in computation, programming, biology, genomics, statistics and teaching to be able to simplify the best practices to novices who often have limited time, and need a high competencie in troubleshooting and technical skills to support the wide range of issues and challenges that the trainees face. Without this role hundreds of computational genomics projects would have taken far longer to be performed and to a lower standard of robustness and reproducibility.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This role is overlooked within the current research culture and evaluation approaches as it is regarded as postgraduate 'training' rather than 'teaching' of undergraduate or masters coruses and hence is not valued to the same degree within the evaluation appoaches in UK academia, despite the impact of it being much more focused and directly influencing research productivity, culture and reproducibly. The role of an effective trainer also requires that person to be performing research themselves to encounter problems trainees themselves will encounter and staying up to date with the current trends in the field. This means there time is split heavilly between research and training and therefore thier research and traditional outputs are not seen as competitive agaisnt full time researchers. In addition often due to the computational interdisciplinary aspects of the role the research projects they work on are very collaborative and can have much longer timeframes to impact and don't result in high authorship positions. It is also hard to have a international impact as the training is focused locally due to restraints imposed by

university administration.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 509

Applicant details

Submission category: 1 - Hidden Role

Hidden role: Technicians

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Ali, Nermeen

Organisation/University: Ulster University School of Pharmacy

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am Dr. Nermeen Ali, a Pharmacy Practice Technician at Ulster University's School of Pharmacy. My submission highlights my vital role in advancing pharmaceutical research and education. My work includes international collaborations on projects such as the Preparation and Evaluation of Targeted Cancer Therapy using novel models, as well as Developing Sustainable Global Partnerships to Strengthen Antimicrobial Stewardship and Enhance Medication Safety. These projects address critical global challenges, from improving cancer treatments to combating antimicrobial resistance.

I have also introduced an educational enhancement project: An Evaluation of Integrating Science-Based Extemporaneous Preparations with Clinical Practice in the MPharm Degree (Module PHA530) for third year students. This initiative bridges the gap between science-based formulations and clinical practice, aligning with the new GPhC standards. By building a bridge between the practical extemporaneous preparations sessions in both the laboratory and a simulated model pharmacy, I have helped students apply scientific knowledge in real-world scenarios using their extemporaneous products. With 96.6% of students recommending its continuation, the project has proven successful in enhancing pharmacy education.

My technical expertise in developing targeted drug delivery systems for cancer underscores the importance of detailed technical work in transforming lab concepts into clinically relevant solutions. I apply skills from my master's and PhD studies, including cell culture and microscopy, to advance precision therapies. Additionally, my work in antimicrobial stewardship programs demonstrates how technical contributions can address global health risks.

Despite these contributions, traditional research metrics often overlook my work. As a technician, I am unable to access the PURE system to log my research outputs, limiting the visibility and recognition of my contributions, even on an international scale.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The significance of my submission lies in my ability to integrate technical expertise, research innovation, and educational enhancement, driving the success of both research and pharmacy education. My work on targeted drug delivery systems for cancer treatment, antimicrobial stewardship, and medication safety directly addresses some of the most pressing global health challenges.

The educational enhancement project I introduced within the MPharm degree is particularly notable. In response to the GPhC's new standards, I developed an integrated approach that combines extemporaneous science-based preparations with clinical practice. This ensures that pharmacy students gain practical experience while understanding the scientific principles behind formulations. I applied research methodologies to gather student and staff feedback, which showed overwhelming support for the project. This evidence-based approach to education has improved student engagement and ensured that pharmacy graduates are better prepared for clinical practice. The success of this project underscores the importance of embedding research into educational settings to enhance learning

outcomes.

Moreover, my interdisciplinary research on targeted therapies for cancer and my contributions to international research on antimicrobial resistance exemplify how technical roles like mine contribute to meaningful scientific progress. My involvement in key research collaborations, combined with my active participation in global research initiatives, has already begun to generate impactful outcomes, with plans for further contributions to REF 2028.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite my substantial contributions to research and education, my work as a Pharmacy Practice Technician remains largely hidden within traditional research frameworks. A key reason is the structural limitations in research evaluation systems. As a technician, I do not have access to the PURE system, which prevents me from formally recording my contributions. This lack of visibility means that, although I am actively involved in high-impact international research and educational projects, my work is not readily acknowledged in institutional research outputs or evaluations.

My role in the simulated model pharmacy, essential for both teaching and research, is often seen as operational rather than scientific. In reality, managing this environment requires advanced technical skills and a deep understanding of pharmacy practice. My involvement in research, troubleshooting equipment, advising on data collection, and ensuring the practical feasibility of research designs is critical to the success of these projects. Yet, this input is rarely recognized in published outputs or funding applications.

Furthermore, my enhancement project within the MPharm curriculum, which applies research methods to improve education, does not fit traditional academic definitions of research, further contributing to its invisibility. The fact that I cannot log this significant work into PURE highlights the broader challenges technicians face in gaining recognition for their vital contributions.

By recognizing my submission, the Hidden REF competition would shine a light on the crucial yet often unacknowledged role of technicians in driving research and educational success.

As chair of the Career Development Working Group under the Technician Commitment, I am deeply committed to promoting the four pillars: Visibility, Recognition, Sustainability, and Career Development. The Hidden REF competition aligns with these goals by providing the recognition that technicians like myself deserve.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0009-0007-9050-8447>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Practices panel

Entry: 374

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Barron, Vera

Organisation/University: Manchester Metropolitan University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

As part of my role as Senior research development lead at the University of Salford I developed 2 online training modules for ECRs and MCRs on a) securing research funding and b) developing partnerships for Oxford University Press / Epigeum. These modules are now offered to research institutions in New Zealand, Australia, the UK and the EU as part of a training programme on research leadership. These modules were peer reviewed by relevant experts in this area and were highly marked by the reviewers and hopefully contribute to the professional growth of emerging academic colleagues in research institutions where they are available.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

These modules represent a summary of more than 20 years of experience as research funding officer, KTP officer, EU liaison officer and research manager, business development professional and EU Adviser based at UKRO. I distilled two decades of experience and technical knowledge of UK and EU research funding policy and partnership development into two succinct online modules to help early and mid-career research colleagues hit the ground running when developing their external partnerships and securing funding for their research.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The REF has so far only recognised the excellence of research staff; similarly, whilst academic staff have clear routes to progression, these are often not available to research professionals. These training modules are a result of 20 years of experience and of developing my own specialist knowledge and expertise in the area of research development & management; researcher development, knowledge transfer and innovation; partnership development and of acquiring technical knowledge on research funding programmes and policy within the UK and international contexts.

As research support professionals, we often play key roles in assisting teams of researchers secure large, prestigious grants, but our contribution is rarely recognised outside of the realm of the scientific team that won the grant.

It would be really nice to be recognised for the contributions we bring to initial brainstorming sessions, project ideation workshops, to the proposal and budgetary negotiations and development; further for bringing key partners into the teams using our own networks, or ensuring that the projects we are proposing are within the technical requirements and scope of the funders. We often bring in linguistic skills, knowledge of other cultural environments and context, awareness of industry sectors and many other perspectives that may be useful. As our work is focused on innovative practice - and is really a mix of many skills, recognising training modules or other outputs where we share many years of experience and best practice could be a good way to assess the excellence of our understanding of our profession.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Vera Barron, Manchester Metropolitan University.

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 380

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: n/a, n/a

Organisation/University: MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Dr. Barsotti is a postdoctoral research science in neurobiology at the MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology. However, her contributions go far beyond research: behind the scenes, she manages and maintains two electron microscopes. Managing these microscopes is an extremely important task both for the continued research output of the institute as well as for the safety of the staff and personnel who work in the institute. At the same time, managing these microscopes is a largely unrewarding task, and it, in and of itself, does not result in publication, pay, or any other form of recognition. Even so, Dr. Barsotti has performed this duty to the highest of standards. She found a radiation safety fault with the microscopes before it became serious, ensuring the safety of all member of the institute. She has also negotiated service and service contracts for the microscopes. In doing this, she has saved the institute more than ~£30,000 in service fees. Her work has been truly outstanding, ensuring the lab is safe and efficient. And all of this is done in addition to her usual research responsibilities.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Dr. Barsotti's role at the MRC Laboratory of Molecular Biology exemplifies the essence of hidden yet vital contributions within the scientific community. While her primary position as a postdoctoral research scientist in neurobiology is noteworthy, it is her extraordinary commitment to managing and maintaining two electron microscopes that sets her apart. These microscopes are indispensable tools in cutting-edge research, enabling breakthroughs in neurobiology. However, the responsibility of managing these instruments is often undervalued, despite being critical to the institute's continued research output and the safety of its personnel.

Dr. Barsotti's meticulous management of the electron microscopes ensures they operate at optimal performance, directly influencing the quality and reliability of research conducted at the institute. Her vigilance in identifying a radiation safety fault before it escalated demonstrates her dedication to maintaining a safe working environment. This proactive approach likely averted a potentially serious safety incident, safeguarding not only the equipment, which costs more than ~£50,000, but also the health and well-being of all institute members.

Moreover, Dr. Barsotti's efforts in negotiating service contracts have resulted in substantial financial savings for the institute, amounting to over ~£30,000. This achievement underscores her resourcefulness and commitment to the institute's operational efficiency, ensuring that valuable resources are allocated effectively.

Despite the critical nature of her work, these contributions are often overlooked because they do not directly lead to publications, promotions, or other conventional forms of recognition. The management of scientific equipment, especially at such a high standard, is a demanding task that requires expertise, diligence, and a deep understanding of both the technology and the research it supports. Dr. Barsotti's exceptional work in this area, coupled with her ongoing research responsibilities, reflects a level of dedication and service that significantly enhances the institute's research capabilities.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

In the current research culture, the value of contributions is often measured by tangible outputs such as publications, grants, and citations. This narrow focus tends to overshadow the indispensable roles that support and enable these outputs, such as the management of scientific equipment. Dr. Barsotti's work is a prime example of a contribution that is essential yet remains hidden within the traditional metrics of academic recognition.

The responsibility of maintaining and managing electron microscopes is a critical function that ensures the integrity and continuity of high-level research. However, it is an area that typically goes unrecognized because it does not directly produce the types of outputs that are traditionally rewarded in academic settings. The fact that such work does not lead to publications or citations means it often remains invisible in evaluations of scientific merit, despite its fundamental importance to the research process.

Dr. Barsotti's contributions highlight a systemic issue in the evaluation of academic and research roles. The current system disproportionately values the visible outputs of research, neglecting the equally important, yet less visible, roles that support the research infrastructure. This oversight not only fails to recognize the full spectrum of contributions necessary for successful research but also risks demotivating individuals who take on these critical, behind-the-scenes responsibilities.

Her work embodies the type of hidden contribution that the Hidden REF competition seeks to acknowledge, an essential role that underpins the success of scientific endeavors but is rarely recognized within traditional frameworks of academic achievement. Dr. Barsotti's ability to balance her research responsibilities with the demanding task of managing vital scientific equipment exemplifies the unrecognized labor that sustains the scientific enterprise. By highlighting her contributions, this submission calls attention to the need for a more inclusive and comprehensive approach to evaluating and rewarding all forms of academic and research work.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-4106-5543

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 395

Applicant details

Submission category: 8 - Research teams
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Corkery, Brendan
Organisation/University: University of Exeter
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate the team which I manage, the Research and Development Workshops team. We design and make items for every academic and student at the University of Exeter. We also teach and support them making items for themselves. We provide mechanical, electronic and software support. We create anything from individual items to complex experimental rigs. For the Physics department, we have made custom microscope stages, precisely machined plates with various patterns to distort light and sound in particular ways and built enclosures to protect academics undertaking experiments with lasers. For Psychology we have built squirrel feeding machines and complex bee hives. For Engineering we have created seismic test rigs and offshore wind turbine experimental rigs. For Geography we have built custom environmental chambers and flowmeter system recording data from 250 different samples simultaneously. For Biosciences we have built custom environmental chambers and a heat differential experiment. This is just a snapshot of the work we do. Each year we complete approximately 700 projects. Generally we design and develop all of these items. An academic or student will approach us with an idea or basic sketch. We take that idea and turn it into something tangible. We have to gain a deep understanding of what they are trying to achieve so we can make something that meets their needs.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The researchers at our institution undertake world leading bespoke research. To do this they need items and experimental rigs which are world leading and bespoke. My team build this diverse range of things which cannot be bought and often has never been made before. We employ a huge variation of skills, experience and knowledge to achieve this. We take researchers ideas and make them reality. Researchers have said that we take their concept and make it better than they imagined, which they have said makes their research better. Many of the research projects we support could not be undertaken without our help because we design and make the physical item to be tested. Recently a researcher was keen to intern in our facilities. I asked why and they said, "I want to do brilliant research. To do this I need to work with brilliant technicians. I need to understand how to work best with you." I recently attended an event at the University which involved researchers and technicians from almost every department. On every stand was an item we made or some research being showcased which we had designed and built.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

There is no link between the value of the research projects we support and the work which we do to contribute to this research. We are facilitating research projects worth millions and are critical to their delivery. We are often viewed as a costly overhead rather than a critical asset. Demand for our support is increasing and there is no investment in the staff to support the increasing demand, which will restrain research. We have occasionally been added as authors to publications but given we often design and make the actual thing being tested, this is not happening enough. There are very few teams which provide research support to every department in a University. We are typical engineers and have a tendency to be introverted and understate the scale of the support we provide. Whilst others tend to advertise every project they contribute to, we don't due to time pressures and the attitude of "getting on

with the work". Every researcher who works with us greatly values our contribution and recognises our value. We enjoy our work and the working relationships we have with the researchers we support.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 404

Applicant details

Submission category: 8 - Research teams

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bianchi, Lynne

Organisation/University: SEERIH, University of Manchester

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Great Science Share for Schools (GSSfS) is a campaign run by the Science & Engineering Education Research and Innovation Hub (SEERIH) within The University of Manchester. The aim of the campaign is to inspire and engage children in scientific discovery, by asking, investigating and sharing a scientific question they care about.

GSSfS is an inclusive and collaborative campaign that promotes teachers to provide opportunities for young people from 5-14 years to ask, investigate and share a scientific question they care about. It can take place in whatever educational setting, anywhere across the world, placing young people at the heart of the communication of science to each other.

The SEERIH are a passionate team of five skilled individuals (mainly professional services staff), who work on the campaign part-time. They encourage and support collaboration within the University with academic research groups and outreach as well as beyond the University and through educational charities, organisations, industry and cultural institutions. These enable stimulus material to produce bespoke resources as well as means to disseminate and share information towards recruitment and retention of participants across the UK and beyond. Most recently, collaboration has been undertaken with the UK Commission for UNESCO, who awarded the campaign National Patronage for 2024. This is further enhancing the global reach of the campaign.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Science lessons to children are invaluable. As well as developing skills and increasing vocabulary, they create an environment where children are able to question, challenge and discover the world around them. Unfortunately, UK primary education has focused most attention on literacy and numeracy, at the expense of science and therefore the quality and quantity of taught science in UK schools, is not a priority as noted by SEERIH's '10 Key Issues in Children's Learning in Primary Science in England Report' (Bianchi et al, 2021).

SEERIH is a nationally recognised centre of science and engineering education whose primary aim is to promote the importance of science education. Since it launched in 2016, the campaign team has evolved and changed, in line with the changing team make up within SEERIH. There has had a consistent Director, Prof Lynne Bianchi, who founded and developed SEERIH as a specialist unit within The University of Manchester. The team's significant contribution to the sector validates the need and impact of developing STEM talent from the early pipeline. This submission marks the contribution of many people over the past decade, with the predominance of staff being ex- primary and secondary teachers working within the faculty's wider Teaching & Learning professional support staff cohort.

The team are passionate about making science inclusive and accessible for all children, regardless of socioeconomic background and location. They engage with all schools in the UK and international, and run activities for free, ensuring equal access for everyone. Providing free accessibility requires additional funding for resource development, events and consultancy. Strong relationships have been developed with industry and charities to gain sustainable philanthropic donations to continue the GSSfS campaign.

The success of the campaign to date is evidenced in the increased number of engaged children actively involved in GSSfS. When the campaign launched in 2016, 3,000 children were enrolled. For the last 8 years, the team have been dedicated to increasing this reach and in 2023/2024, 3,534 schools (50% of

which are classed as in high socioeconomic deprivation) and 673,555 children were engaged with GSSfS activities. This includes 161 international schools and institutions (16,650 pupils) across 36 countries.

Further evidence of the team's successful is found in a recent evaluation of the campaign GSSfS leads to:

• more time for science learning in school and at home

• more open-ended opportunities led by young people asking, investigating and communicating their own scientific questions. Teachers support the pupils in developing and building their questions and shaping the experience in order that it is of the highest quality, always maintain that the young people lead as much as they can in undertaking and sharing of their learning.

• more involvement from different audiences (parents/families, community).

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Over the years we have explored the potential of GSSfS becoming a REF impact case study, however various challenges mean that this hasn't come to fruition. There is significant support for the campaign, however it has been increasingly evident that there isn't a strong enough match to any REF Units of Assessment within the Faculty of Science & Engineering where SEERIH sits. Arguably, the challenge in fixing the project to a UoA should be seen as a measure of the campaign's success. The breadth and volume of contributions from the 6+ UoAs that the project spans undoubtedly have contributed to the scope and success of the SEERIH project. The lack of ownership within any UOA is perhaps better viewed as a positive demonstration of its truly interdisciplinary nature. Its strong focus on educating teachers and young people steers this to other Faculties, however having explored this avenue, it is apparent that GSSfS also sits outside clearly defined research themes and strands, developed and curated over many years in education.

Notably, as professional support staff there would usually be no direct route to REF, and although the campaign is research informed and also informs policy reports and close-to-practice scholarly outputs it is understandable how this has not happened. Prof Lynne Bianchi along with members of the GSSfS and SEERIH team do undertake scholarship activity, which has had bearing in the Science Education sector, with citations from key educational bodies, including OFSTED (Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills) and the Education Endowment Foundation.

The team's work is well recognised within the remit of Social Responsibility and provides the largest data return for the Faculty and University for enhancing social inclusion at pre-14 level. Annual impact is reported via: Research England's Knowledge Exchange Framework (Public Engagement); UoM's statutory return to the Office for Students on Widening Participation; UoM Access & Participation Plan Monitoring Report (T16b_16 (Access)). GSSfS also contributed to success for UoM's Times Higher Education Impact Rankings. The UoM Higher Education Access Tracker contextualises impact stating: [GSSfS data] is more than double the number of participants from the rest of our activities (including partnership activities) combined.

Despite such success, it is understandable, yet challenging that the team miss out on recognition through REF. We consider this to be an ideal example for a Hidden REF application.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Prof Lynne Bianchi, SEERIH, University of Manchester (Academic, Campaign Director)

Grace Marson, SEERIH, University of Manchester (Prof Services, Specialist Lead)

Katherine Goodley, SEERIH, University of Manchester (Prof Services, Business Officer)

David Xu, SEERIH, University of Manchester (Prof Services, Administrator)

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 422

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Macpherson, Fiona

Organisation/University: University of Glasgow

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): The Universities of Glasgow and Sussex

Description of submission

Summary

The Dreamachine Schools Programme integrated science and philosophy in a UK-wide curriculum exploring the human mind, self-perception, and social connection. Over 30 accredited lesson plans in Science, Citizenship, and Health and Wellbeing reached over 1 million children and young people. A key component, Life's Big Questions (LBQ), aimed at children 7–13, comprised a series of videos and interactive activities, and a nationwide interactive children's survey, which brought some of the biggest philosophical questions into thousands of homes and classrooms across the UK. The freely available materials, launched in May 2022 in the UK, and then internationally in 2023, can be viewed at <https://dreamachine.world/for-schools/>.

Professor Fiona Macpherson (philosophy, Glasgow) and Professor Anil Seth (neuroscience, Sussex) contributed content to, and shaped the design of, the ambitious UK wide learning programme, which was commissioned and produced by Collective Act, as part of Dreamachine, and which was developed in partnership with A New Direction, the British Science Association, and UNICEF UK.

To create the LBQ resources, Macpherson and Seth participated in detailed discussions about themes and educational content, and recorded a number of video sessions that were utilised in the lesson plans (<https://lbq.dreamachine.world/>). They also participated in online Zoom sessions with schools in order to directly engage with children's questions about the mind and brain.

Fusing science with arts, the curriculum was built around the ideas explored through the Dreamachine Programme: the power of the human mind, our sense of self, how we see the world, and how we connect with others. Dreamachine is a unique collaboration blending leading academic researchers with world-class artists. Launched in 2020, it received ~£100k from the UK Government for initial development and ~£9 million from the 2022 Unboxed festival. The programme comprises three main components: an immersive live experience, a large scale study of perceptual diversity (The Perception Census), and the Schools Programme.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

A major objective of Macpherson and Seth in making the Dreamachine Schools Programme was to increase understanding of perceptual diversity. While society is increasingly aware and appreciative of the issue of neurodiversity, the idea of perceptual diversity is still underappreciated. Indeed, the very concept of perceptual diversity itself stands as a contribution of the Schools Programme. The concept is that of the perceptual differences that exist between all of us. It is distinct from the concept of neurodiversity which has over time become associated with specific conditions such as autism and ADHD, with the (likely unintended) effect of reinforcing the misleading idea that if one does not have a neurodivergent condition, one is 'neurotypical' and perceives the world just as it is. By contrast, perceptual diversity is widespread: we all differ.

A wider objective was to spark children's curiosity in philosophy and in psychology. These topics are central to everyday life, but are surprisingly neglected in UK national curricula. Extensive work was undertaken to ensure that the educational material in the Schools Programme ignited interest in these

topics yet remained well aligned with curriculum requirements.

Focus groups with teachers who utilized Dreamachine resources highlighted that neuroscience, philosophy, and perception, are seldom included in the national curriculum, making Dreamachine's approach quite novel. They also noted their impact in fostering discussions about tolerance and respecting differences among students.

Students, particularly younger ones, showed enthusiasm for discussing these complex ideas, with many eager to explore topics related to perception and psychology. This engagement often led to stimulating discussions, where children asked profound questions and expressed fascination with how perception varies among individuals.

Moreover, learning about perceptual diversity was seen as beneficial beyond the classroom. Teachers observed that these discussions could reduce conflicts on the playground by helping students understand and appreciate different perspectives. One teacher mentioned that discussing how the brain works and how perceptions differ could prevent disagreements and promote harmony among peers.

At a special needs school, Dreamachine resources were praised for effectively teaching about differences while also nurturing emotional education. This teacher observed that the resources sparked curiosity and a sense of wonder, essential elements of meaningful education. Students were excited about engaging with "Life's Big Questions," and this enthusiasm was sustained over time, with noticeable impacts on students' inquisitiveness and self-awareness.

Teachers noted a lasting change in students' attitudes and behaviors. They reported an increase in the number of questions asked and a greater sense of curiosity and self-awareness among students. The resources also encouraged students to engage more deeply with each other, enhancing peer interactions and collaborative exploration. Overall, Dreamachine resources were recognized for their ability to inspire critical thinking, curiosity, and mutual respect in students.

Continued below...

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Answer to previous question continued here:

British Science Association promoted the resources as part of British Science Week. We received the highest number of downloads for schools resources around British Science Week. Unicef featured Dreamachine school resources, which were shared by them with their Rights Respecting Schools and social media channels. They consulted on Life's Big Questions and some of the Unicef Young Advisory Board contributed answers for the classroom video. All of the content was checked for consistency with the UN Rights of the Child agenda.

A summary video of impact is here: <https://dreamachine.world/wp-content/uploads/2022/11/Collective-Act-Lifes-Big-Questions-Wrap-Up-Film-1280-x-720-HD.mp4>

And to answer the question asked in this text box now follows:

Resources created for schools based on one's research, would not count as an output in the REF. And such resources are unlikely to form a REF impact case study on their own, in part because it is hard to capture the deep, often hidden, impact that these materials have over many years.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Anil Seth, Professor of Cognitive and Computational Neuroscience at the University of Sussex

Funding acknowledgements: The UK Government and the 2022 Unboxed Festival

Entry: 430

Applicant details

Submission category: 7 - Standards

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Kerridge, Simon

Organisation/University: University of Kent / Kerridge Research Consulting

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) is a simple 14 role taxonomy that describes the contributions most typically made to the production of scholarly output (e.g. articles). It represents a small but significant step to making the myriad of contributions to research more visible. It is a community owned initiative and is managed entirely through volunteer research time.

While the CRediT had its origins in supporting science, technology and medicine output, and a focus on the published article format, there has been increasing adoption of the taxonomy across scholarly publishers and research fields. It is now being used by a large and increasing number of research publishers, to capture specific contributions of authors and contributors during article submission processes, and upstream in the research process, for example, to support good practice research conduct guidelines in research institutional settings.

In 2020 the CRediT project was awarded funding from both the Sloan Foundation and Wellcome to continue engagement and outreach activity designed to support continued use and uptake. In 2022 CRediT was approved as a National Information Standards Organisation (NISO) American National Standards Institute (ANSI) standard (<https://www.niso.org/publications/z39104-2022-credit> - ANSI/NISO Z39.104-2022, CRediT, Contributor Roles Taxonomy) and is now available in multiple languages.

In 2024, Crossref announced that as part of their meta-data schema refresh, they plan to capture CRediT roles alongside other researcher descriptors; thus marking an important step in making the specific contributions of researchers highly valued. The need to value the range of contributions to researcher (beyond a focus on author and journal-based metrics) is aligned with initiatives such as DORA and CoARA.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Contributor Role Taxonomy (CRediT) initially emerged from a dissatisfaction with author lists on scholarly research being used in many inappropriate ways. In particular, author position simply fails to capture or represent the range of contributions that researchers make to published output. Additionally, the demand for more information on 'who did what' in delivering research both to shine a light on the diversity of contributions, and to support accountability and research integrity, has grown, and continues to do so.

For researchers it is important to be able to demonstrate the diversity of contributions to research. For research institutions and funders, greater access to information about how and where the researchers they support are making a difference helps to support a more holistic view of research and research evaluation. For publishers, having more information about 'who did what' provides accountability and supports research integrity and provenance checking, helping to ensure trust in research.

In 2012 a workshop co-hosted by Harvard University and Wellcome brought together researchers, institutions, funders and publishers to discuss how to improve the visibility of the important contribution information that resulted in scholarly output. Following the workshop, a pilot project was established to develop a simple, controlled vocabulary of contributor roles that was both practical and easy to implement, while minimizing the potential for misuse.

Most publishers have historically required that authors disclose statements about the contributions of each author upon submission of an article for publication, some using structured lists, but mainly in free-text form and largely inaccessible for any kind of discoverability or analytical purposes. CRediT, a

simple 14 role taxonomy, was developed and designed to be used in workflows to capture basic contribution information in a structured and usable way. Many publishers now use CRediT in their article submission systems and an increasing number of organisations are using the taxonomy upstream in the research process, for example, to give recognition to all contributors to research teams and programmes (not just those that may be a Principal Investigator (PI) or Team lead).

In 2020 CRediT was awarded funding from both the Sloan Foundation and Wellcome to continue engagement and outreach activity to support its adoption. In 2022 CRediT was approved as a National Information Standards Organisation (NISO) American National Standards Institute (ANSI) standard and is now available in multiple languages.

In 2024, Crossref announced that as part of their meta-data schema refresh, they plan to capture CRediT roles alongside other researcher descriptors, marking an important step in making the specific contributions of researchers highly valued. The need to value the range of contributions to researcher (beyond a focus on author and journal-based metrics) is aligned with initiatives such as DORA and CoARA.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

An entirely community-led initiative, CRediT is a small piece of our research infrastructure (alongside things like ORCID and ROR) which could make a huge difference in making research more discoverable, useable and have impact. We neglect the importance of initiatives that can connect research together (research infrastructure), and the requirement for connections is going to become more important with the development of AI and LLM that rely on the availability of well described research and associated meta-data. In this sense, the work and effort involved in developing, leading and implementing CRediT is hidden. But it has potential benefits across all parts of the research system.

CRediT is also providing data to support the 'Science of Science', providing the opportunity for researchers to look, for example, how research is done, the division of labour, and gender roles across research teams. Such insights can help support policy developments to help build a more effective research culture (Larivière, V., Pontille, D., & Sugimoto, C. R. (2020). Investigating the division of scientific labor using the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT). *Quantitative Science Studies*, 2(1), 111-128.). CRediT was also recommended by the UK Academy of Sciences as a tool to improve the recognition of researchers working in large teams (Academy of Medical Sciences. (2016) Improving recognition of team science contributions in biomedical research careers. <https://acmedsci.ac.uk/policy/policy-projects/team-science>).

Ironically, the UK Research Excellence Framework (REF) sets criteria for the multi-authored outputs for the level of contribution that needs to be demonstrated for an article to be included in the submission in relation to an individual author. The CRediT roles would be ideally suited to provide evidence for author contributions, such that the submitting institutions and assessment sub-panels would not need to collect and review additional information.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, G-2020-14051; Wellcome

Entry: 439

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Deane, Katherine

Organisation/University: University of East Anglia

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Access All Areas in Labs team designed the UK's first highly accessible manufacturing development laboratory for advanced therapy medicinal products (ATMPs) (<https://bit.ly/3XCjsHg>). It took account of the UK Equality Act (2010) and was informed by the Social Model of Disability and the principles of Universal Design.

The team surveyed over 150 people with an interest in disability access in labs about current standards of lab access and access solutions in use. Unfortunately, the survey identified that most labs have substantial access barriers in their design and use. The survey results informed the creation of a suite of access guidelines that cover the whole of the lab working ecosystem (<https://bit.ly/3pY5IIR>). These guidelines informed the design of the Catapult Cell and Gene Therapy ATMP lab and ensured that the design of the laboratory can accommodate scientists with most types of impairments.

Currently disabled scientists are drastically under-represented in the workforce. This lack of diversity has a negative impact on research culture, and the utility and quality of research outputs. Accessible labs will allow a greater proportion of disabled scientists to be trained and work in lab settings in a safe and comfortable manner. We genuinely believe improved diversity in the workforce will enhance the quality and potential profitability of the work done in laboratory settings. The highly accessible Catapult Cell and Gene Therapy ATMP lab offers proof of concept. We hope that it will pave the way for the development of future laboratories in the UK and beyond.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Laboratories are often designed without consideration to disability access due to the historic assumption that disabled scientists could not work safely in such environments. If disabled people's needs are not designed into work and workplaces, then few disabled people will be able to work there. Accessibility is about much more than just meeting minimum building standards. In laboratory settings, these standards don't go far enough. So current laboratories do not usually meet an access standard that will provide opportunities for disabled scientists.

This lack of accessibly designed labs is a part of why there is a significant under representation of disabled people working in science, technology, engineering, and maths (STEM). Whilst approximately 22% of the UK adult population of working age are disabled, only around 3.8% of UK STEM academics are identified as disabled. The lack of diversity in research participants and scientists is a factor in wasteful research due to serious flaws in research prioritisation, design, sampling, analysis and interpretation, etc. Research that is informed by a diverse multidisciplinary team is better able to ensure practicality, utility, and impact. The opportunity cost of not having disabled scientists with their diversity of experience and expertise is likely to be significant. Additionally, most disabilities are acquired; the loss of highly qualified scientists from the field when they acquire a disability is a substantial loss on the investment in their training.

We started with the assumption that all disabled scientists are able to work in labs, if the labs are designed with their access needs met. Safety issues can be designed 'out' of the labs; either in the structural or equipment design or in the protocols used. Accessibility also includes the design of the work processes, staff knowledge and attitudes. Accessible labs will allow a greater proportion of disabled scientists to be trained and work in lab settings in a safe and comfortable manner. We genuinely believe this improved diversity in the workforce will enhance the quality and potential profitability of the work

done in laboratory settings.

The Access All Areas in Labs guidelines informed the design of the Catapult Cell and Gene Therapy ATMP lab and ensured the design of the laboratory can accommodate scientists with most types of impairments. The cleanroom provides an aseptic environment where scientists can develop advanced therapy medicinal products. The design ensured that there is sufficient space in the associated changing room for a wheelchair user to change into a dedicated clean wheelchair and protective garments for the laboratory environment. Other access design features included considering the colour contrasts, providing height adjustable benches, and lever-type or touch-free type taps. Additional powered doors were installed to make the route to the lab fully accessible.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Access All Areas project was created by a team of people with a range of disabilities and access expertise. We worked with researchers, technicians, building contractors, equipment manufacturers and disability access experts to gain a diversity of perspectives.

Disability is often the forgotten diversity in Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) plans. The usability of structures in which research is conducted are often overlooked. If disabled researchers cannot get into the labs to work, then they cannot influence the research culture within them. The high frequency of barriers for disabled scientists to use current lab infrastructure and the low level of knowledge required to solve these access problems, means that this project is an essential 'black swan' to prove that solving these access challenges is possible. This lab offers proof of concept; it is hoped that it will pave the way for the development of future laboratories in the UK and beyond.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Dan Burrill, Science Faculty, University of East Anglia, 0009-0005-2541-2137, Technician.

Peter Hemmins, Productivity East, Science Faculty University of East Anglia, Senior Lab Technician.

Jenny Camaradou, Independent Expert on Knowledge Exchange, Grant Writing, and Patient Engagement.

Thomas Fadden, Purple Reach Disability Access Consultancy.

Funding acknowledgements: This project was funded by a grant award from Innovate UK to the Cell & Gene Therapy Catapult. Additionally Katherine Deane, UEA, is supported by the National Institute for Health and Care Research (NIHR) Applied Research Collaboration East of England (NIHR ARC EoE) at Cambridge and Peterborough NHS Foundation Trust. The views expressed are those of the author[s] and not necessarily those of the NIHR or the Department of Health and Social Care.

Entry: 443

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Clements-Brod, Naomi

Organisation/University: Human Developmental Biology Initiative, University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Human Developmental Biology Initiative (HDBI, hdbi.org) is a Wellcome-funded research consortium with scientists in institutions across the UK and Europe who are trying to better understand how humans develop before birth. They work with human fetal and embryonic tissues donated from abortions, as well as early human embryos donated by fertility patients. HDBI research raises complex ethical and moral questions for science and society and HDBI public engagement aims to open research and its implications to broader questioning and consideration by the public.

A core part of the HDBI public engagement programme is training because our research can be tough to talk about for a number of reasons, including: the precious tissues we work with might provoke strong emotional reactions, the fundamental nature of our research might seem distant from most people's daily lives, and in order to have informed and meaningful conversations, we have to put substantial effort into developing shared language and understanding.

Over the course of 2.5 years, HDBI researchers have participated in bespoke hands-on training sessions at biannual whole-consortium meetings aiming to overcome these barriers and prepare and support them to discuss their research with the public. So far six sessions have taken place between February 2022 and June 2024, with more than 30 researchers, from PhD students to group leaders, participating in each session. Topics have included 'Plain English and FAQs', 'Ethical, Legal and Social Implications', and 'Working with the media.'

In anonymous feedback, the training sessions were widely praised for being practical and interactive and the content being of value in public engagement and broader communication activities, such as explaining HDBI research to funders or researchers from other disciplines.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Researchers are connected to the future outcomes of their work and therefore have a responsibility to engage with the public to ensure it is relevant and considered mutually beneficial. However, researchers don't always feel confident having transparent conversations about their work, especially if it involves human embryos or fetal tissue, which can provoke strong emotional responses in members of the public.

Being able to sensitively and confidently speak about this work is a real skill which enables meaningful conversations with the public, who the research will ultimately impact, and allows researchers to ensure their work is societally relevant. However, public engagement and communication training for researchers working in this field is not a standard provision. And as a result, researchers are often left feeling unequipped to answer even basic questions which often come up about their work such as 'why is this research being done?' and 'where does the human embryonic and fetal tissue come from?'

The training sessions have covered a wide breadth of topics, from Ethical Legal and Social Implications, to communicating in plain English and answering frequently asked questions, and Working with the Media. And outputs from training sessions have been shared within and beyond the consortium

afterward. For example, the plain English and FAQs session led to the creation of an FAQs page (<https://hdbi.org/faqs>) on the HDDBI website which has been widely used by researchers in preparation for public engagement activities and helped facilitate multiple Q&A sessions that were part of an HDDBI-funded public dialogue on research with early human embryos (<https://hdbi.org/public-dialogue>). In response to feedback during the session on 'difficult conversations', we also published a 'top tips' guide for public engagement which is freely available online (<https://hdbi.org/s/Difficult-conversations-top-tips-v4.pdf>).

The HDDBI training programme is not only unique but also effective at providing researchers with the skills and confidence to discuss their work with the public. In anonymous feedback, researchers said 'It was interesting to see the types of questions the public have and useful to discuss with other scientists with different experiences.' Many researchers also said that they gained a better understanding of the rules and regulations surrounding tissue use as well as how to discuss this with the public. Several group leaders have also used the consortium training sessions as templates for further discussions within their labs. In feedback about the training programme overall, scientists said 'the training programme has been a really valuable addition to the consortium meetings and [we] seem to gain a lot from being involved.'

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Public engagement training is often deprioritised because it is seen as a non-essential and non-strategic activity. And fundamental researchers are often not exposed to training on how to communicate with the public or actively encouraged to reflect on the Ethical, Legal and Social Implications of their work.

Reflection and communication with the public is both difficult to do well and essential for ensuring that society trusts fundamental research. Lack of transparency and communication is more likely to lead to backlash against potentially controversial research such as HDDBI's. But the absence of backlash is difficult, perhaps impossible, to measure.

It can also be difficult to measure the impact of public engagement training, as it is internal and unique to each researcher. Everyone brings different amounts and types of public engagement experience to the training and will have different opportunities to put the skills developed in the training into practice.

And finally, impact may not be apparent until years down the line, or after grant funding has ended and the practitioners who delivered and evaluated the training have moved on to other roles.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The HDDBI public engagement programme is supported by a Wellcome Research Enrichment grant (215116/Z/18/C).

Entry: 445

Applicant details

Submission category: 8 - Research teams
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Priston, Sarah
Organisation/University: Bath Spa University
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The REF Operational team at Bath Spa University consists of two Research Librarians, a Research Impact Fellow, an Impact Manager, and the Head of Research. The team have worked closely together to develop a distinctive research profile at Bath Spa which reflects our creative and professional practice focus and embeds equitable and inclusive research practice across our research culture.

As part of REF2021, we published open access portfolios outputs for our creative practice research, and taken the lead across the sector in the development of this area. Our Research Librarian, Claire Drake, is a co-lead in the annual Capturing Creativity conference, an event which showcases creative practice research and other non-text-based content via repositories and/or submission of this content to the REF.

In REF2021, our Impact and Library teams worked closely together to develop portfolios of evidence in support of our creative practice to underpin our impact case studies in relevant UoA areas, making this material available to the public in a new and innovative fashion. Building on this, we have used our AHRC Impact Accelerator Award (IAA) to embed creative practice participatory and co-created research and impact approaches across our work. Research Impact Fellow (Dr Astrid Bree) set up an IAA interest group for small and specialist institutions, and her research on participatory research practices is directly informing the development of the impact culture at Bath Spa, and more widely across the sector.

We believe that by working together as a team across the university, we are a pioneer in this area. The research behind creative practice is often not showcased or easily accessible, and by developing this open access process, we hope to foster a better understanding of creative arts practices, and to put them on a level footing to more traditional outputs of research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Bath Spa University (BSU) has developed a strong research, impact and enterprise profile in recent years in arts and humanities, social sciences and most notably in the creative industries with a strong connection to non-academic audiences, few internal boundaries and a national and international profile for creativity, culture and enterprise in research.

The nature of our research mixes critical and creative research approaches and methodologies. These are enabled by interdisciplinarity and by combining creative, innovative and traditional research approaches and engagement strategies. Alongside our excellence in more traditional forms of scholarship, one of our key strengths is practice-based research, where we put conceptual and practical forms of knowledge into conversation with each other and work on, through, or with, practice.

BSU's distinctive approach to impact is supported by original research on impact strategies and frameworks for Arts and Humanities research, which specifically aims to develop innovative strategies for creating and capturing impact. Consideration of impact is embedded in the research strategy and

supported throughout the research cycle.

By working together with our Library team to develop a means of publishing and disseminating this work in an open and accessible fashion, we are able to showcase the richness and variety of our work in this area, as well as highlighting its reach and significance and the impact that these modes of working can have on inter, intra and multi-disciplinary research methodologies and collaborations.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

A&H; approaches to research and engagement, particularly creative practice, are often viewed as a means to showcase research and achieve impact for other disciplines, however we believe this approach is flawed. Creative practice research in particular is able to embed engagement into the research process in a way that positions participants as co-meaning-makers, instead of employing a process whereby completed research outcomes are subsequently applied to a specific context, community or organisation. BSU's distinctive approach to engaged A&H; research can be clearly seen in the Impact Case Studies submitted to REF2021, which demonstrate a breadth of impact types (from changes to practice, perceptions and improved health, wellbeing or educational outcomes) and stakeholders (from audiences to practitioners, community and creative organisations to international policy makers). These were underpinned by creative practice portfolios published on our Figshare repository, and co-developed with our Research Librarian and a team of Research Assistants recruited specifically for this purpose.

Post REF-2021, we have been working across the University, and through our external networks and collaborations, to raise the profile of this approach, and to demonstrate how arts and humanities approaches can add value to science and social science disciplines. Through our IAA, our involvement in creative media and digital projects such as the UKRI funded creative industry based collaboration MyWorld, and partnership with organisations such as the Black South West Network, we are pioneering approaches to show how non-traditional and co-created outputs can give greater access to rigorous and original work and benefit a range of disciplines in new and innovative ways. This equitable approach recognises the value of research participants and communities, and provides access to academic research in ways that still meet the UKRI criteria of transparency, openness, verification and reproducibility as well as improving public value, research integrity, reuse and innovation.

By working together as a team across the University, we have embedded this approach within open research policies, practices and procedures that support those undertaking research. The REF Steering Group supports this approach, and the University has invested in the impact and library teams and in a Figshare repository through which we can publish our portfolios and showcase this work.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 451

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Viggiani, Giulia

Organisation/University: University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The National Research Facility for Infrastructure Sensing (NRFIS) at the University of Cambridge is a cutting-edge research hub that significantly contributes to ground-breaking infrastructure research. Situated in the Civil Engineering Building on the West Cambridge Campus, NRFIS is part of the UK Collaboratorium for Research on Infrastructure & Cities (UKCRIC) and is funded by the Engineering and Physical Sciences Research Council (EPSRC).

NRFIS has been instrumental in advancing sensor technologies, and enhancing the safety, efficiency, and sustainability of critical infrastructure. By capitalising on Cambridge's expertise in sensor innovation, it builds on the achievements of key initiatives like the Centre for Smart Infrastructure and Construction (CSIC) and the CamBridgeSens network. These developments have not only led to breakthroughs in real-time infrastructure monitoring, helping to mitigate risks and extend the lifespan of critical infrastructure systems, but have also informed significant research outputs, such as the Fibre Optic Monitoring Systems in the University of Cambridge Civil Engineering Building. Notable publications include the European Workshop on Structural Health Monitoring (VOL 2, pp. 78-87, DOI 10.1007/978-3-031-07258-1_9).

The facility is also a catalyst for interdisciplinary collaboration and knowledge transfer. Through the Centres for Doctoral Training (CDTs) in Sensor Technologies for a Healthy and Sustainable Future (STHSF), Future Infrastructure and Built Environment: Resilience in a Changing World (FIBE2), NRFIS fosters the development of the next generation of researchers and leaders in infrastructure studies. The integration of world-class facilities and academic excellence at NRFIS has accelerated innovation, shaping the future of infrastructure and making a significant impact on the research community. This is exemplified by NRFIS work on reducing the carbon footprint of new construction projects through geometrical optimisation and the development of novel construction techniques, which supported the research output "A Prototype Low-Carbon Segmented Concrete Shell Building Floor System" in Structures, Vol. 49, pp. 124-138 (DOI: 10.1016/j.istruc.2023.01.063).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

NRFIS advances engineering and sensor technology by integrating cutting-edge facilities and capabilities. This interdisciplinary centre supports civil engineering, infrastructure design, construction and asset management, enabling the development of innovative sensors and instrumentation for monitoring everything from individual assets to complex systems like railways and city districts.

NRFIS stands out as a fundamental for advancing infrastructure research and development. It directly supports over 150 researchers at the University of Cambridge across various groups, including the structures, geotechnical, and environmental teams, as well as the Centre for Smart Infrastructure and Construction (CSIC) and Laing O'Rourke Centre for Construction Engineering and Technology (LoR). The facility also hosts more than 50 visitors annually from both UK and international universities, providing essential support for the design, build and execution of their experiments while creating opportunities for new collaborations and synergy.

The facility's significance extends to its collaboration with major industry partners such as HS2, Heathrow Airport, National Highways and Network Rail, conducting experiments that drive innovation in construction and infrastructure. NRFIS's interdisciplinary approach is evident through its extensive collaboration with other engineering disciplines, chemical, mechanical, computer and

manufacturing, as well as with academic departments such as architecture and computer science. Designed as a collaborative space, NRFIS includes break-out areas and offers 20% hotdesking for academic and industrial visitors. This setup fosters a dynamic environment for cooperation. Additionally, NRFIS supports the development of new equipment and novel test methods, exemplified by its work with Ramboll and GScan.

NRFIS facility provides structured access procedures, including self-operation after training, technical support for experiments, and full consultancy services for experimental design, execution and reporting. These diverse support levels underscore NRFIS's commitment to advancing research and innovation in infrastructure and related disciplines.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite its critical role in advancing infrastructure research, NRFIS's contributions can be underappreciated within the broader research culture and evaluation frameworks. This is largely because its impacts are embedded in practical applications and incremental improvements, e.g. NRFIS's integration of fibre optic sensing technology into the Institution of Civil Engineers guidelines, which are not always quantifiable as traditional academic outputs. As a result, significant contributions, such as advancing sensing technologies and improving infrastructure safety and efficiency, may not receive the visibility they deserve. For instance, in the recent REF 2021, Engineering at Cambridge (CUED) received a 100% score under 'Environment'. Though NRFIS was listed among the CUED important research facilities, its direct contributions, such as its impact on construction-cost savings, enhanced safety, and the protection of historic buildings, were not visible within that evaluation framework. NRFIS research facilities were also instrumental in the success of the REF 2021 impact case titled Smart Infrastructure. The research on infrastructure sensing led to the development and deployment of smart infrastructure approaches for asset monitoring and management. Despite these critical contributions, the role of NRFIS in driving these innovations may remain underappreciated. The facility's advancements in sensing and data analytics, resulting in CO₂-emission reductions and job creation through spin-out companies, are significant achievements that can sometimes remain hidden. The facility's use of up to six sensor packages during the construction of its own building, which monitored various aspects of performance, is a prime example of smart infrastructure, but it may not be widely known outside specialised circles. Furthermore, the open-access data provided by NRFIS has enabled researchers at the University of Birmingham to refine and optimise their building-physics models while setting new benchmarks for energy efficiency. Yet, these behind-the-scenes contributions often do not receive the same level of recognition as more prominent research outcomes.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 454

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Savio, Martina

Organisation/University: Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

RAMP training aims at equipping research support staff with knowledge and tools to better manage externally funded grants. The training covers topics on: Administration, including diary management, minute taking, and travel logistics; Project Management, including risks management, safeguarding, M&E, and the use of tools such as logframes and Gantt charts; and Financial Management, including budgeting, forecasting, and reporting.

The training course promotes equitable research partnerships, by upskilling research administrative staff and programme managers in the UK and in partner organisations in Africa. Sustainability is embedded via a 'Train the Trainers' approach and this has led to the course being successfully delivered in five different countries, with a further two courses scheduled for the remainder of 2024. A dedicated meeting of current and future trainers will be held in 2025, to discuss successes and challenges, and to ensure a consistent approach to course delivery.

The RAMP training benefits participants by increasing their knowledge and skills in research programme management and catalysing the formation of international networks of research support specialists. It benefits projects, by enhancing the quality of project delivery. And it also benefits academic staff and their research teams, enabling them to focus on their own areas of expertise with the assurance that the administrative aspects of project delivery will be efficiently executed.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

In response to partners' requests, a group of experienced programme managers and administrators, led by Martina Savio, established a three-day Research Administration and Management Programme (RAMP) training for research administrators, managers, and finance officers. The training was based on a needs assessment survey drawn from the SARIMA Professional Competency Framework under three themes: Administration, including diary management, minute taking, and travel logistics; Project Management, including risks management, safeguarding, M&E, and the use of tools such as logframes and Gantt Charts; and Financial Management, including budgeting, forecasting, and reporting.

After running an initial pilot session at the Liverpool School of Tropical Medicine (LSTM), this course has now been delivered in 5 different countries. The team have also embarked on a 'train the trainer' programme to ensure the sustainability of the programme and, importantly to ensure it can be delivered by our African partners.

Feedback from the participants has been overwhelmingly positive, with trainees commenting on the engaging nature of the course and how it is designed to ensure wide participation and cross learnings, the excellent way in which cultural contexts are considered, and the value of the material delivered. There has also been positive feedback from funders, who are increasingly recognising the important role of professionals working in partnership with the research teams to deliver the outcomes of a research initiative thereby maximising the impact of the investment.

Via this RAMP training, and other initiatives to increase the visibility of programme managers, Martina and the team are freeing up the time of academic staff to focus on research, building equity into international research partnerships and supporting the career development of critical members of the research ecosystem whose contributions are too often overlooked. Additionally, by standardising research administration practices, RAMP elevates the quality of project execution and reporting across the board. The increasing administrative and management workload due, in part, to more stringent governance research requirements means Principal Investigators spend over 40% of their time on administrative tasks, which could be more effectively done by dedicated research support staff. Despite this, the value of developing and supporting teams of dedicated research programme management professionals is often overlooked, and individuals fulfilling these roles do not always receive the support to conduct their roles effectively, and develop their careers. Furthermore, disparities in the availability of skilled programme management expertise can lead to inequities in research partnerships, with the administrative burden still residing with researchers in many settings.

A good programme management and administrative team adds immense value to a research project. They ensure that the project runs efficiently, delivers the intended outcomes and they support the documentation of the impact of the work. Investing time in training programme management and administrative staff also

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The increasing administrative and management workload due, in part, to more stringent governance research requirements means Principal Investigators spend over 40% of their time on administrative tasks, which could be more effectively done by dedicated research support staff. Despite this, the value of developing and supporting teams of dedicated research programme management professionals is often overlooked, and individuals fulfilling these roles do not always receive the support to conduct their roles effectively, and develop their careers. Furthermore, disparities in the availability of skilled programme management expertise can lead to inequities in research partnerships, with the administrative burden still residing with researchers in many settings.

A good programme management and administrative team adds immense value to a research project. They ensure that the project runs efficiently, delivers the intended outcomes and they support the documentation of the impact of the work. Investing time in training programme management and administrative staff also helps promote sustainability of knowledge and good practice by increasing retention of these skilled professionals and reducing the wastage of each project starting from scratch with new project documentation for each funding cycle.

Despite the clear value added, programme management staff are rarely authors on publications or named on grant applications. By developing the RAMP programme, and training trainers to deliver this programme to wider audiences within partner institutes, Martina and the team are ensuring that good practice in research programme management is embedded and disseminated across the research community. The "Train the trainer" component of RAMP creates a multiplier effect, exponentially increasing the programme's reach and impact. This approach, spearheaded by Martina, is building long-term institutional capacity in our African partner institutes, reducing dependency on external expertise and fostering self-sufficiency in research management.

Martina has invested time, passion, creativity in developing and continuously improving this training and, in doing so she has had a largely unseen but significant impact on the quality and reach of research conducted in the institutes that have benefited from this training to date.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: Initial development of the course material was funded by UKAID via the LIGHT consortium <https://light.lstmed.ac.uk/>

Entry: 455

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Murphy Quinlan, Maeve

Organisation/University: University of Leeds

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

As part of the Hidden Ref competition, I would like to put forward output from my role as a research software engineer in the form of training materials I have developed and delivered to researchers from the postgraduate level up to senior staff members. Specifically, I would like to submit the web app teaching resource I built to introduce researchers to good software development practices; to take the many tools and methods they may have heard of (such as version control, testing, documentation etc.) and incorporate them into a useable workflow that isn't overwhelming for non-computational-specialists: <https://software-dev.streamlit.app/>

This is additionally supported by the stripped-down reference site for the DeReLiCT (Dependencies, Repository, License, Citation, Testing) acronym I developed to help researchers build more reproducible and robust scientific code (<https://derelict.streamlit.app/>), and the detailed course notes and Python Project Template (<https://github.com/murphyqm/python-project-template>) I used to deliver a day-long intensive workshop to researchers (<https://arctraining.github.io/swd3-notes/>). Alongside these software development training materials, I have also developed well-received introductory data visualisation material (<https://arctraining.github.io/data-vis/start.html>) which introduces both theoretical concepts surrounding visualisation design, as well as building practical skills in using Python to script reproducible plotting workflows.

Together, these materials address critical aspects of software development and data visualization, offering researchers the tools to enhance reproducibility, improve data communication, and ultimately advance the quality of their research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The development and upkeep of accessible training materials on both good scientific software development practises and data visualisation are crucial in advancing scientific research. In addition to delivering these courses and providing a welcoming, accessible environment to learn these skills, the published resources allow for asynchronous learning and reference outside of the scheduled workshops I run within my university and enable the material to reach a much wider audience.

1. Increasing reproducibility, reusability and integrity. Software engineering practises such as version control, testing, and documentation, ensure that code is functional, maintainable, understandable. The materials linked (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Layout , https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow) embed these tools in an easy-to-use workflow, while the introductory slides (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow) compare these approaches to various checks and balances used in laboratory analysis to highlight the importance to researchers.

2. Improving communication of research results. The training materials enable researchers to create more impactful and effective graphics for their research output. Visualisation is a cornerstone of research output, yet many researchers do not receive formal training. These materials combine theory including ethics and accessibility, with hands-on code tutorials. The focus on developing useful, readable

documentation for your research code in the software development materials (<https://github.com/murphyqm/python-project-template/wiki/mkdocs-workflow>) results in a better review process, and increasing the likelihood of reuse of their code.

3. Enhancing collaboration and community. The materials linked provide pathways for researchers to implement version control workflows, automated testing, and documentation as part of their computational research. These tools allow for better collaboration, both with close colleagues and with researchers around the globe through public repositories, by making the code findable, accessible, and more understandable, and by reducing the likelihood of conflicts when developing in tandem.

4. Reducing the cognitive load on researchers. In addition to being domain experts, increasingly researchers require a full suite of software development skills. Frequently, tutorials and documentation on tools and methods such as version control systems, code packaging, and testing, assume a level of formal computational expertise that many researchers do not have. However, these tools are crucial in ensuring reproducible code and robust results. To that end, these materials stitch together these disparate tools into an intuitive workflow. The workflow page linked provides a simple script that will create customised bash scripts to build a project folder structure (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow#2-create-package-repository-and-directory-structure), and a script to create a pyproject.toml file for you based on form entries (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow#7-build-package-with-pyproject-toml). Example GitHub action scripts are provided (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow#8-build-automated-workflows) for simple testing, packaging and documentation workflows. Detailed explanations and code snippets are provided to enable the researcher to effectively use conda environment yaml files to record their development environment (https://software-dev.streamlit.app/Project_Workflow#3-create-a-dev-env). The material provides a very accessible, immediately implementable workflow to improve the quality of the researchers' computing work.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The development of teaching and training materials for research on topics such as software development and visualisation best practices are often overlooked. Research evaluation tends to reward more tangible outputs such as publication and grant application successes, at the cost of support work to build the foundational skills that underpin these results. The focus on high-impact outputs often sidelines the importance of training, and the development of scientifically robust workflows to enable the research. The inputs, though crucial, are less tangible or directly measurable than research findings.

Additionally, academic evaluations frequently emphasise domain-specific expertise over methodological skills; valuing the researcher and their output's contribution to their field's body of knowledge over the quality of their research tools and methods. The availability and use of training and training materials for good research software skills are not obvious in traditional research output; however, the lack of these tools and skills can be seen systemically when we look at the reproducibility crisis.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 460

Applicant details

Submission category: 8 - Research teams
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Milligan, Gordon
Organisation/University: University of Dundee
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

We are nominating our combined data and research software engineer team from the Alleviate Pain Data Hub for the Research Team category. The technical team based at the Universities of Dundee and Nottingham working with Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) has been instrumental over the last 4-5 years to develop efficient processes for standardising data to the Observational Medical Outcomes Partnership (OMOP) Common Data Model (CDM). In providing design input, and software development efforts, to a suite of open-source tools called CaRROT Mapper (<https://carrot.ac.uk/>) that improved the speed and efficiency of mapping data to OMOP and in being central to the mapping of over 10 million individuals UK electronic healthcare records.

The team has worked across multiple domains during this time including two years mapping COVID-19 data during the pandemic (in the CO-CONNECT project), two years mapping health data related to chronic pain as part of the Alleviate project and a range of population scale and biobank collected health data.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Research datasets are often not maintained and siloed away when data collection has been completed. This results in important research outputs not being FAIR: Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. With medical and health data there is an opportunity to rationalise existing data to the OMOP common data model and linking it via a federated network such as the HDR UK cohort discovery tool and the European Health Data & Evidence Network (EHDEN) thereby breaking down silos and making it FAIR.

Taking existing datasets and „Ämapping,Ä them to OMOP is a time consuming, manual process. The team has mapped over 25 data sets to the OMOP standard and in doing so has developed a set of tools for streamlining reproducible workflows at population scale datasets. The team took on the challenge of standardising data to OMOP before it become widely adopted and therefore, we have had to overcome several challenges during this period to keep moving forward and creating these standardised data sets available for reuse.

The team's work has also been pivotal in the development of the UK-wide HDR UK Cohort Discovery Tool due to the datasets they have mapped for the purposes of being able to run discovery queries to find existing data that is suitable for researchers needs and thus saves significant money and time for researchers. Now researchers can query the metadata of over 5M individuals' data in real time for the first time.

Furthermore, there is a growing need for data to support real world evidence studies where OMOP is particularly well suited to. For example, a multinational COVID-19 study from a baseline of 493 million patients from 26 datasets in 12 countries identified 24 million COVID-19 patients (doi: 10.1016/j.eclinm.2023.101932).

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

There is substantial interest in performing increasingly more studies based on real-world evidence from NHS patient data since the pandemic as we all saw how important it is to get real-time and real-world information to make health decisions at scale. The issue is that patient data is not designed for research and is extremely complex to work with routinely both technically and in terms of information data governance rules outside of a pandemic.

There are whole teams of professionals spread across the UK who have decades of experience of managing health data to support research, who rarely get acknowledged and even less added as co-authors despite the fact that research would be impossible without them. This team has made significant contributions to the UK data landscape through delivery of a large cohort of federated OMOP data. In this team submission we include data managers, data analysts, data engineers as well as information governance specialists, research software engineers and service team leads who all make vital contributions in terms of data and software infrastructure that UK health data research is intrinsically dependent on. Acknowledgement through Hidden Ref would go some way to start to highlight this important hidden role.

Further details

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Dr Tom Giles - Nottingham University

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Dr Sam Cox ,À Nottingham University

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Prof Phil Quinlan ,À Director of Health Informatics, Nottingham University

Dr Esmond Urwin ,À Nottingham University

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Funding acknowledgements: The Alleviate Pain Data Hub was funded under the Advanced Pain Discovery Platform consortium by the MRC, Versus Arthritis, Lilly and the Medical Research Foundation grant number: MR/W014335/1

Entry: 464

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Montague-Hellen, Beth

Organisation/University: Francis Crick Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Ensuring the integrity of scientific research is of utmost importance. Without safeguards and assurances that research is accurately reported, and outcomes are reproducible, it cannot be used as the foundation for future research or for medical advances. One important step in ensuring research integrity is in making sure that raw data underlying published discoveries is securely archived, alongside metadata, ensuring it continues to be understandable and reuseable.

At the Francis Crick Institute, a secure internal data archive was set up to ensure the archiving of all raw data associated with written outputs written by employees or students of the institute. Where data can be openly shared, this is encouraged, but the new process allows for the management of data which is personally or commercially sensitive, in addition to that which can be made open.

The archive is an internal system, utilising existing secure tape storage and the HPC data centre, and is triggered by the same systems that tell the library team a paper has been published. Researchers are asked to deposit their raw data in a structured folder hierarchy alongside documentation and explanatory metadata. The submission is checked for completeness, and understandability, by a data librarian before it is sent to write-only tape storage. While the data is still retrievable, it is no longer immediately available, and the version archived on tape cannot be altered.

The archive was soft launched with volunteer research groups during the first five months in 2024, and was made compulsory for all data-based research outputs from July 2024. In the two months since it has gone live, at least one member of 1/3 of research groups have been trained in the use and rationale behind the archive. The data behind 12 research papers has been successfully stored, with another 42 in progress.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Research Integrity has become a clear concern across biological and medical sciences. Failures in ensuring the accuracy and completeness of research data can lead to adverse health effects. Whilst it is important for the progression of science that researchers share their data openly and FAIRly, wherever possible, when patient data is involved this is not always possible. Much of the research at the Crick involves clinical or identifiable health data, and in these cases it is crucial that data that substantiates published outputs can still be safely retained.

The new internal data archive at the Francis Crick Institute allows all researchers to securely archive the data associated with their research outputs alongside documentation and explanatory metadata. This means that for up to 20 years all research from the Institute can be traced back to its original raw data ensuring that any concerns about research integrity can be investigated.

Bringing in a new archiving process has also allowed for a new training course to be run alongside it, primarily to teach researchers to use the new system, but also to teach research data management and research integrity basics. This training has so far been taken by 60 members of the Crick covering 37 research groups. Through a train-the-trainer ethos this has allowed us to have promoted best practice

across one third of the Institute.

Conversations during our training sessions have shown that the process of carefully documenting and storing data for future use is not always a prioritised part of the research cycle, and as such the culture change necessary for all researchers to archive their data is significant. The new archive will force a behaviour change on researchers and will hopefully help to showcase the importance of good post-project data management. Responses from training session attendees imply that this is already happening.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Research Integrity Data Archive will sit behind all research articles published by Institute authors from July 2024 onwards. Whilst the research articles themselves are subject to evaluation by the Institute's funding bodies (MRC, Wellcome, CRUK), and through metrics such as citations or altmetrics, it is only with the assurance of the data in the archive that we can trust the integrity of the research that the articles describe. The archive allows for reproducibility and transparency of any research integrity investigations but is not a visible part of the research.

It is to be hoped that the archive will hardly ever be used in a research integrity investigation as its use will likely imply that something has gone wrong, or that research has been carried out in an improper way. In cases where bad practice has been proved by the archive, organisations and individuals are unlikely to celebrate this, even though it would be a win for ensuring the integrity of the scientific process.

The project to develop the archive and its regulation and guidance documents was managed by the Library and Information Services (LIS) team, with technical expertise provided by the Research Computing Platform team, and the ServiceNow Development team in the IT Office. Initial guidance and expert advice was provided by the Research Integrity team. The cross-team nature of this output means that internally the archive is seen as a new Institute initiative rather than the success of any one team. Science and research are still seen as the preserve of a lone genius, or at the least, of discrete teams. Within this framework it is difficult for whole organisation wide initiatives to be appropriately evaluated and celebrated.

Further details

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Primarily responsible for development of archive, training and reviewing submissions

James Turner, Assistant Research Director Research Integrity, 0000-0003-1722-7677

Initial development of project, project sponsor and oversight, expert advise

Eleanor Adams, Research Integrity Officer, 0000-0003-1758-7103

Expert advise, reviewing submissions & training

Funding acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Francis Crick Institute which receives its core funding from Cancer Research UK (CC0103, CC2052), the UK Medical Research Council (CC0103, CC2052) and the Wellcome Trust (CC0103, CC2052)

Entry: 465

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Turner-McMullan, CJ

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Bath Spa University's Public Engagement Toolkit is a digital resource aimed at supporting researchers and research support professionals across the university to reflect on and determine actionable strategies for effective public engagement. The Toolkit aids the university's strategic commitments to deepening our community impact and enriching our public and civic offerings by developing institutional support and training for staff, helping them deliver and learn from publicly engaged research and activities.

The Toolkit's central page will be located under the Knowledge Exchange subsection of the university's intranet and host a series of mini 'kits' that focus on various PE principals and practical considerations, such as 'Defining Public Engagement' and 'Delivering Ethical Engagement'. The kits will be downloadable as individual guidance sheets or as a single document to serve as open resources for permanent and casual staff, external collaborators, and in teaching. The Toolkit continues to develop as staff begin to engage with it in practice and will eventually be made available for wider external use via Figshare.

The Toolkit is an engagement resource created through engagement. The content and format of the kits were determined through an internal project, which involved staff to explore their research strengths and challenges in relation to public audiences, participants and partners, engagement formats, ethics, accessibility, and practical approaches. The project engaged staff to help identify areas for confidence- and capacity-building, informing the kits and the framework around which they are structured. The framework, which features sections on Planning, People, Impact & Evaluation, and Resources, reflects the university's creative and practice-based research culture, modelling as well as advocating for purposeful and reflexive PE practice through an emphasis on embedded engagement and action research processes as tools for building sustainable engagement and lasting collaborations.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The research found that a lack of coherent definitions of what public engagement is, or what it could be in the contexts and disciplines characteristic of BSU, presented a barrier to effective PE across the university. Staff expressed a need for interdisciplinary perspectives and resources that account for creative flexibility and relationality within the bounds of established KE, collaboration, and participation models. To address this in line with BSU's strategic aims, which look to maximise partner-focused collaborations locally, nationally and internationally, the Toolkit emphasises the effectiveness of co-creation and durational engagement in developing impactful, reciprocal relationships. The checklists, worksheets and reflective exercises will prompt users to examine their motivations and place stakeholder, audience and participant needs before the needs of the research, approaching them as the guiding components of engagement formats and activities.

The project has had impact in other areas of research support. Conversations with the University Ethics Committee helped identify the need for a PE-specific ethics process and implement a framework for categorising administrative, evaluation and research data in PE contexts. In another collaboration, the organisers of Being Human: Bath festival hub developed an 'Inclusion Guide' as a menu tool to help

potential participants access support for Being Human Festival events. The 'Inclusion Guide' template will be shared via the Toolkit for use across the university to benefit future PE organisers and publics engaging with participatory events.

The development models a co-creation process that will ensure the Toolkit's future continuity and flexibility to meet the changing needs of BSU staff and research. Through participation in the internal and public-facing events, sandpits, and consultation activities through which the development occurred, staff had opportunities to experience and learn about best practice in interdisciplinary contexts, including practical delivery, ethics and data management, and scrutinising public interest in their research to inform funding bids. Once consolidated within the Toolkit, the guidance, case studies and templates will act as a scaffold for future in-practice PE capacity-building, holding and functioning to channel PE knowledge within and beyond BSU.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Toolkit is just a fragment of the support that enables research projects and training across the university. As the Toolkit section dedicated to 'People' demonstrates, much of this work is relational and concerned with the quality of the partnerships and discreet practices that support PE to connect publics with research in meaningful ways. The work behind the Toolkit is also predominantly internal, particularly in its current phase where the project to ensure its appropriateness and accessibility is still ongoing. While the Toolkit's early effectiveness might be recognisable within BSU, its implications for the strength, integrity and impact of our external engagement are measurable primarily in the effectiveness of the projects it will support.

Resources like the Toolkit are designed to be embedded into professional practice, so recognition for this work is, rightly, shared with others who implement their learning to achieve what are often primarily qualitative outcomes. These projects are unlikely to contain scope for acknowledging this support when traditional KPIs and reporting models place greater importance on quantitative metrics for determining impact and outcomes. These models leave outcomes such as public trust or participant safeguarding outside the scope of compulsory evaluations, so the values of resources supporting these capacities go overlooked.

Support for public engagement is often not available at smaller institutions, and yet embedding these principles and processes in an ethical and equitable manner is key to their success. The contribution that research assistants and administrative staff make to this process is often overlooked or not acknowledged. This nomination recognises the substantial contribution that resources like this make to our externally facing work.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 470

Applicant details

Submission category: 7 - Standards
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Cole, Christian
Organisation/University: University of Dundee
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Trusted Research Environments (TREs), also known as Secure Data Environments or Data Safe Havens, are restricted computing environments for securely managing sensitive data such as patient health records or administrative data for research within legal frameworks like GDPR. The use of TREs has grown rapidly over the last 10 years in the UK and more are being established across the world. Yet this growth has been organic and ad hoc leading to fragmentation, complexity and lack of interoperability and transparency.

The Standardised Architecture for Trusted Research Environments (SATRE) is a specification designed to try and bring together the TRE community around a core set of principles and capabilities.

The SATRE specification was developed with input from around 60 different organisations as well as members of the public in the open through github <https://github.com/sa-tre/satre-specification>. The first stable release (v1.0) was published in October 2023 and has since been taken up nationally and internationally by academic, government and industrial organisations for either assessment of existing TREs or for development of new ones.

For the first time, there is a nationally relevant specification for TREs in UK to help identify gaps and similarities across a diverse landscape of solutions. It has been enthusiastically taken up by academia, industry, the NHS and other research organisations.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Prior to the publication of SATRE there was no specification nor best practices guide to support new and existing organisations define how well their TREs conformed with others in the UK. This uncertainty made it harder for organisations to develop their own and for data governance specialists to define consistent requirements.

In 2008 the „Five Safes“ were published as an overall set of principles in ensuring sensitive data is managed securely. In 2014 the Scottish Government published the Safe Haven Charter which provided guidance on the expectations for Safe Havens in Scotland should follow and in 2017 the Digital Economy Act included provisions for the use of data for research including accreditation. All the developments are useful, but do not help in defining best practice nor identify how to improve.

In bringing the UK TRE community together to develop a set of core capabilities that a TRE needs to fulfil in under a year shows the level of interest and desire for everyone to work together for a common goal. Contributors to the SATRE specification included academic institutions, public representatives both within and external to the project team, industry as well as government organisations such as the NHS and the Office for National Statistics.

Given that the project was run fully transparently in the open meant that anyone could engage and contribute reflecting all voices as much as possible within the nine-month project. The co-development and joint ownership resulted in a v1.0 release that reflected the pluralist view and could quickly be taken

up by the TRE community to assess themselves against the SATRE Specification.

NHS Secure Data Environment technical leads have used SATRE as a blueprint in part with a public cloud provider who are building a novel solution. Industry are using it to showcase the suitability of their TRE solutions such as Aridhia or to ensure that their clients are adequately secure in using their solutions such as Canon Medical. The Scottish Safe Haven Network (covering 99% of the population's health data for research) have self-assessed and peer-reviewed their five Safe Havens against the SATRE specification.

Further afield, the EU Horizon project EOSC-ENTRUST (<https://eosc-entrust.eu/>) is using the SATRE specification as a baseline reference for defining core capabilities across the Secure Processing Environments in the 15-nation consortium. The project aims are to develop a blueprint for a European network of trusted research environments.

Defining a specification is the first step towards a formal standard which enable multinational research using sensitive data in the most secure and efficient ways.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Research infrastructure is not novel nor exciting for researchers or funders, but is critical for the support and enablement of discovery science. There is a growing need for the use of sensitive data in research, regardless of whether it is health data or social data or governmental data, to inform on the health, wealth and status of country-wide populations.

Much of the work to establish resilient and reliable research infrastructure is either funded through central university funding, big one-off grants or drip-fed through project grants supporting staff in short term contract roles. There is usually little longterm support available and within the traditional REF is included in the research environment that an institution provides. This is helpful for REF-able research staff, but does not recognise the fundamental importance of delivering innovative infrastructure solutions like TREs to meet the needs of research.

I believe the SATRE specification and project team are a clear example of research-relevant activities that deserve to be acknowledged in the Hidden REF.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-2560-2484

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: See here
<https://zenodo.org/records/10055345>

Funding acknowledgements: This work was funded by UK Research & Innovation [Grant Number MC_PC_23008] as part of Phase 1 of the DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) programme, delivered in partnership with Health Data Research UK (HDR UK) and Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK).

Entry: 474

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Walls, Richard

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Our submission is for the role that HIC (the Health Informatics Centre, The University of Dundee, School of Medicine) has provided and developed over 20 years in advancing research infrastructure (Established in 2004).

HIC has implemented and operationalised a range of research infrastructure services enabling a secure ISO27001 accredited 'Safe Haven' (or Trusted Research Environment) as part of the Scottish Safe Haven Network (SSHN) for Scottish Government. This range of technical infrastructure services (infrastructure & data engineering, software development and data science research), developed by sustaining a technical staff of c.45 experts spanning academia and the NHS supporting >£20M grant awards in the last 5 years. This has ensured a secure analytics platform that enables researchers and innovators to access sensitive data for research, which is linked, deidentified electronic health records (EHRs) while managing the risk of unauthorised reidentification. HIC as research infrastructure and a team of experts is recognised in Scotland as contributing to the success of research and innovation:

The research infrastructure operated with expert staff, developed and maintained has resulted in (to date) 372 Research Outputs. Some of the most recent being:

-Artificial intelligence-assisted automated heart failure detection and classification from electronic health records. Oo, M. M. (Lead / Corresponding author), et al, 3 May 2024, (E-pub ahead of print) In: ESC Heart Failure. 9 p.

-The Scottish Medical Imaging Archive: 57.3 million Radiology Studies Linked to their Medical Records. Baxter, R. et al, Jan 2024, In: Radiology: Artificial Intelligence. 6, 1, 6 p., e220266.

Recent milestone or flagship projects have been advanced for research infrastructure and enabled by the technical combination of expertise, technology and securely held sensitive data such as: CO-CONNECT, PICTURES, SMI service, ALLEVIATE, SHARE register, Childsmile, Tayside Biorepository and SATRE.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The significance of the HIC research infrastructure is to drive and enable research using sensitive health and administrative data that addresses research and innovation priorities for Scotland and UK. HIC has played a key role for 20 years as a safe haven environment but in particular for the last 8 years on technical research infrastructure innovation to support access to data for secure research using multi-modal data such as imaging, genomics and e-health records as well as the application of cloud computing, machine learning, natural language processing and omics for innovative research.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

HIC as a technical team enabling research infrastructure is a hybrid group with both a team of academic researchers (non-clinical, embedded within it and assessed along traditional lines for REF, including learning & teaching) as well as an advisory group providing services for research enablement / research

impact and engagement / enterprise in line with our University of Dundee core strategy to be triple intensive. Our technical team as HIC provides a centre with considerable impact across all three core areas. As our research, research enablement and research services are often key elements to delivering innovative research for others we are not always credited with our hidden role in ensuring sustainable, innovative success within the traditional REF program.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 475

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sims, David

Organisation/University: University of Oxford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Technological advances have enabled a wide range of quantitative biological assays to become widely used in biomedical research (e.g. genomics, proteomics, metabolomics, imaging). Training in computational methods is vital for modern quantitative biology but is not always part of traditional biomedical degrees. The Oxford Biomedical Data Science training programme offers a wide range of in-depth face-to-face training courses ranging from basic data science skills to advanced computational biology analyses.

The programme was established in 2018 and runs three times a year aligned with university terms. Courses last from 5-10 days and offer multiple real-world hands-on exercises to develop coding and problem-solving skills. Expert support is always on hand to reduce learning curve and discuss methods and parameters. The programme provides professional development for researchers across a wide range of career stages giving them new career perspectives and opportunities.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Training of post-graduate researchers, post-doctoral scientists and technicians underpins the analysis and interpretation of an increasing proportion of biomedical research projects.

To date we have trained over 250 doctoral students, post-doctoral scientists, research technicians and group leaders from a biomedical background in data science and computational biology. Participants use the skills gained on our courses to analyse and interpret their own biomedical data sets, resulting in peer-reviewed articles, conference presentations and doctoral theses. In feedback surveys participants consistently rate the courses as excellent and acknowledge a substantial contribution to their research projects and career progression. Many course participants return for multiple courses and go on to pursue careers in biomedical data science.

Developing and maintaining training materials, as well as providing regular face-to-face training takes considerable time and effort. Furthermore, training in advanced and specialised topics requires experience and expertise that are currently in very high demand. It is important that individuals and teams that give up their valuable time to train others have this recognised as an important output that can contribute to their career progression.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Provision of specialised and advanced training for post-doctoral scientists and technicians is not a widely recognised as a research output. Recognition of the vital role of such training in underpinning a wide range of research projects is important to maintain funding and to attract and develop trainers with highly sought after skills and experience.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 478

Applicant details

Submission category: 8 - Research teams

Role submitted: n/a

Name: de Cogan, Rosin

Organisation/University: Slade School of Fine Art - University College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Slade School of Fine Art Technical Team, consisting of seven full-time and part-time staff members specialising in fabrication, print, media, and photography, plays a vital role in supporting a diverse range of research projects at the Slade.

Their contributions are pivotal to both individual and group research, including work by Slade research staff such as Professors Sharon Morris, Kate Bright, Lilah Fowler, Graham Gussin, Jo Volley, as well as Onya McCaulson and Lesley Sharpe. They also support collaborative efforts like Spineless Wonders, an international network of artists, writers, academics and librarians, creating and researching small press publications including artists books and the Materials Research Project, which spearheads research into the role of materials within the creative process.

In addition to continually supporting the research of others, the technical team regularly undertake technology and area improvement plans and bid for funding from a variety of sources, including several successful bids in recent years from UKRI's Research Capital Investment Fund. These improvements are made to expand the research possibilities available to Slade School of Fine Art researchers and facilitate a dynamic research environment.

The technical team have created well equipped workshops that are open and accessible to all, allowing speculative, open-ended, materials-based experimentation and production to flourish. In the Slade research, discourse, dialogue, making and reflection are hosted in equitable spaces reflecting the diverse research practices and voices in the department.

The Technical team, as a whole, play a core role in a vast amount of the research produced within the Slade. Their role within this research often goes unacknowledged and unrecognized in the grander scheme of research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The practice-based nature of research within the Slade School of Fine Art means that the workshops and the technical team form the base structure of the research produced. The day-to-day work of the technicians in maintaining, running and supervising the use of the equipment and workspaces is what allows researchers to focus on the work at hand and think and act in the dynamic ways needed for true advancement and success.

The academic staff conducting research in the Slade work hand in hand with the technical team while conducting research. They understand the importance of the framework that the technical team provides them. They are continually supportive the advancements the team undertake, as seen in the departmental support of the technical teams Research Capital Investment Fund bids. However, even with this support, the true extent of the technical teams input into research is not fully recognised or understood.

The Slade School of Fine Art has a long history of significant practice-based research, and this is only possible because of the long-standing technicians who support research. Until the importance of these

regularly uncredited participants in the research is recognised we are not fully understanding the work that has gone into the research. This submission is an attempt to shine a light on the work behind the scenes of the research coming out of the Slade and to finally acknowledge the hard work and dedication of the technical team in supporting its production.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Current research in the world of Art and Creativity regularly overlooks the contributions and roll of technicians in supporting research. Although technicians may be mentioned or thanked in research papers the sheer scale of work behind the scenes is rarely recognised or acknowledged. Without the hard work and dedication of the technical team in supporting researchers, developing research spaces and creating and maintaining the infrastructure required much of the research generated in the Slade would not be possible.

This is in juxtaposition to other areas of research such as scientific research, where the pivotal roll of the technician is well understood and acknowledged. Most researchers in the creative sector will know the names of other researchers in the same field however they do not know who the technicians behind the research are. An acknowledgment of these technicians behind the scenes of creative research is the first step to putting a spotlight on all of the hidden and overlooked people assisting in the creation of research within creative disciplines.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 479

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bayley, Amanda

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

'Hear Water: cross-disciplinary community and education resource' was a Leading Impact project at Bath Spa University (2023-24) funded by an AHRC Impact Accelerator Award. It focussed on listening, nature connectedness, sounds of nature, science, music technology, creativity and wellbeing, through workshops delivered by Kathy Hinde, Jill Parsons and Matthew Olden, in partnership with Ian Thornhill (University of Manchester) and Tom Walmsley, Avon Schools Eco Network (ASEN). It combined participatory artistic and scientific approaches, enabling research into blue spaces (e.g. ponds, rivers, streams, lakes) in urban environments. The project expands and strengthens researcher-user partnerships established in its precursory interdisciplinary project, 'Hear Water: building environmental empathy through deep listening', funded by NERC in 2022 under the 'Creative Climate Connections: COP26 environmental science public engagement scheme. Working with 36 young people from Imayla, a community-based organisation in Bristol, it aimed to increase knowledge and understanding of climate change, the value of blue spaces, and actions individuals can take, whilst assessing the extent to which the aural perception of environmental issues could be a new approach to achieving positive social change and increased environmental empathy. It also aimed to inspire environmental stewardship (e.g. through the revaluing of river systems), and creativity (e.g. through the manipulation of recorded sounds).

Hear Water 2.0 has resulted in a suite of resources and bespoke training for teachers and community leaders to build hydrophones to use with their classes or community groups to collect scientific data, as well as to create artistic experiences and outputs. Two primary schools in Bristol were involved through the partnership with ASEN; Walmsley is following up with teachers to facilitate the sharing of hardware between schools. The Hear Water resources are designed to upskill primary and secondary school teachers in interactive and participatory learning activities that combine listening, technology, science, eco-therapy, creativity, and wellbeing.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The significance of the project lies in the educational value of the resources, and the innovative content resulting from a productive partnership of researchers, artists and educators. Activities were tried and tested with two different community groups in 2022, then expanded, tested and refined among researchers, teachers and young people for Hear Water 2.0. Both projects were based around and within local water courses where participants were introduced to a range of activities and participation in citizen science including: listening walks; testing water quality of rivers; hydrophone building; sound recording; digital music creation; interpreting scientific data via sounds using a music box; games; reflection and group discussions.

With a focus on listening to our environment, cross-curricular learning and training resources aim to improve staff knowledge and confidence in delivering an eco-creative curriculum. The development of ecoliteracy is encouraged through participatory listening practices. The guides show teachers how to implement the activities, with exercises to try, and resources they can tap into, to enable more interactive learning.

The significance of the research and the resources are so far evidenced at a local level from evaluation

reports from the participants (young people, community leaders, teachers and researchers) involved in each iteration of the project and are now being disseminated more widely.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The immediate beneficiaries are teachers, community organisations and young people, rather than academics. The first output was a soundscape film made from participants' contributions, screened at the culminating celebration event at Bristol Aquarium, October 2022: <https://vimeo.com/757986035>. The outputs from Hear Water 2.0 are resources (online and practical) in the form of activities with downloadable pdf guides and online tutorials:

<https://submergedsounds.co.uk/2024/06/16/hear-water-training-sessions/>. They enable teachers to work with their classes to:

- Learn outdoors to listen and sense nature in new ways
- Explore Nature Connectedness through listening games and activities
- Build hydrophones to listen underwater
- Collect underwater sounds to generate artistic outputs with music technology
- Gather scientific data on aquatic biodiversity
- Compose and improvise with sounds from nature

The resources suit the different contexts of school classrooms (ca 30 children) and community organisations, combining cross-curricula activities, wellbeing and the outdoors. They provide teachers, community members and young people with various means of changing eco-anxiety into eco-agency. The emphasis is now on dissemination and a video was created to promote the resources to teachers: https://youtu.be/zCcMx_ZZv-E. Quantitative information in terms of engagement of children, wellbeing measures and nature connectedness have been reported to the Nature Premium campaign (<https://www.outdoor-learning.org/community/sector-specialist-groups/nature-premium.html>) with the project to be featured as a case study on their website. Following a presentation (with Jill Parsons) at the Association for Science Education conference in January 2024, we have been invited to contribute an article to Teaching Times (in preparation). I have also been invited to BCfm studios in Bristol to talk about the project on the environmental show One Love One Planet, leading up to Our Earth Week in November 2024, which brings together community radio stations across the country.

The impact of the research activities is evidenced from the evaluation reports: the 2022 report emphasised how the different elements were significant for developing connections between listening, technology, nature sounds, science, creativity, and wellbeing, and embedding them alongside pedagogy. It documented how young people of Imayla learnt about their connections with nature, primarily through listening activities and the respective technologies: e.g. 'Usually modern technology takes us further away from nature but this time it's doing the complete opposite and that's a change'. The mixed methods evaluation report of Hear Water 2.0 is an output in its own right, with thematic analysis of observations and quotes triangulated with quantitative data.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: TBC

Funding acknowledgements: Leading Impact fund, AHRC Impact Accelerator Award

Entry: 480

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Colyer, Edwin

Organisation/University: Scientia Scripta

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Whilst at Manchester Met as an Impact Manager, Edwin developed a close and unusual collaboration with Prof Keeley Crockett around the ethics of AI which Edwin identified as an emerging field of important research, several years before ChatGPT placed AI ethics firmly in the public consciousness. Edwin designed and led some collaborative research to compare a set of practical ethical AI toolkits which revealed public engagement as a neglected dimension of ethical practice in AI research, development and deployment (DOI:10.1109/TAI.2021.3137091). This work persuaded Edwin that hearing different perspectives from a wide range of diverse people was an ethical imperative across the AI development and deployment life cycle and should be embraced and embedded as standard practice.

Through his own agency, Scientia Scripta, Edwin independently worked with colleague Holly Cave to develop training on public engagement with AI, with a strong emphasis on "participatory AI" and involving diverse and seldom-heard communities in research, development and deployment processes, deliberation and decision-making. The training highlighted this public involvement as an ethical imperative. It was delivered to professional services teams at The Alan Turing Institute, and proved to be transformative. It led to launch of the Institute's 2022 Public Engagement Fund, to which Dr Annabel Latham and Prof Crockett independently submitted a proposal to set up, train and pilot a People's Panel for AI which would probe and scrutinise the AI R&D; and ethics practices of SMEs and researchers in Manchester. Evaluation of the pilot shows significant personal benefits to participant members of the public as well as triggering changes in research design and business operation. Manchester City Council's Digital Strategy team adopted the model; over 20 people from the authority's most digitally excluded communities have scrutinised AI plans and system in several public service providers and Citizens Advice Bureau, again changing decision-making.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

**** Personal significance to panel members ****

Evaluation shows that the training and participation for panel members has given them much greater understanding of how AI works, where it is being used as well as its potential risks, benefits and ethical dimensions. It also boosted their confidence to ask questions about AI. They felt that their voice was heard. Quote from panellists in the original Turing pilot project include:

- "It's been a confidence builder for me, I feel more confident. Also, it has given me something to focus on, especially since the pandemic, it's given me an outlet."

- "The fact that my opinions were welcomed meant I was considered important, and I felt heard."

- "I went in knowing a little bit, but my ideas about AI were not the same as what we ended up talking about."

Participants from the Manchester City Council adoption and roll out of the People's Panel also talk about boosted confidence and interest in AI, with one going on to complete an AI bootcamp and increasing digital skills.

**** Significance for businesses and public services ****

Many participating businesses and public services reported how the insights and questions from the

panel, and their findings from the panel consequence scanning exercise, were invaluable and led to changes in decisions and operations. Comments from businesses, researchers and public service providers include:

- "We also have looked at the right to be forgotten and the impact of removal of datasets from training lifecycles. The feedback has filtered down through the team in terms of how we're talking about risks and mitigations and what that might all look like. It has given us an expanded language."

- "One of the recommendations of the panel is that the sample data used so far for the system is quite small. As a result I have been looking for more volunteers to participate in the ongoing training of the AI system."

* Significance of Manchester City Council's adoption *

The adoption by the council is a validation of the model and indicates how the council think it can help deliver on its digital strategy. The council is now looking at how to extend this model of engaged working beyond the Digital Strategy. The project officer reported significant interest in the model from other local authorities elsewhere in the UK. The model is a win-win: public participants enjoy the experience, learn about AI, boost confidence and develop critical thinking skills. Some go on to develop new digital skills in AI. The diversity of participants also support community cohesion. The feedback from the panel support more responsible and carefully considered AI development and deployment.

See <https://www.mmu.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2023-04/PeoplesPanelforAIv2final.pdf> and <https://manchesterdigitalstrategy.com/projects-1/peoples-panel-for-ai>

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

There is a linear pathway from the published research to the pilot People's Panel for AI, and the subsequent adoption by Manchester City Council. By REF 2029 it is hoped the model will have grown to some kind of distributed national infrastructure that organisations of all kinds can access for scrutiny and feedback. However, the critical role of the training delivered to the Turing Institute which underpinned the creation of the Public Engagement Fund 2022 risks being overlooked, especially as Edwin is no longer working in academia. However, this training was absolutely critical to pivoting the Turing's perspectives on public engagement away from events and lectures and instead reaching out to neglected and ignored communities, involving them and allowing their perspectives to shape research and innovation processes.

Further details

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Keeley Crockett, Manchester Metropolitan University, <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1941-6201>, Professor

Mohammed Kaleem, Manchester Metropolitan University, <https://orcid.org/0009-0004-7147-4147>, Lecturer

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Institute, Manchester City Council

Entry: 485

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sanderson, John

Organisation/University: UK Data Service (University of Essex, University of Manchester, Jisc, UCL and University of Edinburgh)

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission nominates the work of the UK Data Service, especially during the period 2017-2024, representing the most recent phase of delivery of a vital part of the UK's research data infrastructure which has been in existence for almost sixty years.

The UK Data Service (UKDS) is the principal repository for economic, population, and social research data in the UK. UKDS hosts the largest trusted digital archive of its kind, with expertise in the collection, preservation, and dissemination of quality data to enable high quality and impactful research.

Our digital data collection comprises nationally and internationally significant datasets. On behalf of governments, Office for National Statistics, ESRC, and diverse other funders and data producers we curate and archive, but also provide seamless access through a single portal, ensuring regulatory and privacy compliance for data users.

On an annual basis UK Data Service supports over 50,000 registered users, from over 140 countries around the world, accessing our collection of over 9,000 studies.

In support of the wider research ecosystem UK Data Service also provides wide ranging programmes of training and support for researchers, data depositors and other stakeholders, across the full data lifecycle to maximise the possibilities of data use and re-use. We train over 5,000 researchers each year with over 10,000 views each month of our online Learning Hub.

As pioneers in data curation, data literacy, data impact and actively managing long-term access to high quality data, our expertise continues to transform social science research, teaching and learning.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Relevance & Temporality:

Underpinned by our data access policy for open, safeguarded and controlled data, UK Data Service UKDS provides researchers worldwide a wide range of heavily utilised research resources including: Census data from 1971-2021/2, major UK longitudinal and cohort studies; data from UK government surveys ; international macro-data from World Bank, International Monetary Fund, OECD and much more.

UKDS continues to enhance our collection of research ready data collections. From 2017 to 2024, 937 new studies, and 618 new editions of existing studies, were added to the curated collection, along with the significant addition of census resources from the 2021/22 Censuses across England, Wales, Scotland and Northern Ireland, making these resources quickly and easily available for research use.

By maintaining long term relationships with producers of data we have ensured the ongoing and reliable availability of these valuable resources to the research community.

Continuity in service provision has enabled the UKDS to support consistent growth in data use across a wide user base (up from 22,551 registered users in 2017 to 52,764 registered users in 2024). Overall 'downloads' from our curated collection increased from 65,946 downloads in 2017/18 to 87,699 downloads in 2023/24). In the same period census data usage has totalled over a quarter of a million downloads and our macrodata resources have seen over 160,000 downloads.

Our comprehensive data collection, tiered approach to data access, and range of access solutions, has enabled data users to access the right data at the right time for their research.

Alongside data provision UKDS activity has built substantial social science research capacity in the research community through a relevant, evolving and extensive training and support programme, including ongoing development and curation of our online resources for user benefit. Through partnerships with others in the data skills training ecosystem we have provided opportunities for knowledge communities to coalesce. We have doubled our user base at live training events from 2,703 (Oct 2017- Sept 2018) to 5,204 (April 2023- March 2024) attendances per year (29,778 over the last 7 years). The UKDS online Learning Hub now achieves 10,000 unique views per month, with over 7,000 views per month of content on our expanding YouTube channel.

Leadership:

Above the direct function of UKDS as a provider of training, archiving & curation and data access solutions, UKDS has been active in leading the thinking and development of a range of areas across the data service landscape: from chairing the CoreTrustSeal Board, a leadership role in developing requirements for data repositories globally that sees us shaping policies that enhance data integrity and security across borders; to publishing our Data Skills Framework, which offers a comprehensive structural approach to developing skills for the next generation of researchers.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Our vital, behind the scenes, infrastructure does not result in outputs typically measured by the REF such as peer reviewed publications 'outputs' or direct societal 'impact' (since impact is achieved by researchers *using the data*, leaving UKDS a step removed), nor is the staffing of UKDS typically within REFable institutional units in our host organisations.

Many instances of highly impactful use of data, enabled by UKDS, also fall outside of current approaches, such as the Good Childhood Report on young people's wellbeing (Children's Society), proposals for poverty measures adopted by the UK government (Social Metrics Commission), and reports by the Equalities and Human Rights Commissions underpinning understanding of the state of diversity and equality in the UK and recommendations for improvement, all of which have used data from UKDS.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6471-6145>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Details to follow

Funding acknowledgements: The UK Data Service is funded by UKRI through the Economic and Social Research Council.

Entry: 486

Applicant details

Submission category: 2 - Training materials and courses

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Howkins, Ashley

Organisation/University: Experimental Techniques Centre, Brunel University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Materials characterisation is a vital technical skill that researchers require to conduct research and development of novel materials. A technique commonly used for materials characterisation is electron microscopy, which uses high energy electrons to visualise material microstructure, determine chemical composition and crystalline nature.

The ability to visualise and characterise materials at the micro and even nano scales, makes electron microscopy a very powerful tool; it is used at all levels of research and development, i.e. from small-scale under graduate projects and 3+ year post-graduate research projects up to industrial development and product evaluation. A quick search on Web of Knowledge for electron microscopy articles published in 2024 lists over 30,000 research articles.

In order for new and inexperienced electron microscopy users to conduct their research, the role of technical experts, who make a career out of getting the most from electron microscopes is vitally important.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Operating an electron microscope is a skill that requires understanding of both the microscope, the sample and how the two will interact. New and inexperienced researchers using electron microscopy, usually at the post-graduate, often have little understanding of the former.

It is the role of a technical expert to assist new researchers to get the most from the instrument. Furthermore, they will provide training on the instrument and pass on their expertise to equip researchers using EM with the skills to get the most from the technique.

In the Experimental Techniques Centre of Brunel University, the electron microscopes are run by a dedicated team of Scientific Officers. It is the role of the SOs to be electron microscopy technical experts, to work with the 102 active researchers on the electron microscopes, passing on training and experience to get the most from the system.

The ETC are keen to give new researchers the tools they require to conduct good research. As such, the majority of people requiring electron microscopy are provided with training from highly skilled electron microscopy technical staff.

In the past 12 months 29 new researchers have passed the ETC SEM training programme. The training programme requires the any researcher wishing to use SEM autonomously to complete a series of online lectures covering the fundamentals SEM characterisation, hands on demonstrations and then receiving hands on training on the system.

During the training Scientific Officers will give a new researched an appreciation of the technical requirements to conduct electron microscopy so they have the skills required to generate research outputs and publications.

The SOs are also keen to promote ongoing learning, so they will assist researchers where they may be struggling and/or upgrade the system they are working onto higher specification instruments whenever the researcher has exhausted the instrument they are utilising.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Of some 25 papers generated within Brunel utilising electron microscopy since 2022, the Scientific Officers are acknowledged within 6 of the publications despite all individuals receiving training using the technique. Furthermore, published research has shown electron microscope parameters are not reported in publications, and the microscopy facilities are often under recognised in the acknowledgements [Marques, 2020].

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-9435-523X

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 489

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Pereda, Javier

Organisation/University: Liverpool John Moores University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission highlights the development and use of an innovative research infrastructure that merges Digital Humanities, Critical Design and Cultural Heritage alongside decolonial practices. This focuses primarily on projects under the Printinteractive Research group and the Unlocking the Colonial Archive research projects. These interdisciplinary projects use cutting-edge digital tools to engage with hidden histories, cultural heritage, and the decolonial narrative. Through AI-driven data models, interactive installations, and digital platforms, the research infrastructure created fosters collaboration between academic researchers, cultural institutions, and community groups. These projects enable public engagement with complex historical and cultural narratives, such as the Trans-Atlantic slave trade, Latin American printmaking, and local folklore, in new, accessible, and creative ways. By combining AI, interactive technologies, and tangible interfaces, the infrastructure not only contributes to academic research but also ensures that marginalised voices and stories are brought to light in impactful ways.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Digital Humanities component includes projects like "Unlocking the Colonial Archive," which uses AI to analyse indigenous and colonial documents, fostering new methods for research and public engagement with cultural heritage datasets. The project contributes to more inclusive academic frameworks, where underrepresented voices in the colonial past are brought into focus.

Afrobits is a groundbreaking example of how interdisciplinary collaboration between historians, technologists, and artists can result in interactive installations that allow users to engage directly with intangible cultural heritage. The installation offers a multi-sensory experience of African music and the Trans-Atlantic slave trade, using low-cost and open-source digital technologies to make this history accessible to diverse audiences. It makes use of digital audio collections from the British Library and Sophia National Library of Brazil, and the Library of Congress in the USA. This approach has been especially impactful in bringing attention to the often-overlooked contributions of African cultures to global heritage.

Popular Graphic Arts digital repository (including A Liverpool Bestiary and El Taller de Gráfica Popular) further demonstrates the infrastructure's ability to blend cultural heritage with visual and graphic arts. The digital platform preserves and revitalises printmaking traditions, from local English folklore to Mexican political art, providing a valuable resource for both scholars and the public. We have been involved in the digitisation, capture and annotation of the collection using Linked Data and the Europeana Data Model and Wikidata to describe its collections. Furthermore, we make the collections available fully as Open Access through platforms such as IIRIF. We have also trained students into digitisation and preservation practices, and are currently focusing on the development of a crowdsourcing platform to annotate its contents. By engaging with graphic arts as a medium for historical storytelling, the platform challenges traditional modes of cultural heritage preservation and contributes to global conversations around decolonisation and social justice.

Collectively, this infrastructure enables a more inclusive research environment that supports the creation of new knowledge while promoting public engagement with hidden and marginalised histories.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The contributions of this research infrastructure are often overlooked because they operate outside the conventional boundaries of academic research outputs. While traditional research outputs such as monographs, journal articles, or formal exhibitions are easily recognised, the development of interactive installations, AI-driven datasets, and digital platforms is often invisible within standard research evaluation frameworks.

Afrobites, for example, plays a crucial role in public history and cultural education, yet its impact is primarily experiential, making it less visible in formal academic recognition systems. Similarly, Popular Graphic Arts provides a vital infrastructure for studying and preserving graphic arts, but as an interactive digital platform, it may not fit the traditional models of research evaluation. Furthermore, the Digital Humanities work done through Unlocking the Colonial Archive produces datasets and tools that are indispensable for researchers, but these tools themselves often remain hidden behind the success of the larger research they enable.

Additionally, the focus on decolonial approaches means that the very nature of these projects challenges the established, often Eurocentric research norms, making them even less visible in mainstream academic assessment. Despite the significant contributions these infrastructures make to advancing knowledge, preserving cultural heritage, and enabling new forms of public engagement, they remain overlooked in current research culture and evaluation systems.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8211-4914>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Hannah Fray
Neil Morris

Funding acknowledgements: Institute of Art and Technology QR, Facilitating Citizen Science on Museum Collections. An Analysis of Decolonial Narratives Through El Taller de Gráfica Popular, Grant value (→£): 2,300. 2021

Entry: 490

Applicant details

Submission category: 4 - Research Infrastructure

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Pereda, Javier

Organisation/University: Liverpool John Moores University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission highlights the development and use of an innovative research infrastructure that merges Digital Humanities, Critical Design and Cultural Heritage alongside decolonial practices. This focuses primarily on projects under the Printinteractive Research group and the Unlocking the Colonial Archive research projects. These interdisciplinary projects use cutting-edge digital tools to engage with hidden histories, cultural heritage, and the decolonial narrative. Through AI-driven data models, interactive installations, and digital platforms, the research infrastructure created fosters collaboration between academic researchers, cultural institutions, and community groups. These projects enable public engagement with complex historical and cultural narratives, such as the Trans-Atlantic slave trade, Latin American printmaking, and local folklore, in new, accessible, and creative ways. By combining AI, interactive technologies, and tangible interfaces, the infrastructure not only contributes to academic research but also ensures that marginalised voices and stories are brought to light in impactful ways.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

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Collectively, this infrastructure enables a more inclusive research environment that supports the creation of new knowledge while promoting public engagement with hidden and marginalised histories.

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Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-8211-4914>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Hannah Fray
Neil Morris

Funding acknowledgements: Institute of Art and Technology QR, Facilitating Citizen Science on Museum Collections. An Analysis of Decolonial Narratives Through El Taller de Gráfica Popular, Grant value (→£): 2,300. 2021; Arts and Humanities Research Council (AHRC-UKRI) and National Endowment for the Humanities (US), Unlocking the Colonial Archive: Harnessing Artificial Intelligence for Indigenous and Spanish American Historical Collections, Grant value (→£): 361,236.00; Liverpool John Moores University, Printinteractive. Developing a practice towards the integration of interaction design and printmaking., Hannah Fray, Grant value (→£): 2,000; Liverpool John Moores University, Towards an LJMU Linked Data Repository, Hannah Fray, Grant value (→£): 2,000

Entry: 505

Applicant details

Submission category: 7 - Standards

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Forshaw, Matthew

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

To address the skills barriers limiting AI adoption in businesses, the Alan Turing Institute, with Innovate UK BridgeAI [1] and the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology (DSIT) - has led the development of the AI Skills for Business Competency Framework to define the competencies required to enable responsible and safe AI. The project empowers businesses to understand the competencies needed to deliver value from AI, and support them in identifying upskilling routes for their existing workforce.

We believe a competency-based approach is essential to underpin more equitable recruitment practices, and facilitate the increased number and diversity of employees across the UK workforce with access to relevant, high-quality AI training, ultimately addressing the skills barriers limiting AI adoption.

Following extensive public consultation, the Framework was released in May 2024. We have since supported the uptake of the framework through 26 online webinars, seven regional events targeting difficult-to-reach SMEs and targeted interventions towards high-priority sectors experiencing the greatest risks and opportunities of AI, namely Agriculture and Food Processing, Construction, Creative Industries, and Transport, Logistics and Warehousing.

The Framework has achieved several major impacts since its launch in May 2024.

- The Framework has been adopted to underpin the Department for Science, Innovation and Technology's (DSIT) AI Upskilling Fund pilot [2] scheme will support small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) by match-funding AI skills training for their employees.

- The Framework underpins UKRI's AI Skills Hub [3], a major –£5m investment to stimulate adoption by addressing one of the major barriers in AI adoption, identified by both government and industry surveys, as the gap in data and AI skills in the industry.

- The Framework has been adopted by the Institute for Apprenticeships and Technical Education (IfATE) as the guidance underpinning the approval of new and revised occupational standards, apprenticeships and T-Levels.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The National AI Strategy highlighted skills and training as a core enabler to the effective uptake of artificial intelligence, and to strengthen the UK's position as an AI and science superpower over the coming decade [4]. However, there are ongoing issues across the UK's AI workforce including lack of skills [5], lack of training [6], and issues of equality, diversity and inclusion (EDI). The key to the adoption of AI is ensuring that students, employees, decision-makers, and data/AI professionals understand the opportunities, limitations, and ethics of using AI. Consistent and interoperable national-scale competency frameworks which embody equity at their heart, are critical in ensuring safe and responsible adoption of AI, and mitigating its potential harms.

The AI Skills for Business Competency Framework has not only already gained significant early impacts (c.f. Summary) but also exemplifies the Turing's ethos on equitable co-development.

1. Interdisciplinary input: The framework draws on interdisciplinary expertise and inputs across the UK's national skills landscape. These include BridgeAI partners (Digital Catapult, STFC Hartree Centre, BSI) and Professional Statutory Regulatory Bodies including members of the Alliance for Data Science Professionals.

2. Public engagement: Extensive public consultation was conducted between November 2023 and January 2024, spanning industry, academic, and public sector organisations. The consultation specifically sought diverse perspectives, and extensive follow-up engagement to ensure diverse inputs were actioned. Over 130 responses were received spanning nine industry sectors and all regions of the UK.

3. Supporting the breath of the UK's workforce: With 80% of 2030's predicted workforce already in employment [7], and an estimated 70% of roles at risk of disruption due to automation and AI held by women (ONS), the AI Skills for Business Competency Framework plays a crucial role in ensuring training, reskilling, and upskilling opportunities are required for individuals across all levels of the workforce. We were mindful to ensure that our efforts to enhance AI skills and literacy are inclusive and address any disparities or barriers to access across different demographic groups and regions.

4. Promoting open research practices within government contexts: The Framework is maintained through permissively licensed (CC-BY 4.0) outputs on Zenodo. The project team advocated for the importance of open licensing and leveraging best practice infrastructures.

5. Promoting FAIR training and interoperability: The framework promotes FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) training principles by supporting the discoverability of training through training landscape and resource mapping. The framework increases usability for trainees through greater clarity of training audiences and pre-requisite competencies.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Much of the attention in AI development and innovation focuses on technical breakthroughs and high-profile research outputs. Meanwhile, the creation of competency frameworks like the AI Skills for Business Competency Framework are essential to making AI accessible to a broader audience, and cultivate the skills required to maintain the UK's strength in research and innovation. However, these initiatives are rarely recognised in traditional academic award structures.

The ethos and values (Question 2) which underpinned the Framework's development were instrumental in ensuring the Framework achieves maximal benefit for the breadth of industry and the population, but are not recognised through existing measures. The Framework serves as an example of best practice in community engagement, interdisciplinary collaboration and advocacy for open practices in Government policy making.

Hidden REF nomination would not only raises awareness of this best practice exemplar in collaborative co-design of national competency frameworks, but provides valuable recognition of the wide range of contributors to the Framework project, whose contributions would otherwise go unrecognised.

[1] <https://iuk.ktn-uk.org/programme/bridgeai/>

[2] <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/flexible-ai-upskilling-fund>

[3] <https://www.delta-esourcing.com/delta/respondToList.html?accessCode=92BQ84YEP3>

[4] <https://www.gov.uk/government/publications/national-ai-strategy/national-ai-strategy-html-version>

[5] <https://www.ibm.com/downloads/cas/GVAGA3JP>

[6] https://www.turing.ac.uk/sites/default/files/2021-09/ai-strategy-survey_results_020921.pdf

[7] Industrial Strategy Council (2019) UK Skills Mismatch in 2030; Labour force survey, ONS, 2019.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-7014-9837

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: I would like to provide the full list of contributors at a point beyond submission before the Zenodo deposit. I am contactable at mforshaw@turing.ac.uk.

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Contexts panel

Entry: 360

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Clark, Timothy

Organisation/University: University of the West of England, Bristol

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The recent publication of *Critical Perspectives on Educational Policies and Professional Identities: Lessons from doctoral studies* (Waller, Andrews and Clark, 2024) marks the culmination of an 18-month long project focused on supporting 14 graduates of the Professional Doctorate in Education (EdD) at the University of the West of England (UWE) to develop positive experience of writing for publication. Arising from a concern that the academic activity of recent graduates from practice-based doctorates such as the EdD often stalls as the demands of their personal lives and professional roles returns to the fore after completing their studies, the project aimed to support and scaffold graduates' academic writing to allow them to share learning from their doctoral studies. Curating and developing the collection was also aimed at helping to strengthen the education research community within UWE and between the university and its partner organisations, offering clear routes into publication.

To support the process, expressions of interest were invited for an early career researcher (Clark) to join the experienced editorial team (Waller and Andrews), to gain experience as a co-editor and further enhance the research development value. Then, following an initial opportunity to submit abstracts for consideration, 21 submissions were received, of which 14 were chosen for inclusion in the edited collection. Each graduate was paired with a member of their supervision team and/or another experienced colleague and the project supported development of a research community through briefing sessions, writing retreats, and a structured timeline. Each chapter had a lead editor from the editorial team, and authors were paired as 'critical friends' to exchange feedback. The review process included three cycles of feedback, which took a supportive approach and applied a standardised template for consistency. Following the success of the project, this model is now being replicated for a follow up edition, focussing on doctoral research into learning and teaching

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This project is significant in its focus on developing a model which reflects the hidden-REF criteria relating to research leadership, responsibility, originality and local importance.

Research Leadership/Responsibility - this project aimed to share learning, build a research community and engage professional doctoral graduates who may have previously found it challenging to continue their academic journey outside of the university. Taking a positive and supportive approach, the publication was driven by an aim to enable others by scaffolding writing skills, building a writing community and showcasing graduates work, supporting their next steps upon completion of their doctorate.

Originality/creativity - this book project is the first within the discipline to seek to create an aspirational model for supporting professional doctoral graduates to write for publication. Starting with a focus on research development, rather than on the output itself, multiple activities were firmly embedded in the project to maximise its value to participants (including an Early Career Researcher as co-editor, framework for peer support, and collaborative presentations at conferences including BERA and SRHE), whilst also creating a valuable and high quality collection which will have utility for future EdD students and graduates.

Local importance - this project placed a significant focus on local importance, in the sense of the individual students, the immediate research community and also the partnerships with the organisations (schools, colleges, etc.) within which the research and the graduate were based. The project focused on enabling and supporting research development and on building connections and partnerships. This was reflected in a successful book launch event, which was attended by authors, partners, colleagues and current doctoral students.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Whilst this work offers significant potential to inform a positive research culture and environment, due to its primary focus on doctoral research and researcher development, it is likely that the intangible nature of aspects of this may also contribute to the likelihood of it being 'hidden' in terms of its value as an 'output'. Whilst it is a highly significant piece of work in developing future researchers and in taking responsibility for supporting researcher development beyond the completion of the doctorate (including in considering some key factors which may have relevance to REF) given its focus on showcasing doctoral work and on supporting those outside of the university to lead on publications, these may be less likely to be seen as REF outputs in their own right.

Beyond the collection as a 'product' (which in itself offers potential to support other doctoral researchers to reflect) the process of developing and curating it facilitated an important process of reflections for graduates and for the editing team/school. This represents a potentially powerful, but 'hidden' contribution to aspirations, accessibility and morale within, and beyond this community, which have the potential to inform future REF-able activity, but are difficult to capture in measures of current research excellence.

Reviewer Comment (Carol Azumah Dennis): "This is more than a departure; it is a welcome revelation. It serves as a powerful reminder that doctoral training goes beyond providing the technical skills required to manage small scale research project, urging us to embrace knowledge generation that is applied, transdisciplinary, and deeply contextualized."

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 400

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Walls, Natalie

Organisation/University: The Gurdon Institute (University of Cambridge)

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Aspiring Scientists Training Programme (ASTP) offers an immersive research experience at a leading university for high-achieving A-level students across the UK from under-served backgrounds and without network in the academic world. Since its inception in 2018, ASTP has grown significantly, from 10 students hosted in one department to 38 students across eight departments and two university colleges in 2024. The programme offers participants exposure to cutting-edge research environments, mentorship from leading scientists, and insight into university life and scientific careers.

ASTP addresses barriers to higher education for students in underrepresented groups, including those from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, care leavers, young carers, first-generation students, and students from underrepresented ethnic groups. By fostering diversity, the programme contributes to scientific innovation, as varied perspectives lead to more creative solutions to complex challenges. Promoting diversity ensures research benefits are shared equitably, making the scientific community more reflective of society.

Participants gain crucial skills for university applications and career development. Over 91% of students report that ASTP helped them build scientific networks, gain relevant experience, and better understand research careers, boosting their chances of entering scientific fields.

The programme also benefits the researchers, enhancing their leadership, communication, and teaching skills. Mentoring students from diverse backgrounds provide researchers with fresh perspectives, improving their approach to teaching and research.

In addition, ASTP strengthens institutions' commitment to diversity, elevates their role in promoting educational access, and cultivates a more diverse talent pool, which is essential for innovation. By contributing to an inclusive academic environment, ASTP helps research institutions excel not only in discovery but also in fostering a culture of collaboration and inclusivity for future success. Despite its crucial role in shaping the future of science, conventional evaluation frameworks do not recognise ASTP's impact on inclusivity and research culture, aligning with the Hidden REF's call to value contributions beyond typical outputs.

<https://www.gurdon.cam.ac.uk/programmes/astp/>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

ASTP plays a critical role in shaping the future of scientific research by diversifying its pipeline. The program provides underserved students with the opportunity to enter a leading university, helping them make informed decisions about which university and course to apply for. Traditional research culture often ignores such outreach initiatives in favour of more conventional research outputs, like university ranking criteria.

The significance of ASTP lies in its commitment to removing barriers to scientific careers for students who face systemic disadvantages in accessing higher education and research opportunities. Participants

get practical experience in research labs, learn about the scientific research process, and build valuable connections with established researchers, significantly enhancing their educational and career aspirations and trajectories.

Moreover, ASTP contributes to the larger goal of enhancing diversity in academia, which is vital for innovation and inclusive excellence in research. By nurturing a new generation of scientists from varied backgrounds, ASTP indirectly strengthens the overall research community. The program's impact is clear: participating students are more likely to apply to university science programmes and pursue scientific careers.

ASTP is crucial in addressing the significant underrepresentation of marginalised groups in scientific research. The programme data show that 73 out of 79 participants came from disadvantaged socio-economic backgrounds, as indicated by their eligibility for free school meals. Additionally, 55 participants belonged to underrepresented ethnic groups, 46 were first-generation students, 46 reported disrupted education, and 6 had care-leaving status. It has shown that with the right support, students from these backgrounds can thrive and make significant contributions to science. 98% of the participants reported gaining relevant research experience.

ASTP provides participating labs with a robust, tested framework, alleviating common concerns such as safeguarding and a lack of knowledge of best practices. By offering clear guidelines and support, ASTP reduces the administrative and logistical burden on researchers, making it easier for them to participate. This encourages broader involvement in the programme and amplifies its impact on the university's equality, diversity, and inclusion (EDI).

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

ASTP's primary goals, 'broadening access to research and fostering diversity,' do not result in immediate, quantifiable research outputs. Instead, the program contributes to the creation of future researchers from underrepresented backgrounds, which is a long-term investment in the scientific community. Traditional evaluation frameworks fail to account for this impact, as they do not recognise the importance of building the next generation of researchers or fostering a more inclusive academic environment.

The current evaluation culture also overlooks the labour in running programmes like ASTP. Significant effort and expertise are required in coordination, mentorship, securing funding, and managing safeguarding and logistics. Faculty and staff dedicate time to building a more inclusive research environment, yet their work is undervalued compared to conventional academic outputs.

Moreover, the programme's focus on working with underrepresented groups means it operates in a space often seen as ancillary to the core mission of research institutions. Although universities publicly champion diversity and inclusion, the work required to make these goals a reality is seldom factored into measuring academic success. ASTP demonstrates that such initiatives are essential for research's broader success and sustainability.

Unlike traditional programs tied to specific research or labs, ASTP enhances the broader research culture by promoting the importance of diversity and inclusion across the institution. Despite universities publicly supporting these values, the effort required to implement them is often not reflected in how success is measured. ASTP's impact, though crucial, remains hidden under current evaluation systems, making it an ideal candidate for the Hidden REF. Its focus on inclusivity is integral to the sustainability and innovation of the scientific community.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

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Funding acknowledgements: Funded by the Issac Newton Trust (2023-2025), Cambridge University Widening Participation Fund (2018-2022)

Entry: 410

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Doran, Heather

Organisation/University: Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science, University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This application is to recognise a deliberate engagement process that was implemented to improve research outputs for the forensic science justice system in the UK by the Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science. Forensic Science is in crisis, and this has been recognised by the UK Parliament, House of Lords and US government. The scale of the challenge is unprecedented, and the Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science was established in 2016 to address it. Previously, forensic science has existed in silos and in isolation but the establishment of LRCFS was an opportunity to adopt a different approach, one that was essential to change the status quo. This approach involves rigorous research to improve the robustness of forensic science but importantly this research isn't in isolation but is conducted in an interdisciplinary way involving expertise from within the justice system and outside of this system, including direct input from members of the public.

In order to achieve this, LRCFS set up a process where 'Strategic Conversations' bring together individuals to address a single issue within forensic science. It is a cross-disciplinary exercise that breaks down barriers and produces results. They are not seminars or workshops but rather concentrated fast-paced discussions facilitated by a design thinking approach. Strategic conversations bring together not only the relevant parties from across law enforcement, crime scene investigation, judicial, legal and forensic specialisms, but also include colleagues not directly involved within the justice space. The intention for such a wide participation is to encourage the sharing of different perspectives and experiences and to bring a richness to our discussions, enhancing our understanding of the 'art of the possible' which we sometimes lose sight of. The strategic conversations could not be undertaken without the support of the research centre manager, administrative team and professional service personnel.

LRCFS has hosted 7 of these strategic conversations.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Strategic Conversations have involved 210 participants from across the globe over two days each time. Each conversation has around 30 people. The planning, facilitation and evaluation required for each strategic conversation takes months and is supported by a wide team of individuals at LRCFS including administration staff, the Centre Manager, research staff, public engagement staff and catering staff.

This original approach to the establishment of research projects goes beyond the expected. We know the value of these conversations lie not only in improving the research outputs from the Centre but also the impact on the participants and how they continue conversations in their own workplace. Some of the feedback has included "very good combination of people, known and previously unknown, and made us focus on things we probably had thought of only inarticulately," UK Supreme Court Judge "The opportunity to work with highly skilled and accomplished educators, scientists, and practitioners in forensic science and the agitators in related fields was nothing short of spectacular" Canadian Supreme Court Judge

The Strategic Conversations focused on improving forensic science and could not be hosted successfully by any other organisation involved in this ecosystem. Power, hierarchy and tradition are all large barriers to change and there is little opportunity for the players in the Justice System to pause, reflect and informally engage with each other (and with those external to the system) in order to shift the dial. A university is well placed as a broker of knowledge to host and implement these discussions and an important part of the process is removing the power in the room, including for example removing ties and other indicators of status. Sitting judges next to school children and involving non-experts in the conversation ensures that the deliberations do not veer into acronyms and usual complaints but are focused on potential solutions and outcomes. All participants are given a 'blah blah blah' card which they can use to challenge the use of specialist terminology or explanations which are not understandable. These are very powerful tools that enable the participants to ensure knowledge is shared in a clear and understandable way.

At the conclusion of the conversation the participants are invited to vote on which of the projects discussed are most valuable and achievable. They are also invited to participate in these projects going forward. From here LRCFS implements the planning to achieve this and so far has produced a vast range of traditional and non-traditional outputs which are creating change in the justice system.

The Strategic Conversation approach has been so successful that LRCFS has delivered sessions in Australia and on behalf of new EU projects that are looking to establish collaborative projects.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Although the robust research outputs from these conversations are of value to the traditional metrics of how a university values research the 'hidden' work of the support for these Strategic Conversations isn't recognised in this process.

The conversations are captured by a live illustrator which is a more engaging way of summarising the journey and outputs than a written report.

The value of this approach to the establishment of long-lasting and valuable relationships between the research centre and external partners which include judges, law enforcement, The Crown Office and Procurator Fiscal Service and the Scottish and UK Governments is not overtly recognised. This work has established and solidified these relationships which has enabled LRCFS to be an anchor in brokering conversations to slowly but steadily begin to establish the change that is necessary in the justice system.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

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Marj Davis, Centre Manager, Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Anna Beattie, Research Centre Administrator, Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Heather Doran, Public Engagement Manager, Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Visual Illustrators at Live Illustration

The University of Dundee Catering team

Funding acknowledgements: The Leverhulme Trust

Entry: 423

Applicant details

Submission category: 3 - Citizen Science

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Macpherson, Fiona

Organisation/University: University of Glasgow

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): The Universities of Glasgow and Sussex

Description of submission

Summary

The Perception Census (<https://perceptioncensus.dreamachine.world/>) is one of the largest ever scientific studies on perception. Led by philosopher Professor Fiona Macpherson and neuroscientist Professor Anil Seth, The Perception Census investigates the unique ways we each experience the world around us. In so doing, it demonstrates to the participants that in everyday life we each experience the world differently. There is an internal 'perceptual diversity' to mirror our externally visible individual differences. Running from June 2022 to November 2023, 34,963 people took part, contributing around 68,000 hours of research. Participants ranged in age from 18 to 80s and hailed from 133 countries, including the USA, Australia, India, Japan, and Brazil, indeed, including every continent except Antarctica. The results are currently under analysis.

The Perception Census is one of three elements of the Dreamachine Programme, a unique collaboration blending leading academic researchers with world-class artists. Created and produced by Collective Act, Dreamachine received £100k from the UK Government for initial development and £9 million as part of the 2022 Unboxed festival.

The Perception Census is a suite of online questionnaires, interactive tasks and illusions, brief experiments, and educational resources developed to examine individual differences in perception. There are ten sections, each taking about 30-40 mins to complete, representing a substantial time commitment for those who completed all sections. (Almost 110,000 sections were completed.) All participants completed the 'Fundamentals of Perception' section first, which covers a range of different aspects of perception. Then they could choose from the further nine sections such as: sound and music; time; great expectations; the power of imagination; and our colourful world. Where possible information about how the participant performed was provided, and there was an 'Ask the Experts' page where visitors posed questions which were then answered by the researchers.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

When it comes to online scientific studies of perception involving the general public, the Perception Census (PC) is an unprecedentedly ambitious attempt to map out this inner diversity. Previous studies have looked at one or a few aspects of perception, but PC is the first to examine many different forms of perception together, painting a detailed and multi-dimensional picture of how we each encounter the world in a unique way.

Creating the PC was a large undertaking that involved developing over 60 individual tasks and experiments examining different aspects of how we experience the world, making them accessible and easy for users to complete by themselves on their own computers, and ensuring that the users had (as much as possible) a fun and engaging experience. From the start we wanted to make the PC a truly citizen science project. By taking part in PC users make a real contribution to the science and philosophy of perception, generating knowledge of significant value. And this value flows back to the users taking part too, as they have the chance to learn more about how their minds and brains actively create their experiences. These tasks were developed primarily by the core team led by Macpherson and Seth, who are Dr Reny Baykova and Dr David Schwartzman (postdocs, Sussex), Trevor Hewitt (PhD student,

Sussex) and Dr James Alvarez (senior web developer, Sussex), but also drew in dozens of national and international collaborators.

The scientific impact of the PC will be substantial. As well as a primary paper describing the main findings, 12 additional papers are in progress, with pre-registrations submitted. The PC will represent a landmark not only in perception science, but in open science more generally. Following our initial analysis, the entire database will open-access to the scientific community for further discovery.

The PC posed significant data management challenges. Data provided by participants is stored pseudo-anonymously on servers at the Joint Information Systems Committee (JISC) (from where the PC is delivered). We undertook extensive work to ensure that the PC ran smoothly from remote servers, and that participant pseudo-anonymity was rigorously maintained according to stringent ethical application and approval. We believe the PC represents a new standard in how to combine citizen science with data privacy.

Although the vast majority of data are still being analysed, early indications show that some participants in the Perception Census have gleaned previously undiscovered insights about their own powers of perception, discovering they have unique perceptual conditions, such as synaesthesia, aphantasia, or visual snow.

Answer continues in the box below...

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Continuing the answer to the previous question:

In addition, participants in the Census were shown to experience colour differently. 20% of people experienced one illusion very strongly, experiencing a very different shade of colour to the average participant. However another 20% of people barely experienced the illusion at all. This result provides fascinating new clues into how the human brain takes light and shade into account when perceiving colour.

Further, 31% of people who participated in the Body and Belief section of the Census reported having an 'out-of-body' experience, and 66% of those people said they had such experiences many times. Reports of these experiences have circulated for centuries, but they are usually thought confined to rare events such as moments of spiritual ecstasy. The number of people reporting this experience in the Census are surprisingly high and provokes to understand these experiences further.

Altogether, the findings of the PC have the potential to rewrite our understanding of how we perceive the world, forming a unique body of scientific and philosophical research that will be valuable for years to come.

And to answer the question in this box:

The Perception Census will yield a large dataset, which would not normally be considered as an output for the REF in Philosophy or Neuroscience. The project contains many elements from public engagement to impact, to science methodology and scientific results that do not neatly fit into one category for REF submission.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Professor Anil Seth (Professor of Cognitive and Computational Neuroscience, Sussex)

Dr Reny Baykova (former postdoc, now lecturer, Psychology, Sussex)

Dr David Schwartzman (postdoc, Neuroscience, Sussex)

Mr Trevor Hewitt (PhD student, Psychology, Sussex)

Dr James Alvarex (Psychology Software Team Leader, Sussex)

Funding acknowledgements: The UK Government and the 2022 Unboxed Festival

Entry: 425

Applicant details

Submission category: 6 - Grimpect

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Di Cara, Nina

Organisation/University: University of Bristol, School of Psychological Science

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): University of Bristol

Description of submission

Summary

Data Hazards is community project to help people identify the hazards of doing data-intensive work, and has been in development since 2021. The project provides opportunities for researchers reflect on ethical issues that go beyond traditional research ethics such as environmental impact and potential for misuse, and emphasises making accessible resources that support interdisciplinary communication.

The Data Hazards project currently consists of eleven Hazard labels (similar to COSHH hazards), which have descriptive icons, descriptions, examples and safety precautions analogous suggestions of safety precautions that could be taken to mitigate any risks. We have also developed a reflective workshop format where those running data science projects can present their work to a group of 'outsiders' and listen to objective feedback about how the worst-case scenarios of their work could play out. We share resources to organise workshops, as well as running train-the-trainer resources for those wanting to teach others, and support those teaching data ethics to students.

So far, the project has been used to prompt ethical reflection for newly funded data science pilot projects, by NHS and local government teams who wish to consider ethical risks and mitigations before starting new data science projects, and used to teach data ethics to students across multiple courses and universities over the past 3 years. Additionally, the project is being extended by contributors into other data-intensive fields of Synthetic Biology and Neuroscience to increase ethical awareness of others in their areas. Ultimately the success of Data Hazards is difficult to measure, given that it allows researchers to identify precautions that can be taken to slow 'Grimpect'.

The Data Hazards project fills an extremely important gap in making ethics accessible for those developing data science research, which can go on to have huge impacts for all of us in our everyday lives.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

In an era when artificial intelligence and data science is moving at speed it is extremely important that ethics is considered from the earliest possible stages. However, researchers usually lack the incentives, training, confidence, support, and (sometimes) willingness to truly consider the broader impact of their data-intensive work. This scrutiny is also not often provided by Ethics Committees, whose expertise lies in upholding the privacy and informed consent of human participants. The risks associated with data science and AI can be much wider, such as exploitation of data-labellers, or machine learning models predicting incorrectly for minority groups. Work that does discuss these wider concerns is often not accessible to data science researchers, as it is written for a philosophy audience.

Ultimately, the researchers are those who have most control of the process of the design and specification of data-based tools. Therefore, the Data Hazards project focusses on creating practical materials, and finding opportunities to meet, talk to and engage with researchers about ethics. By making resources that are highly accessible, including creating animations to describe Data Hazards, and focussing on the visual communication format of labels, we have also started to open more detailed conversations about AI ethics to the public and collect their views too.

The flexibility, accessibility and utility of the project is recognised in the variety of use cases we have seen. Data Hazards encourages genuine reflection, rather than simply being a tick-box exercise, and recognises both the skill of data scientists in addressing hazards, and the vital contribution gained from having multiplicity of perspectives and lived experiences to identify possible Data Hazards in our work.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Data Hazards project started in 2021 and is led by Early Career Researchers (ECRs) who have been motivated to prevent the ‚ÄúGrim pact,Äù caused by artificial intelligence and data science, seen in their own fields. It has grown slowly but steadily over several years of continued effort, outreach and collaboration by the project team, who do this work outside of their usual research roles, largely unfunded.

The core ethos of the Data Hazards project and its success relies on time-consuming practices which run counter to the incentives of traditional research culture. These are: trust-building, interdisciplinarity, collaboration, and accessibility.

Many researchers approach ethics with suspicion or concern about being restricted, and so reassurance that responsible research practices can improve our work is an essential part of our outreach to new communities.

Trust is also required for effective interdisciplinarity, which can include convincing computational scientists that social science approaches add value to their work, and vice versa. Ironically, as an interdisciplinary project, Data Hazards is often seen as not technical enough to be recognised as a data science output, but too simplistic to be recognised as a contribution to the social sciences.

The project is run with a strong open science ethos and prioritises collaboration and crediting all contributors for their time and effort, as opposed to focussing on individual excellence. The project team also encourage ECRs to take on positions of leadership and develop their skills. This has included mentoring several PhD students who volunteer their time. This method of organising, collaborating and encouraging contributions is time-consuming but extremely valuable.

Last, considering how to make a project accessible, from the tools we made to build the website, to the ongoing effort made to reach new audiences, is what allows us to reach people with multiple perspectives and insights. In doing so we build a richer and more valuable output, even though this is not an output that we can measure.

Further details

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Patricia Holley, Jean Golding Institute, University of Bristol, Institute Manager

Funding acknowledgements: Jean Golding Institute, University of Bristol and Research England Research Culture Initiative

Entry: 428

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Cann, Alice

Organisation/University: Brunel University London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The webpage <https://researcherlibrarian.wordpress.com/library-conferences-on-bluesky/>, lists upcoming and previous conferences within librarianship and other information professions. It focuses on events which have content on the relatively new, and expanding, social media site BlueSky. A key aspect is the inclusion of links to this content, via conference hashtags.

In my role as an Academic Liaison Librarian I have, for many years, recorded and shared conference notes on social media, predominantly Twitter, gaining from backchannel communication and networking. I've also gained from others' posts at events I didn't attend, and know this experience is common among many library professionals and beyond.

Librarians' experiences at conferences influence their work with students and researchers, such as advising on and teaching information literacy and data collection. Hearing about the experiences of other researchers, including librarian researchers, inspires professionals to develop their research skills and confidence, and fosters progress on new and ongoing research projects.

Since Twitter (now X) was bought by Elon Musk in 2022 tweeting at conferences (and otherwise) has reduced, including among the librarianship community, likely due to changes in functionality and concerns about the ethos and activities of the owner.

I created the webpage in Spring 2024, when hashtags became fully useable on BlueSky, meaning that posts containing common hashtags, such as #RLUK24 (the Research Libraries UK 2024 conference) were findable before, during and after the event.

The page is organised by year, and into past/current and upcoming conferences. I update it with conferences and hashtags as I learn about them, through searching and through asking others on BlueSky to share details of events they are attending or have attended. The remit is wide, including any conference or event which is relevant to people in library and information roles, in any sector and any country.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The webpage supports ongoing online content and communication from conferences within librarianship and related fields. It is particularly important now with changes in Twitter/X, the previous predominant location for this activity, increasing the need for promoting and keeping a record of the use of hashtags at conferences.

Conferences are an opportunity for presenters to share activities, research and expertise; attendees learn about new and changing ideas, impacting their own professional practice and research.

Conference presentations are not always developed into publications, and slides/recordings are not consistently available open access or in perpetuity, so social media posts are a useful and accessible record and reference tool. This is particularly within librarianship, since librarians are more likely to

present than to publish journal articles and books (CILIP LIRG, 2024).

Networking, connecting through conference discussions and informal chats, is a key benefit. For attendees, this can happen in person, but social media provides for further connection between people who don't already know each other, and for longer-term discussion.

Online notes allow those who can't attend an event to get some of the experience and knowledge, and to contribute to discussions. (One example is a discussion during the #LILAC24 conference about the use of cake as an analogy when teaching about Generative AI). This activity is particularly valuable for people who can't attend in person due to finances, health or caring responsibilities, especially as many organisations have returned to in-person events, in place of online/hybrid events during and following Covid-19 lockdowns. People are able to follow conferences beyond their primary profession, benefiting interdisciplinarity and international collaboration.

Online activity during conferences and events has previously been standard, with conference organisers promoting hashtags and posting on Twitter from organisation accounts. The reduction of the use and confidence in Twitter has led to uncertainty about ongoing 'conference tweeting'. The BlueSky webpage is a part of ensuring the benefits of online activity at conferences continue, encouraging interested attendees to look for and share hashtags in advance, and post about their experiences. It is a step in encouraging organisers to facilitate this by creating and promoting hashtags.

The webpage, and regular promotion and requests for information about conferences, is a resource for people interested in learning about the many library and information related conferences. A record of previous and upcoming conference hashtags resolves the difficulty in identifying hashtags for upcoming or past events, something that has been especially challenging with the reduction in the use of Twitter resulting in some conferences being less likely to create and promote an event hashtag.

The page has been widely shared on BlueSky, increasingly as more people join the platform; one example in August 2024 had 28 reposts and 51 likes.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The webpage has been created and updated by one librarian. Reaction to it on BlueSky has been good, but there are many people for whom it could be relevant who are not using BlueSky, or who are not aware of it yet. As a resource to facilitate research communication, created by someone in a research adjacent role, it is less likely to be recognised in traditional research sources.

The skills that librarians have (in part developed by conferences and events) and the benefits of librarian participation in research projects, is appreciated by individuals, but often without time and structures set up to ensure that this value is fostered and developed.

Recognition would promote the webpage and its' benefits; it would be helpful in facilitating future research and creation of guidance for conference organisers, and a more robust system for recording and promoting conference hashtags, in librarianship and other sectors.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 446

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Priston, Sarah

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Studio was established in 2020 as a research and enterprise hub in the centre of Bath; it offers access to University resources and expertise, fostering collaborations between entrepreneurs, researchers and students. It sits within the strategic research centre, the Centre for Cultural and Creative Industries (CCCI). Launched in 2019, The Studio supports 100 Resident micro-businesses, offering development programmes, equipment, access to research, funding and co-working space. The Studio's leadership team has won local and regional acclaim, winning awards for its support of creative industries. Through CCCI The Studio has received in excess of ~£1m of research funding, most notably through Research England's Connecting Capabilities Fund, the AHRC's Creative Industries Clusters programme as well as UKRI's Strength in Places Fund.

The Studio has developed a unique offer, supporting locally based creatives to develop sustainable businesses by utilising immersive technology to prototype, test, and launch innovative projects. Capital investment from externally funded research projects has brought in a range of immersive media technology which is available for free hire to the Resident and local communities for training and development purposes.

An individual Residency is valued at ~£12K per year and the total value of services and support to the local economy is estimated at ~£1M per annum. This year's annual survey has recorded:

- 73% of respondents said their Residency at The Studio has played a role in their successes
- 87% of respondents have forged new collaborations
- 80% of the respondents are making income from their Studio-based practice.

Residents are supported to showcase their work locally and beyond; Studio projects have reached over one million people through initiatives like techSPARKS' Bath Digital Festival, as well as Glastonbury 2024. The Studio's methodologies support the impact and development of the creative industries at a local, national and international level within both academia and industry.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Staff at The Studio support a range of micro business and sole traders who find access to academic expertise and collaborative funding opportunities difficult. They often have innovative ideas and expertise, but need support to develop their businesses and to build an appropriate network to develop test and launch their products.

The focus is on supporting innovators who are working in the area of immersive media technology, and who are developing a range of creative media approaches to develop innovative ways to reach new audiences, working on ideas and projects that focus on creativity and technology. By developing a supportive network of innovators, thinkers and entrepreneurs, the Studio supports them to develop their practice and to use this knowledge to collectively provide a springboard for new technologies. There is an annual evaluation of the impact of this work, shared with the academic community for consideration and Knowledge Exchange.

Each year the University provides HEQR funding for the Studio's Innovation Fund, which supports three Studio Resident-centred collaborations to explore creative technology solutions addressing pressing social issues. This year the funding is being used to support projects which:

- empower people to access and create innovative, cutting-edge visual, musical, and digital performances that support alternative and unheard voices
- prototype a one-stop-shop web tool to revolutionize volunteering by building an interactive online map and using creative approaches to capture the stories and voices of grassroots groups, starting in the BANES area
- address the countless unused or underused buildings in communities by exploring a new creative use of increasingly common 3D space capture technology to unlock greater social, environmental, and economic value.

All of these outputs are examples of non-traditional outputs of significance and rigour which reach a range of audiences and significantly move forward knowledge and understanding of research in the creative industries.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Studio provides a space for local micro-businesses, Bath Spa University students, academics, and graduates to work on projects and ideas which focus on creativity and technology. It is also a space to collaborate, share ideas, host events, for Residents, and the wider community. It is unusual for a University to bring together this type of community to work and to support them in an inclusive, interdisciplinary and practice based environment.

By supporting research, innovation and enterprise across disciplines, staff at The explores how technology expands and augments creativity, and creates sustainable work that has a lasting impact on the world.

Access to creative technology applications and innovations is often not made available to the wider public, and one of the aims of The Studio is to explore how local communities can better engage with creative technology. This work takes many forms and represents an ongoing process of applied discovery. It spans the programming of fully subsidised public workshops, providing access to immersive technology equipment, and collaborating with BSU researchers to uncover how they are using creative technologies in their own research and projects.

As an example of this, in summer 2024, a team of academics and residents from the Studio attended Glastonbury festival and used a diverse range of technologies, including artificial intelligence, virtual reality, physical computing, and creative coding, to create playful encounters that encouraged critical reflections around technology and its impact on society by allowing audiences to experience the installations through interactive technologies, theatre and storytelling. This gave the team a greater understanding of how creative technology can engage diverse audiences, enhance artistic expressions, and support the growth of the creative economy.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 453

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rogowsky, Rayna

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The submission category proposed is Equality, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI).

'Diversity Points' is a monthly online seminar series that explores EDI topics relevant to health sciences and higher education within the School of Health Sciences at the University of Dundee. It involves participation from academic and professional services staff, students, practitioners, and people with lived experience.

The seminar series was conceived as an opportunity to engage with education, research, and practice stakeholders, as well as members of the public, around crucial EDI topics. It aims to facilitate opportunities for audiences to think differently and see a role for themselves in making things better. This knowledge exchange activity is online and open to all.

Diversity Points to date has covered a range of topics, including: racism and supporting nursing students (presented by a student and academic), supporting the health needs of refugee and asylum-seeking populations in Scotland (presented by senior nurses); embedding LGBTQ+ health in nursing and midwifery programmes (presented by an academic); decolonising nursing and midwifery curriculum (presented by an academic); models of disability and inclusive leadership (presented by an academic with lived experience).

The series has been developed collaboratively within the School of Health Sciences, local NHS practice partners, and the growing network of past attendees. Colleagues are increasingly providing ideas and directions for future seminars, which has demonstrated the shared value of the series. New approaches to co-develop seminars are also being used; for example, in the coming months an undergraduate student, PhD student, and several academic nurses are meeting with an international expert on the topic of men in nursing to co-develop a seminar. The series is chaired by an academic and the School President enabling a collaborative and inclusive approach to student involvement.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

'Diversity Points' is well-attended with the audience size typically reaching at least 50 attendees. Seminars are typically recorded and stored within the Teams meeting space, and requests for access are common. Written and verbal feedback is consistently positive (e.g. 'I always got a lot out of them,' 'Thought provoking,' and 'Impressive'). Presenters consistently report positive experiences contributing to the series (e.g. 'Inspirational,' 'I found the experience worthwhile'). It has created conditions for discussion and collaboration with the potential to enhance curiosity, understanding, positive culture, sense of belonging, and work and study experiences and outcomes, in particular for minoritised staff and students. It can inspire global citizenship and inform curricula and policy as well as ideas for future initiatives. Some examples of known outcomes of the series include: a sparked collaboration for a published editorial; invitation to join a UK-wide funding application; revision of a case study-based activity in the curriculum; and an agenda item added to a university strategic meeting. The impact of the series has also been measured by small survey data, which showed that seminars have helped to change views, opinions, and potential behaviour (e.g. 'I will be more conscious of how I ask

questions of others and be mindful of the potential for microaggressions. I will also ensure that I address others' behaviours,Äù). Therefore, 'Diversity Points' has contributed positively to the local research environment through engaging diverse audiences, facilitating a network for fostering collaboration, and exchanging knowledge of topics relevant to improving the practices within institutions that host research activity as well as the experiences and outcomes of researchers at any career stage.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Engagement with EDI topics relevant to research activity is a means for enhancing research culture. This is distinct from EDI as a consideration in the evaluation of research culture (e.g. EDI and career development, diversity of research teams). Therefore, an EDI initiative such as 'Diversity Points' may be overlooked given that it does not have specific outcome measures as in the examples of EDI and career development and diversity of research teams. Rather, the wide range of topics introduced, through a co-creative and collaborative approach, has the potential to catalyse positive change to a research environment that may not link to current metrics used to evaluate EDI in research culture.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 456

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Vazquez Arango, Pilar

Organisation/University: University College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Around 3% of babies are born with problems that often start early in pregnancy but we know very little about why and how they happen. The Wellcome-funded Human Developmental Biology Initiative (HDBI, hdbi.org) is the first consortium in the world bringing together researchers in the fields of reproduction, developmental and stem cell biology to unravel how human embryos develop and provide insights into how this process can go wrong. Building an open collaborative environment of 60 researchers in 25 groups, 12 institutions and 4 main work packages has been key to the success of our project.

Since starting in November 2019, we have built a research community through various activities, including: Two consortium meetings per year; meetings with each work package every 2-3 months; monthly meetings where only early career researchers (ECRs) present and attend; yearly laboratory site visits; bespoke training sessions (imaging, cell-lineage tracing, data management); an internal quarterly newsletter and two ethics seminars each year (tinyurl.com/3xkf8kxz). All these allow sharing of ideas, methods, results and data analysis so that everyone is aware of the overall progress, challenges and priorities of the consortium.

We believe we are an example of how multi-institution research initiatives can accelerate research; this undoubtedly requires joining efforts rather than working separately. HDBI has not only advanced the generation of data and development of techniques but provided a unique platform for ECRs as well as fostered collaborations across groups that, otherwise, would not have necessarily occurred or would have taken longer to form via individual efforts.

As we approach the end of our project, having built a strong community, our dissemination plans aim to ensure the wider research community also benefit. As part of this, we are establishing two research hubs to train researchers in the techniques developed and holding an international conference in 2025.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Research is collaborative by nature; over the past two decades there has been an increase in large research collaborations (tinyurl.com/5c9e83u3). Our field (human development biology) required an even larger collaboration as research has been held back by challenges such as limitations in the availability of research material (human embryonic and fetal tissue samples) and lack of techniques; the only way to tackle those and make progress was bringing the research community together.

In our experience, large-scale international multi-institution collaborations involve specific considerations:

- Substantial long-term investment (~£10 million over 5 years)

- Strong leadership from the Chief Investigator, Management Committee and Scientific Advisory Board

- A Project Manager to establish research collaboration agreements, monitor budget and progress of research activities, coordinate meetings, prepare reports to funder, organise training and seminars and run day-to-day operations.

- A Data Outputs Manager to develop and manage processes, tools and infrastructure for FAIR sharing of outputs as well as developing resources and training and consulting on data management challenges.

- Closely working with a research infrastructure providing material for research (Human Developmental

Biology Resource, hdbi.org)

-Embedding an integrated 'Public Engagement Programme' (funded separately and led by a Public Engagement Lead and Public Engagement Manager) covering: Institution-led sci-art collaborations, a podcast, a Public Dialogue to understand hopes and concerns around the regulation of research involving human embryos, regular meetings with a group of public stakeholders and training to develop the knowledge, skills and confidence of researchers to discuss our research with the public ('Plain English & FAQs', 'Difficult conversations', 'Media training').

-Connecting with external researchers and related consortia via our consortium meetings, training and ethics seminars.

We believe all these have contributed to establishing a cohesive group, helping advance research in the field of human developmental biology and setting the bases for other groups to adopt this type of research.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

To our knowledge, current research culture and evaluation approaches do not recognise 'Community Building' among higher education institutions, perhaps because researchers are inherently expected to establish collaborations (as part of their work, career and funding). The lack of bespoke metrics for the quality of scientific collaborations further aggravates this.

Assessment at the Institutional level also leaves cross-institution consortia out; these environments are necessary to connect large groups of specialists who can contribute to different aspects of complex research areas.

The organisational effort necessary for researchers from multiple institutions to meet regularly and exchange updates is considerable but allows members to establish familiarity with and understanding of the varied expertise within the consortium upon which they can call to leverage in their own work. This more frequent contact in a rather informal setting facilitates more dynamic collaborations but is difficult to capture in current evaluation approaches.

Through our consortium we have learnt that building a research community requires considerable efforts. The investment has been fruitful, not only evidenced by our outputs (hdbi.org/overview-of-outputs) but also by:

-Multiple new internal and external collaborations

-Active participation in meetings, training, ethics seminars and newsletters

-Early career researchers devising a proposal for a Royal Society Meeting, successfully held in May 2024 (tinyurl.com/yvz55djs)

-Three early career researchers becoming independent group leaders

-Taking part in 1) a 'Guidelines Working Group' to develop a code of practice for UK research involving embryo models (tinyurl.com/2hy8s5w3) and 2) a consultation by the 'Human Fertilisation and Embryology Authority' on modernising the regulation of fertility treatment and research involving human embryos

-Researchers leading/participating in multiple public engagement activities

It is encouraging to see how recent work by others provides 'further evidence that successful team science is not about picking the right people, but on how to build the right team for success' (tinyurl.com/mr26983d).

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: 215116/Z/18/Z

Entry: 457

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bayley, Amanda

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The project Exploring and Exchanging Communications about Trees (EECAT), funded by Bath Spa University (BSU), has brought together six researchers from six different disciplines across three universities (BSU, University of Zimbabwe (UZ), and Rhodes University (RU)), to work with community members, and school teachers in a rural village in Zimbabwe to answer the question: How can intercultural dialogue and cross-disciplinary educational activities contribute to a better understanding of the ecological value of trees in local food growing environments? Its purpose was to focus on a planting project, Trees of Hope (ToH), a community interest company begun in 2019 to return trees to rural Zimbabwe and in turn bring back their physical/medicinal attributes, birds, insects and other wildlife, and associated celebratory songs, dances and stories, about trees, nature, land and water. The development, documentation and local evaluation of the reforestation activities of ToH undertaken during the EECAT project in 2023 to 2024 have led to unexpected findings that directly benefit the local community and have resulted in a sustained collaborative partnership between the local community, Govera Primary School and the University of Zimbabwe.

The EECAT project aimed to:

- 1) engage school teachers and children as reforesters and agroforesters, alongside ToH workers and the local community;
- 2) generate data about community perspectives on the significance of trees in the local environment;
- 3) encourage children to express their feelings through words and music about trees they have planted.

Training the diverse stakeholders in small-scale permaculture was provided by the Schools and Colleges Permaculture Programme (SCOPE) at the Zimbabwe Institute of Permaculture, using the integrated land use design (ILUD) model which promotes participant agency in project design. SCOPE gave practical demonstrations outside the classroom, working with agroforestry techniques in ways that are sensitive to indigenous knowledge and skills held within the community.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Eighteen months into the project, UZ is now working with the community and ToH to mitigate against climate change, and to establish new food products from the seeds and fruits of specific trees. Bringing different members of the community together in dialogue gave them the space, the opportunity and the authority to question the reliability of some of the shared knowledges, e.g. the elders sharing how they value certain trees for their medicinal properties. They are now working with UZ scientists as marketing and industrialisation take centre stage. Teachers and children added their voices on how they benefitted from the project and from working with UZ. From a local, community perspective, the multivoicedness of intergenerational learning goes beyond verbal utterings to include other actions and products of human participation as a decolonial approach to curriculum innovation.

Outcomes and findings of this community-building project suggest a number of ways in which eco-community learning themes can be more directly reflected in areas such as curriculum reform and innovation, by supporting participatory action research in schools, and including indigenous knowledges and practices in learning activities. Recommendations resulting from the research provide a starting point

for discussions with policy makers, including the Zimbabwe Ministry of Primary and Secondary Education, regarding the implementation of eco-pedagogies to transform schools and community landscapes into functional landscaping, strengthening learner sustainability competences, and addressing food shortages. The findings should be of interest to education departments in universities and colleges across Zimbabwe and southern Africa.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The immediate beneficiaries of the research are in a poor, rural area, and are in Zimbabwe. The outcomes and outputs from the project are not measurable according to the criteria for conventional research outputs. So far, the impact has been significant but local. Many examples show how the thinking, the actions, and the training have transformed lives in the local community in Domboshava, both on an individual level and on a collective level: the children in the village have set up a Saturday ecology club:

<https://youtu.be/k4ZTOkqQv8I>; Govera Primary School is now growing its own crops; the Chair of the School Development Committee showed UZ researchers the trees he has now planted at his homestead; and the head of ToH now regularly shares with community members the benefits of composting, and why tree growing is important. Four other village heads, members of the Environment Management Agency, and the Ministry of Youth, all attended a celebratory event in February 2024 that showcased their indigenous tree seedling bank. So there is strong potential for expanding this work as a community-building project regionally, nationally and internationally.

Tangible outcomes of the community-school-university partnership include indigenous food products, 'Ài porridge, bread, jam and goat pellets, 'Ài that can improve local livelihoods. The new instant porridge, created from processed powder from indigenous fruits of the *Piliostigma thonningii* (Musekesa tree), and the goat pellets, are currently undergoing lab tests at UZ, the results of which will be fed back to the community. These products were exhibited at the annual summit in Harare of the 44th Southern African Development Committee with 14 Heads of State present, and at the Harare Agricultural Show (both in August 2024).

Intangible outcomes include reflexive products, in the form of descriptive, narrative and photographic accounts complemented by music and stories that trigger participants to rethink their practical situation for themselves. Multimedia outcomes demonstrate participants' exciting new experiences with trees and stimulate further reflections and actions. New songs, poems and storysharing emphasise how collective learning and active participation are important processes for community building while also contributing to problem-solving models in the practice of curriculum innovation, and in livelihood transformation.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: HEQR international funding, Research England

Entry: 463

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Biggs, Patti

Organisation/University: Francis Crick Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

A series of expert written search strategies were created for topics associated with the 3Rs project (Replacement, Reduction and Refinement) which aims to ensure that any animal research carried out is essential and is done so humanely. The search strategies were originally written at the request of the Biological Research Facility at the Francis Crick Institute who manage all in house animal research.

Previously, time consuming and non-comprehensive searches were being carried out by both those supporting animal license applications, and the researchers themselves, to ensure that new applications for projects involving animal research were using best practices and not replicating previous research. These searches were being carried out in a redundant way by many different individuals, with no standardisation, and it was not clear if these were always comprehensive and complete.

To address this issue, a comprehensive set of search strategies was created by an expert librarian and information specialist. These new search strategies allow for searches to be carried out in a comprehensive and systematic way. Rather than creating one single search strategy, a mix and match approach was used, creating a set of search strategies for animals and concepts relevant for a new research project. This allows those carrying out the searches to carry out tailored, expert led searches without having to approach the library staff each time.

To increase the impact of this output, the searches have been shared with all animal researchers and support staff at the Francis Crick Institute and shared openly at <https://doi.org/10.25418/crick.26948119.v1>.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The 3Rs is an important set of ethical principles promoting best practice around reducing the use of animal models in research. The 3Rs stand for Replacement, Reduction and Refinement. In-line with the 3Rs, preparation for a new research proposal involves ensuring that similar work has not already been carried out by others, and that best practice in reducing the use of animal models is adhered to. This involves detailed and thorough literature searching.

Ad hoc literature searching will often miss important outputs and multiple individuals redesigning search strategies can take up a lot of time. To reduce this issue, a set of comprehensive search strategies were developed. This set of pre-prepared search strategies can be carried out on a regular schedule or for specific projects and is rigorously designed by an expert librarian. Use of the search strategies allow for researchers to make better use of their own time, ensure that animal research is only carried out when necessary, and improve chances of grant success by ensuring there is no duplication.

Academic researchers conducting literature or systematic reviews often contact librarians for support. This is far rarer with members of technical staff who many not even realise this support is available. In this case the request was from staff involved in animal licensing and compliance regulation, an essential part of allowing any animal research to go ahead. The role of the requester has meant that this output supports a wide range of research at the Institute rather than a single project.

Although the strategy was requested by technical staff, is designed to support all of the animal research currently undertaken at the Francis Crick Institute it has since been shared with the whole community of animal researchers at the Institute and more widely through the institutional repository.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Current research evaluation prioritises written outputs, and in the biosciences, this is predominantly in the form of a peer-reviewed journal article. Although methodology concerning the creation of data and results should be clearly and transparently detailed, the methodology surrounding literature searching rarely is. Therefore, non-traditional outputs such as this are unlikely to be referenced in traditional outputs and metrics such as citations are unlikely to accurately reflect the usefulness and impact.

Librarians and information specialists are often asked to help with systematic reviews and can often be seen in acknowledgments or even as authors. However, literature searches are undertaken for many reasons other than a systematic review. They underpin research design, methodological and technical developments and the introduction sections of journal articles and reports, but the process of searching for information to support this writing is usually hidden. Where it is technical staff performing these searches, it is yet another step away from any eventual papers and research outputs, and those who helped design the search may not even reach the level of inclusion in the acknowledgments.

In systematic reviews, the searches have been specifically designed for one research project, and are a part of the methodology, and so it is more likely that significant help is acknowledged. However, a more generalised search, such as the one described here is likely to be used at a much earlier stage of the research, and where resources such as this have been shared widely it may no longer even be clear who had originally created it. In this specific case, the resource is unlikely to be acknowledged or cited in any associated written outputs and therefore will be missed by current research evaluation approaches.

Further details

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<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-0946-1842>

Submitted on behalf of PB, Involved in initial request and promotion of output.

Funding acknowledgements: This work was supported by the Francis Crick Institute which receives its core funding from Cancer Research UK (CC0103), the UK Medical Research Council (CC0103) and the Wellcome Trust (CC0103)

Entry: 476

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sims, David

Organisation/University: University of Oxford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The X-NET cross-disciplinary network is a collaboration of technical experts, research professionals and interdisciplinary researchers started by the Universities of Oxford, Edinburgh, Dundee and Aberdeen. The network was funded by the MRC to investigate career barriers facing interdisciplinary researchers in the UK. Over the last two years we have assessed the challenges facing interdisciplinary researchers through surveys, workshops and interviews. Our study highlighted the need for widespread changes in research culture to move towards inclusive collaborative environments to reduce 'hostility' and 'othering' towards those that don't fit the traditional academic career path or template for particular fields.

The project was designed to give a voice to researchers that often find themselves unsupported at the junction between two or more fields. Interdisciplinary researchers are essential for driving innovation at the boundaries of different disciplines, as well as training and supporting the next generation of researchers. Whilst problems affecting interdisciplinary research, such as unsupported career structures and challenges with reward and recognition, have been discussed for years, research culture change has been slow to penetrate the academic system and hard to sustain. To create an inclusive environment and minimise barriers enabling a collaborative, productive and innovative research we have:

- 1) Built a UK network of interdisciplinary researchers (>4500 LinkedIn followers) to gather qualitative and quantitative evidence from current researchers.
- 2) Engaged with voices from outside of academia (public, patients, funders, industry) to learn lessons and identify interventions that could tackle the challenges facing interdisciplinary research and researchers in academia.
- 3) Produced a set of recommendations for funders with practical interventions to accelerate the support for interdisciplinary researchers required to drive innovation.
- 4) Created a YouTube series with advice from researchers at all career stages to support those navigating interdisciplinary career challenges.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This 'research on research' project has given a voice to interdisciplinary researchers who often don't fit into traditional research categories or career templates and feel overlooked by the research system. Care has been taken to engage with voices from all career stages but particularly those in early career positions (e.g. post-doctoral positions) who often receive the least support and face uncertain career paths with larger personal risks. Focus groups with members of the public, patients, funders, interdisciplinary and industry experts have enabled input from a wide range of stakeholders and enabled learnings from outside of academia. This resulted in a series of recommendations to funders on how to enable sustainable interdisciplinary and collaborative research environments. The recommendations aim to drive mobility and exchange of ideas across disciplines and sectors, encourage nurturing collaborative environments for all researchers and make the evaluation of interdisciplinary individuals and teams more equitable. All these suggested interventions are needed to tackle the wider culture and inclusivity changes required for truly diverse interdisciplinary working to thrive and drive innovation. The diversity in perspectives of the X-NET team (researchers, technical experts and research professionals) has

elevated and enriched the projects outputs far beyond its original scope.

All of our focus groups have been recorded and are available open-access to the research community including reports on:

- o Overcoming barriers to Cross-Disciplinary research (Workshop with researchers from academia and industry)
- o Prioritising Cross-Disciplinary Training Needs (Workshop with biomedical industry leaders)
- o Creating & Nurturing Diverse Teams for Effective Biomedical Science (Workshop with Public and Patients)

Inclusivity is at the core of the principals of X-NET and the team has been careful to follow best-practises in teamwork and highlight and champion inclusivity for all researchers in its recommendations. All findings from the project are being reported to local research culture, strategy and policy teams. We have also contributed to wider research culture initiatives ongoing through the university. All outputs have been published, freely available on our website (x-net.bio) and YouTube channel. To be as inclusive and sustainable as possible all activities were carried out online.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Considerable progress has been made in diversifying research representation within the REF. However, significant barriers remain for non-traditional research, interdisciplinary research and non-academic staff to be fully recognised.

The REF's structure, organised around discipline-focused units of assessment, poses challenges for interdisciplinary research, making it harder to select and assess such work appropriately. Traditional evaluation metrics, such as publications and grants, tend to be categorised within discipline-specific boundaries, often overlooking contributions at the intersection of disciplines, which can also be undervalued in conventional academic frameworks.

Identifying and assessing excellent outputs from all staff is also a challenge, given finite institutional resources and time. Initial focus will probably be on staff included in REF volume measures, leaving exceptional work from others hidden.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 482

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: McCutcheon, Valerie

Organisation/University: Open Research Scotland Group

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

While most researchers support the idea of open research, navigating the paths to make their work openly and widely accessible can be challenging in a rapidly changing environment. That is why we founded Open Research Scotland, an inclusive group that facilitates discussions around the world of open research and provides hands-on support for researchers. We started in 2016 initially focused on open access and we're now proud to be a platform for a multi-disciplinary community that supports the openness of traditional and non-traditional research outputs. We further research by staying ahead of new developments, encouraging the uptake of new practices, and helping academics and students cut through policies and requirements so that they have more time to get on with their research.

We are the leading focal point for open research support in Scotland, which is highly relevant for building the environment that fosters good research practices. The collegiate nature of our group has bolstered the 'above and beyond' openness of the members to share details of experiences and practical advice. This ensures that information recorded and reported about research outputs is high quality. The supportive space allows everyone to contribute, voice questions and reflect honestly on previous decisions. Sharing knowledge, practical solutions and best practice contributes to the successful dissemination of research. Our members are typically 'research enablers' from research organisations, who provide excellence in supporting researchers locally, thereby being able to share their individual journeys with the wider group. Importantly, our group also includes funders and suppliers, and we're proud to foster collaborations between stakeholders and influence policies on behalf of Scottish organisations. Overall, there is no doubt that our group makes an important contribution to the quality and management of research in Scotland and beyond.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

How do we further research? Our group allows members to be confident and make informed decisions to support the open research agenda. This helps with increasing impact and visibility of outputs and the quality of the information used for research evaluation exercises. Our group is approachable and provides a supportive environment for everyone with an interest in open research to discuss topics such as good research practice, research data management, open access publisher agreements, Research Excellence Framework (REF) deposit requirements, or questions around non-traditional outputs. Based on our considerable shared experience, we constantly strive to be ahead of the game in today's ever-changing research environment, gathering information, cutting through the jargon and providing clear up to date information to researchers.

We show leadership, for example our members were amongst the first in the UK to introduce rights retention policies. Similarly, we actively influence policies, having submitted a response to the REF open access consultation, which might seem unusual for an informal group. Several meetings were held to discuss the consultation, and these were extremely helpful to attendees who had different levels of exposure to REF. Critical to this was the representation from Scottish Funding Council who are the Scottish members of the REF 2029 Steering Group and provided clarity on REF developments. We network with similar groups in the UK, but we believe that our group is one of the most active ones, providing regular opportunities for participating members to get advice, share ideas and provide

feedback on national initiatives.

We meet formally twice a year, attracting typically 30-50 attendees representing organisations with diverse characteristics to discuss shared interests. This enables us to synthesise points of common needs, plan and implement actions, and obtain advice from peers with a large reach. We work hard to include all members' interests in the agenda and routinely make outcomes of our meetings openly available. An active sub-group meets regularly to discuss publisher open access arrangements. Ad hoc meetings on specific topics such as the REF open access consultation are also held during the year. Additionally, we have a very lively mailing list that ensures continuous communication between meetings, and we are planning the launch of a new journal soon. Members of our group are working together to improve the quality of open research support in Scotland and continue to make the research outputs created in Scottish organisations available to all.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Firstly, REF results are presented as relating to individual institutions and therefore the environment section may not capture cross-institutional or regional communities of practice. Secondly, the output-focused research culture is not designed to evaluate and appreciate groups like ours, whose spirit is purely community-driven to further research and research visibility, rather than promoting specific fields. Therefore, we are overlooked by current evaluation approaches. Thirdly, many of our members work behind the scenes, spending a lot of time setting up robust systems and processes to support open research. They facilitate openness, increasing visibility and accessibility to research outputs. While they play a crucial part in furthering research in the UK, they may never be credited directly when REF results are announced. We therefore believe that by appreciating the spirit of our group free of personal gains, the Hidden REF would send a signal towards a modern, fairer research environment.

Further details

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Authors: Writing - Original Draft: Valerie McCutcheon; Writing - Reviewing and Editing: Mary Donaldson, Matt Mahon, Lisa Turner Warnecke

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 483

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Smith, Cassie

Organisation/University: Health Data Research UK

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate the Contracts, Policy and Procurement Team at Health Data Research UK. Research contracts are vital to the successful delivery of research. A well-drafted contract clearly sets out the expectations of the different parties and how they will collaborate as well as protecting the interests of researchers and of the University's charity status. Critically, contract terms can be used to ensure that research outcomes are utilised and shared in the public good and that research is conducted with integrity.

An efficient contracts and procurement function can accelerate good research, whereas a slow inefficient function can be a significant barrier. The Contracts, Policy and Procurement team at HDR UK is pragmatic, high performing and quite simply best in class. It is a small team of three, who handle all contracting and procurement and coordinate internal review, benchmarking, updating, and dissemination of policies. These important functions underpin all of HDR UK's operations, allowing for essential activities to take place within a robust framework combining compliance and efficiency. Ultimately having a high performing Contracts, Policy and Procurement team enables HDR UK to deliver on its mission to unite the UK's health data to enable discoveries that improve and save lives.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Excellence: The Contracts, Policy and Procurement Team exemplifies excellence. The team has an impressive two-day average turnaround time for contracts, handling over 600 contracts per year. This is significantly faster than most research organisations, where weeks or even months is typical for contract review. The team is agile to changing needs and priorities. For example, the team supported a call for funding and drafted and issued 16 award letters to research organisations across the UK within 2 days, which enabled rapid vital research to relieve winter pressures on the NHS.

Originality/creativity: The contractual set up for HDR UK as an Institute is a unique and highly effective framework. It enables 36 University partners to collaborate seamlessly on the same terms, allowing the agile issuing of award letters in order to speed up contracting and allows research work to start without months of delays to negotiate and agree on contract terms. The efficient functioning of the Institute is a tribute to the excellence and originality of the Contracts, Policy and Procurement Team.

Appropriateness, relevance and rigour: The team plays a key role in ensuring research appropriateness and rigour by putting in place procurement processes that are fair, transparent, and proportionate and ensuring contracts are clear, fit for purpose and protect the organisations involved, while clearly setting out roles and responsibilities.

Reflexive & positional: The team understands limitations of knowledge and expertise and utilises relevant expertise in other teams, such as information governance and IT security.

Leadership: The Contracts, Procurement and Policy team are regularly called on to go above and beyond what is expected by their roles, by providing strategic input into formation of research projects and general operations. They use their general knowledge in relevant legislation and regulation to

provide advice and guidance to different teams within the organisation, for example, highlighting requirements in relation to subsidy, tax and employment legislation.

Temporality: The team ensures appropriate terms are included for ensuring outputs are used for public benefit and published in accordance with open-source guidelines and policies following project completion, ensuring project partners are clear on processes for dissemination of valuable outputs over the long term.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Contracting and procurement teams are typically seen as a compliance function and a common source of delay and frustration. However, contracting is a key part of the research lifecycle and an enabler of research. Procurement teams contribute to the successful performance of research by obtaining good value for money and ensuring responsible use of funding.

The importance of contracts, policy and procurement teams is often overlooked and undervalued. I hope this nomination for the HDR UK Contracts, Policy and Procurement Team highlights the value we place on the team members and their importance in delivering on our charitable mission.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 488

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wilkinson, Catherine

Organisation/University: Liverpool John Moores University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to nominate my pedagogic and autoethnographic research into imposter syndrome, which culminated in the publication of my research 'Imposter syndrome and the accidental academic: An autoethnographic account' in the International Journal for Academic Development. To my knowledge, this was the first study to use an autoethnographic approach to focus on the lived experiences of Imposter Syndrome for one lecturer.

In the paper I argue that mentoring for lecturers, particularly on aspects of dealing with nerves and classroom behaviour management could be useful, not only for improving practice, but also improving student experience. I argue that this is particularly important when considering feedback received at faculty level that confident and animated lecturers rate higher in student evaluations.

Emerging from my study, the field diary, used as a methodological tool, became a 'friend to confide in'. I used my diary as a space to divulge and to help me 'work through' my nerves. The content of the diary revealed that the process of keeping the diary regularly may help in the management of stress and emotions. In particular, I found it useful to look back on specific days or weeks in order to unlock and resolve my personal feelings and to address imposter thoughts, and recommended other academics to consider using a diary to record and document their thoughts and emotions.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

I have received unsolicited feedback on social media and via email from over 20 academics and students (inter)nationally about the impact of my paper. Many shared the personal influence the research and manuscript had on them and their teaching:

'I have just read this and I totally identify with it. Imposter syndrome is very real and quite debilitating. Thank u [sic] for sharing this. Its [sic] so important and not addressed by many universities.' (PhD student at University of Birmingham)

'I've just read this paper. It's great. I am sure that there are parallels with marginalised students' experience during their studies too. ThankQ [sic] for sharing your experiences. I kept nodding as I read it-remembering some of my own experiences! (Early Career Researcher at University of Leeds)

'After having a hard week, a fellow Ph.D. student sent me your paper. Thank you so much for writing this piece! I think that being conscious of how feeling like a fraud impacts not only the quality of my work, but my overall wellbeing is key for me to be kinder with myself.' (PhD student at Yale University)

"I have recently read your article titled Imposter Syndrome and The Accidental Academic: An Autoethnographic Account. I found your research incredibly important as I have personally struggled with imposter syndrome for much of my college career thus far. I plan on working in the higher education field one day, so understanding that I am not alone dealing with these feelings has helped me find comfort in my work and in my personal confidence. I appreciate your autoethnographic account of some of your personal experiences and your vulnerability to discuss them in your work...Your work has

encouraged and inspired me to advocate for students to have access to support for imposter syndrome symptoms and increase education surrounding imposter syndrome in higher education". (Doctoral student, University of Kentucky).

My pedagogical work on imposter syndrome has also had significant international impact. For instance, my research led to new training on imposter syndrome designed for an induction programme for women in engineering and IT, organised by the Faculty of Engineering and Information Technology, University of Technology Sydney. My work fed into their programme which has been designed to ensure that the study and career journeys in Engineering and IT are not limited by gender. Further, I was notified by the Assistant Headteacher at The British International School Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam that my research on imposter syndrome and my recommendations around the value of using a diary have led to the implementation of journaling for staff at this school.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This work is overlooked within current research culture and evaluation approaches owing to its pedagogic and autoethnographic focus. With its emphasis on personal pedagogy, it may be considered not to make significant theoretical advances. Further, via the approach of autoethnography, rather than a robust and objective methods using a large scale sample, it focuses on personal and subjective experiences of one individual (myself). Arguably, it therefore lacks generalisability and rigour under traditional research evaluation approaches.

Further, whilst more than 20 academics and doctoral students shared with me via written communication (some examples of which I have included above) the personal impact my work and writing had on them, REF criteria tends to prioritise research with measurable, significant impacts on academic knowledge or policy changes rather than indirect or inferred improvements.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: There is no funding associated with this work.

Entry: 494

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Broadbridge, Ang

Organisation/University: Ways to Wellness

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission highlights a collaborative community building partnership led by the Voluntary, Community and Social Enterprise Sector, together with partners across the health and care system; a test and learn project triangulating findings from frontline practice with professional health workers experiences and crucially placing the voices of new Mums front and centre in relation to maternal mental health. This work is hidden as public bodies do not routinely use the wealth of data and intelligence that VCSE organisations hold to inform service design and planning, this project created collaborative opportunities for this to happen regularly and using a wide range of feedback mechanisms.

Ways to Wellness is a charity that brings people together to tackle health inequalities across the North East and North Cumbria. Our mission is to develop and test innovative programmes and prototypes that improve health and wellbeing, tackle health inequalities, and reduce demand on NHS services. We explore and test new ways of working together and delivering services to patients, showing real-world impact.

This nomination is for a project, namely 'VCSE Maternal Mental Health Services Prototypes' recognising the contributions made by the team of Link Workers, their Senior Leads and connected colleagues through our steering group and evaluation sub group who have embraced a learning community approach, together the insights they have gathered contributed to the successful delivery of four place based prototypes in the field of maternal mental health, designing and delivering responsive services meeting the needs of local families.

The research conducted has had wide reaching impacts, leading to system change, leveraging funding to support local families and springboarding new research collaborations locally, regionally and nationally.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The link worker learning community for the VCSE Maternal Mental Health Services Prototypes programme meets monthly. Frontline link workers who are engaged in one to one support of mums with maternal mental health needs meet through the expressed importance of creating and protecting space for reflection and contemplation.

Learning is integrated into recruitment to attract and retain a workforce who take a learning approach and who are prepared to be vulnerable in their practice, engage with 'test and learn' approaches and surface gaps and challenges facing new parents as identified at the place based level.

Rigorous commitment to research is represented at every level, from recruitment to shaping how the community operates. The link worker team co-designed their Learning Community. This enabled a sense of belonging and ownership by the team who in their everyday practice are based in different localities, employed by different host organisations.

The co-design process began by seeking consensus on the team's conditions for working together,

guided by The Learning Communities Handbook.

We asked questions that placed reflexivity front and centre - what do we need as a collective?

• Practising empathy and curiosity - not blaming parts of the system if we notice something isn't working

• Having an open dialogue approach, learning as a dialogic process where we come together to talk about what we hear and see in caseloads, in conversations with professionals

• Making a commitment to taking perspective, realising we all see different sides of the beach ball - being curious about what we see

[The Learning Community], it's the best part of my week (Link Worker)

Being situated in the voluntary sector means that the link worker team is well positioned to listen to the voices of mothers, in all their diversity.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Research and evidence held by VCSE organisations is often hidden as public bodies do not routinely use the wealth of data and intelligence that VCSE organisations hold to inform service design and planning, this project created collaborative opportunities for this to happen regularly and using a wide range of feedback mechanisms.

Furthermore, this submission challenges assumptions about who can do research and be involved in leading research, this work was led by frontline VCSE practitioners taking an action research approach - itself an undervalued approach as highlighted by University of Reading in their PAR Toolkit <https://research.reading.ac.uk/community-based-research/wp-content/uploads/sites/114/2023/06/PAR-Toolkit-v10.pdf> :

"This is partly because the outputs are not purely for academic benefit: it's producing things that are accessible and work for the community, for the participants. It's not just for writing papers" (p.29)

To this end we prioritise knowledge mobilisation - as the project has progressed the Learning Community approach has been taken out in to the wider system, with Ways to Wellness together with the NENC Applied Research Collaborative and Local Maternity and Neonatal System colleagues co-hosting a series of learning community events bringing together people across the system to learn and explore together.

Briefing notes follow each event so that learning can be disseminated widely and those interested to follow up can come together to take forward learning and explore any actions, sparking 'mini experiments' within the prototypes.

This approach attempts to overcome the narrative widely reported that on average it takes 17 years for research evidence to be implemented into daily clinical practice. This learning community approach is practical and generative - link workers are empowered to test and learn through these mini experiments, and some of these experiments, for example the link worker being based in clinic, are now becoming embedded in practice.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: To be completed later if required

Funding acknowledgements: Funding is provided by the North East and North Cumbria Mental Health ICS and Perinatal Mental Health Clinical Network team, as part of the NHS England Maternal Mental Health Fast Follower programme

Entry: 495

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lee Steele, Anne

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating The Turing Way's (TTW) Accessibility Working Group for the "Everything else!" category, with Liz Hare as its representative, for their work in highlighting accessibility-related needs and practices used to remove those barriers.

The Turing Way is a globally recognised, open science project based at The Alan Turing Institute. Its community-driven data science handbook includes over 350 chapters across five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration, and Ethical Research. Since its inception, The Turing Way has supported multiple initiatives, including working groups that contribute to making research more inclusive and accessible.

Liz Hare, co-lead of the Accessibility Working Group, has been instrumental in advancing accessibility in research. She organised a 2022 workshop at The Turing Way's bi-annual contribution event with Andrea Sanchez-Tapia, focusing on accessibility for disabled researchers in data science (workshop recording: https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ARMs7C_wE04). This prompted the formation of the Accessibility Working Group in early 2023, which has most recently culminated in a Fireside Chat discussion on aligned topics (talk recording: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Ac9czT3Tr8A&list;=PLBxcQEfGu3DI521skBqVilQVsSUZ-VYi2&index;=1>). The Accessibility Working Group has also provided guidance about which collaborative tools are accessible, planning for the bi-annual contribution event, and how to use collaboration tools like Slack in accessible ways.

The working group has since tackled key challenges in open science, developing processes to improve accessibility for contributors facing various barriers. It brings together experts and researchers from diverse backgrounds, including those from low-to-middle-income countries, to address accessibility in a broader sense as well as ensure that disabled researchers can participate in shaping data science practices and research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Accessibility Working Group has been integral in shaping how accessibility is considered and implemented within The Turing Way, extending into the broader ecosystem of open science and data science research. This submission highlights the critical and often invisible work of fostering accessibility and inclusion within The Turing Way community and open science broadly.

Liz Hare, alongside the Accessibility Working Group have taken a proactive role in shifting the conversation towards considering accessibility not as an afterthought, but as an integral component of research. This submission aims to highlight a non-traditional but crucial output: accessibility practices that are rarely measured by traditional research metrics but have a far-reaching impact on both the research community and the quality of research produced.

Leadership:

Liz Hare's leadership is noteworthy for going above and beyond. Her workshop in 2022, alongside Andrea Sanchez-Tapia, set the foundation for the Accessibility Working Group, offering guidance on how

to think critically about inclusivity in the field of data science. By advocating for this crucial aspect of research and engaging with a global community, Liz has demonstrated a clear vision for how open science can be made accessible to all, particularly those traditionally excluded from this space.

Reflexivity and Positionality:

The group operates within a reflexive framework, constantly evaluating and refining its approach during monthly meetings. This reflection is evident in how the group assesses its work, ensuring that it remains open to feedback and that its processes evolve as the needs of the community change. Furthermore, their emergent accessibility policy is rooted in rigour, continuously updated in line with new technologies and feedback from the community. Their process recognises that accessibility is not a one-time achievement but an ongoing process that requires community engagement, transparency, and accountability.

Responsibility:

The group has demonstrated a strong commitment to responsible research, ensuring that accessibility practices are designed to serve a much broader research community. Their efforts are grounded in principles of research integrity and social responsibility, reflecting an awareness of the structural barriers that exist for researchers with disabilities. By addressing these barriers, the group contributes to the creation of a more ethical research ecosystem, where diverse voices can shape the research agenda.

Temporality:

The impact of this working group goes beyond immediate outputs; it is rooted in the long-term relationships and continuous contributions of its members. The creation of the group itself stems from ongoing efforts within The Turing Way to be inclusive and responsive to the needs of its community. Their approach ensures that the work is not simply a one-off intervention but part of a sustained effort to improve accessibility in open science over time. "Moving at the speed of trust" has been integral.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Turing Way community defines accessibility practices as a set of community-wide, behavioral, social and technical decisions that can be taken to ensure that all are welcome to enter and participate in research, data-driven processes, communities and events despite any barriers for access.

Traditional academic culture and evaluation often neither incentivise nor support access-related work, which prioritise the speed of publications over the long, slow work of addressing access-related needs and broader inclusivity. This is a critical, yet often-overlooked aspect of research culture that the Accessibility Working Group has sought to address within The Turing Way community. In developing principles and ways of working, as well as practical guidance for working professionals, they have sought to highlight the current gap between principles and practices.

Similar to anthropologist Susan Leigh Star's observation that infrastructure is only visible when it breaks, the Accessibility Working Group's contributions become apparent only when accessibility issues arise or are not addressed pre-emptively. Their behind-the-scenes work in ensuring that our existing resources and events meet accessibility standards, as well as writing guidance or implementing necessary changes is often slow, requires moving at the speed of trust on multiple fronts: both within the community as well as within the working group itself, which often involves working across intersectional identities and lived experiences of exclusion from the practices they are working to improve.

Highlighting the work of the Accessibility Working Group within The Turing Way is crucial, as they have shifted the culture of our project and community, and have been integral in stewarding these discussions and resources. Similarly, this submission highlights the need for a broader category of Accessibility within the Hidden REF submission categories, as this topic remains an urgent but overlooked priority for researchers across all institutions everywhere.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-9262-8641

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Way is funded by the Alan Turing Institute, but has volunteer contributors and collaborators from across different institutions.

Entry: 496

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lee Steele, Anne

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating The Turing Way's (TTW) Accessibility Working Group for the "Everything else!" category, with Liz Hare as its representative, for their work in highlighting accessibility-related needs and practices used to remove those barriers.

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The working group has since tackled key challenges in open science, developing processes to improve accessibility for contributors facing various barriers. It brings together experts and researchers from diverse backgrounds, including those from low-to-middle-income countries, to address accessibility in a broader sense as well as ensure that disabled researchers can participate in shaping data science practices and research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Accessibility Working Group has been integral in shaping how accessibility is considered and implemented within The Turing Way, extending into the broader ecosystem of open science and data science research. This submission highlights the critical and often invisible work of fostering accessibility and inclusion within The Turing Way community and open science broadly.

Liz Hare, alongside the Accessibility Working Group have taken a proactive role in shifting the conversation towards considering accessibility not as an afterthought, but as an integral component of research. This submission aims to highlight a non-traditional but crucial output: accessibility practices that are rarely measured by traditional research metrics but have a far-reaching impact on both the research community and the quality of research produced.

Leadership:

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to think critically about inclusivity in the field of data science. By advocating for this crucial aspect of research and engaging with a global community, Liz has demonstrated a clear vision for how open science can be made accessible to all, particularly those traditionally excluded from this space.

Reflexivity and Positionality:

The group operates within a reflexive framework, constantly evaluating and refining its approach during monthly meetings. This reflection is evident in how the group assesses its work, ensuring that it remains open to feedback and that its processes evolve as the needs of the community change. Furthermore, their emergent accessibility policy is rooted in rigour, continuously updated in line with new technologies and feedback from the community. Their process recognises that accessibility is not a one-time achievement but an ongoing process that requires community engagement, transparency, and accountability.

Responsibility:

The group has demonstrated a strong commitment to responsible research, ensuring that accessibility practices are designed to serve a much broader research community. Their efforts are grounded in principles of research integrity and social responsibility, reflecting an awareness of the structural barriers that exist for researchers with disabilities. By addressing these barriers, the group contributes to the creation of a more ethical research ecosystem, where diverse voices can shape the research agenda.

Temporality:

The impact of this working group goes beyond immediate outputs; it is rooted in the long-term relationships and continuous contributions of its members. The creation of the group itself stems from ongoing efforts within The Turing Way to be inclusive and responsive to the needs of its community. Their approach ensures that the work is not simply a one-off intervention but part of a sustained effort to improve accessibility in open science over time. "Moving at the speed of trust" has been integral.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Turing Way community defines accessibility practices as a set of community-wide, behavioral, social and technical decisions that can be taken to ensure that all are welcome to enter and participate in research, data-driven processes, communities and events despite any barriers for access.

Traditional academic culture and evaluation often neither incentivise nor support access-related work, which prioritise the speed of publications over the long, slow work of addressing access-related needs and broader inclusivity. This is a critical, yet often-overlooked aspect of research culture that the Accessibility Working Group has sought to address within The Turing Way community. In developing principles and ways of working, as well as practical guidance for working professionals, they have sought to highlight the current gap between principles and practices.

Similar to anthropologist Susan Leigh Star's observation that infrastructure is only visible when it breaks, the Accessibility Working Group's contributions become apparent only when accessibility issues arise or are not addressed pre-emptively. Their behind-the-scenes work in ensuring that our existing resources and events meet accessibility standards, as well as writing guidance or implementing necessary changes is often slow, requires moving at the speed of trust on multiple fronts: both within the community as well as within the working group itself, which often involves working across intersectional identities and lived experiences of exclusion from the practices they are working to improve.

Highlighting the work of the Accessibility Working Group within The Turing Way is crucial, as they have shifted the culture of our project and community, and have been integral in stewarding these discussions and resources. Similarly, this submission highlights the need for a broader category of Accessibility within the Hidden REF submission categories, as this topic remains an urgent but overlooked priority for researchers across all institutions everywhere.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-9262-8641

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Way is funded by the Alan Turing Institute, but has volunteer contributors and collaborators from across different institutions.

Entry: 501

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lee Steele, Anne

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This nomination is for the Book Dash Working Group, composed of Arielle Bennett, Esther Plomp, Emma Karoune, Carlos Martinez-Ortiz, Susana Roman-Garcia, and Alexandra Araujo Alvarez. The working group, comprised of volunteers that organise and facilitate the project's bi-annual Book Dash event has been essential in fostering collaboration, community-building, and the continued creation of high-quality, open access resources for widespread use by researchers and scientists.

The Turing Way is a large open science and community-led project at The Alan Turing Institute, widely known and renowned for its high-quality data science handbook. Co-created by a global community, the handbook includes over 350 chapters across five guides on Reproducible Research, Project Design, Communication, Collaboration, and Ethical Research. With over 500 contributors from various backgrounds, identities and lived experiences, the project has expanded greatly in its past five years of growth. Web analytics show monthly engagement with 7,000 users, 17,000 page views, 35,000 resource downloads (from Zenodo), and 100+ citations to date. Readers and users span multiple countries, including Australia, Argentina, Brazil, Germany, India, the Netherlands, Nigeria, Saudi Arabia, South Africa, Turkey, the UK, the USA, Venezuela, and beyond.

Book Dashes are integral for this global community, as events where participants collaboratively work on The Turing Way guides to develop new chapters, review or edit existing work, maintain resources, or work on other subprojects. A cornerstone of the project, 11 Book Dashes have been hosted both online and in-person over the past five years of the project's growth and development.

As the community and project has grown, Book Dashes have become increasingly important in stewarding diverse contributions. The Book Dash Working Group, which decides the strategic direction of the event has demonstrated leadership in maintaining both the quality and inclusiveness of the event.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The Book Dash Working Group is composed of long-time volunteer leaders of The Turing Way community. They play a crucial role in organising and sustaining the Book Dash event, and have been instrumental in maintaining the event's inclusivity and effectiveness, ensuring that both new and experienced contributors have a meaningful and enjoyable experience.

Local Importance:

The Book Dash Working Group has been pivotal in organising hybrid events that accommodate participants from a wide range of geographies and backgrounds. From the start, Book Dash events have been organised as hybrid events with participants joining from at least 6 different time zones, as well as in-person hubs outside of London, UK where the project team is based.

The Book Dash Working Group has been integral in ensuring the development of local hubs, previously organised in Delft and Amsterdam in the Netherlands, as well as Bristol, UK. In order to accommodate and support contributors across different geographies, remote working sessions are also organised for Americas and Asia-Pacific time zones. This ensures that the widest number of participants can join and

contribute to the project, reducing barriers to global cooperation.

Leadership

The Book Dash event remains a focal contribution event for The Turing Way community. The Working Group's role in steering and managing this key event highlights their significant contribution to the project's continued growth and community cohesion.

Reflexive and Positionality

As experienced contributors to The Turing Way community and Book Dash events, the Book Dash Working Group has a strong understanding of the project's culture and community. The working group regularly reflects on the inclusivity, accessibility, and engagement of the week-long event based on participant feedback, and how it can better reach and engage with the global community that contributes to the resource.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Ensuring the strategic direction and continuity of The Turing Way Book Dash event is crucial, yet the contributions of the Book Dash Working Group are often overlooked. Similar to any organising committee or for any ongoing event, their essential role is frequently underestimated within current research culture and evaluation frameworks, which focus on research outputs rather than service efforts. In addition, since much of the Working Group members time is spent supporting and mentoring others to contribute. In supporting a culture of collaboration rather than individual outputs, the work of the group involves developing systems and convening capacity that ensure community health and growth of the project. This involves planning training workshops, onboarding sessions, networking events, and carrying out other crucial activities, including integrating new contributors to the project. As a result, the impact of this work is often cumulative and ongoing, rather than tied to a single, easily measurable output. Their work exemplifies the invisible labour that sustains many other open source and collaboration research communities, often hidden from traditional evaluation metrics. This type of invisible labour is vital for sustaining The Turing Way community, and enhancing the collective infrastructure of the project.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-9262-8641

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Way is funded by the Alan Turing Institute, but has volunteer contributors and collaborators from across different institutions.

Entry: 502

Applicant details

Submission category: 3 - Citizen Science

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Morris, Jonathan

Organisation/University: n/a

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This was/is a low cost but obscure renewable energy concept developed in 2008 onwards, largely for developing communities. Patents searched and the configuration found to be new and novel so patent applications made. In 2010 I discovered some similarities to the layout of Stonehenge so set about disproving it could be so (US Patent law did not, at that time, allow a Utility patent to be granted if something has been done before). As at 2024, the rapidly decreasing cost of Photo Voltaic modules has made the concept too relatively expensive to be cost beneficial.

Disproving it proved difficult. It predicts certain features that were found, over the next ten years or so, to be correct. Nothing discovered in the 2010-2024 period went against the principles of the hypothesis. By 2021, I was being invited to give presentations of the concept to scholarly groups (Neolithic Studies Group).

If this simple but obscure technology were used in Neolithic Britain, its use would be as a form of Geocentric Orrery explaining how the Universe works (though the Universe isn't Geocentric, it was thought to be so right up until the 16th century). Its plan layout also is arranged as a 2-D description of a geocentric universe.

The concept was written up as a low cost 'project book' using black and white. It's a little too bonkers to be considered by Academic Publishers (I have no academic qualifications other than a batchelor's degree in engineering and Fellow of a couple of engineering institutions). I felt it should have a fixed ISBN and publication date (current edition is ISBN: 0956861733: "A Neolithic Universe") so that it could be included in REF type research if that were necessary.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The research shows a viable non-religious explanation for some (albeit limited) monuments of the past. It uses only materials technology known to be available at the time. It also uses no devices (eg aliens, special advanced technology, ritual and so on).

The alternative given is one based on a past motivation to understand the world.

Its importance, as an alternative to current widely believed hypotheses, is to demonstrate that people of the past may have been just as intelligent as we are today and that technological progress could, and can, be lost.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The concepts are very difficult for people outside solar engineering professions to understand. To verify that they are correct, the ideas would require the input of a number of different specialisms: this would be very expensive to do and there's not much in the way of funding for archaeology. However, in the past 12 years or so, I haven't come across anyone in the heritage/archaeology industry who would counter the hypothesis by saying why it may be wrong (many dozens of archaeologists have read the book).

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 507

Applicant details

Submission category: 5 - Community Building, collaboration and partnership

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rajendran, Lakshmi

Organisation/University: University College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This interdisciplinary project focuses on the challenges and opportunities of peri-urban regions in India, proposing a transformative framework for their sustainable development. The collaboration brought together diverse fields, system engineering, architecture, urban planning, design, and environmental sciences, to analyse peri-urban dynamics through creative methodologies like sketching and mapping residents' everyday lives. These approaches produced a rich dataset that offered unique insights into the peri-urban reality, breaking away from traditional urban-rural binaries and introducing the concept of the "peri-urban turn."

The project was conducted with a strong emphasis on building equitable, long-lasting partnerships with local planning authorities, practitioners, and residents who contributed lived experiences. It resulted in a variety of impactful outputs, including a film, conference presentations, public roundtables, and an open-access journal publication. The project highlighted the ethical challenges of conducting research in the Global South, especially with regard to extractivist research models and neoliberal institutional guidelines. It also underscored the importance of collaboration and trust-building across varying career stages within the research team, promoting an equitable model of knowledge production.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This submission is significant because it presents a new framework for understanding peri-urban regions, particularly in the Global South. By integrating a range of disciplines, system engineering, architecture, environmental science, and more, the project has developed an innovative, holistic approach to sustainable peri-urban development. Importantly, the concept of the "peri-urban turn" challenges conventional urban-rural binaries and advocates for decolonizing urban development practices. This shift has the potential to reshape both academic and policy approaches to sustainable urbanism, making it particularly relevant in the context of increasing urbanization.

Additionally, this project demonstrates how interdisciplinary collaboration can generate more equitable partnerships and ethical research practices. It builds a model for community engagement that includes stakeholders at all levels, from academic collaborators to residents, ensuring that the voices of those directly impacted are heard and valued. The project's outputs have also led to broader visibility and advocacy, raising the profile of peri-urban issues through accessible mediums such as films, public discussions, and open-access publications.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This submission may be overlooked within current research culture due to the complexity of interdisciplinary work and the challenge of fitting non-traditional methodologies into standard evaluation frameworks. The focus on creative methods like sketching and lived-experience mapping, while innovative, might not align with conventional, quantitative research paradigms, making it harder to evaluate through standard academic metrics.

Additionally, research in the Global South often faces marginalization, both in terms of funding and

recognition. The ethical challenges addressed in this project, such as resisting extractivist research models and prioritizing equitable knowledge production, are not always considered a priority in mainstream research cultures dominated by neoliberal and Western-centric evaluation systems. The time and effort required for true community collaboration and trust-building are often undervalued, despite their critical importance for producing socially responsible and impactful research. This submission challenges those norms, advocating for a more inclusive and equitable approach to research.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: data collection for the project has been funded by 1) SHLC, the Centre for Sustainable, Healthy and Learning Cities and Neighbourhoods. SHLC is funded via UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) as part of the UK Government's Global Challenges Research Fund (GCRF) 2) The Climate Emergency Fund from the UCL Environment Domain and UCL Grand Challenges and their support is gratefully acknowledged.

Entry: 508

Applicant details

Submission category: 11 - Everything else!

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Rajendran, Lakshmi

Organisation/University: University College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Traditional models of leadership have long been characterised by hierarchical structures and top-down decision-making processes, deeply rooted in imperialist and colonial legacies. These traditional approaches often prioritise efficiency and control, perpetuating exclusionary practices and reinforcing power imbalances. In contrast, the modern world's increasing emphasis on diversity, equity, and inclusion necessitates a rethinking of leadership paradigms. One innovative model that addresses these needs is the decolonial approach to leadership. Our Submission highlights our research collective, Decolab, a largely women-led, interdisciplinary, and international collaboratorium, has implemented a radical leadership model that exemplifies decolonial principles. By decentralising leadership and fostering inclusivity, Decolab offers a compelling example of how organisations can create equitable and transparent research work cultures.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Decolab: A Women-Led, Decolonial Collaboratorium is significant in the research context because it exemplifies a transformative model of leadership and collaboration developed as part of a 2-year British Academy-funded project. This initiative challenges conventional hierarchical structures by decentralizing leadership, promoting equity, and emphasizing empathy and inclusivity in decision-making. This decolonial framework directly addresses the limitations of traditional, patriarchal leadership models in academia, which often exclude diverse perspectives and perpetuate inequalities.

By providing leadership opportunities to all team members, regardless of career stage or title, Decolab fosters a research environment where emerging scholars can meaningfully contribute. This model not only diversifies decision-making but also enhances the research process, allowing for more innovative and creative approaches to problem-solving. Decolab is especially significant as it demonstrates how decolonial practices can reshape knowledge production and organizational structures, providing a model for more equitable research environments. Decolonial leadership involves redistributing power, promoting collective responsibility, and integrating diverse perspectives, with a particular focus on elevating voices historically excluded from leadership roles.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Decolab's innovative approach may be overlooked in current research culture due to its departure from traditional hierarchical leadership models that dominate academic evaluation. Research institutions often value formal titles, seniority, and individual achievements, metrics that may not align with Decolab's decentralized and fluid leadership structure. This makes it difficult to assess the contributions of such a collaborative model using conventional benchmarks focused on outputs, such as publications and grants, rather than the quality of the process and the equity it fosters.

The decolonial and feminist principles that underpin Decolab also present a challenge to the neoliberal and patriarchal norms prevalent in academia. Research culture tends to marginalize projects that critique and attempt to deconstruct existing power structures. Consequently, Decolab's emphasis on empathy, shared responsibility, and inclusive leadership, which are often undervalued, may result in its

contributions being under-recognized. Its efforts to promote social justice, especially as part of a Global South research framework, may also struggle to gain visibility in an academic environment that often overlooks non-Western and feminist perspectives.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: British Academy

Communicative outputs panel

Entry: 359

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Asher, Claire

Organisation/University: n/a

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Robot Talk is a weekly podcast hosted by Dr Claire Asher, which aims to engage the public in robotics research and innovation through relaxed, jargon-free interviews with robotics researchers and industry experts. Launched in 2020 with funding from the EPSRC-funded UK RAS Network (and now supported by Imperial College London's Hamlyn Centre) Robot Talk completed its fourth season in June 2024 (with Season 5 due to launch in September). To date, the podcast has featured over 120 robotics experts from across the UK and internationally. By making robotics more accessible and offering an opportunity for members of the public to ask questions directly to academic researchers, Robot Talk is playing an important role in responsible innovation. As well as covering technical developments, Robot Talk explores the social and ethical implications of new robotics innovations, opening up a conversation that helps the public better understand the advantages and pitfalls of robotic technology and helps roboticists to take the hopes and concerns of the public into account in their research.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As one of the only podcasts focussed on academic research in robotics and autonomous systems, Robot Talk is an original and creative approach to communicating research. It contributes to responsible innovation by creating an open dialogue between end-users of research (including members of the public) and the researchers in academia and industry who are driving innovations in robotics and autonomous systems. Robot Talk has also become an important educational tool, providing an introduction to a broad range of robotics topics for undergraduate and postgraduate students across the UK and beyond. Its lengthy track record of nearly 100 episodes over a 4-year period demonstrates temporality and continuity that listeners and researchers have come to rely upon.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Public engagement activities are often not fully captured by the REF evaluation framework, and as an ongoing, long-term public engagement exercise, podcasts are particularly difficult to include in the traditional framework. I welcome Hidden Ref for providing this opportunity to bring the Robot Talk podcast to the attention of REF.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 362

Applicant details

Submission category: M - Performance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Shaw, Graeme

Organisation/University: Brunel University London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

'Made of Night', a theatrical sound art performance that explores themes of night time synaesthetic psychosis.

Duration: 40 minutes

World Premiere: Saturday 27th May 2023, Antonin Artaud Building, Brunel University.

Video of Performance: <https://youtu.be/za0Zq5ZIJ64>

The Making of Made of Night: <https://youtu.be/FFtAZcxQZDg>

Working as a Technician in the Arts & Humanities I am surrounded by a diverse range of technology ranging from everyday used equipment to high-end specialist software. Central to my role as a Technical Specialist is a remit to engage and support students using this broad range of technologies in both a pragmatic and inspiring way. Going beyond just the practical explanations of using the equipment I formulated ways that high and low tech could be integrated so as to foster imaginative understanding of the technology. I also importantly developed collaborative artist practice in such a way as to provide cohesive and ethical team work bringing students and staff together. In a working environment which leaves little time in the working week for creative practice, this requires significant rigour and commitment from me.

I choose to develop my ideas of technology integration through a series of workshops leading to a live performance. This involved weekly practical rehearsals (always at weekends) from January 2023 to May 2023. Integrated into this process was a select team of Undergraduate theatre students taking on roles of technical assistants and stage hands which empowered them with learning new technical and leadership skills while in the process giving them the first-hand experience of working in a live scenario (as opposed to classroom simulation).

This research was evidenced by a single theatrical performance allowing me to positively impact the following Brunel University London (BUL) learning outcomes:

• Digital Literacy

• Communication and Collaboration

• Creativity and Innovation

• Core Content Knowledge

• Cross-Disciplinary Knowledge

Supporting Documentation submitted: info@hidden-ref.org

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

There are three key significant engagements in the work carried out:

1. The development of integrative technologies. The computational system I developed is based around an overhead camera looking straight down onto the stage at the performer. The data that is generated from the camera's image is received in Isadora software which is then sent to Max/MSP via Open Sound Control (OSC) on the same computer to be processed and outputted as sound. For the sound worlds I took inspiration from the early compositional techniques of John Cage and Karlheinz Stockhausen e.g. the use of spoken word, repetition, variable pitch and speed, tape delay, resonators, ring modulators, wave shapers, oscillators and filters all programmed in Max/Msp. I developed a computational system that allowed a performer on stage to manipulate the speed, pitch and volume of sound in real time. Running parallel to this system are, sound samples, drones, live microphones that are placed on the stage to process the sounds generated in the performance area along with a contact microphone hidden in a wooden bowl (choreographic object) as used by the performer that enabled me to process, again, in real-time, the sound of a wooden bowl which, in this, case, was full of marbles. (metaphoric planets).

2. The dramaturgy of this performance is firmly rooted in cross-cultural East meets West disciplines, something hugely important in today's cultural environment. Primarily drawing upon the theatre works of Robert Wilson (American experimental theatre and stage director) and Maro Akaji (Japanese actor, Butoh, and theatre director) and his dance company Dairakudakan, Made of Night sees a protagonist respond to searching questions through a sequence of different technical scenarios (scenes).

3. The neurological condition of synesthesia 'Äwhere the stimulation of one sensory or cognitive pathway leads to automatic, involuntary experiences in a second sensory or cognitive pathway' is something that was also hugely important in the work. Myself and the team explored how the stimulation of physical gesture can lead to the involuntary experience of sound, allowing creative decisions to be made through added layers of creativity. I view the performance of Made of Night as the first stage towards exploring much more in terms of how technology and synaesthesia might work in harness.

The immersive sonic environment was created through the combination of the computational system, sound design, lighting design, and the dramaturgy. The resulting highly original piece of research provides a robust example of the successful utilization of multiple agencies from technical/digital techniques through to the analogue physical human form all packaged in a single theatrical performance. This performance received a standing ovation.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

At the time of writing, there is no job-family at my institution called 'ÄResearch Technicians', although in some projects Technicians can be paid from research funds. At a local level, I am not aware of Arts & Humanities technicians work being recognized as part of the REF submission, as such, my work does not provide accountability for public investment in research or provide benchmarking information, or establish reputational yardsticks for use in the higher education sector, nor for public information nor inform the selective of funding for research.

Ultimately this performance sets out to explore the potential of connections that can be made between technology and a performer as well as directing critical attention to the relationships to sound, physiological movement and the environment - this approach of practical exploration sits outside both the thinking of classical theatre and the realms of traditional scientific research.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 363

Applicant details

Submission category: H - Website Content

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Donnay, Michael

Organisation/University: University of London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Seized Books! Project explored a Customs and Excise raid on Gay's the Word bookshop (GTW) in 1984, with c.140 titles seized as 'obscene'. The project digitized the c. 120 of these titles held within the Haud Nominandum Collection at Senate House Library (SHL) and used both the cover art and content of the books to interrogate ideas of 'indecent', 'obscenity' and approaches to reading queer literature. Among the many activities of the project, a primary output was an online, digital exhibition using the digitized material from the collection and research from members of the project team. The website allows viewers to engage with the books, bibliographical research, and additional historical context in a dynamic environment - providing the opportunity to take their own journey through the material.

The project built on a long-standing relationship between GTW and SHL that grew out of a 2018 SHL exhibition *Queer Between the Covers*, which explored the context and validity of the 1984 raid and included a talk from Graham McKerrow, original member of the Defend GTW Campaign. McKerrow later wrote a chapter in an edited volume published by the University of London Press in 2021. The long-term nature of the partnership, as well as shared interest in marking the 40th anniversary of the 1984 raids, meant that the project team collaborated with staff from the bookshop throughout. This included launching the exhibition at a public event at GTW. Through the creation of the online exhibition, as well as accompanying workshops, training, and public engagement activities, the project was able to highlight an underexplored event in LGBTQ+ history, while showing the ongoing importance of GTW and print media to queer place-making in the UK.

The exhibition can be viewed at <https://www.london.ac.uk/seized-books>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As a locally important project focused on Bloomsbury's GTW bookshop, the project commemorated the historic (and traumatic) 1984 raids by HM Customs and Excise, putting them in a longer context of queer literary censorship and state intervention into queer and radical bookselling and book cultures.

The Seized Books! Research has at its heart the material culture of the seized books, and remains rooted in the library's collection and the evidence it provides for better understanding Operation Tiger, particularly as very little has been written about most of the titles. It is notable that this material could not be published as a traditional research output because the range and extent of material covered (captions for some 140 books running to c. 20,000 words, plus digitised covers of each) could not be published for copyright reasons and the financial cost of image permissions. The majority of the works are still within copyright, which limits the levels and modes of reproduction permissible, and required a cautious - and institutionally supported - approach (no pages from within the books were reproduced, for example). The online exhibition format allowed the team to make best use of the material within the copyright restrictions ('fair use'), foregrounding the books' materiality for an audience unable to visit the physical copies at SHL.

Further research was undertaken primarily using archival documents created within queer social

movements of the 1970s and 1980s, which necessitated critical consideration of often personal opinions. Many of these documents are fragmentary, so the research process required extensive synthesis of various sources. Through this research, the collection has been shown to have wider potential: it touches on queer publishing history in the USA and illuminates how queer literature was disseminated and read during the latter 20th century.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The project's primary outputs are the Seized Books! website and associated Omeka gallery; currently overlooked within research culture and evaluation approaches, they nevertheless led to measurable (local and global) public engagement and made a real impact on the lives of the people who engaged with the research they showcase. Working closely with the shop's staff meant that GTW marked the event in ways they were not otherwise planning to. People who engaged with this content (e.g., by commenting under social media posts), who were part of these historic events, had their life experiences recognised by an academic community as well as the LGBTQ+ communities of which they are part. Moreover, current GTW customers felt connected to these historic events on seeing digitised images of books that they had purchased second-hand from the shop; they have a new understanding of the significance of the material book in queer history. Participants in our workshops, which helped to develop our public tone of voice for exhibition content, noted that they were belatedly discovering aspects of their own queer history that had passed them by during the period under discussion (despite their involvement in the LGBTQ+ community). The project led to increased awareness of the events of Operation Tiger, not only among academic and community audiences but also within the media (e.g., Times Literary Supplement exhibition review). This close relationship with GTW, their audiences/customers and with former members of the Defend GTW Campaign team demonstrates the integrity and ethics practised by the project. The current manager of the shop stated that we 'did them proud'. These multifaceted relationships with key participants have longevity: plans are in place for the development of a musical based on this research, which again requires positive buy-in from those whose lives were altered by the events we are remembering and researching.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 371

Applicant details

Submission category: N - Research report for external body

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Armstrong, Sarah

Organisation/University: University of Glasgow

Nominating other (name): Mirza, Nughmana

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I (Sarah Armstrong, University of Glasgow) am nominating this report and lead researcher: 'Diversifying Justice: Revealing domestic abuse realities and viable help-seeking pathways for South Asian women in Scotland' by Nughmana Mirza and Lisa Bradley and Nic Dickson.

This report, commissioned by the Scottish Government, is an outstanding example of responsible research with a marginalised and invisibilised community in Scotland, that sheds new light on understanding gendered violence in non-White, Euronormative family structures. The report is the culmination of intensive engagement with South Asian women, in which the research team took the time to build relationships, hold a series of creative arts interventions and then carefully develop an analysis with the women they worked with. They also demonstrated huge tenacity in negotiating with Government to ensure they presented the stories of women in ways that conveyed a rich sense of their situations and personhood. They achieved this against pressure to remove uncomfortable details purportedly to minimise risk of disclosive information, but which would have decontextualised and homogenised the women and their lives.

The result is a report which offers important insights into gendered violence and South Asian women's experiences that challenges stereotypes of women lacking agency or family structures being monolithic and controlling.

Dr Mirza was a driving force in the research and focused on issues that might have been missed if the research had been done without anyone with links to the community. A key example of this is her analysis of how participants conceptualised justice, exploring women's views of 'divine justice' in a way that resisted reducing this to religious folly or giving up on achieving justice in their own lives. Instead, she developed a sense of the divine being connected to a present, moral sense of accountability that shaped women's healing from victimisation in ways that didn't depend on the state.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The rigour of this report is exemplary: its reflexivity and coverage of the positionality of each researcher is linked clearly to choices about research design and practice, and suggests why the high level of engagement with participants was achieved. A thorough and sensitive account of participants and their specific experiences and perspectives of domestic violence allows for a diverse picture of gendered violence in the context of South Asian families to emerge.

The rigour and findings of the report secure its significance. This should become a core reference point both methodologically and in terms of its findings. Methodologically, creative methods were designed and led by those with strong background in working this way - where in some cases it can come across as a superficial gimmick. The effectiveness and depth of this method is clear in how comprehensively the research process is documented. In terms of the report's findings, we gain new knowledge about how women think about and pursue justice, whether leaving or staying within relationships and affinal families where they suffered abuse. The findings dig into this, showing how women exercised agency even in constrained settings. The significance of the work therefore will be in providing a crucial point of reference for understanding violence experienced by South Asian women, but also should influence

gendered violence studies generally.

The report is already having impact in that the Scottish Government is developing priorities and approaches for addressing domestic violence in non-majority contexts, of which the South Asian community in Scotland is significant. Dr Mirza has been invited to participate in policy contexts to explain the implications of the research, and this also will be informing Government responses. Finally, there is impact in the process of this research, where the participants were given space to share not only experiences of trauma (the damage narratives that can position women as powerless and in need of saving) but also in their visions and strategies of justice, empowering them as their own saviours and experts in understanding what would restore them.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Research reports are generally under valued in an exercise fixated on peer reviewed journal articles as the gold standard (despite the many failures and citational biases known attaching to this mode of output). There will inevitably be pressure on the authors to produce a journal version - truncated, instrumentally reporting on findings - of this report. However, the length of this research report allows for careful, reflexive and illuminating attention to the ethical and inclusive approach of the research, and an extended and nuanced account of its findings. This is a hugely important resource for other researchers who want to see process fully documented so they can emulate this great practice. It is nearly the length of a monograph, which is valued by REF, but where methodological reflections, a powerful and beautiful strength of this work, often are minimised, in favour of the 'meat' of results.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7814-590X>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 372

Applicant details

Submission category: N - Research report for external body

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Graham, Zoe

Organisation/University: University of Bristol

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating on behalf of myself for the Hidden REF competition in recognition of my contributions to the Wireless Networks Market Research Insights Report (and other Insight Reports). As a Partnerships and Engagement Manager, my primary role typically involves fostering collaborations and managing stakeholder relationships. However, in this project, I took on additional responsibilities that extended well beyond my usual duties and comfort zone. Specifically, I conducted qualitative interviews, arranged and transcribed these interviews, and summarised the findings for inclusion in the final report.

Coming from an academic background in Film Studies, I never imagined being credited in a report so far removed from my original field of study, and history of work in largely operational and professional services roles.

I should recognise I was credited for the work for which I am grateful but wanted to mention this in this space to shine a light on the often overlooked work and contributions of non-academic professionals in research, particularly those who bridge the gap between academia and industry or play supporting roles (for instance I, and other colleagues, also act as secretariats for various expert working groups across UKTIN in addition to our regular roles). My work on this report not only contributed to a deeper understanding of the UK's telecoms sector but also exemplifies the diverse skill sets required for successful research projects; in this case stakeholder management and ability to engage academic colleagues whilst working to deadlines.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This report offers a comprehensive, high-level overview of the research, development, and innovation activities occurring within wireless networking technologies across the UK telecoms sector. My contributions were pivotal in gathering the insights necessary to shape the report, ensuring that it accurately reflected the current landscape of wireless networking research and development from an academic standpoint. Despite the significance of this work, roles like mine often go unrecognised in traditional research evaluations, which tend to prioritise academic publications and more conventional research outputs.

UKTIN's Market Research Insights Reports are a key resource for understanding the current state of wireless networking technologies in the UK telecoms sector, offering non-technical insights into ongoing research and innovation, and ultimately to government. My role was crucial in gathering and analysing qualitative data through interviews with key stakeholders. This data provided valuable context and nuance, enriching the report's overall analysis. By translating complex research into accessible insights, the report facilitates knowledge exchange and supports informed decision-making in the future of the telecoms industry. This work underscores the importance of qualitative research in complementing technical analyses and highlights the significant impact that non-academic professionals can have on research projects.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

In traditional research evaluations, contributions from non-academic professionals like myself often go unrecognised. While my primary role is in partnerships and engagement, my work on this report was essential to its success but falls outside typical research metrics.

This lack of general recognition reflects a broader issue within the research community, where vital contributions that don't fit traditional academic roles are often invisible, from larger undertakings such as this, to day-to-day support provided by administrators and other professionals.

My nomination aims to shine a light on these hidden contributions, advocating for a more inclusive and equitable approach to research evaluation that values all forms of input and recognises them too.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: DSIT

Entry: 377

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Baumeister, Hannah

Organisation/University: Liverpool John Moores University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Our multi-disciplinary, multi-sector team created a comic to teach teenagers in UK secondary schools about forced marriage. The project was funded by the AHRC (AH/X004325/1).

Our comic tells stories about different types, causes and consequences of forced marriage, focusing on possibilities for resistance and intervention. They are informed by our expertise as researchers and professionals working on forced marriage, relationship and secondary education, literature and comic art, and by survivors' and teenagers' relationships experiences. The team included myself, Emma Brown, Alex Carabine, Catherine Kirk, Helen McCabe, Karma Nirvana, Savera UK, and the students and staff at Nottingham Girls' Academy and Childwall Sports and Science Academy.

We agreed that the researchers would script the comic and the team would provide feedback to ensure that stories are realistic, sensitive, nuanced, and age-appropriate. E.g., stories changed based on discussions about differences between preventative and crisis point interventions.

Emma then drew the comic, continuously incorporating feedback. E.g., she found a middle ground between cartoon style and more realistic images that was well received.

We used the comic in two trial sessions with Year 8-9 students. The results of pre- and post-session self-assessment questionnaires with five-point rating scale and open-ended questions and our observations and discussions with students demonstrate that the comic is an effective tool to improve students' understanding of forced marriage (mean scores: 3.05/3.88) and increase their likelihood to raise awareness (mean scores: 3.22/3.78) and help those at risk or already experiencing it (mean scores: 4/4.15). E.g., students understood that forced marriage 'can happen to anyone' and suggested to 'ask [the person] if there are any concerns' and 'recommend different helplines' to support them. After the trial sessions, we incorporated student feedback to improve the comic. E.g., we clarified that a protagonist is not yet married to the person chosen for her.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Forced marriages occur when one or both spouses do not or cannot (legally) consent, or have been pressured to 'consent'. Around 500 people asked the UK Forced Marriage Unit for advice in 2023. The UK Government criminalised the practice and created civil legal remedies. In addition, the Government, anti-forced marriage organisations, researchers and affected communities have highlighted the importance of education to prevent and end forced marriage.

We responded to this call for (better) forced marriage education by creating the comic 'I choose' and a guide that explains how it can be used as a teaching tool.

Comics are an accessible, inclusive and engaging medium to tell nuanced and sensitive stories about difficult experiences. They challenge readers to identify, understand and confront injustice, and to act for a better world.

Our findings demonstrate that a better understanding of injustices like forced marriage contributes to prevention. It creates communities of care who know that forced marriage is illegal but that it 'can [still] happen to anyone' and that 'people might be too scared to admit that they don't want to get married' and 'will not always openly disagree'. In addition to knowing how to spot the signs, they know how to respond and intervene, for example by 'ask[ing] [the person] if there are any concerns', 'help[ing] [them] to get confident enough to explain 'why they don't want [to get married]', and to 'recommend[ing] different helplines'.

Creating this impact would have been impossible without engagement with the project partners. The researchers are experts in forced marriage, law, literature and higher education. However, we lack the first-hand experience and frontline supporters' understanding of forced marriage, experiential knowledge of and access to secondary and relationship education, Gen Alpha experiences of relationships, and artistic skills of the project partners. Our collaboration was essential to create a comic that is realistic, sensitive, nuanced, and age-appropriate. Through our collaboration, project partners gained experience of working on academic research projects and developing educational materials that they are now using in their own work and/or can add to their CV.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The current focus of public engagement and research impact appears to be on international collaboration with 'the big shots' to achieve wide-reaching policy impact. Projects like ours, with an intentional focus on the local, inclusion of 'the new kids on the block' and grassroots social change remain overlooked/hidden. Yet, it allows for deep and continuous public engagement that is genuinely beneficial to and impactful for all project team members. E.g., it made it possible for us to keep in very regular online and/or in-person contact, build flat hierarchies, engage with each other freely with an open mind, and approach and shape the project in a way that worked for us and was useful to our stakeholders. Having said that, the project has the potential to achieve a wider reach. The comic and educator guide are available online for free. Access data shows that there is a global interest in the materials. Access will be facilitated further through the forthcoming French translations of the comic and educator guide. The translation is produced by a new project partner, Association Voix de Femmes, who will use it in their anti-forced marriage work in France.

Furthermore, public engagement in and creative approaches to legal research are often seen as frivolous and therefore overlooked/hidden. However, both are crucial to dismantle the unrealistic legal silo, improve people's understandings of and experiences with the law and create a more just world.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8470-7585>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: AHRC follow-on funding for impact and engagement (AH/X004325/1)

Entry: 383

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Sherwood, James

Organisation/University: University of York

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I have developed a web-based tool to allow users to understand the environmental sustainability of their diet (please access it at <https://jamesrsherwood.github.io/fsnc/>). I designed this tool to make my research accessible to non-specialists with an interest in sustainability. The user can select a single food item, or choose multiple foods to create a meal. Climate change impact, land use, and freshwater use across the food supply chain is included in the assessment. The calculation is based on my research paper published in February of this year (<https://doi.org/10.1002/fft2.371>). The user is provided with a visual representation of the sustainability score, derived from nutrition, environmental impact (from farm to fork), demand for food, and the ability of the Earth to sustain agricultural practices (which is constrained by land availability, the effects of climate change, etc.). With this tool I am able to communicate sustainability science to a wider audience to inform them and influence their decision making as consumers. I judge the success of my work on how useful it is to others. By producing fun tools to supplement research articles, I can reach out to difference audiences. I use this tool in workshops, talks, and open day events.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The food sector has a very large environmental impact, which is increasing annually. It is imperative that action is taken to reduce greenhouse gas emissions, land use, water use, and fertiliser use in agriculture before irreparable damage is done to the environment that impairs future food production. This can partly be achieved with technological advances, but a much larger benefit would come from consumer action. Less food waste and less meat consumption are required to reduce the environmental impact of food production to sustainable levels. The sustainability of agricultural practices is widely studied at the national and international level. However, it has never been clear to individuals how to act sustainably when it comes to food choices. For instance, contrary to common belief, eating local produce has a very small effect on greenhouse gas emissions because the vast majority of the climate change impact happens on the farm, not in transport. Also, with previous methods it was not possible to definitively calculate the sustainability of foods, we could only say one food is better than another without knowing if either is actually sustainable. My research has now introduced a new method of calculating the 'absolute sustainability' of food called 'Performance-weighted Environmental Sustainability' (PwES). It is a quantitative assessment that determines an appropriate environmental impact for the amount of nutrition (energy, protein, fibre, vitamins and minerals) in a food compared to the actual impact. If the PwES score is less than 1, the food is sustainable with respect to that impact category (I have focused on climate change, water use, and land use). The web app (<https://jamesrsherwood.github.io/fsnc/>) now allows people to interpret the environmental impact of their diet without having to understand the underlying theory or equations. It is important that consumers can understand what a sustainable diet is, and challenge assumptions. What I have found is that bread and vegetables are excellent sources of sustainable nutrition, while red meat has such a high climate change impact it is not possible to eat it regularly as part of an environmentally sustainable diet.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

I cannot get recognition for this work for a couple of reasons. Firstly, I am a chemist working in a chemistry department, not an environmental scientist. I have a strong interest in sustainability and so I developed the 'Performance-weighted Environmental Sustainability' metric in my own time (initially during the COVID lockdowns when I could not enter the labs). This is not chemistry and so it is not suitable for a REF submission from the department of chemistry. Secondly, due to my non-academic, research-only contract, I have never been invited to submit my research in REF assessments. I am fortunate that my boss lets me pursue my interest in other areas of research and publish them independently of her. However, this means my work 'falls through the net' because there are no REF-eligible academics on the author list.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-5431-2032

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 389

Applicant details

Submission category: 10 - Campaigns

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bianchi, Lynne

Organisation/University: SEERIH, University of Manchester

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Great Science Share for Schools (GSSfS) is a campaign run by the Science & Engineering Education Research and Innovation Hub (SEERIH) within The University of Manchester. Its aim is to inspire and engage children in scientific discovery, by asking, investigating and sharing a scientific question they care about. The SEERIH are a specialist unit whose work focuses on the upskilling of teachers of Science, Technology, Engineering and Computing of 5-14 years. GSSfS has a diverse programme of professional learning for teachers, and campaigns that enable pupils to have high-quality experiences in these disciplines. GSSfS's reach and impact of the pupil events and teacher professional learning has grown exponentially in size importance and overall impact over the past decade, now achieving UNESCO National Patronage and international spread.

The GSSfS campaign is open to everyone and can take place in any educational setting, across the world, placing young people at the heart of the communication of science to each other.

3 simple values provide the foundations to all campaign activity:

• Learner-focused science communication

• Inclusive and non-competitive engagement

• Promotes collaboration on many levels

The GSSfS concept is simple and transferable. Young people decide on a scientific question they care about, either by drawing on learning taking place in their own schools and environments or using the stimulus resources provided by the campaign team. The campaign supports and upskills teachers to enhance opportunities for work scientifically in which young people take ownership. The key focus is on sharing learning with new audiences, which may include peers of same or different age groups in the same school or in cluster schools locally. Other audiences include parents/families, community industry partners and STEM professionals, as well as MPs and dignitaries.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Science lessons to children are invaluable. As well as developing skills and increasing vocabulary, they create an environment where children are able to question, challenge and discover the world around them. Unfortunately, there are continued issues with the status and profile of science education in primary schools and primary teachers often lack confidence and skills in science, which means that the sequencing of the curriculum is not always sensible, and misconceptions are not corrected. Recent policy and research reports, such as the '10 Key Issues in Children's Learning in Primary Science in England' (Bianchi et al, 2021) identify that children:

- lack autonomy and independence in learning science
- are engaged in prescriptive practical work that lacks purpose
- are not encouraged to use their own curiosity, scientific interests and questions in learning science.

GSSfS is an inclusive, free, campaign that supports all teachers and educators to raise the profile of science in schools and communities, recognising the value of science in primary education. GSSfS models best practice through publication of teacher resources, professional development and events across the UK. This is unique in the sector in doing this, being the only campaign of its kind to operate at scale.

Since launch, GSSfS has shown significant reach as can be seen in the infographic. For the year of

2023-24, registration figures were as follows:

3,534 schools (477 in Greater Manchester, 3,057 schools UK and internationally)

Of these 50% were in areas of high socioeconomic deprivation (for Greater Manchester the figure was 70%)

673,555 pupils (104,025 in Greater Manchester; 569,530 pupils across the UK and internationally)

161 international schools and institutions (16,650 pupils) across 36 countries with international reach into Argentina, Australia, Belgium, Botswana, Brazil, Bulgaria, China, Cyprus, Finland, France, Hungary, India, Ireland, Italy, Malaysia, Mexico, Montenegro, Netherlands, New Zealand, Nigeria, Norway, Pakistan, Peru, Philippines, Portugal, Singapore, South Africa, South Korea, Spain, Switzerland, Thailand, Tunisia, Turkey, United Arab Emirates, USA and Vietnam.

Evaluation has evidenced that GSSfS leads to:

• more time for science learning in school and at home

• more open-ended opportunities led by young people asking, investigating and communicating their own scientific questions. Teachers support pupils in developing and building their questions and shaping the experience in order that it is of the highest quality.

• more involvement from different audiences (parents/families, community industry partners, MPs and dignitaries who may not traditionally engage with science learning

• more focus on real-world issues aligned to global sustainability within a curriculum, mainstream context. Achieved by considering questions related to the global sustainability goals inherent in all GSSfS Guided Enquiries.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Over the years we have explored the potential of GSSfS becoming a REF impact case study, however various challenges mean that this hasn't come to fruition. There is significant support for the campaign, however it has been increasingly evident that there isn't a strong enough match to any REF Units of Assessment within the Faculty of Science & Engineering where SEERIH sits. Its strong focus on educating teachers and young people steers this to other Faculties, however having explored this avenue, it is apparent that GSSfS also sits outside clearly defined research themes and strands, developed and curated over many years in education.

GSSfS is research informed and also informs policy reports and close-to-practice scholarly outputs, published by Prof Lynne Bianchi and the SEERIH team. These bear significant weight in the Science Education sector, with citations from key educational bodies, including OFSTED (Office for Standards in Education, Children's Services and Skills) and the Education Endowment Foundation. Additionally, SEERIH-advised Education Endowment Foundation's 2023 'Systematic Review on Primary Science' also highlighted the need for children to have links to real-world contexts.

Within the University GSSfS also provides the largest data return for the Faculty and University for enhancing social inclusion at pre-14 level. Annual impact is reported via: Research England's Knowledge Exchange Framework (Public Engagement); UoM's statutory return to the Office for Students on Widening Participation; UoM Access & Participation Plan Monitoring Report (T16b_16 (Access)). GSSfS also contributed to success for UoM's Times Higher Education Impact Rankings. The UoM Higher Education Access Tracker contextualises impact stating: GSSfS data is more than double the number of participants from the rest of our activities (including partnership activities) combined. Despite such success, it is understandable, yet challenging that we find GSSfS unable to play a fuller role in REF. We consider this to be an ideal example for a Hidden REF application.

Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5064-6972>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 390

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bianchi, Lynne

Organisation/University: SEERIH, University of Manchester

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

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• more focus on real-world issues aligned to global sustainability within a curriculum, mainstream context. Achieved by considering questions related to the global sustainability goals inherent in all GSSfS Guided Enquiries.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

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Further details

ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5064-6972>

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 394

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bayyat, Adnan

Organisation/University: niversity of Salford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The "Human-Tech-Books" project was designed to make academic research more accessible and engaging to non-academic audiences during key events including We Invented the Weekend (WITW) festival and the Festival of Social Science (FoSS). The project comprised of two components: 1. Costumes with integrated technologies (iPads & QR codes) crocheted by an academic from compostable clingfilm supplied by Wrapmaster, an industry partner; 2. The digital gamification of complex Salford-authored business research and website development providing visitors a variety of interactive activities, including micro-CPD courses, crosswords, word searches, and AI-generated artwork. QR codes on the costumes link to the interactive activities, allowing users to explore the research content on their mobile devices.

URL: <https://salfordbusiness.net/>

https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=9R5RoG3s_Xo

The project addresses the barriers of academic jargon and paywalls that often limit public access to scholarly work. By transforming academic papers into visually appealing and interactive experiences, Human-Tech-Books fosters greater public accessibility and understanding of business research.

Additionally, the project emphasizes sustainability, with the compostable clingfilm costumes and digital content designed for reuse in future exhibitions and educational settings as knowledge portals.

Key contributors to the project include Dr. Gordon Fletcher, Dr. Adnan Bayyat, and Saomai Vu Khan, students and industry partners. Their combined efforts resulted in a unique transdisciplinary blend of fashion, technology, education, and industry collaboration that pushes the boundaries of traditional academic research and dissemination.

Human-Tech-Books is significant because it reimagines how academic research can be shared, making it accessible and enjoyable for a broader audience. However, it is often overlooked in current research culture and evaluation because it falls outside the conventional metrics used to assess academic impact.

The project's focus on public engagement and innovative dissemination methods challenges the traditional norms of academic research evaluation, highlighting the need for broader criteria that recognise diverse and creative approaches to knowledge sharing.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The "Human-Tech-Books" project represents a groundbreaking approach to academic research dissemination, making it both accessible and engaging for non-academic audiences. Its significance lies in its ability to bridge the gap between scholarly research and public engagement, addressing a critical need in the academic community. Traditional academic papers are often inaccessible to the general public due to the specialized language and paywalls that restrict access. Human-Tech-Books challenges this norm by transforming complex academic content into interactive, user-friendly experiences that appeal to a wide audience.

At the core of this project is the innovative use of generative AI, which translates Salford-authored research papers into various interactive formats. These include micro-CPDs, crosswords, word searches, and augmented reality content, all of which are accessible through QR codes displayed on dynamic costumes at the We Invented the Weekend Festival. This approach not only makes academic research

more digestible but also adds an element of fun and creativity, thereby increasing public interest in and understanding of scholarly work.

The project's importance is further underscored by its emphasis on sustainability and reusability. The costumes and digital content are designed to be reused in future exhibitions, ensuring that the impact of Human-Tech-Books extends beyond a single event. This forward-thinking approach demonstrates a commitment to long-term public engagement and the continuous dissemination of research in innovative ways.

Moreover, Human-Tech-Books is a pioneering example of how academia can evolve to meet the needs of a 21st-century audience. By blending fashion, technology, and education, the project offers a novel way of sharing knowledge that goes beyond the traditional classroom or academic journal. It reflects a broader vision of how research can be made relevant and accessible to everyone, not just those within the academic community.

In a time when public trust in academia is increasingly important, Human-Tech-Books serves as a model for how academic institutions can engage with the public in meaningful and impactful ways. The project's focus on creativity, interactivity, and accessibility positions it as a significant contribution to the future of academic research dissemination.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The "Human-Tech-Books" project, despite its innovation and impact, is often overlooked in the current research culture and evaluation systems due to its non-traditional nature. In academia, the value of research is typically measured by conventional metrics such as publication in high-impact journals, citation counts, and research funding. These metrics prioritize outputs that cater to scholarly audiences and often fail to recognize the importance of public engagement and innovative dissemination methods. Human-Tech-Books challenges these traditional norms by focusing on making academic research accessible to a broader audience through interactive and creative formats. This focus on public engagement, however, is not always valued or recognized in traditional academic evaluations. The project's use of generative AI to create micro-CPDs, crosswords, and augmented reality content from research papers does not fit neatly into the conventional categories of academic output. As a result, the project may be dismissed as peripheral or supplementary rather than as a significant contribution to the research community.

Furthermore, the project's reliance on fashion and technology as mediums for dissemination is another factor that contributes to its being overlooked. In the academic world, these mediums are often seen as outside the core activities of research. The blending of fashion and technology with academic content is a novel approach that defies the traditional boundaries of academic research, making it harder for the project to be recognized within the existing evaluation frameworks.

Additionally, the impact of Human-Tech-Books is primarily measured through public engagement and feedback rather than traditional academic metrics. This focus on real-world impact and public understanding is crucial for the future of academia, yet it remains undervalued in a system that prioritizes scholarly recognition over societal impact. The project's emphasis on sustainability and reusability, while forward-thinking, also falls outside the conventional measures of academic success, which are often short-term and publication-focused.

In summary, the innovative and public-focused nature of Human-Tech-Books places it outside the mainstream of academic evaluation. It challenges the traditional metrics used to assess research impact and highlights the need for broader criteria that recognize the value of creative, interactive, and public-engagement-oriented projects. By expanding the definition of research excellence to include such non-traditional outputs, academia can better reflect the diverse ways in which knowledge is generated, shared, and applied in the modern world.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: ,Äç Dr. Gordon Fletcher (Associate Dean for Research)

,Äç Dr. Adnan Bayyat (Knowledge Exchange Fellow and Garment Designer)

,Äç Saomai Vu Khan (Graduate Researcher)

,Äç Hannah Day (BA Fashion Business and Promotion Student)

,Ä¸ Tom Kelly (Photography Student)

,Ä¸ Deborah Smailes (MA Programme Leader)

,Ä¸ Wrapmaster Representatives: Libby Coe and Mike Lewis

,Ä¸ WITweekend Festival Organisers

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 403

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Blake, Holly

Organisation/University: University of Nottingham

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Within 3 weeks of the outbreak of the COVID-19 pandemic, we developed a digital package for health and care workers including 110 pages of evidence-based guidance, support and signposting relating to mitigating the psychological impacts of the pandemic. The package outlines the actions that team leaders can take to provide psychologically safe spaces for staff, together with guidance on communication and reducing social stigma, peer and family support, signposting others through psychological first aid, self-care strategies (e.g., rest, work breaks, sleep, shift work, fatigue, healthy lifestyle behaviours), and managing emotions (e.g., moral injury, coping, guilt, grief, fear, anxiety, depression, preventing burnout and psychological trauma). The e-package includes advice from experts in mental wellbeing as well as those with direct pandemic experiences from the frontline, as well as signposting to public mental health guidance. The most important messages are the normalisation of psychological responses during a crisis, and encouragement of self-care and help-seeking behaviour.

The package was developed by a psychologist and a mental health researcher, with technical support from a Digital Marketing Team. We followed rigorous Agile methodology involving 162 people with relevant subject or healthcare expertise. This took a 3-step approach to establish the need and focus through public involvement activities (n=97), develop content with expert peer review (n=10), and conduct an evaluation (n=55) which confirmed relevance, usability and utility. Assessment of implementation qualities indicated that the package was perceived to be usable, practical, low cost and low burden by health and care workers.

This was a timely digital intervention for health and care workers, which forms the basis of research that is the most highly cited in its field and generated impact. It is free and open access and has been highly accessed globally; 17,633 users within the first 7 days and >77,000 users within 12 months.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The COVID-19 pandemic spread rapidly around the world and led to over 7 million deaths. The impact on health and care workers across the globe was unprecedented. In the context of a global workforce shortage in the sector, there were population declines in physical and mental health, huge pressures on service provision, and dramatic impacts on access to care. Health and care workers worldwide, exposed to the virus themselves on the frontline, experienced significant psychological distress, including anxiety, burnout and post-traumatic stress (e.g., [1]).

Yet, there were few (if any) supportive interventions at that time. For context, the overall costs of mental ill-health equate to double the NHS's entire budget in England (~£153bn) and mental ill-health is the leading cause of NHS sickness absence. Urgent action was needed.

At the University of Nottingham, we produced the first digital support package, globally, to mitigate the psychological impact of COVID-19 on healthcare workers, within 3 weeks of UK outbreak (in March 2020) [2]. Through evidence-based guidance and signposting, the intention was to normalise psychological responses during a crisis and encourage self-care and help-seeking behaviour. The e-package content was perceived to be meaningful and valuable to healthcare workers [3] and

healthcare trainees [4] around the world. It was adapted by the Royal College of Nursing for pandemic leadership training during the early stages of the pandemic. The timeliness of this digital package was evident in that it was accessed by >77,000 health and care workers within the first 12 months. It is included as a case example of best practice in a book published by Elsevier during the pandemic called 'Health and Wellbeing at Work for Nurses and Midwives' [5]. Our intervention was subsequently ranked in two bibliometric analyses [6,7] as the most influential digital innovation for supporting psychological wellbeing in the sector.

[1] Couper, K., & Blake, H. et al. The impact of COVID-19 on the wellbeing of the UK nursing and midwifery workforce during the first pandemic wave. *IJNS*, 2022; 127.

[2] Blake, H., Bermingham, F. Psychological Wellbeing for Healthcare Workers: Mitigating the Impact of COVID-19. 2020. https://www.nottingham.ac.uk/toolkits/play_22794. The University of Nottingham, 02 April 2020. Last updated 18 June 2020 (update will occur in Autumn 2024).

[3] Blake, H., et al. Mitigating the Psychological Impact of COVID-19 on Healthcare Workers: A Digital Learning Package. *IJERPH*, 2020; 17; 9: 2997.

[4] Blake, H., et al. Psychological Impacts of COVID-19 on Healthcare Trainees and Perceptions towards a Digital Wellbeing Support Package. *IJERPH*, 2021; 18; 20: 10647.

[5] Blake, H., Stacey, G. Health and Wellbeing at Work for Nurses and Midwives. Elsevier. Available at: <http://shop.elsevier.com/books/health-and-wellbeing-at-work-for-nurses-and-midwives/blake/978-0-323-88053-4>.

[6] Ansari, Y., et al. Modeling Socio-Economic Consequences of COVID-19: Evidence From Bibliometric Analysis. *Front. Environ. Sci.*, 2022, 10.

[7] Armaou, M., et al. Evolution of Primary Research Studies in Digital Interventions for Mental Well-Being Promotion from 2004 to 2023: Bibliometric Analysis of Studies on the Web of Science. *IJERPH*, 2024; 21: 375.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

As a digital resource this could not be returned in REF2021 as an 'output'. This was a rapid contribution to the pandemic response. We did not receive research funding and relied on the support of a technician to upload content to Xerte (open-source software for authoring learning objects) and 162 people who contributed their time as part of a rigorous development and evaluation process, attending stakeholder consultations, peer reviewing content and technical presentation or completing evaluation surveys.

The resource was released to the health and care workforce when no other pandemic-specific psychological wellbeing interventions existed. While rigorously developed and evaluated, there was no time or funding to conduct a multicentre randomised controlled trial of effectiveness that would be required to generate a 3/4* output for REF in our discipline area. Yet the wide reach and high access demonstrate its value to health and care workers at a critical time.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0003-3080-2306

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Fiona Bermingham (co-author of the package with Holly Blake), Mental health researcher, University of Leicester (at the time of the work being conducted)

Richard Kish (technical support), Communications Coordinator, School of Medicine, University of Nottingham

162 contributors to development and research processes were health and care workers, healthcare trainees, and technologists or researchers with interest in digital innovations (not named individually as they were participants in the methodology but they are acknowledged in our evaluation paper).

Funding acknowledgements: No external funding - time supported by the University of Nottingham as COVID-19 response

Entry: 405

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Costa Gomes, Beatriz

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating myself for the Public Engagement award. I have been a host of The Turing Podcast (which has over a thousand constant listeners per episode), where we disseminate AI research and regulations for a more general audience. Guests have included anything from a Lord from the House of Lords to PhD students. Furthermore, I've been presenting about science to general audiences, particularly with school children, through activities such as I'm A Scientist and Science Live!

I am one of the people behind a format called Imagined Futures, where scientists creatively describe what the future looks like decades from now. It was a successful panel at AIUK (conference) and Pint of Science. This will now become a podcast series and will be again re-hashed for other conferences. The format allows for a shift in the conversation surrounding AI, as the perspective is "We are from the future. The actions you did in 2024 led to X" rather than the other way around.

I've been moderator and chair of more public engagement sessions than I can count, and including lectures at the Royal Institution, conference stages and scientific and scientific lives panels.

Finally, I've been training other scientists (and particularly students) how to present their science in a meaningful way for general audiences.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

As a long-term host of the Turing Podcast, my episodes have reached thousands of listeners and they dissect and expand on complicated science issues in a more general way. Furthermore, the Imagined Futures session is an innovative and enthusiastic new approach to discussing the future of science with the general audience, which has been proven a success with both scientific (conference) and general (Pint of Science) audiences.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The work has been overlooked as only my research outputs tend to be the important bullet points in my career. The dissemination of information is not necessarily a skill that tends to be appreciated, and such, traditional roles don't consider my eclectic science communication and public engagement career to be relevant.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 407

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Coles, Alf

Organisation/University: University of Bristol

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I would like to submit, for consideration, the immersive "Living Tree Mirror Maze" installation, which was at The Egg Theatre, Bath in the summer of 2022 (17th June to 3rd July). The installation was a collaboration between myself (a mathematics educator), three artists and an architecture firm, in the context of the annual "Forest of Imagination" event which takes place in Bath.

Part of my own research involves work on the primary mathematics curriculum and this research formed part of an Impact Case Study for REF2021. In essence, I advocate for a mathematics curriculum in which learners can experience mathematics as a communal, material and vibrant subject - a subject about which students can ask questions. My involvement in the "Living Tree Mirror Maze" was the design and implementation of the mirror maze aspect, where the aim was to embody an approach to learning mathematics begins with provocations that elicit students' questions. In other words, the "Living Tree Mirror Maze" was an opportunity for the implications of my research to be experienced by the people about whom the research is about - i.e., primary age children, as well as teachers, parents, carers and other adults. The mirror maze aspect involved entering immersive mirrored spaces based on a triangle, square and pentagon, and being invited to attend to the similarities and differences in the experiences.

Many schools brought classes to The Egg to spend time with the installation and there were days when it was open to the public. Families and others, local and visitors, came to the exhibition. For the schools, these were opportunities for teachers to observe their children, in the installation space, acting in ways which had a sophistication that may not always be visible in the classroom.

For a case study of the work see: https://www.doc.mode.unibo.it/sites/default/files/documentazione3_scheda/FOI-LivingTreeMirrorMazeCaseStudyFinal_compressed.pdf

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The "Living Tree Mirror Maze" installation became a locally important event. Over 400 visitors a day attended when it was open to the public and several schools visited every other day it was up. However, what was most striking was the quality of engagement of the children. Our documentation (see case study link, above) provides evidence of some of the statements made by children as they encountered the installation.

For instance, when inside one of the mirror spaces (and able to see many, many copies of themselves) one child asked "which one is the real me?". This question is a profound one and can be interpreted, of course, in many ways. There is a mathematical significance to the question as it relates to the notion that, in a space of reflections, there might be a transformation which does nothing - that leaves you as you were "the real me". The question therefore raises the notion of what is an "identity transformation" and this is a question that could be pursued in the classroom. This one example (and there are many others) shows how children are, indeed, able to ask meaningful and deep mathematical questions, arising from provocations and prompts.

I believe a strength of this submission is its originality and creativity. Through working with a team of

artists and architects, the space created was quite arresting - combining sight, sound, smell and touch. Our documentation indicates many "gasps" as students first entered the space. The installation involved a juxtaposition of a "natural" habitat (a forest literally transported into the theatre space) and a more "conceptual" set of mirror spaces. The children enjoyed and made connections between these elements.

The relevance of the work was in evidence through the engagement of participants. The mirrors in the forest, both literally and metaphorically, provoked reflections on the human relationship with the living world - a world we are part of and yet, for many of us, feel separated from. Ideas of infinity and pattern were heard and some children wanted to introduce their own mirror into the mirror space (which we were able to provide) to explore its effects - exhibiting an agency in relation to mathematics often missing from classroom practice.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Through engaging the public in an immersive experience, this submission is not text based and, although we do have an evaluation booklet (see link above) there was no journal submission and this booklet would not be acceptable as a REF publication. Equally, the significance of the submission was in the experience, not the documentation. The public are left with their own memories of their participation and there is no way to quantify the impact of these memories (in the short, and especially the long term). And yet the work was both based in (and inspired by) research and offered visitors an experience of that research (rather than a description of it), that was palpably effective.

Our documentation of responses to the installation indicate that it occasioned reflexivity - also, something not particularly valued in typical REF criteria. Visitors saw themselves (again, both literally and metaphorically) in many different ways and were invited to reflect on what they noticed. The triangle, square and pentagon mirror spaces produce quite different kinds of symmetrical pattern on the floor and thinking about the similarities and differences has the potential to lead to mathematically significant insights.

Another impact of this submission that is hidden from current evaluation approaches to research was the effect on teachers, of seeing their classes engaging mathematically in a space, without the need for learning objectives or success criteria. In other words, the installation offered an antidote to many primary school classroom practices and offered an image of how education could be different - an education that has the potential to follow children's fascinations. Many of the schools who visited have an on-going relationship with "Forest of Imagination" (who organised the space for the installation) and we know that several of them followed up the visit with work in class.

In essence, because this submission was performative, it does not fit with the REF criteria. And yet, by instantiating research findings, the installation offered the potential for the kinds of direct insight and new awareness, for participants, that can be hard to gain through engaging in text alone.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-7301-409X

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Penny Hay, Bath Spa University, 0000-0001-8320-7418, Professor of Imagination.

Penny curated the whole Forest of Imagination event, of which this was a part, and facilitated the conversations across all the contributors to "Living Tree Mirror Maze".

Funding acknowledgements: The work was supported by FCB Studios and Forest of the Imagination

Entry: 408

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Andersen, Claire
Organisation/University: University Of Dundee
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Guiding Schools to Improved Performance by using a Data Envelopment Analysis approach, aims to improve standards in Scottish primary and secondary education by producing a toolkit that uses data from the National Improvement Framework Interactive Evidence Report to evaluate school performance. This Framework is a plan for primary and secondary education that is published by the Scottish Government and serves as the single, definitive plan to improve education. Currently, while the Interactive Evidence Report generates data on key drivers of improvement, it lacks an in-depth analysis necessary to drive substantive changes in how the educational system operates. The objective of this study is to explore how the Framework influences education in Scotland, collaborating closely with school managers and teachers. We will create an aggregated educational target index based on data from the Interactive Evidence Report at a local authority level, and on data that we will gather at a school level. The NIFIER data currently publishes data about each of the key driver/priority for individual schools and local education authorities. This study has an alternative approach and will apply a model of efficiency that can aggregate all the key drivers and priorities together to create individualised results for each school and the local education authority. The model will automatically find areas of best practice and areas for improvement. We will interview school managers to understand how the Framework is integrated into school practices and use a questionnaire to understand teachers' perceptions of the Framework. Both sources of information gathered will be used to inform an educational improvement index. To prevent cross-comparisons or league table type rankings, our results will be accessible through a Power BI toolkit, including a user-friendly individualised and anonymised dashboard for identifying areas of best practice and targeted areas for improvement.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The results from the model will have wide-ranging impacts on public engagement. There are 32 local authorities in Scotland and presently there are 5,052 schools in total. From this total, 2001 are primary schools and 357 are secondary schools. In 2022 there were estimated to have been over 798,000 pupils attending schools in Scotland, with primary school students numbering 388,920 and 309,133 being secondary school pupils. Currently there are 54,000 classroom teachers in Scotland. Schools will be selected to ensure a balanced comparison between urban and rural, socio-economically advantaged and disadvantaged, small and large schools at both primary and secondary level. A combination of this data and stakeholder engagement will provide policymakers with new evidence to guide schools in improving performance, impacting all local schools and improving attainment and performance outcomes within Scottish education. For policymakers, DEA provides a robust tool for evaluating the impact of educational policies and funding decisions. By understanding which schools use resources most efficiently, policymakers can replicate these models on a broader scale, driving system-wide improvements.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

In the first stage of the project, we will use the Data Envelopment Analysis on the data currently available in the Interactive Evidence Report at a local authority level. Although a few studies have been published that examine the UK educational efficiency, these are based on the English curriculum (such as Bradley et al., 2001). This project will be the first study to examine the educational efficiency in Scotland. One of

the main advantages that makes Data Envelopment Analysis the appropriate technique for this project is that its efficiency estimate is a radial improvement factor, which means that it yields specific targets that can be used by the schools that lack in terms of performance to improve and reach the best-performing schools which serve as role models. However, there is a possibility that education stakeholders are apprehensive about the results being interpreted as a league table ranking system which may contribute to being overlooked. However, to address this assumption, essentially, this target-setting framework, which will be presented in the form of an easy-to-read and anonymised dashboard on Microsoft Power BI, will provide the means to better understand the data available by the National Improvement Framework. This will be particularly useful for the Scottish Office, local authorities, and schools.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 409

Applicant details

Submission category: M - Performance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Doran, Heather

Organisation/University: Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science, University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Evidence Chamber exemplifies an innovative approach to public engagement, integrating immersive performance with rigorous research to address the complexities of forensic science in the criminal justice system. Established in 2019, it has engaged over 700 participants, in small jury-sized groups. This project is significant because it tackles the critical challenge in forensic science of conveying complex and uncertain scientific information to non-specialist audiences such as jury members.

Through a combination of videos and prompts participants become the jury in a simulated fictional trial. The creative process involved academics, public engagement professionals, the public and members from the criminal justice system with ex-theatre production company Fast Familiar. The project has not only enhanced public understanding of forensic science but has also provided valuable data on how different audiences interpret expert testimony. This data has informed further research, including a Master's project exploring the use of science comics as tools for explaining complex scientific information.

In 2023 and 2024 The Evidence Chamber expanded its reach, engaging diverse audiences, including school pupils and community groups in low-income areas. The project has been showcased at prestigious events like the University of Dundee Festival of the Future, Techfest Science Festival, Orkney Science Festival and The Royal Society's 'Science Lates'. Peer-reviewed publications and critical acclaim from media outlets like The New York Times underscore the project's excellence and originality, solidifying its value within the broader research landscape.

This project was created by a group of individuals at the University of Dundee and at arts-charity Fast Familiar with support from members of the public through the LRCFS Citizens' Jury.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This project stands out for its innovative approach to engaging the public in forensic science. Unlike traditional research outputs, such as a survey, The Evidence Chamber uses an immersive performance format to simulate the jury experience, and participants are faced with the real-world challenge of interpreting forensic evidence in a simulated criminal case. The project directly addresses the difficulty faced by forensic scientists of communicating complex scientific information in a criminal justice context, where juries often struggle with uncertainty and expert disagreement. The Evidence Chamber not only educates participants but also generates insights that can inform future science communication strategies, the deliberations of the jury and their interpretation of expert witness statements were supported by the use of informative comics that explained the science. Its relevance is further demonstrated by its use as a training tool for members of the judiciary and legal professionals, helping them understand the viewpoint of the jury and the challenges of science communication.

The project's originality is further highlighted by its adaptation during the COVID-19 pandemic, where it successfully transitioned to a virtual format, expanding its reach.

The project is underpinned by rigorous academic research and has contributed to peer-reviewed

publications, such as Doran et al. (2021), with another publication forthcoming in 2024. The data collected from participants has been used for a Master's research project looking into the value of comics for scientific understanding in this context. The project's success in engaging audiences and generating insightful data in an innovative way underscores its high standard of research excellence and contributes to the broader discourse on science communication in the courtroom.

The Evidence Chamber exemplifies the kind of non-traditional research output that deserves recognition and inclusion in broader research evaluation frameworks.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Despite its appeal, The Evidence Chamber does not fit into current metrics of research success, such as journal publications or citations. This project, which blends performance art, science communication, and research, challenges conventional boundaries of what 'research' is.

While The Evidence Chamber has resulted in peer-reviewed publications, the primary value of this project lies in its ability to engage the public in complex scientific discussions, an impact that is difficult to quantify in traditional academic terms. The use of an immersive experience as a research method and communication tool is a clear example of originality and creativity. In addition, the project's iterative design process, involving continuous feedback from public participants (our Citizens' Jury) with the creators and forensic scientists, ensured that it is both scientifically accurate and accessible but was also captivating to a public audience.

The interdisciplinary nature of The Evidence Chamber, which spans forensic science, performance art, and education is a fantastic asset of the project but the players (actors, creators, freelancers, tech experts and public engagement staff) that created and deliver the experience are not recognised under traditional structures. The project's success in engaging diverse public audiences, including those from underserved communities, adds another layer that can be underappreciated in traditional research evaluation.

The project's impact has been ongoing since its inception in 2019, evolving through continuous public engagement, adaptation during the pandemic, and further research applications in 2023. The long-term nature of its impact is not easily captured in the short-term evaluation cycles typical of academia.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: WRITER Rachel Briscoe (Fast Familiar)

DIRECTOR Dan Barnard (Fast Familiar)

COMPUTATIONAL ARTIST Joe McAlister (Fast Familiar)

Professor Niamh Nic Daeid Director Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Dr Heather Doran Public Engagement Manager Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

Chris Hall Forensic DNA Expert, Scottish Police Authority

Paul McFadyen, actor and script development Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science

| CAST Sabrina Carter, Gillian Lees, Gary Mackay, John Milroy, Graeme Rooney

| WITH THANKS TO Kris De Meyer, William Galinsky, Marianne Maxwell and the LRCFS Citizens Jury Members

Funding acknowledgements: The Leverhulme Trust, Arts Council England

Entry: 432

Applicant details

Submission category: M - Performance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Jones, Michael

Organisation/University: Liverpool University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

In 2017 a concert I wrote, directed and produced was held at Liverpool Philharmonic. The title of the concert was 'George Harrison: the Beatles and Indian Music'. It stemmed from an email I received from the son of one of the Indian musicians who played on the 'Within You, Without You' session during the recording of the 'Sgt. Pepper's' album. The significance was that no other musicians were credited on the sleeve (the conceit being that all were members of 'Sgt. Pepper's Lonely Hearts Club Band'). Utkarsha Joshi, son of dilruba player Anna Joshi, felt that it was time that the musicians' contributions were acknowledged.

My first call was to a well-known English tabla player John Ball. His inquiries showed that no-one in the Indian classical community appeared to be aware of the identity of the players. We then divided our efforts between interviewing participants (I was able to discuss with Sir Peter Blake and received guidance from Sir George Martin) and following connections in the Indian music community, beginning with Anil Bhagwat who had played tabla on the Beatles 'Revolver' album.

We were able, eventually, to identify the players. A contact at Liverpool Philharmonic suggested we present at the 120 capacity 'Music Room'. In imagining and then organising such a presentation (which would involve an Indian ensemble, a rock band and a string section) we came to realise that we needed the main hall (1700 capacity). Clearly this involved much planning and organisation but the concert was staged with great acclaim in the week of the 50th anniversary of the release of 'Sgt. Pepper'. Subsequently, we were offered a national tour. The pandemic obviated this and the forward momentum was stalled. The event was exciting and fulfilling, but the promise of the research feels unfulfilled.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The concert in question was not submitted to the REF and yet it ticked all the boxes of publicly-accessible research. It began from an inquiry made by a member of the general public in response to an interview with me in The Times newspaper. I do not teach or research in Indian classical music, I simply knew someone active in the sector. I had produced a report into the economic value of Beatles tourism to Liverpool's economy so this gave me a stake in research into the Beatles, but this was a comparatively slim connection. By engaging in a kind of 'detective story', my collaborator and I were able to set the historical record straight in a particular regard. This is an interesting research outcome. By staging a public concert informed by the research effort, we made our findings publicly accessible in a non-academic form. Somehow, though, this only scratches the surface of the effort because what really was at stake was an engagement with diaspora and how cultural identity is preserved through adaptation to settling in a new environment.

Clearly, there is a literature on diaspora generally, and on the Indian diaspora specifically. What the concert offered was the opportunity to engage in research of the audiences a local concert had generated and a national tour was likely to produce. One of the many dimensions of continuing cultural prominence of the Beatles is that their audience is substantially cross-generational (this has been confirmed by my participation in delivering the MA in the Beatles: Music Industry and Heritage over the past few years). What I feel we had unwittingly initiated was a vehicle that would generate new data on diaspora by engaging wherever possible with diasporic communities. Certainly, for reasons of economic

viability, the concerts would have needed to take place at suitable venues but the intention was to precede them with publicly-accessible workshops and exhibitions on the crossover between the Beatles and Indian classical music. We were encouraged in this idea through discussions with the families of the musicians surviving from the 1967 sessions and with the members of their community they introduced us to. To return to what was (a successful concert) rather than stay with what might have been, the work itself was not some kind of 'tribute band' exercise but a multi-media telling of a complex story utilising an on-stage narrator and an extensive moving image backdrop which included previously unseen footage of pre-war visits of a then very young Ravi Shankar playing with his elder brother in the UK sourced from Pathe Pictures.

Taken as a whole, this was a successful exercise in public engagement with academic research made entertaining.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

At the risk of being extremely negative about both the REF and Music teaching in Higher Education, it needs to be said that both are exercises in the reproduction of elitism. As someone with a background in popular music and a specialism in studying the Music Industry, neither the REF nor the Russell Group Music sector represent conducive environments to study, explore and celebrate why non-classical and non-Western musicians make the music they do, and why audiences enjoy that music. The only way that the original concert could have proved 'valuable' would have been had I written up its various aspects as a series of journal articles which would have then needed to appear in upper-echelon publications to have stood a chance of being adjudged 'four star'. Had I been active in social sciences, perhaps I might have fared better but, then, had I been active in social sciences I would have not been interviewed by The Times!

Essentially, 'Music' goes on being an almost Leavisite preserve. This is not to condemn all people who teach in all Music departments, for example, there has been a strong EDI presence in the sector since the emergence of this as a cohesive set of considerations in recent years. Even so, teaching music industry remains an adjunct in a handful of Music departments and is wholly absent from the vast majority (especially, again, in the Russell Group). It is extraordinary to me that the lived experience of everyone outside of those who listen to classical music and attend classical concerts is basically ignored by HE. Taking one Russell Group Music department as an example (not my own!) of 25 members of staff only one has a connection to popular music and no member of staff teaches music industry but all encounters with music consist of the actions of non-musicians, and those actions obey their own imperatives. In researching and assembling the concert I had encounters with sectors of experience that were inspirational. Further, the considerations I needed to make to organise the onstage delivery were demanding and exciting. There were so many aspects of that were sites of research in and of themselves - from the pre-diaspora roots and routes of Indian classical music in the UK, to how young children in Indian UK communities negotiate their dual cultural heritages through music - and this is to not begin to mention the engagement of the Beatles with aspects of Indian heritage and culture (from George Harrison's absorption in sitar playing to the decapment to Rishikesh). Overall, what needed to be recognised as the gift of a treasure trove was simply silenced and I welcome the opportunity offered here to revisit this rich research experience.

Further details

ORCID: Sorry, I have a problem with my Orcid number that is challenging to resolve.

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 433

Applicant details

Submission category: 10 - Campaigns

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lincoln, Soo

Organisation/University: University of Leeds (UoL)

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Research Culture team at University of Leeds (UoL) have developed a project to better identify and celebrate diverse forms of research activity at the University, which was identified as one of the four strategic objectives in our institutional Research Culture Strategy, launched in 2023 (<https://researchculture.leeds.ac.uk/wp-content/uploads/sites/116/2023/09/University-of-Leeds-Research-Culture-Strategy-Report-1.pdf>).

The team collated baseline data using two methods: 1) content analysis of university communications, and 2) pulse surveys that capture staff perceptions of recognition and value within the research community. Initial findings from comms analysis indicate that senior academic and leadership roles dominate university communications, with non-research staff receiving minimal attention, particularly technicians staff. Such bias poses a direct threat to research culture, as well as undermines public commitments we have made to celebrating diverse research activity, such as in the University's Technician's Commitment (<https://researchculture.leeds.ac.uk/technician-commitment/>) and Fair Attribution Guidelines (<https://ris.leeds.ac.uk/research-excellence/fair-attribution-guidelines/>), demonstrating the scale of the systemic problem. This same bias was also felt keenly by our university community, as is evidenced in our pulse survey responses, where only a small percentage of respondents (22%) felt that their roles were explicitly valued in university-wide communications.

With these baseline data, the DIVERSE project is now working closely with internal communication teams (at faculty, institute, and school level) on a campaign to highlight opportunities for diversification and improve the visibility of underrepresented roles and research outputs. The project's ongoing efforts include refining communication strategies to better align with the university's strategic objectives, thereby fostering a more inclusive research culture where all contributions are acknowledged and valued.

We believe the DIVERSE project is critical in reshaping the research culture at the University of Leeds, promoting equity, and ensuring that the full spectrum of research activities and roles are recognized and celebrated.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The DIVERSE project at UoL specifically confronts the hiddenness of research activity within current research cultures by addressing how non-traditional outputs are often overlooked in conventional evaluation approaches and how sector recognition is mainly, and disproportionately, reserved for senior academics. While this project is localised to UoL communications, our methods are designed to be reproducible sector-wide. The project is also timely given the increased focus on research-enabling staff as part of REF2029, both as active members of a research environment, and as potential contributors to research outputs submitted to the REF. We believe this project challenges existing norms and provides new metrics and standards to better promote a supportive and inclusive research culture that recognises every individual and output that forms part of that culture. This project is appropriate and significant to the Hidden REF overall project due to its focus on increasing visibility of all research contributions. However, this project also aligns with the Hidden REF criteria in the following ways:

Excellence & Leadership: This project redefines excellence across the research lifecycle, promoting the

critical contributions of all research staff, the value of collaborative and interdisciplinary working, and expanding traditional definitions of success, to include non-traditional outputs. The project also puts in stark contrast the disproportionate recognition given to senior researchers compared to other research-enabling staff, thereby offering a new model of leadership for the University: one which is actively working to change institutional practices and perceptions surrounding research, setting a new standard for research evaluation.

Reflexive & Positional: The project takes a reflexive approach, continuously analysing its methods and impact through pulse surveys and communication analyses. One aspect of this has involved continuously recalibrating the search terms used in our analysis of internal communications, seeking input from domain-specific teams (e.g. Open Research, Researcher Development) to ensure accuracy in the analysis. This ongoing reflection ensures the project remains relevant and responsive to the needs of the research community, adapting its strategies to foster a more inclusive culture. In turn, the research findings are intended to prompt reflectiveness within content creation processes by providing communications teams with data and analysis in support of more equitable representation of the full breadth of staff roles and research outputs.

Temporality & Rigour: Acknowledging that cultural change is a long-term process, the project values the continuity of contribution over time. It employs a rigorous methodology, working with colleagues in comms and our Data Officer, to ensure that its findings and recommendations are reliable and grounded in solid evidence, as well as reproducible. This rigour supports the project's resilience in challenging traditional norms and promoting transformative change.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The DIVERSE project provides an opportunity to reflect on research activity that is hidden in two ways.

Firstly, how research is communicated (here, in university comms), is metadata that would not typically be collated or analysed as part of the REF. While the REF itself has begun to move away from a focus on other metadata (e.g. citations), how research is discussed in the workplace plays an important part in employee morale and feelings of belonging. So, how research is discussed internally is inherently hidden from larger evaluations such as the REF but are no less important. Secondly, by choosing to celebrate some research contributions over others, the research sector continues to fail to represent the full variety of research activity within the UK and fails to offer examples of the very real contributions being made every day. This keeps the diversity of research activities and research roles hidden. By challenging who and what are celebrated in UoL communications, DIVERSE provides that increased visibility and recognition.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 435

Applicant details

Submission category: N - Research report for external body

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Alexis-Martin, Becky

Organisation/University: Peace Studies, University of Bradford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The submission, an Asia Pacific Leadership Network report titled "Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons: Victim Assistance and Environmental Remediation in the Pacific," provides a significant contribution to the success of research on nuclear disarmament and environmental justice. The report explores the devastating impacts of nuclear testing in the Pacific, highlighting the experiences of affected communities and the long-term environmental degradation caused by nuclear weapons testing.

By focusing on victim assistance and environmental remediation, the report advances our understanding of how international treaties can address both human suffering and ecological damage. It presents thorough research on the legal obligations under the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW) and emphasizes the importance of integrating humanitarian and environmental perspectives into nuclear policy.

This research contributes to the success of broader disarmament efforts by raising awareness about underrepresented Pacific communities that have endured the legacy of nuclear testing. It advocates for stronger international collaboration in the areas of victim support and the restoration of affected ecosystems. The report's recommendations are grounded in extensive field research, interviews with victims, and collaboration with regional stakeholders, ensuring a well-rounded approach to policy-making.

Overall, this submission exemplifies how academic research can influence global disarmament policies and support the broader goals of peace, security, and sustainable development. It bridges the gap between legal frameworks and the lived realities of nuclear testing survivors, providing valuable insights that contribute to the ongoing dialogue on nuclear weapons prohibition and global environmental sustainability.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The submission holds significant importance within the context of the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW) by addressing key areas that are often overlooked in nuclear disarmament discussions: the human and environmental consequences of nuclear testing. The report not only advances the conversation on nuclear weapons prohibition but also underscores the treaty's unique approach, which extends beyond disarmament to include victim assistance and environmental remediation.

The TPNW, adopted in 2017, is the first international treaty to comprehensively ban nuclear weapons, including their use, threat of use, development, production, and stockpiling. Beyond this, it also addresses the humanitarian and environmental impacts of nuclear weapons, particularly in regions that have suffered from nuclear testing. The Pacific Islands, where extensive nuclear testing occurred during the 20th century, is a key focus of this report. It shines a light on the long-lasting devastation that nuclear testing has caused to the health of affected populations and the environment, a topic that is often sidelined in high-level disarmament negotiations.

This submission is significant because it highlights the real-world implications of Articles 6 and 7 of the TPNW, which outline the obligations of States Parties to provide assistance to victims of nuclear weapons use or testing and to undertake environmental remediation. By focusing on the Pacific region, the report brings attention to historically marginalized communities that have borne the brunt of nuclear colonialism. The detailed examination of the Pacific context gives the treaty's provisions greater relevance, illustrating how they can be applied in practice to assist affected populations and rehabilitate contaminated environments.

The research contained in this report provides a framework for understanding how international law can be used to address the legacies of nuclear harm. It emphasizes the responsibility of nuclear-armed and nuclear-testing states to offer assistance to those suffering from radiation-related illnesses, displacement, and loss of livelihoods. Additionally, the report stresses the importance of restoring ecosystems damaged by radioactive contamination, which is vital for ensuring the long-term sustainability and health of affected regions.

Furthermore, the report contributes to the broader goal of disarmament by drawing connections between environmental justice, human rights, and nuclear disarmament. In doing so, it supports the growing global movement to see nuclear disarmament not just as a matter of military security but as an issue of human and environmental security as well. This holistic approach strengthens the relevance of the TPNW by expanding the discourse to include the social, legal, and environmental dimensions of nuclear weapons policy, demonstrating the treaty's potential to address not only the abolition of nuclear weapons but also the rectification of their past harms.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This work represents an important yet often overlooked contribution within the current research culture, largely due to systemic biases that prioritize the work of institutions and scholars from the Global North. Research produced in and about the Global South, particularly in the form of reports, tends to be underappreciated in mainstream academic and policy evaluations. This submission highlights key issues affecting marginalized communities in the Pacific, yet it is precisely these issues and regions that tend to receive limited attention in global disarmament and environmental justice discourse.

One reason for the marginalization of this work lies in the dominance of Western-centric perspectives in international research and policy discussions. Global North institutions, scholars, and policymakers often drive the discourse on nuclear disarmament, shaping the research agenda in ways that emphasize strategic, military, or geopolitical concerns, rather than the lived experiences and humanitarian consequences faced by communities in the Global South. Consequently, research that focuses on these consequences, such as victim assistance and environmental remediation in the Pacific, is sidelined or viewed as peripheral. This reflects a broader trend where research that centers the voices and experiences of those most affected by historical injustices, like nuclear testing in the Pacific, is deprioritized in favor of high-level policy analysis or theoretical work.

Another factor contributing to the underappreciation of this submission is the form in which it is presented. Reports, as opposed to peer-reviewed journal articles, are often viewed as less prestigious or rigorous within academic and policy evaluation frameworks. These frameworks tend to prioritize research outputs that adhere to traditional academic publishing norms, often ignoring or undervaluing the real-world impact of policy-oriented reports. In particular, reports that emerge from grassroots or regional organizations, as this one likely does, are often excluded from mainstream academic recognition, even when they address urgent and neglected issues such as environmental remediation and victim assistance under the Treaty on the Prohibition of Nuclear Weapons (TPNW).

Furthermore, the broader work of scholars and activists from the Global South is frequently marginalized within international research forums and evaluations, which are dominated by Global North institutions with greater access to resources, funding, and visibility. As a result, critical research from the Global South is often left out of key discussions, limiting the diversity of perspectives that inform global policy on nuclear disarmament and environmental justice.

This report's focus on the Pacific Islands, a region deeply impacted by nuclear testing yet often excluded from disarmament narratives, demonstrates how vital Global South contributions remain overlooked. By neglecting such perspectives, the research community risks perpetuating a narrow, inequitable understanding of nuclear disarmament and environmental issues. The submission thus highlights the need for a more inclusive approach that values the research and lived experiences of marginalized.

Further details

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Qurat Ul Ain, research assistant

Kolby Kaller, research assistant

Ben Donaldson, UNA

Matthew Maslen, research assistant

Project report:

<https://www.apIn.network/analysis/special-report/treaty-on-the-prohibition-of-nuclear-weapons-victim-assistance-and-environmental-remediation-in-the-pacific>

Funding acknowledgements: We received funding from ICAN for this work.

Entry: 438

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Johnson, Miriam

Organisation/University: Oxford Brookes University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

In 2023-24, I scraped all jobs that appeared on The Bookseller, which is the UK publishing industry's magazine. The work was based on a session I ran for PhD candidates about getting started with data scraping and mining and finding the stories in your data. Over 9/10 months I scraped the jobs weekly and compiled them into a dataset with over 700 jobs from the publishing sector. Then I began by looking at the language in the job adverts. Using a list of key words and roots that are identified as gendered by prior (not mine) research, I ran the jobs through code that identified the terms used as strongly feminine, feminine, neutral, masculine, strongly masculine. I then pulled out all the jobs with salaries included in the job description. I found that, as one might imagine, masculine coded jobs were paid more and that recruitment agencies do not list salaries at all. I wrote my findings up and posted them on LinkedIn. https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/gendered-job-adverts-issue-publishing-miriam-johnson-ur1me?lipi=urnlipaged_flagship3_profile_view_base64MTpaSzmHjyjqe0DHw.

I was then asked by people who came across the post to look into ableism and ageism in the job descriptions. I did this and posted them also on LinkedIn: https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/ageist-language-publishing-job-ads-miriam-johnson-eg5pe?lipi=urnlipaged_flagship3_profile_view_base64MTpaSzmHjyjqe0DHw; https://www.linkedin.com/pulse/ableism-publishing-job-adverts-miriam-johnson-zykje?lipi=urnlipaged_flagship3_profile_view_base64MTpaSzmHjyjqe0DHw.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The significance of this work is that it highlights that some of the issues in the inclusivity of the publishing industry that is mostly female, middle class, white, straight, and not disabled; stem from the way jobs are advertised.

This work showcases the issues of inequality across pay (in all three areas of gender, ageism, and ableism), and asks those who work within the industry to take note and make changes within their HR departments to champion equality.

This series of 3 pieces of research has led to a working group to host an industry symposium for publishers to share best practices on inclusivity across areas of the industry (academic, educational, trade publishing, etc).

It has also directly led to me building a website (and learning to work in a lot of code that was new to me - I'm learning as I go) where people can put in a job description and it will be combed for ageist, ableist, and gendered terminology, that is then highlighted and suggestions offered. I recently updated it so that it also tells you 'whoops, looks like you forgot to include a salary' if they do not include one in the ad. <https://jobs.booksaresocial.com/>

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This work is hidden because I actively chose not to publish it in an academic journal as I didn't want it to be locked behind a paywall and wrapped in a lot of academic wording.

The value in this research is that it is accessible, shareable, and links to other sources to further the reader's learning.

The more people in the industry can access this research - the more likely it is that it will be taken on board and further full inclusivity and equality in the publishing industry, which employs tens of thousands of people in the UK.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-6488-5619

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: none!

Entry: 442

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Clements-Brod, Naomi

Organisation/University: Human Developmental Biology Initiative, University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Human Developmental Biology Initiative (HDBI, hdbi.org) is a Wellcome-funded research consortium with scientists in institutions across the UK and Europe trying to better understand how humans develop before birth. They work with early human embryos donated by fertility patients. HDBI research raises complex ethical and moral questions for science and society. HDBI public engagement aims to open research and its implications to broader questioning and consideration by the public.

In a public engagement project facilitated by the Gurdon Institute, researchers working with early human embryos discussed their work with members of the public, an artist (Anna Dumitriu), a policy expert (Sandy Starr) and a sociologist (Marieke Bigg) in a series of meetings over several months. The artist then created an interactive digital artwork with a soundtrack, 'Precious Cells' (<https://www.gurdon.cam.ac.uk/precious-cells/>). The artwork reflects the conversations that took place, telling the story of early embryos used in research to uncover how we develop from a fertilised egg to a fully functioning human being. Embryos at various stages of early development are shown floating in a liquid, representing the environment in which human embryos are grown in the lab. The embryos shown were drawn based on microscope images from laboratory research. They are depicted in a glowing golden colour, which represents their preciousness, a quality that multiple participants in the meetings highlighted.

The artwork is freely available online and has also been exhibited in an immersive, large-scale projection in a shopping centre as part of the Cambridge Festival 2024. This location was selected so people who aren't necessarily interested in science would find it, and over 200 people experienced the artwork there. It has also been exhibited in BioArt Revolution (part of Timisoara 2023 European Capital of Culture) and BioArt Knowledge (Yarrow Gallery at Oundle School).

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The use of human embryos in research may trigger a strong emotional response in members of the public, from curiosity to fear. This project aims to encourage conversations between science and society about this potentially controversial research and, hopefully, decrease fear about it by increasing the research's transparency.

The significance of this piece rests not just in the artwork itself and the number of times it has been exhibited or the number of people it has reached. It also lies within the interdisciplinary conversations which inspired the artist and made the artwork possible.

Fundamental biology can be difficult to discuss because the practical impacts are often unclear until long after the research has taken place, and the science often feels far-removed from people's everyday lives. Questions such as 'Why do you use human embryos for research?' and 'Where do they come from?' are often raised when discussing this research with the public. Informed conversations require substantial groundwork to develop shared language and understanding. And the transparency necessary to bolster trust in science requires more than just provision of information to the public; it requires dialogue.

This project is rooted in dialogue, from the multidisciplinary meetings where the idea for the artwork was conceived to the conversations among the public viewing the finished piece in person. From its conception to its flexible format and even its name (inspired by dialogue between participants), this project exemplifies the collaboration necessary to create shared language and understanding between the public and scientists working in a potentially contentious area of research.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This project was supported by the Human Developmental Biology Initiative's public engagement programme.

Public engagement and involvement with fundamental research has been advocated since the Human Genome Project in the 1990s. It was recognised then that reflection and communication between fundamental researchers and the public is critical for ensuring that society trusts research and its eventual outcomes and that a lack of transparency and communication is more likely to lead to backlash against potentially controversial research. However, public engagement requires time and training for the participating scientists and is often deprioritised and seen as a non-essential, non-strategic activity in the scientific community.

This may be because measuring the exact outcomes of public engagement projects such as this one is often difficult. While participating in this project may have influenced scientists' thinking about their research, the impact of this shift in thinking may not be evident until long after the current grant funding has ended, and the practitioners who delivered and evaluated the public engagement may have moved on to other roles.

It's also often difficult to capture the impact of art on the viewing public, as this usually requires time and reflection, perhaps even discussion with friends and family. By then, it's not possible to capture a person's thoughts as they are likely to have left the exhibit.

In addition, public engagement often takes place after the research agenda and funding have been set, so it's not often possible to change directions, even if an interaction with a member of the public may highlight the need to reconsider research plans.

Finally, current research and evaluation often focus on the end result rather than the process. In this case, the process of participating in an interdisciplinary conversation was of value in itself. Scientists built their communication skills by thinking carefully about how they presented their work to ensure it was understandable to the public participants. Public participants gained a better understanding of how embryos are used in research and valued by the scientists working with them.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Helene Doerflinger, Public Engagement Manager, Gurdon Institute, University of Cambridge

Natalie Walls, Public Engagement Coordinator, Gurdon Institute, University of Cambridge

Funding acknowledgements: The HDBI public engagement programme is supported by a Wellcome Research Enrichment grant (215116/Z/18/C).

Entry: 444

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Clements-Brod, Naomi

Organisation/University: Human Developmental Biology Initiative, University of Cambridge

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Human Developmental Biology Initiative (HDBI, hdbi.org) is a Wellcome-funded research consortium with scientists in institutions across the UK and Europe who are trying to better understand how humans develop before birth. They work with human fetal and embryonic tissues donated from abortions, as well as early human embryos donated by fertility patients. HDBI public engagement aims to open research and its implications to broader questioning and consideration by the public.

HDBI research raises complex ethical and moral questions for science and society because of the sensitive tissues used in research and the potential for widespread impacts on health and medicine. This creates a public engagement paradox: the fundamental research is distant from people's daily lives and clinical applications are currently unknown, but donating fetal and embryonic tissue to research is intimately linked with personal experiences.

We can't anticipate everyone who might be impacted by our research, but tissue donors have a direct connection to our science and our research wouldn't be possible without them. Therefore, we have adopted a unique experimental approach to public engagement with fundamental research and established a panel of public stakeholders, the 'Insights Group', whose members have a relationship to HDBI tissue donation situations (e.g. abortion and/or fertility treatment). The Group advises on how HDBI research is conducted and communicated and represents an ongoing opportunity for HDBI and related researchers to discuss their work with the public.

Over the last 2.5 years, the Group has held 12 meetings and engaged with 30 HDBI members and affiliates. They have contributed to activities such as: HDBI public engagement training for researchers, an HDBI FAQs resource, a large public dialogue project, and rewriting a patient information leaflet for tissue donation.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Public engagement and involvement with fundamental research has been advocated since the Human Genome Project in the 1990s. It was recognised then that communication between fundamental researchers and the public is critical to ensuring society trusts research and its outcomes and a lack of communication is more likely to lead to backlash against potentially controversial research. This is still recognised today in calls for 'Responsible Research and Innovation' (RRI), which involves discussing research with the public early on, before innovations leave the laboratory.

RRI has widely been embraced by funders and scientists as a way of improving acceptance of new technologies, likely encouraged by the negative reaction of the European public to genetically modified foods in the early 2000s. However, RRI with fundamental research has multiple challenges to success: practical impacts are often not clear until long after the research has taken place, the research revolves around topics that seem distant from most people's daily lives, and meaningful conversations require substantial groundwork to develop shared language and understanding.

The HDBI Insights Group is a unique public engagement project, borrowing Patient and Public

Involvement (PPI) methodology (common in clinical research) and applying it to fundamental biology. We are not aware of any other attempts to involve public stakeholders in fundamental biology in a similar way. This might be a result of the challenges outlined above or the substantial resources involved in setting up and maintaining a group such as ours. And these resources are often not considered in grant applications for fundamental research.

Since interacting with the Group, researchers have had a range of insights about their science and its communication. In feedback, they have shared: 'words that are innocuous to me can have emotive responses in others', 'making the slides made me focus on the 'big questions' we are asking in our project', and 'the ethics of biological research is not something that can be avoided in conversations with the public'. Comments such as these illustrate how interacting with the Group has provoked researchers to think differently about their work, and especially about how it is communicated.

The Group has also advised on logistics for a public dialogue project, contributed to HDBI researcher trainings and resource development (such as the HDBI FAQs: <https://hdbi.org/faqs>) and provided valuable insights which enabled a patient information leaflet for tissue donation to be redrafted.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Public engagement is often deprioritised because it is seen as a non-essential activity so the substantial resources required to do public engagement carefully and strategically are often not included in grant applications. And in order to truly fit RRI criteria, groups such as ours would need to be engaged even earlier, ideally during the grant writing phase, to ensure the public has an opportunity to feed into the research agenda from the very beginning. However, fundamental researchers do not typically have a public stakeholder group which is easily accessible for advice on how their research should be conducted and communicated - the HDBI Insights Group represents a new way of working in the field.

While researchers and public participants are surveyed after every meeting, it is still difficult to measure the impact of interactions, as they are unique to each researcher. Everyone brings different amounts and types of public engagement experience to interacting with the Group and will have different opportunities to put any insights gained into use.

The ultimate impact of the HDBI Insights Group may not be apparent until years down the line, or after the current grant funding has ended and the practitioners who delivered and evaluated the project have moved on to other roles.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The HDBI public engagement programme is supported by a Wellcome Research Enrichment grant (215116/Z/18/C).

Entry: 452

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wickersham, Alice

Organisation/University: CAMHS Digital Lab, King's College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

At the CAMHS Digital Lab, we analyse a variety of administrative data in our research, including health, criminal, and education records. As part of a fellowship funded by Administrative Data Research UK (ADR UK), Alice used linked education records (Department for Education) and police records (Ministry of Justice) to understand relationships between school performance and involvement in the criminal justice system. The implications of administrative data research such as this are strongly within the public interest, as they have substantial implications for policy. Yet, when consulting the public about this and other administrative data research projects, we sometimes find that people are surprised that information collected about them by public services is used for research. If the use of administrative data in research is not adequately publicised, this can raise undue concern that the practice is secretive and underhand.

Involving the public in research through a variety of media is crucial to ensuring that there is transparency in our use of these data. That's why we made a short animated video (<https://www.adruk.org/news-publications/publications-reports/animation-improving-our-society-through-administrative-data-research/>) to explain what administrative data is, why we use it, and how we keep it safe. The video was a collaboration between Dr Alice Wickersham, the CAMHS Digital Lab (King's College London), ADR UK, and Really Bright Media, produced in close consultation with the, ÅYoung National Children's Bureau Advisory Group, Åand Lambeth Youth Advisory Group. By engaging the public, in particular young people, with administrative data research, we are enhancing public trust in this research and thus securing its longevity into the future.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

To increase public awareness of administrative data research, we produced a short, animated video for online dissemination targeting adolescents and young adults: school record data is being collected for this age group now, and is the future of educational research, so it is important to promote awareness and support for administrative data research in this younger generation. Key messages included:

- (1) Introducing administrative data, using examples;
- (2) Emphasising that individual data is kept secure and anonymous for research, referencing the Five Safes framework;
- (3) Highlighting a finding from Alice's research fellowship to demonstrate how research can inform support for young people and improve services.

The video can be viewed here: <https://www.adruk.org/news-publications/publications-reports/animation-improving-our-society-through-administrative-data-research/>

The video was developed in close collaboration with young people, and with other professionals with expertise in administrative data, to ensure that the final product was appropriate, relevant and interesting. Adolescents and young adults were consulted at several key stages of production. Firstly, prior to scripting and storyboarding, we consulted with the Young National Children's Bureau (YNCB) Advisory Group on our plans for the video, who offered recommendations for the process; we later fed back how we actioned these recommendations in a, Åúyou said, we did, Å session. After developing the script and

storyboard, we consulted with the Lambeth Youth Advisory Group on these drafts. Lastly, the animated storyboard was taken back to the YNCB Advisory Group for final suggestions and to choose our voiceover artist.

The importance of this submission is therefore in its illustration of creating novel outputs which communicate complex scientific concepts for young people, with young people. It is also important because, by promoting transparency about administrative data research in this age group, we can ensure the trust in and longevity of this research, and its impact on policy - into the future.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

In academia, publication in academic journals continues to be the focal output of many research projects. While this is still a valuable step in many ways, outputs which engage and inform the public are often overlooked when considering academics for promotion or evaluating the 'impact' of a research project. Moreover, time is rarely 'reserved' for researchers to do public engagement; they often have to take time away from producing articles and other academic outputs to do this kind of work. Alice's passion for meaningfully engaging the public in science motivated her to produce this video, although it took time away from the academic work which is more explicitly expected and rewarded by universities, funders, and the REF.

This submission illustrates that novel outputs can be just as valuable, and moreover, illustrates the importance of engaging with young people to produce those outputs. Since a lot of our administrative data research addresses young people's mental health and data, we need to produce types of media which they are likely to engage with. This video presents complex research in simple, easy-to-understand language. It can serve as a gateway for young people who are interested in psychology to understand more about different types of research, and possibly stimulate their interest in pursuing the sciences.

Administrative data research affects public trust not only in research, but in all public systems we analyse data from, schools, healthcare providers, and more. It is therefore imperative that we produce outputs which seek to stimulate public trust and engagement with research. The process of engaging with the public on outputs designed for other members of the public creates a continuous cycle of involvement, wherein members of the public are positioned as science communicators and contributors to public narratives about scientific research.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 458

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bayley, Amanda

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The film, 'Transforming Lives through Ethnomusicological Engagement in Kwando, Namibia', <https://youtu.be/29lw64NDWgY> (April 2024) was funded by a Rapid Impact fund, AHRC Impact Accelerator Award, to capture the activities taking place in Kwando village since October 2023. The project evolved from a musical encounter with the Kwando community, from the lead researcher and a student from Bath Spa University, in April 2023, hosted by a researcher and student from the University of Namibia (UNAM)). The aims of the project were then co-designed with Dr Perminus Matiure (an ethnomusicologist at UNAM), and the Kwando community:

- a) to reverse the fears of the Kwando community's cultural extinction by creating opportunities for transmitting their knowledge and traditions to the younger generation;
- b) to divert attention away from harmful behaviours such as substance abuse by engaging young people in creative and artistic activities.

The film shows how these aims have been addressed through workshops led by UNAM researchers (October and November 2023, April and August 2024), where the rich cultural heritage of the Kwando community has begun to be shared through folk and contemporary songs, stories, children's games, mbira, marimba, dance, drama, arts and crafts. The youth have been equipped with transferable skills in instrument-making and performance, opening doors for them to earn a living while preserving their traditions.

Collaborating with researchers from different disciplines enables participants to learn about conservation and ecology, regarding the use of locally sourced materials. The project continues to assess its initial success and growing impact, including income from regular performances at three local tourist lodges, and making and selling instruments and crafts. Researchers are continuing to develop ways of co-producing impact with and for the community that can reap wider regional benefits, e.g. establishing a community arts centre as a hub for innovative artistic endeavours.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The project is highly significant, directly impacting 16 young people and their families, by providing leadership responsibilities for youth, especially women. Many young people are forced to drop out of school due to an alarming rate of teenage pregnancies, partly caused by the younger generation's greater interest in modern recreational activities such as disco which often leads to drug abuse. The consequences of these negative influences perpetuate a cycle of limited education that hinders the overall development of the younger generation in Kwando, resulting in a poverty trap status. The objectives are thus to:

- train young people to collect materials for making musical instruments and artefacts from their environment;
- impart knowledge and skills on how to make mbira and marimba instruments;
- teach them to play the instruments;
- encourage them to appreciate their culture through listening to folk stories and singing folksongs and game songs (in English, Shona and their local language, mbukushu);
- promote and preserve indigenous music heritage;

- encourage them to write their own songs and music;
- teach them drama, theatre and poetry;
- teach visual arts and crafts;
- help them to be resourceful and entrepreneurial at an early age by making and selling art products;
- establish a Youth Community Arts Centre
- raise awareness of ecosystem services and sustainable use of resources.

Despite the Hambukushu ethnic group having a deep connection to their cultural heritage, (examples of which can be seen at the Kwando 'living museum' for tourists), the elders face challenges in transmitting their knowledge and traditions to the younger generation. The project addresses their concerns of ongoing cultural extinction by providing a sense of purpose for the young people, and a positive drive for social change.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The film is a non-standard research output showcasing how opportunities for skill development in arts disciplines can lead towards the strengthening of individual, community, and societal wellbeing. The documented workshops demonstrate immediate impact, as well as the transformative potential of ethnomusicological research. Impact is local: Kwando is a small traditional village on the Kwando River in the Zambezi region of Namibia; its demographic population has a high number of children and youth. Surveys of participants showed that 100% enjoyed taking part, with comments such as 'I love it' and 'It is changing my lifestyle and teach[ing] me how to do things on my own' (April 2024). However, they are afraid the project will stop (April 2024), and they think the film was made for financial gain (August 2024). Benefits to the community are ongoing and long-term, not all immediate. The film aims to reinforce the project's direction and objectives, providing further stimulus to participants and to the community. It is being shared with the Namibian Broadcasting Company for wider dissemination, both regionally and nationally.

The initial positive responses and the subsequent social benefits are integral outcomes of musical and scholarly encounters. Immediate contributions to societal transformation are invisible to the REF, yet applied ethnomusicology gives community members access to strategic models and conservation techniques, for cultural heritage and natural heritage, respectively. The submission is hidden because the immediate beneficiaries of the research are young people living in a poor, rural community, and the project is in its infancy.

The project hopes to stimulate original creative outputs, providing opportunities for skills development in arts disciplines, particularly through intergenerational learning, thus leading towards the strengthening of individual, community, and societal well-being (UN SDG3). By continuing to work closely with the community head, and other community partners, music can act as a catalyst for building sustainable partnerships that drive artistic solutions for societal change.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-2114-5917

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: TBC

Funding acknowledgements: Rapid Impact fund, AHRC Impact Accelerator Award

Entry: 461

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Breel, Astrid

Organisation/University: Bath Spa University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Bath School of Art, Film and Media at Bath Spa University has been developing innovative and creative engagement strategies, with the aim to expand the University's public and civic engagement with art research, teaching and practice. Through a sustained and diverse series of practice led events we opened our art and design campus to our local community situating them directly in the processes and methods of visual art. Rather than a passive reception of art, our aim was to engage our community directly in our art practice (research and pedagogic) alongside our students, artists, researchers.

Part of this work has been the Bath School of Art, Film and Media, Ås (BSAFM) collaboration (2021-2024) as a partner institution in the West of England Visual Arts Alliance (WEVAA). WEVAA was a three-year Arts Council England funded programme of activity that aimed to transform the West of England into a place where the visual arts can thrive, providing critical opportunities and support to enable artists, curators and young people to develop their careers and achieve their potential. WEVAA aimed to demonstrate the impact of the visual arts on regeneration, well-being, and economic and community development. At BSAFM the project was led by led by artists/academic Dr Natasha Kidd and artist/creative producer Simone Hesselberg. The WEVAA work at BSAFM aimed to invite our local community to into the research and pedagogy of art. Through the project we have employed/commissioned 34 artists to deliver sessions as part of the programme of activities (including 11 students, and 7 alumni) and built relationships with several schools, youth organisations and arts organisations in BANES. Working with schools provides value locally through exposure to art learning and creative research and ongoing work is happening to engage local communities by sharing arts-based news, events and opportunities in and around BANES.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The project has included a range of partnerships, activities and outcomes; working most closely with young people and the artist community within BANES. Key partnerships include The Carers Centre, the West of England Combined Authority, and the project has been able to connect those partners to different parts within the University, including EMERGE, The Studio and Student Recruitment and Outreach.

Project activities include:

3 summer yearly summer schools, welcoming 64 participants across the three years. Exploring the role and experience of a visual art education, these weeklong courses directly explored the experience of 'art school' culminating in the production of a collaborative film with the artist researcher.

2 practice led inset sessions to secondary art teachers, welcoming 10 teachers from across BANES. These sessions considered what artist teachers need as practitioners.

5 hands on introductory sessions to local youth organisations (including campus tours and creatives workshops), welcoming 90 young people to the campus

14 workshop and talks for staff, students and the creative community in Bath and North-east Somerset (BANES), welcoming 348 attendees across the programme.

The summer school has been a central activity within the project, which has now been embedded within the University's central activities; connecting art research practices with the Student Recruitment and Outreach team. The summer school continues to present an accessible and socially inclusive programme, where young people from a range of backgrounds can participate with minimal (to no) barriers. It uses an embedded evaluation methodology to understand the barriers for young people from local communities (which face different types of marginalisation) to engage with the art school, the creative industries and higher education more widely. To address this, the programme provides a much-needed space for young people to experiment and take risks without the pressure of academic attainment, thus building confidence and developing new skills in a safe but enriching environment. Towards the end of the programme, young people were able to express themselves more freely - even making suggestions for future iterations of the programme based on their needs. It also gave young people the opportunity to experience what their learning and independence could be like in creative HE. Approximately 50% of participants have expressed a desire to pursue the arts and/or HE increased because of taking part in the programme.

As a direct result of the University's partnership with WEVAA, we have achieved greater civic engagement through a varied but strategic approach. As a result, and in order to sustain public engagement beyond WEVAA, BSAFM successfully received funding from the West of England Combined Authority to deliver further public engagement activities at the Locksbrook Campus from 2024. [continued below]

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

This includes a further series of professional development events as well as a training programme and commission opportunity that focuses on creative learning resources. The University has also created a new role for Dr Natasha Kidd to build a creative engagement strategy as part of the institution's civic engagement agenda.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches.

The kind of engagement work that has been central to the WEVAA project at Bath Spa is not easily captured within structures such as REF (or KEF). It is engaging local communities and stakeholders in the heart of the art school, which combines pedagogy with research in a range of different formats, strategies and methods. Without being able to easily tie such work to one or more 'research outputs' makes it difficult to include projects such as this within the impact section of the REF submission, whilst mentioning it in passing within the institutional environment statement does not do justice to the meaningful impact the project has created.

Please see here (link: <https://bathspaonline.sharepoint.com/:f/s/AccessibleDocumentSharing-Casual-CF-IKE-Staff/EmHRBOoTYS1Ntbtm8a1AtR0BNZnM3ZYPIGpKZSOSQDUgCQ?e=DHXqwr>) for images documenting the impact of the project (it is interesting how the Hidden REF still preferences the written word!)

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 462

Applicant details

Submission category: 9- Public Engagement

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Fisher, Judith

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Chronic pain is pain that lasts for three months or more - is a highly prevalent condition affecting 35-51% of the UK adult population and there remains an unmet need of recognition and treatment. There have been no major new treatment breakthroughs in over a decade.

Alleviate Hub's Lived Experience Advisory Group, led by two funded public members, consists of seven individuals who all live with chronic pain. The LEAG have brought their diverse life experience together over the last three years to focus on a group mission: to raise awareness of the impact of chronic pain within the research community. They are encouraging the public to share their lived experience of chronic pain and ensuring that the voices of people living with pain are heard at every stage of project decision making. This takes many forms from social media campaigns (see: <https://www.youtube.com/@alleviate-hub>) where they share the impact pain has on their daily life and to running training sessions for researchers to build their understanding. They have also established an online group of >310 people with lived experience.

This culminated in Alleviate Hub starting an annual UK National Pain Survey in 2023, in collaboration with Chronic Pain Australia, Pain UK and the Advanced Pain Discovery Platform. This initiative was suggested by one of our Lived Experience Leads and was then co-produced with our Lived Experience Advisory Group, Alleviate Hub team and principal investigators. The aim being to collate the current lived experiences of chronic within the UK and focus research on their needs.

For the 2024 survey, we have further developed the survey based on suggestions from people living with pain, to further increase the relevance of the data gathered, with our Lived Experience Advisory Group members using their networks to improve the reach of the survey.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Chronic pain causes significant impacts on people's lives making day-to-day activities harder. The Lived Experience Advisory Group (LEAG) have used their skills, experience and networks to significantly positively impact on Alleviate's work. Their insights have ensured our work is clearly focused on using research to improve the quality of the life of patients. Their skill in taking complex, technical work and identifying the key points to share with people living with pain and finding accessible ways to present these have enabled a wider range of people living with pain to input into our research.

By being willing to share their personal experiences, they have improved the research team's understanding of the human cost of living with pain which is often missing in basic research projects.

As an example of their contribution, The LEAG have masterminded a campaign to promote the human element of this year's UK National Pain Survey. The 'My 3 Words' campaign encourages people living with pain to describe how they are feeling. The campaign videos can be viewed at https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PLleRjBrO_0rlzXfaNOnJlgiSfTD-i0dfd. The campaign expresses individual pain experience, with each person's experience being brought together into a single word cloud, to demonstrate both the diversity of people living with pain and that they are not alone. This

ongoing piece of work can be viewed at <https://alleviate.ac.uk/my-3-words/>.

The LEAG generated the original idea, worked together to develop the campaign, participated in recording videos to promote it and disseminated it through their own networks.

LEAG members have substantially contributed throughout the project. They have taken their turn in chairing fortnightly project team meetings, led monthly LEAG meetings, participated in conferences and webinars, developed and recorded social media content and written blogs. The patient voice has been represented in all the 65 outputs from Alleviate: <https://discovery.dundee.ac.uk/en/projects/alleviate-hub-for-pain-pain-research-data-hub-ukri-and-versus-art/clippings/>

The LEAG have contributed to other projects by advising on their research proposals and the Alleviate model is being replicated into the wider Advanced Pain Discovery Platform consortium.

The model we have developed in Alleviate to include funded public leads within the core project and have an inclusive and active LEAG has positively changed how an academic project can function. We are fundamentally more aware of the impacts of chronic pain, we communicate better, are more empathetic and more focused on delivering change to the pain research community.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Pain is invisible. For people living with pain, it can be a lonely, frustrating experience. Our 2023 survey indicated that 77% of women and 62% of men living with pain experienced feeling ignored or dismissed by health professionals, with 66% of women and 56% of men experiencing feeling powerless.

Not all researchers in chronic pain appreciate the value of having those who live with pain as core members of the research team. There can still be the perception that understanding complex research projects is beyond the abilities of patients and members of the public and that these members will slow down the research team.

Researchers do not always appreciate the impact that pain has on people's daily lives because it is unique to each patient, hard to measure, complex and variable. This is particularly true for those working with data as they are more removed from the underlying stories hidden in the data.

Public engagement is sometimes a requirement by funders on researchers who often comply to the rules, but not necessarily embrace the spirit. In Alleviate we have shown that the lived experience can be at the core of the project ensuring inclusion, diversity and ownership of public engagement and hearing the patient voice throughout everything we do. This is an uncommon and underappreciated way of working.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Judith Fisher, PPIE Coordinator, University of Dundee

Jillian Beggs, Associate Staff, University of Dundee

Antony Chuter, PPIE Layperson

Claire Beers, PPIE Layperson

Kausar Iqbal, PPIE Layperson

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Gillian Martin, Trial Manager, University of Dundee

Funding acknowledgements: "The Alleviate Pain Data Hub was funded under the Advanced Pain Discovery Platform consortium by the MRC, Versus Arthritis, Lilly and the Medical Research Foundation grant number: MR/W014335/1"

Entry: 487

Applicant details

Submission category: Q - Digital or Visual Media

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Wilkinson, Catherine

Organisation/University: Liverpool John Moores University

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The project 'Coming to Spinal Clinic' explored the participation of young people with scoliosis in their consultations. The research team comprised of a children's geographer and two children's nurse academics. We co-ran two participatory design workshops with young people with scoliosis and their parents and worked with surgeons and an illustration artist. The project resulted in a multi-media resource (animation; preparation sheet; and information leaflet), co-created with young people with scoliosis, their parents, children's nurse academics, spinal surgeons and an illustrator. The free and downloadable resource was launched at International Philip Zorab Symposium (2019), Dublin, attended by scientists, spinal surgeons and specialist nurses. The resource can be accessed here: (<https://sites.dgehill.ac.uk/coming-to-spinal-clinic/#:~:text=Wedevelopedtheresource'Coming,madeupofthreeparts.>). It comprises of:

- A short animation aimed at young people to help them know what to expect when they come to spinal clinic and how to get the most out of their clinic visit.
- A prep (preparation) to help young people and parents think about what they want to ask or find out about when they are in clinic.
- An information leaflet for parents to help them know what to expect when they bring their child to spinal clinic.

The research was shared in Scoliosis Support and Research newsletter Backbone. The resource has been shared with hospitals and clinics so that young people coming to spinal clinic can access them easily. Alder Hey Children's Hospital promotes the resource on their spinal clinic webpage. The study was mentioned in a feature on helping adolescents cope with the burden of scoliosis in The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health by journalist Peter Ranscombe.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

We have detailed the significance of this submission against the Hidden REF criteria:

Visibility: to include everyone and everything and leave nothing behind

Participation / co-production: The Coming to Spinal Clinic project actively involved multiple stakeholders - young people with scoliosis, their parents, children's nurse academics, spinal surgeons, and an illustrator.

Comprehensive Resource Development: Each component of the multi-media resource is designed to cater to diverse needs, from reducing anxiety through visual storytelling to providing practical information for parents.

Accessible and Wide-Reaching: The resource is freely available and downloadable, making it accessible to a broad audience. Its promotion and use within the NHS including at Alder Hey Children's Hospital and

its presence in reputable newsletters and publications help ensure that the information reaches those who need it, not just those sitting in ivory towers with institutional access to leading journals.

Visibility Within the Medical Community: The project's inclusion in scientific and medical discussions, such as the International Philip Zorab Symposium and The Lancet Child & Adolescent Health, underscores its broad relevance and importance. This visibility within the medical community helps to reinforce the project's commitment to addressing all facets of the clinic experience and ensuring that the needs of young patients and their families are fully met.

The 'Coming to Spinal Clinic' project is significant in the context of UK research due to its contributions across the diversity, richness, and variety of research in several key ways:

Multidisciplinary Approach: The project integrates diverse perspectives from children's geographers, nurse academics, spinal surgeons, and an illustrator. This multidisciplinary approach enriches the research by incorporating various expertise and viewpoints, contributing to a more holistic understanding of the clinic experience.

Inclusion of Young People and Families: By actively involving young patients with scoliosis and their families in the design process, the project emphasises the importance of patient and family-centred care. This participatory approach ensures that the resources are directly relevant to the users' needs and experiences, reflecting a broader spectrum of voices in healthcare research.

Practical Impact: The project's focus on providing practical tools to help young patients and their families navigate the

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The 'Coming to Spinal Clinic' project, despite its significant contributions is overlooked in the current Research Excellence Framework (REF) exercise for several reasons. Firstly, because of the emphasis on practical resources. The multimedia resource does not align with traditional REF criteria which emphasises academic publications, principally peer-reviewed journal articles. Further, the participatory design workshops and collaborative creative process, whilst innovative and inclusive, are arguably not valued in the same way that controlled studies are. Moreover, while the multi-media resource has a clear impact on improving patient experience, the REF criteria may emphasises academic contributions such as theoretical advancement and significant empirical findings. We also consider that the project's multidisciplinary nature might complicate its assessment within traditional disciplinary categories used in REF evaluations.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: British Scoliosis Research Fund

Entry: 497

Applicant details

Submission category: V - Translation

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Lee Steele, Anne

Organisation/University: The Alan Turing Institute

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

I am nominating The Turing Way's Translation and Localisation Working Group, led by Batool Almarzouq and Andrea Sanchez-Tapia for their critical contributions in making The Turing Way more globally accessible. The Turing Way is an open-source project housed at The Alan Turing Institute, offering practical guides on reproducibility, ethics, and collaborative research. The project's success extends beyond the UK, reaching diverse communities through its translation and localisation efforts.

The Localisation Working Group, initiated in 2021, has enabled The Turing Way to be translated into 8 languages, expanding its reach across regions beyond the United Kingdom. The group has developed workflows, governance structures, and tools to support community-driven translation, ensuring that international contributors can participate meaningfully and with recognition. The team is an active part of our community, conducting bi-weekly co-working calls and regularly presenting at international conferences, including CarpentryCon, Write the Docs, and FORCE11.

This working group's success lies in its dual focus: co-governing the human infrastructure to ensure inclusivity and visibility, and integrating technical tools to streamline multilingual deployments. The co-leads of the localisation working group in particular have played a vital leadership role in advancing these efforts, making the knowledge and tools in The Turing Way accessible to communities traditionally excluded by language barriers.

The group's localisation guidelines and technical solutions, such as the deployment of the Arabic version, demonstrate their commitment to enhancing the usability of the project across different cultural and linguistic contexts, benefiting both The Turing Way and other similar open-source initiatives.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The work of the Translation and Localisation Working Group of The Turing Way addresses a critical imbalance in scientific communication, where the dominance of English marginalises non-native speakers as well as excludes vast segments of the global community from contributing to and accessing scientific knowledge. In highlighting the work of this group of volunteers, this submission highlights the broader significance of translation and localisation work as a form of supporting knowledge equity and broader access to data science guidance outside of English-speaking contexts.

In particular, this submission highlights the contributions of the Translation and Localisation Working Group in the following categories:

Local Importance

Localising open access scientific resources is crucial for addressing place-based knowledge gaps. The group's work is particularly important for the Global South, where access to research and educational resources is often restricted due to language barriers. In translating The Turing Way, the group addresses local needs and allows regional scientists and practitioners to engage with high-quality data science and reproducibility practices.

Localisation goes beyond mere text translation; it involves making knowledge culturally relevant to facilitate broader knowledge exchange. In some cases, such as with Arabic, this requires developing new terms to express concepts that currently lack equivalents in the language. For open science practices and principles, the necessary vocabulary doesn't exist in Arabic, so it must be developed and included in

glossaries

The Turing Way Translation and Localisation Working Group is at the forefront of this multifaceted work, guiding these discussions and processes alongside community members with lived experiences of exclusion due to language and/or other barriers related to linguistic and cultural difference or racism.

Leadership

The leadership demonstrated by co-leads and volunteers Batool Almarzouq and Andrea Sanchez-Tapia has been exceptional, extending far beyond the working group itself.

Furthermore, after a period of immense growth for the project broadly, the Translation and Localisation Working Group was the first to incubate governance structures that have since inspired similar work across the project more broadly. In a multi-lingual, multidisciplinary environment, the working group has implemented internal structures that promote inclusive decision-making and value the contributions of marginalised voices as a default.

By fostering collaboration across multiple regions and time zones, the group is empowering communities from the Global South and non-native English-speaking regions to actively participate in open science and knowledge production.

Reflexive & Positional and Temporality

I have witnessed first hand how reflective the Translation and Localisation Working Group is in its approach to improving The Turing Way resources. Their ongoing governance work begins from a place of critically addressing global knowledge disparities, reflecting on how their work can help dismantle the power imbalances between the Global North and Global South in the context of scientific production.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

While The Turing Way itself is a non-traditional resource that is often overlooked in traditional academic publishing, the work of the Translation and Localisation Working Group is hidden twice-over. They embody both an urgent need, as well as a hidden role that is often overlooked in both traditional research culture as well as in open science.

The Translation and Localisation Working Group, co-lead by Batool Almarzouq and Andrea Sanchez-Tapia have demonstrated firsthand how to make research guidance accessible and inclusive across diverse global communities.

While research culture in the United Kingdom operates within an English speaking context, stewarding the development of resources that can reach diverse audiences outside of the Anglophone sphere, and ensure broader participation in the research process. This work of expanding and translating existing work, does not fit within conventional metrics for research evaluation, which tend to privilege generating publications and new outputs written in English alone.

Indeed, despite the essential nature of their contributions, traditional research evaluations often overlook translation and localisation work, even more so in the context of open access resources like The Turing Way. These contributions do not result in original research papers, nor do they typically receive authorship credit in publications, even though their work significantly enhances the reach, inclusivity, and usability of such work. The value of their contributions is not easily captured by citation metrics or impact factors, yet their role is vital in broadening participation in global research ecosystems, and enabling knowledge equity.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0002-9262-8641

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: The Turing Way is funded by the Alan Turing Institute, but has volunteer contributors and collaborators from across different institutions.

Applications of Research panel

Entry: 418

Applicant details

Submission category: S - Research Datasets and Databases

Role submitted: n/a

Name: NicDaeid, Niamh

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This submission highlights how collaboration between research and professional support staff is essential to establish open data in forensic science. The Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science has created 21 publicly available datasets that have supported a number of research projects. These datasets are the result of interdisciplinary and international collaborations, including data from fire tests conducted across Denmark, Sweden, and Scotland, and have been important assets to establish new lines of forensic research.

Dr Farhan Tanvir Santo, Data Engineer, played a key role in integrating our research into the University's IT infrastructure, leading to the development of a new research data framework that supports data collection from citizen science projects and our data characterisation work with the Scottish prisons including the construction of a bespoke dashboard allowing researchers to better access the data. Dr Herve Menard (senior lecturer) supported by Dr Farhan Tanvir Santo has created coding solutions that has unlocked valuable data from analytical summaries from INTERPOL reports, enabling researchers to recover and use information that was previously unsearchable. Drs Roberto Puch-Solis (principal investigator) and Farhan Tanvir Santo have collaborated to curate and publish data from previous PhD research projects supervised unlocking this data for future use and finally, Mr Vincenzo Rinaldi (senior VR application specialist and software engineer) has managed and curated datasets from multi agency fire tests, which have been critical in establishing proficiency testing standards for Scottish fire investigators.

This submission acknowledges the work to create open and accessible data behind the scenes and the impact this has on the advancement of forensic science.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Globally, forensic science data isn't readily available as it often sits within private organisations or government led establishments and when it is made available it is often not searchable or easily usable by the forensic science research community. The work of the Leverhulme Research Centre for Forensic Science has changed this landscape. The team, "Farhan, Roberto, Herve, and Vincenzo," have pioneered the development of open data practices and innovative technical tools. The availability of 21 freely accessible datasets is a direct outcome of their efforts, providing essential resources for researchers worldwide. These datasets, stemming from interdisciplinary projects and international collaborations, have contributed to new lines of inquiry in forensic science. Beyond the datasets, the team's work has established new proficiency testing standards for fire investigators in Scotland, showcasing a real-world impact. The significance lies in both the breadth of data shared and the innovative frameworks created, which have strengthened the research infrastructure and promoted the principles of open science within the forensic science community.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

While academic researchers frequently receive recognition, those who enable open research through technical innovation and data management often remain hidden. Vincenzo is a research engineer and

Farhan is a data engineer ,À they have worked with research team members in order to curate and publish various data types from forensic science. These resources are now used globally used by forensic researchers.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: Leverhulme Trust

Entry: 440

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Bhatia, Sangeeta

Organisation/University: Imperial College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The COVID-19 pandemic, and multiple recent outbreaks of re-emerging pathogens such as Ebola and Mpox, have highlighted the continuous threat of infectious pathogens to humans. During any outbreak, reliable and robust data about the epidemiology of the causative pathogen is needed to inform the public health response. In the absence of a pre-existing curated resource, researchers must often scramble to gather vital information from scientific literature in the early phases of new outbreaks. Our work addresses the unmet need for an easily accessible, up-to-date resource.

In a series of systematic reviews, we have extracted information on the epidemiological parameters and mathematical models of nine pathogens prioritised by the World Health Organisation (WHO) for Research and Development. To streamline and simplify access to such information, we designed {epireview}, an R package that serves as a centralized repository of this systematically extracted data. Importantly, we have designed {epireview} to integrate seamlessly into the public health data and modelling ecosystem, with established tools such as EpiEstim, and tools that are under active development such as the {epiverse} family of packages.

{epireview} is an open-source package, allowing other researchers to easily contribute new data, ensuring that it remains a continuously updated and relevant resource. Finally, {epireview} ships with a flexible database schema that can be adapted to store information for any other pathogen. Indeed, WHO have recently adapted this schema to release a similar library of parameters for Mpox.

Thus, {epireview} fills a crucial gap by providing a centralised, accessible resource for key epidemiological data, and has been designed to be adaptable, ensuring it remains a continuously evolving tool that can facilitate an agile response to emerging threats to public health.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Our work addresses a critical and common problem in outbreak response unmet by traditional static systematic reviews to make the latest data available in an accessible reusable and dynamic format, which allows researchers to quickly access the data they need and update as new data are generated. Indeed, WHO have recognised this as a critical data need, and are developing a Global Repository of Epidemiological Parameters. The development of this WHO repository has in large part been informed by our work and the database structure of {epireview}. Our flexible template has been used to build libraries for other pathogens, most recently by the WHO for Mpox after its re-declaration as a Public Health Emergency of International Concern, and by our team for ongoing work on oropouche virus. The data that we have shared through {epireview} can also serve as a benchmark for training models for automated data extraction, offering a faster, more efficient way to keep information up to date as is being done by researchers at Public Health Agency of Canada.

By providing this adaptable and reusable dataset, we are setting a new standard for how public health data can be shared, used, and maintained, driving faster responses to future outbreaks. Our contribution has laid the groundwork for more efficient research and collaboration, enabling public health efforts to move from reactive to proactive in combating emerging threats.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

We have submitted our work for consideration in Hidden REF because it falls into two categories that often receive limited recognition: large collaborative efforts and software development.

Our work is grounded in rigorous systematic reviews, conducted by a group of researchers who volunteer their time for this project. The scale of this task is immense, involving the extraction of data from thousands of research articles. Despite the critical importance of this work, large group efforts like ours are often undervalued in academia. The reality is that when such work is published, the resulting papers list many authors, which dilutes individual recognition. Most contributors will not receive the prominent authorship or the visibility that comes from being first or last author on a high-impact publication, even though their efforts are indispensable to this ambitious project. Furthermore, systematic reviews, although critical to any field, are often not valued as highly as ‚Äúoriginal research,Äù which contributes further to this problem.

Moreover, we have gone beyond the traditional boundaries of systematic reviews by transforming our findings into a scalable, persistent resource in the form of a software package. Developing and maintaining such a software does not result in publications, which of course constitute the metric of productivity in academia. Nevertheless, in working on {epireview}, we have been motivated by the desire to produce a tangible resource of continuous value to the public health community.

We have adhered to the best practices in software engineering, which given the varied background of the researchers necessitated a lot of capacity building. While {epireview} is a key output of our work, we expect that it will be largely invisible in conventional measures of academic impact such as REF case studies, especially as it is difficult to quantify impact of a software which is often indirect.

This submission to Hidden REF highlights the critical but often overlooked contributions of our large collaborative work and software innovation, both of which are essential for the progression of research yet remain underappreciated and structurally underfunded.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-6525-101X

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 459

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software
Role submitted: n/a
Name: Friel, James
Organisation/University: University of Dundee
Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a
Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

The Research Data Management Platform (RDMP) is an open-source software tool that facilitates the transformation of clinical data into pseudonymised, ready-for-research datasets. Along with dataset generation, RDMP provides reusable cohort generation functionality. This allows for the generation, and reuse of cohort definitions, reducing the time required to generate research dataset cohorts and reduce the error rate of entries within the data. Over the past 11 years RDMP has been used by data analysts to provide over 1321 dataset extractions for research projects. The use of RDMP has reduced these data extractions error rate by 9.6% to 3.1% and has reduced the mean hours spent per data release by 21.6 hours to 3 hours.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

RDMP reduces the complexity of research data curation and cohort building into quick, reusable processes. Used heavily within the Health Informatics Centre at the University of Dundee, RDMP has proven to reduce the error rate within research datasets while lowering the turnaround time for new and existing dataset cohorts.

RDMP is the only free and open-source tool that empowers data analysts to streamline and collaborate on data transformation, summarization, and quality assessment.

RDMP operates as a command centre for data management and analysis, allowing data analysts to access, maintain and update each step of their data pipelines from a single, user-friendly interface. This interface abstracts away the nuances of individual pipelines and steps allowing analysts to focus on the research task at hand rather than configuration and data compatibility issues.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Often only considered as a business tool, RDMP's integration of emerging research outputs are often overlooked. Originally designed for tabular data, RDMP has transformed in recent years to support automated TRE (Trusted Research Environment) integrations, medical imaging transformation and deidentification, and integrate machine learning prediction models. These improvements allow for research datasets to be generated faster, use new and complicated types of data, and build upon the research that has gone before to empower new projects with higher-fidelity data. It is these advancements in the provisioning of data for research that RDMP facilitates, providing higher-quality data to researchers at increased volumes and reduces turnaround times.

Further details

ORCID: 0009-0008-4243-5885
Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a
Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 471

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Jones, Claire

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

Since 2006 the Scottish Government have funded Childsmile, a national programme designed to improve the dental health of children in Scotland. Childsmile is a multi-component preventative programme operating at policy, community and clinical levels, aimed at universal interventions to all children, targeting children predicted to be at higher risk of dental caries from the most socioeconomically deprived backgrounds. The target population is preschool children up to 5 years old.

The programme consists of three main interventions:

Supervised toothbrushing, 'making sure that young children brush regularly with a fluoride toothpaste and aims to help children to develop an important life skill at an early age.

Fluoride varnish in Nursery and School - preventative dental care delivery in nursery and school setting by mobile clinical teams. Implementing scientific research from around the world which shows that fluoride varnish is effective in reducing the decay rate in children, when used in addition to brushing teeth regularly with fluoride toothpaste.

Practice & Community, 'community support, and oral health promotion and clinical caries prevention delivered by the dental team. Designed to address oral health inequalities through embedding support workers within the more disadvantaged communities, including local community services such as foodbanks, parent/baby groups and dedicated ethnic minority services.

At the heart of the Childsmile programme is the invaluable data collection software developed, supported, and updated by the Health Informatics Centre, University of Dundee.

The software consists of an NHS administration website providing functionality such as user and establishment management, diary/event creation, dental contact and validation, data query validation and data reporting at local and national level. The Practice (data collection for recording interventions) and School/Nursery (managing fluoride consents and applications) Software is a desktop application installed on NHS laptops, which can be used in offline mode while users are on site at Schools.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Since its introduction in 2007, Childsmile's community-based, preventative approach has revolutionised dental healthcare from birth for all children up to the age of 12 years of age in Scotland resulting in delivery of Childsmile to over 730,000 children per year. The system currently has over 450 active users across Scotland with over 300 unique users logging in on a monthly basis.

In 2011, Childsmile was formally incorporated into the primary care dental contract and in 2012 it became part of the universal child health surveillance programme in Scotland.

In a 2015, Scotland's public health minister reported that the Childsmile programme has led to savings of almost £5 million a year in treatment costs because fewer children required extractions, fillings and

general anaesthetics.

"This is a really tremendous example of spending to save. The Childsmile programme shows what can be achieved when we have a real focus on prevention - in particular in the world of public health." Public Health Minister Maureen Watt - June 2015

The results published in 2020 from the Childsmile programme have shown a reduction in the prevalence of tooth decay, with less than a third (26%) of 5-year-old children having obvious decay experience in their primary teeth. Decay was still higher in children from most deprived backgrounds but had also reduced from 79% to 55%.

The data collected using the Childsmile software is reported at local and national level and is used to not only improve the programme but also to carry out embedded trials, look at the effectiveness of different interventions over time and with the use of data linkage has been included in over 30 research papers.

In 2021 the Childsmile software was adapted and rolled out in Bradford supporting their fluoride varnish programme.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

The Childsmile Programme has clearly demonstrated its significant contribution to improving the oral health of children in Scotland, evidenced not only in the research context, but up to government level resulting in policy change.

The Health Informatics Centre and individuals within the unit have contributed to the publications and have been acknowledged in support of the Childsmile programme, however the team involved are not researchers or academic staff and therefore their contribution is not recognised by traditional ref. Nearly 20 years of research would not have been possible without the software underpinning all aspects of the Childsmile programme, yet the software has received no formal research recognition for the Health Informatics Centre, or the team involved in developing and supporting these tools.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-6136-7111

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Keith Milburn, Service Delivery Manager, 0000-0002-4618-8729

Funding acknowledgements: The Childsmile Software was funded by the Scottish Government

Entry: 473

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Jones, Claire

Organisation/University: University of Dundee

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

For over 12 years, the Health Informatics Centre, University of Dundee in collaboration with multiple relevant stakeholders (Clinicals, Researchers, Trial Managers, Drug Suppliers, Research Nurses, Pharmacovigilance Monitors, Reviewers, Data Managers and Statisticians) has developed a suite of independent bespoke tools to support clinical trial functions such as: drug management and randomisation; pharmacovigilance reporting and monitoring; and patient contact and pathway tracking. Each of these web-based, remote access tools have been developed in-line with software development best practices and comply with regulatory guidelines including role-based access, full audit and accountability and allow for extractable reports. The software tools have been developed and architected in a way to be adaptable to suit different trial designs and data collection parameters but by using a core generic code base which is central to each. Through dynamic administration interfaces these tools can be tailored specifically to each trial allowing for customisation to the trial participant pathway; collecting trial specific data, participant visit schedules, drug request and release forms in the randomisation system and treatment and drug guidelines in pharmacovigilance tracker without requiring any further development.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

The tools developed have been core to the management of over 400 projects/trials.

- TRuST, a Randomisation System and Drug Management, supported over 100 trials (randomisation only, drug light or full drug max with accountability and full drug tracking from supplier to participant). In 12 years, 550 sites have been active including across Europe, 1,300 users have been supported, with multiple drug suppliers. TRuST has been audited at 2 MHRA inspections at trial unit and sponsor inspections where it received an acknowledgment in the audit report. To demonstrate the impact on research over 18,700 participants have been randomised and followed up using TRuST. TRuST is currently being developed to support platform trials.

- Patient Tracker System is used to track patients over the patient pathway of projects, the simplicity in design allows for quick and easily accessible reporting figures e.g. number consented, withdrawn, to be contacted or completed. The tracker securely stores participant identifiers for contact and can collect additional project specific data to allow for participant management all within one tool. The tracker has been used in over 300 Projects, managing 70,000 participants with 650 users supported.

- The latest trial support software released by the Health Informatics Centre is the PV (Pharmacovigilance) Tracker used to capture, monitor, classify and report significant events. The tool has a built-in communication and notification platform, defined timelines for notification and reminders to comply with regulatory guidelines and an automated pathway for submissions. It was initially developed for Tayside Medical Science Centre (TASC) and has been live for just over a 1 year with 160 users, 4 projects, 18 significant event reports recorded, and 11 follow ups. The next step is to licence the tool and roll out across multiple sponsor units. The PV tracker is being presented at the International Clinical Trials Methodology Conference in October.

The Early Detection of Cancer of the Lung Scotland (ECLS) Trial is just one example of how these tools directly supported research. The significant outcome of the trial ,À two years after taking the blood test, the number of people with a late-stage diagnosis of lung cancer was reduced by more than a third compared to people who received normal care. In the main trial over 12,000 participants were randomised across 3 sites using TRuST and over 20,000 potential participants managed using the Patient Tracker, several sub studies were also supported including SWAT trials and PHDs. ECLS has published over 20 papers.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

Research outcomes from clinical trials conform to the traditional research culture: publications, conferences, new drug discoveries, however the underpinning software and infrastructure to support this research typically isn't recognised even by funders. It can be difficult to obtain initial funding to support the development of these core systems and even harder to then receive further funding required to support their maintenance and future developments. Such tools are required to ensure the repeatability, auditability, quality, integrity and security of the data and without which trial management would be more manual, error prone and time consuming. The tools described have all been designed, developed and published by software engineers ,À non-academic or research staff who don't qualify for ref contributions.

Further details

ORCID: 0000-0001-6136-7111

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Keith Milburn, Service Delivery Manager, 0000-0002-4618-8729

Ross Teviotdale, Senior Software Engineer, 0009-0005-7609-2102

Funding acknowledgements: The software developed has been funded by various sources including MRC, CSO, NIHR

Entry: 481

Applicant details

Submission category: P - Devices, products, interventions and other tools/guidance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Brindha, Sarjhana

Organisation/University: CAMHS Digital Lab, King's College London

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

myHealthE is a secure web-based platform developed by King's College London and the South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust to enhance the collection of patient-reported outcome measures in Child and Adolescent Mental Health Services (CAMHS). This innovative system was designed to transform how CAMHS gather mental health data from young people engaging with their services.

Launched in 2021 by a dedicated team of NHS clinicians, researchers, and software developers, myHealthE provides a streamlined, digital approach to gathering essential mental health data for both researchers and clinical services. It invites caregivers whose children have been referred to CAMHS to complete mental health outcome measures about their child via a user-friendly web application - accessible on smartphones, tablets, and computers - which are automatically integrated with the child's electronic healthcare records. Through myHealthE, young people and families who have been referred to CAMHS are also invited to give consent for researchers to contact them about taking part in research projects via Consent for Contact. This crucially streamlines and increases research recruitment, enhancing the quality of data used to inform evidence-based practice.

Data collection and service efficiency are facilitated through key product features such as sending text and email reminders when new outcome measures are due. The application is integrated within the SLAM Azure framework and adheres to the same technical and governance standards as the Trust's existing electronic patient record systems (ePJS), ensuring data security and confidentiality.

myHealthE has dramatically increased outcome completion in the Trust by over 90% when compared with traditional methods, yielding an additional 39,000 outcome measures in the past year. By facilitating data collection, myHealthE significantly improves the quality of data available for clinical research at the same time as increasing the quality of care provided to young people and their families.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

Routine outcome measures, wherein caregivers provide information about a child's mental health symptoms through regular questionnaires, are an essential part of CAMHS. They are also a valuable source of research data, offering unique insight into treatment efficacy and outcomes for different diagnoses. Traditionally, paper-based questionnaires were distributed by post and in waiting rooms. However, the COVID-19 pandemic has necessitated a shift to remote services, requiring innovative approaches to collect this vital information safely and efficiently.

myHealthE represents a significant advancement in modernising the process of collecting routine outcome measures. In a trial conducted by the South London and Maudsley NHS Foundation Trust comparing myHealthE with paper forms, over 70% of those using myHealthE returned completed questionnaires, compared to just 8% with traditional methods. Since its implementation, myHealthE has been extended to CAMHS in four local boroughs, supporting automated enrolment of over 400 referred patients monthly.

myHealthE has also proven to be a powerful tool for enhancing equity in healthcare and research. The

platform has led to a 314% increase in completed outcome measures from minority ethnic groups, demonstrating its effectiveness in engaging diverse populations who may have faced barriers with traditional methods. This improvement is critical both in ensuring that mental health services meet the needs of all communities, and in increasing the quality and representativeness of data collected for research.

Through the Consent for Contact feature, myHealthE users can consent to be contacted by researchers about projects they may be eligible for. This change was brought about after consultation with families, who told us that they would like the opportunity to be involved in research early in their CAMHS journey and would be happy to provide consent digitally. The feature has led to a significant increase in the number of families consenting to be contacted for research; last year, almost 3,000 families gave Consent for Contact, an increase of 66%, compared to 2019. We are especially delighted that this included an increase of people from non-white ethnic groups and lower income homes. Overall, we hope that these changes will enhance the representativeness of our research, and in turn the quality of evidence-based practice that service users receive.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

In academia, recognition is often focused on academic outputs, such as journal articles and conference presentations. This emphasis can create a barrier to the full implementation of digital technologies in clinical services. Typically, researchers develop an innovative tool, conduct a randomised controlled trial, and then publish the results. However, after publication, there is often little incentive for academics to continue advancing the tool for real-world clinical use.

myHealthE challenges this conventional model by reversing the process. We began by collaborating directly with clinical services to develop a product that met their operational needs. Only after myHealthE was successfully implemented did we consider producing academic outputs around it. This approach balances real-world impact and the improvement of services with the traditional focus on generating academic publications, a balance that is often not sufficiently rewarded in research environments.

Additionally, while the outcomes of clinical data evaluation may receive attention through traditional academic routes, the foundational work that enables data collection and analysis often remains hidden. The research informatics, platform development, and technical infrastructure building that underpin myHealthE are essential for utilising this data for research. However, these contributions often do not receive the recognition they deserve; for example, platform engineers may not be lead authors on papers analysing myHealthE data, despite their critical roles in enabling this research. We want our informaticians' and platform engineers' work to be recognised for how it has contributed to research that will change young people's mental healthcare.

Further details

ORCID: n/a

Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: n/a

Funding acknowledgements: n/a

Entry: 498

Applicant details

Submission category: G - Software

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Tamborska, Arina

Organisation/University: Bennett Institute for Applied Data Science, University of Oxford

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

This nomination is for the software team from Oxford University's Bennett Institute for Applied Data Science for their development of ehrQL: a query language for electronic health record (EHR) data.

Traditional research and analysis on EHR data generally require researchers to write bespoke SQL code to extract a research dataset specific to each EHR database. To replicate studies across databases, researchers are then required to rewrite their analytical scripts, tailoring their code to each database's SQL dialect and re-mapping data structures to generate reproducible results. ehrQL was developed to support reproducibility and flexibility in research code development while providing security of the sensitive personal information contained within EHRs.

ehrQL provides a unified, consistent language that can be used across any database. It comes with the necessary adaptor codes that allow such inter-database communication. Further, an extensive and rigorous test framework ensures that queries behave in the same way across databases. A query optimiser deals with the different efficiency needs of each database. ehrQL also removes the need for transfer of sensitive data, reducing the risks posed by this approach.

ehrQL was developed over a period of over two years by a team of eleven research software engineers and other contributors who generated over 5,000 github commits. Beyond the software itself, the team also developed extensive documentation, including a full language reference, and self-study tutorials which make ehrQL accessible to new users without prior coding experience. ehrQL is also designed to be readable by those with no data science background.

ehrQL is deployed within OpenSAFELY, a trusted research environment providing researchers with access to secure, transparent analysis of electronic health record data. It is also freely available under an open license, with extensive accompanying technical documentation.

Full documentation is available here: <https://docs.opensafely.org/ehrq/> whereas the development of ehrQL is open and accessible here: <https://github.com/opensafely-core/ehrq>

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

EHR data in the UK is a vital resource for the whole academic and NHS analytic community, with countless applications for improving service delivery, monitoring health inequalities and understanding which therapies improve patient outcomes.

However, huge sensitivities surround EHR data access and processing; with inherent risks when access models require data dissemination, and rely on trusting researchers' skill and intention. Furthermore, the onus is on researchers to understand how data processing decisions and database software differences might impact their analysis. Frequently, such sensitive data has to be transferred into one common environment from environments using different query languages. Researchers are also often provided access to raw data, which creates risks and public scepticism and consequently impedes delivering on

the UK's full EHR data potential.

The development of ehrQL addresses these challenges, establishing a new paradigm for working with EHR data. ehrQL communicates with multiple databases, using one query language, without the need to transfer sensitive records or translate the code. Its rigorous testing ensures that one code script will behave the same in different databases, providing more robust analyses and allowing researchers to focus on their research questions rather than the structural differences between the EHR sources. Additionally, ehrQL deployment via OpenSAFELY creates a software infrastructure which allows research populations to be defined and analysed without accessing the raw data and inside of a secure environment.

Unlike other, non-EHR-specific query languages, ehrQL also provides methods specific to the columns present in the EHR, allowing to utilise information more efficiently. For example, a single phrase of code can extract patients registered with a general practice within a time interval, and another can filter those of certain age, with diagnosis or prescription. These methods make ehrQL code very readable, also for non-coders. Altogether, ehrQL responds to both sensitivity concerns over EHR data on one side and steep technical requirements for users on the other, consequently establishing a new paradigm for working with EHRs.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

As discussed above, development of ehrQL will enable many users, including those with less experience in coding, to tap into the unmatched resource that are the electronic health records. ehrQL is fundamental to operate OpenSAFELY and its revolutionary approach of analysing health records in situ, without researchers accessing potentially sensitive patient level data. Despite its significance and substantial effort that went into this pivotal project, the research software engineering team responsible for ehrQL development received limited recognition.

There are multiple reasons why this important contribution is overlooked. Firstly, despite many of our software team having a background in industry, they chose to work in academia, where credit is measured by the number of research publications, conference presentations or grants. Naturally, development of a coding language does not lend itself to multiple publications which would reflect the amount of work that went into ehrQL. Secondly, the primary users of ehrQL (the academic community) may be more focused on the data needed for research and may not have appropriate background to appreciate the complexity of the software that enables secure access to that data. Thirdly, although there are several awards in the software development community, none are sensitive to recognising the intricacies of working with electronic health records. Our team of research software engineers developed ehrQL taking these into account, and working in close collaboration with the EHR software providers to ensure security and safety. And finally, it is common for the success of software to be recognised through commercial and financial success. However, in line with our organisation's principles of open working, ehrQL and all accompanying documentation has been made freely available for use by others. For these reasons, Hidden REF provides our dedicated software team with the long-overdue recognition they very much deserve.

Further details

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Funding acknowledgements: NHS England

Entry: 499

Applicant details

Submission category: P - Devices, products, interventions and other tools/guidance

Role submitted: n/a

Name: Barasabha, Thareq

Organisation/University: University of Oxford & Universitas Brawijaya

Nominating other (name): n/a, n/a

Nominating other (organisation): n/a

Description of submission

Summary

We have digital stethoscope that can record and send sound signals from patient body to the doctors.

1. Explain the significance/importance of this submission

This invention could support telemedicine, especially teleconsultation and telemonitoring. It also will make auscultation examination interpretation more objective and minimize misdiagnosis while increasing patientsafety.

2. Please describe how/why this submission is overlooked/hidden within current research culture and evaluation approaches

We can't publish our innovation to scientific papers because we are registered and still waiting for patents. Also not so many clinicians used to utilize digital stethoscope, so our research still get a resistance to gain more data to make AI-system in symptoms detection.

Further details

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Name, affiliation, ORCID and job type of other contributors: Muhammad Abdul Raziq

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Funding acknowledgements: Universitas Brawijaya